

EU-CIEMBLY

Creating an Inclusive European Citizens' Assembly

Deliverable 3.3

Exploring Intersectionality in Citizens' Assembly Practices

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

EU	European Union
PMIMG	People belonging to multiple intersecting marginalised groups
RQ	Research question
SQ	Survey question

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present deliverable moves the EU-CIEMBL Y project from the stage of ‘theorising’ intersectionality in citizens’ assemblies to that of ‘evaluating’ current citizens’ assembly practices through an intersectional analytical lens. It follows from, and builds on, the research completed in Work Package 2, which consisted of the elaboration of the project’s intersectional analytical and normative framework (Deliverable 2.2) and the development of potential models for the incorporation of intersectionality into citizens’ assembly design choices (Deliverable 2.3).

Building on the analytical and normative framework elaborated in Work Package 2, this deliverable assesses how intersectionality, understood through the principles of equality, inclusion, and good deliberation, is reflected in the design and operation of existing citizens’ assemblies in practice. It has three interconnected objectives. First, it seeks to evaluate existing citizens’ assemblies through an intersectional analytical lens to identify gaps, good practices, and opportunities for improvement. Second, it aims to test the EU-CIEMBL Y conceptual framework by applying it empirically to real-world assemblies, thereby acting as a testbed for the application (albeit ex-post) of the project’s intersectional analytical framework within the context of real-life examples from across three levels of governance: local, national, and transnational. Third, the deliverable aims to generate insights for the design of the intersectionality-oriented pilot assemblies that will be further developed in Deliverable 3.4 and tested in Work Package 4.

To achieve the above objectives, the evaluation was developed using a mixed-methods approach which combines: (1) qualitative interviews with 15 organisers and facilitators of citizens’ assemblies at local, national, and transnational levels; (2) secondary analysis of participant-evaluation datasets from two past assemblies at a local (regional) level; and (3) a case-study of EU-based Assembly-like practices, namely the EU Citizens’ Panels. Together, these strands explore how intersectional equality, inclusion, and deliberation manifest in practice across the input, throughput, and output dimensions of design choices; in selected participants’ experiences; and in EU-based practice.

The objectives of the deliverable are achieved across five sections. **Section I** explains the link between Deliverable 3.3 and the preceding deliverables from Work Packages 2 and 3. It sets out in further detail the objectives of the deliverable, and explains the methodology behind the research. **Section II** finalises the EU-CIEMBL Y framework for an intersectional citizens’

assembly by bringing together the findings of the theoretical work conducted in Work Package 2 of the project. It puts together the analytical and normative dimension developed in Deliverable 2.2, and the scoping exercise for operationalising intersectional citizens' assemblies that took place in Deliverable 2.3. **Section III** contains an analysis of the interviews conducted under Task 3.2 with individuals directly involved in planning, conducting, and evaluating citizens' assemblies. Drawing on 15 interviews with practitioners, this section explores how intersectional principles appear (mostly implicitly) in assembly design across all three categorising dimensions of input-throughput-output design stages. It identifies good practices as well as trade-offs between procedural and substantive inclusion.

Section IV evaluates the secondary survey data gathered as part of Task 3.3, which considers the perception of participants in existing citizens' assemblies and ways of evaluating citizens' assemblies. Analysing datasets from Scotland's and Catalonia's Assemblies on climate change, this section explores how participants from different demographic and intersectional backgrounds experienced their participation in the assemblies. The analysis provides both substantive and methodological findings. **Section V** applies the analytical and normative dimension of our intersectional framework to existing EU-level citizens' assembly practices (i.e., the European Citizens' Panels) to consider whether and how intersectionality concepts are integrated into such practices. **Section VI** concludes by tying together the findings and their implications, as well as the derived recommendations, both for our framework, and as we move to the pilot design in Deliverable 3.4.

The elements of this report (i.e., findings from our own-conducted interviews; from the secondary analysis of participation evaluation data; and from a case-study on the European Citizens' Panels) contribute both to the project and, more broadly speaking, to existing research on intersectionality in citizens' assemblies in two ways. The first contribution of the report is **methodological** in that it illustrates three different ways in which an intersectional analytical lens can be applied to the (ex-post) evaluation of citizens' assembly practices. Deliverable 2.2 has shown that there is currently no explicit research methodology for exploring intersectionality in citizens' assembly practices. **Deliverable 3.3 contributes to covering that gap by showing three different ways in which citizens' assembly practices can be assessed from an intersectionality point of view.** It builds on previous research that we conducted in our project, where we created the basis for a conceptual framework for an intersectionality-oriented citizens' assembly. With the dimensions of that framework in mind, we then designed and conducted an intersectionality-oriented assessment of existing citizens' assembly practices in three different ways. The first way examines how intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation show up (or do not show up) in the design choices

and the implementation of those design choices in citizens' assemblies. This examination was done via the above-mentioned qualitative interviews conducted by our project team. The second way consists of an exploration of how different social groups experienced their participation in assemblies. This was conducted via an analysis of existing datasets of evaluations provided by participants in selected assemblies. The third way is an ex-post review of EU assembly-like practices against the three qualities of intersectional equality, intersectional inclusion, and intersectional deliberation, that make up the analytical and normative dimension of the project's framework.

The second contribution of this report can be found in its **substantive findings** regarding the manifestation of intersectionality in citizens' assembly practices. **The overall findings of our evaluation of existing citizens' assembly practices based on the project's conceptual framework reinforce our existing assumptions, as reiterated in the existing literature, that intersectionality is not being explicitly considered in the design of citizens' assemblies.** Rather, existing practices exhibit features of the qualities through which we have constructed our intersectional analytical framework, namely the qualities of equality, inclusion, and good deliberation but without addressing these qualities from an intersectionality perspective. This means that existing efforts at incorporating these qualities into citizens' assemblies fall short of an intersectional approach and can instead be described as contributing to more general efforts at 'diversity', which while laudable, do not always encapsulate an intersectional lens.

Nevertheless, **the existing practices provide valuable lessons and good practices on which we will build in the design of our pilot citizens' assemblies.** We have collated these lessons and practices in the form of key findings and recommendations to be taken forward throughout the remainder of the project. **Finally, our analysis here has also identified methodological gaps, from an intersectionality perspective, in the identification, gathering, and evaluation of data concerning the design and conduct of citizens' assemblies.** These gaps suggest a need to reconsider the methodological assumptions underpinning (intersectional) empirical research into lived experience of citizens' assemblies.

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I. Introduction

1. From Theorising to Evaluating

The present report moves the EU-CIEMBLY project from the stage of ‘theorising’ intersectionality in citizens’ assemblies to that of ‘evaluating’ current citizens’ assembly practices through an intersectional analytical lens. It follows from, and builds on, the research completed in Work Package 2, which consisted of the elaboration of the project’s intersectional analytical and normative framework (Deliverable 2.2) and the development of potential models for the incorporation of intersectionality into citizens’ assembly design choices (Deliverable 2.3).

Taken together, the research completed under Work Package 2 has resulted in the EU-CIEMBLY framework for an intersectionality-oriented citizens’ assembly (Figure 5, below).

This framework is essentially composed of four interrelated dimensions:

- (1) the adoption of intersectionality as an **analytical lens** composed of the qualities of (intersectional) equality, inclusion, and good deliberation, which reflect our **normative** understanding of intersectionality as set out in Deliverable 2.2;
- (2) the use of the labels of ‘input, throughput, and output choices’ to **categorise** citizens’ assembly design choices;
- (3) the development of potential models for testing the **operationalisation** of intersectionality in citizens’ assemblies, which will allow us to select the relevant design features in Deliverable 3.4 to be particularly emphasised in our pilot assemblies; and,
- (4) **recommendations** for an intersectionality-oriented EU Citizens’ Assembly.

In this way, dimensions 1 to 3 of the framework inform the design of the pilots to be tested, while dimension 4 will evaluate the pilots that will have been conducted and make our overall recommendation as to the design of an intersectionality-oriented (EU) Citizens’ Assembly. At the same time, there is an overlap between each of these dimensions in that intersectionality pervades all aspects of the project, from theorisation and operationalisation models to pilot design choices and recommendations.

2. The Objectives of the Deliverable

In continuing and expanding this research, Work Package 3 has a dual objective. The **first objective**, which is addressed in the present Deliverable 3.3, is to evaluate existing citizens’

assembly practices vis-à-vis the intersectional analytical dimension developed in Deliverable 2.2. The current report, therefore, is a mixed methods assessment of the strengths and shortcomings of existing practices within citizens' assemblies from an intersectionality perspective based on the project's analytical framework, gauging the space for increased consideration and integration of intersectionality considerations into current practices. Intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation are the three criteria against which current practices are reviewed and evaluated.

Figure 1. The progression of the EU-CIEMBLY project's work packages

As explained in Deliverable 2.2, adopting intersectionality as an analytical lens has two broad purposes, namely: (1) to describe and assess the 'problem' of the absence of explicit intersectionality considerations in citizens' assemblies; and (2) to propose innovative solutions to those same problems by developing models for an intersectionality-oriented (EU) Citizens' Assembly in the form of the recommendations to be produced in Work Package 5. Deliverable 3.3 undertakes the first, 'diagnostic' task by evaluating existing citizens' assembly practices in light of our analytical approach. In other words, this deliverable identifies and 'problematise' the extent to which intersectionality is apparent (or not) in existing citizens' assembly practices on the ground. It does so in three ways: (1) through the evaluation by means of qualitative interviews of the experiences of citizens' assembly organisers and facilitators; (2) through understanding, by way of secondary data analysis, the experience of participants in citizens' assemblies; and (3) through an evaluation of existing EU practices in the design of citizens' assemblies. The latter will consist of an intersectional assessment of existing EU-level practices in the form of the EU Citizens' Panels with the aim of identifying deficiencies and opportunities, from an intersectionality point of view, within these existing EU practices given the project's objective of recommending an intersectionality-oriented (EU) Citizens' Assembly.

In this research, therefore, the 'effectiveness' of existing citizens' assembly practices is measured against the project's understanding of the notions of intersectional inclusion, equality, and good deliberation. The more 'normative' question of the added value of

intersectionality, i.e., whether it *should* be a consideration in the design and delivery of citizens' assemblies, has already been addressed in Deliverable 2.2. The question addressed by Deliverable 3.3 concerns the ways in which intersectionality *is* considered in such practices, which also provides a valuable opportunity for us to 'test' our analytical framework against existing practices, including those practices aimed at improving the equality, inclusion, or otherwise the diversity of citizens' assemblies.

The **second objective** of Work Package 3, which is addressed in Deliverable 3.4, is to design the three pilots that are to be tested by the project team in Work Package 4 at a local, national, and transnational level. That deliverable will focus on the second function of intersectionality as an analytical lens, namely the use of intersectionality to 'address' the problem and propose solutions. In so doing, Deliverable 3.4 will deploy all dimensions of the project's framework for an intersectionality-oriented citizens' assembly by exploring how intersectionality can be operationalised in the context of citizens' assemblies.

The two objectives of Work Package 3 are also mutually reinforcing in that while Deliverable 3.3 consists of an evaluation of existing experiences using intersectionality as an analytical lens, it simultaneously looks for further good practices to adopt for the design and evaluation of the pilot assemblies in Deliverable 3.4.

Figure 2. The relationship between the data collected in Deliverable 3.1, and Deliverables 3.3 and 3.4

The work that supports Deliverables 3.3 and 3.4 took place across 19 months, starting with a mapping of existing citizens' assemblies in Task 3.1, and continuing with the collection and analysis of primary and secondary data collected in Tasks 3.2 and 3.3. Under Task 3.4, a two-day experts' workshop hosted by the University of Essex team in July 2025 provided the team with helpful feedback, which has been incorporated into the two final deliverables of Work Package 3 (i.e., Deliverables 3.3 and 3.4).¹

Figure 3. The overlapping progression of tasks in Work Package 3

Figure 4. The overlapping progression of deliverables in Work Package 3

The particular added value of Deliverable 3.3 to the EU-CIEMBL Y project, beyond the wider insights that it provides, is that it allows us to apply (and thereby test) our intersectional analytical framework within the context of real-life examples, drawing on interviews with those

¹ See Figure 4 for an illustration of the progression of all deliverables under Work Package 3.

who were involved, surveys of participant experiences, and a case study assessment of existing EU practices. This allows us to move from thinking about intersectionality in citizens' assemblies **in the abstract** towards an approach that is **practically and empirically grounded** and which will serve as a bridge between the project's theorisation (Work Package 2) and operationalisation (Work Package 3) of intersectionality in citizens' assemblies as we lay the ground for the pilot assemblies to be tested in the next stages of the project (Work Package 4).

3. Evaluation Methodology

Deliverable 3.1 contains an Explanatory Note, which is available on [Zenodo](#), addressing our methodological approach to conducting the qualitative interviews under Task 3.2 and the secondary survey data analysis that took place under Task 3.2. The salient methodological points are reiterated throughout the discussion below, where relevant to explaining our approach to the evaluation and analysis of this data. Below we also set out the particular research questions that we sought to address and which were tailored to each component of our evaluation of existing citizens' assembly practices (i.e., the qualitative interviews, the secondary survey data analysis, and the evaluation of EU-level practices). The commonality across all three components of our evaluation is our analytical and normative assessment based on the concepts of intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation.

Moreover, the present deliverable has the overarching research objective of assessing how intersectionality (-related) concepts have been integrated into the design and delivery of existing citizens' assemblies, across local, national, and transnational levels. In this way, the deliverable adopts a mixed methods research (MMR) methodology (Escobar & Thompson, 2019) to apply our intersectional analytical framework to the evaluation of existing citizens' assembly practices. Following an MMR methodology, we developed this study 'guided by the object of our inquiry rather than the preferences or habits of our disciplinary and methodological silos' (Escobar & Thompson, 2019, p. 501). In this sense, the object of our inquiry is to complement the theoretical work that has taken place in Work Package 2 by understanding how intersectionality (as understood in light of our intersectionality framework) plays out in the practice of citizens' assemblies, including how persons belonging to different social groups have experienced citizens' assemblies differently.

This approach complements the overarching research question that guided Work Package 2, i.e., the extent to which intersectionality features in the literature on citizens' assemblies, some of which also documents existing practices on the ground. The present deliverable seeks to

enhance the findings of Work Package 2 by lending an empirical angle to the link between citizens' assembly design and intersectionality. One of our key findings in Work Package 2 was that intersectionality has not yet been systematically integrated or operationalised into the practice of citizens' assemblies as documented in the literature explored in Deliverable 2.1 and 2.2. It was shown there that existing research on marginalisation or exclusion from deliberative processes has primarily been conducted from the perspective of discrete or individual identities or social groups (e.g., sex, race, or age) rather than through the lens of intersectionality i.e., multiple overlapping marginalised social groups (e.g., the Black female or the migrant lesbian experience).

Although some of the literature that we explored in Deliverables 2.1 and 2.2 was based on empirical analysis of citizens' assemblies, other aspects were more theoretical. We were, therefore, interested in finding out whether the practice of organising, implementing, and evaluating citizens' assemblies may be more revealing regarding practices supported by intersectionality considerations. To identify and understand such practices, it was necessary to consider how existing approaches correspond to our definitions of intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation essentially in the absence of *explicit* or direct consideration of intersectionality in citizens' assembly design. While not intended to constitute a representative example of existing practices, this approach allows us to assess and test the 'applicability' of our framework to some of those practices. We have also attempted to evaluate a range of 'types' of practice/experience whether through the interviews (design and delivery of citizens' assemblies), secondary data analysis (participant experience and citizens' assembly evaluation) and the evaluation of the EU Citizens' Panels (ex-post application of our framework to the evaluation of existing EU-level practices).

In doing so, we have also been able to capture and assess practices from existing citizens' assemblies at different levels (local, national, and transnational) as well as of different types (top-down and bottom-up). For our purposes, **local** citizens' assemblies are those taking place at a sub national state level, whether at a regional level or at the level of a local community or whose recommendations can be directed towards or acted upon by a local or sub national decision-making authority. **National** refers to citizens' assemblies that take place at a national level and which are typically initiated by a national public authority. A national citizens' assembly usually discusses topics of concern to the population of the state as a whole, and its recommendations can be directed towards or acted upon by a national decision-maker. Finally, a **transnational** citizens' assembly is one that takes place beyond a single state. A transnational citizens' assembly will discuss issues that transcend national borders and its

recommendations may be directed towards or acted upon by a transnational decision-maker such as an EU institution for example.

Of course, we accept that our approach(es) to the evaluation of existing citizens' assemblies comes with inherent **limitations**. We do not claim to provide a conclusive overview of the wealth of practices that exists in citizens' assembly organisation, conduct, and evaluation. Professional practitioners who have been running citizens' assemblies at least for the last decade have undoubtedly added and continue adding innovations around various stages of the process such as recruitment and facilitation (Talpin, 2019). Instead, we have tried to capture the role of intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation (which constitute the key analytical dimension of our framework) within existing practices.

The interviews that we conducted under Task 3.2 were aimed at understanding further and qualitatively analysing the practical operation of citizens' assemblies. **They focused on exploring the extent to which intersectionality or intersectionality-related concepts and design features have been incorporated into citizens' assemblies in practice.** Although our dataset of 15 semi-structured interviews includes interviews with practitioners working across various citizens' assemblies and various roles, it is inevitable that the data collected reflect the interviewees' own experiences and insights regarding the organisation and implementation of citizens' assemblies in practice rather than providing a holistic picture of the vast field of citizens' assembly practices.

Additional limitations concern the secondary data analysis. **The secondary data analysis offers insights into the perceptions of individuals who have participated in specific citizens' assemblies and provides further information on how participants belonging to different social groups have experienced citizens' assemblies differently.** Of course, the findings of this analysis are not generalisable or universal given both the specific context in which the relevant assemblies were conducted but also due to the restrictive nature of the accessible data. This limitation is due to both the difficulties in accessing data (we were able to access two datasets, one from Scotland and one from Catalonia), and the absence of explicit intersectionality considerations in the design of those existing surveys.² Furthermore, while survey responses can capture the perceptions of individuals, these particular surveys cannot adequately capture (on their own) the collective or structural dimensions of intersectionality. Moreover, the predominant focus of the discussion in the qualitative interviews was on the conducting of citizens' assemblies, while the focus of the available

² On researching deliberative mini-publics quantitatively, see Beste & Wyss, 2019.

survey data was on discrete identities (rather than intersecting social groups). In other words, there is an (over) emphasis in our interviews on ‘process’ and an (over) emphasis in our survey data on individual social groups both of which have drawbacks from the perspective of an intersectionality evaluation which (in addition) necessitates a consideration of more substantive issues of intersectionality in the design and conduct of citizens’ assemblies, as well as an analysis grounded in overlapping or intersecting social groups and power relations.

Finally, at this stage of the project we are applying our framework to *past* citizens’ assembly practices, and so we must work within the confines of the material that is available. Moreover, those existing practices (and unlike our own pilot assemblies) will not (necessarily) have been designed with intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation in mind. This may hinder a ‘direct’ application of our framework to the existing practices, and so we have been alert to identifying and evaluating ‘intersectionality-like’ concepts, notably those existing efforts at ‘general’ equality, inclusion, and good deliberation in much the same way as we approached the existing literature on citizens’ assembly practices in Deliverable 2.2 itself.

We are grateful to the interview participants and the dataset holders for their contribution to our project.

4. Structure of the Deliverable

The report proceeds as follows. Section II brings together the findings of Deliverables 2.2 and 2.3 to finalise the EU-CIEMBLY framework for an intersectionality-oriented citizens’ assembly. It puts together the analytical and normative dimension developed in Deliverable 2.2, and the scoping exercise for operationalising intersectional citizens’ assemblies that took place in Deliverable 2.3. It will be recalled that Deliverable 2.2 provided the analytical and normative lens for the project through the articulation of intersectionality via the qualities of intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation. At the same time, it explained the project’s use of input, throughout, and output choices as ‘organising’ concepts. Deliverable 2.3 built on the work of Deliverable 2.2 to provide potential model choices for ‘operationalising’ intersectionality in citizens’ assemblies. Section III contains an analysis of the interviews conducted under Task 3.2 with individuals directly involved in planning, conducting, and evaluating citizens’ assemblies. Section IV evaluates the secondary survey data gathered as part of Task 3.3, which considers the perception of participants in existing citizens’ assemblies and ways of evaluating citizens’ assemblies. Section V applies the analytical and normative dimension of our intersectional framework to existing EU-level citizens’ assembly practices (i.e., the European Citizens’ Panels) to consider whether and how intersectionality concepts

are integrated into such practices. Section VI concludes by tying together the findings and their implications both for our framework, and as we move to the pilot design in Deliverable 3.4.

II. The EU-CIEMBLY Framework for an Intersectional Citizens' Assembly

The aim of this first substantive section of Deliverable 3.3 is to set out the project's finalised framework for an intersectionality-oriented citizens' assembly design which combines the analytical/normative dimension and categorising dimensions developed as part of Deliverable 2.2 and the operationalising dimension of Deliverable 2.3. The framework is depicted in Figure 5, below.

EU-CIEMBLY Framework for an Intersectionality-Oriented Citizens' Assembly		
1. Analytical and normative dimension	Intersectionality as an analytical lens informs the qualities of:	
	Equality	Inclusion
		Good deliberation
2. Categorising dimension	Which are then used to inform citizens' assembly design choices , categorised according to:	
	Input choices:	Throughput choices:
	Output choices:	
	Governance, organisation and management; selection and recruitment of participants; topic and agenda-setting	Experts and witnesses in the educational phase; facilitation; deliberation
		Influence on public decision-making processes; impact on participants
3. Operationalising dimension	Which are incorporated through one or more of the models for operationalising intersectionality in citizens' assemblies:	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Model 1: Descriptive representation; ● Model 2: Discursive representation; ● Model 3: Subaltern counterpublics; ● Model 4: Power sharing; ● Model 5: Agonistic pluralism; ● Model 6: Relationality and interdependence. 	
4. Evaluation and recommendations dimension	Which then inform the development of:	
	An intersectionality-oriented citizens' assembly	

Intersectionality

Figure 5. The EU-CIEMBLY framework for an intersectionality-oriented citizens' assembly

The analytical and normative dimension of the framework developed by Deliverable 2.2 highlights that the EU-CIEMBLY project identifies and addresses patterns of exclusion from citizens' assemblies through the adoption and application of intersectionality as an analytical lens for understanding and overcoming structural marginalisation.

Intersectionality, understood as the analysis of multiple, overlapping oppressive structures, reinforced by underlying power relations, is thereby employed as an **analytical lens** through which to assess and promote the **qualities** of equality, inclusion, and good deliberation in all aspects of citizens' assemblies design and delivery. In this sense, Deliverable 2.2 provided the definitions of what we consider to constitute intersectional equality, intersectional inclusion, and intersectional (good) deliberation, with these qualities considered to be interrelated and mutually dependent:

- An intersectional approach to **equality** necessitates a departure from procedural or formal conceptions of equality (equal treatment) towards more substantive conceptions that recognise the potential need for *more favourable treatment* to be offered to structurally marginalised groups, i.e., the focus is on power structures and relations rather than equality between individuals. The idea is to remove barriers to participation in citizens' assemblies rather than merely providing everyone with a formally equal 'opportunity' to participate.
- Intersectional **inclusion** challenges conventional approaches to the constitution of citizens' assemblies, which tend to emphasise 'representativeness', i.e., an assembly as a reflection of the composition of the relevant polity. An intersectional approach requires a broad conception of the 'citizen', one that goes beyond political or legal conceptions of citizenship. Inclusion here concerns both the internal and external dimension. The external dimension focuses on who is given genuine access to the room, while the internal dimension is concerned with the quality of inclusion while in the room. An intersectional analysis of inclusion will go beyond deliberation itself to assess who has the agenda-setting power or the power to make decisions.
- Finally, intersectional **deliberation** requires taking account of power dynamics and structural marginalisation to ensure equality of voice among participants by addressing structural biases.

The above qualities are interrelated and mutually dependent. They are used to inform citizens' assembly **design choices** as **categorised** through the lens of input, throughput, and output choices (the categorising dimension of the framework). **Input choices** concern the question of who deliberates and what they deliberate on, including the quality of information provided. **Throughput choices** concern the nature of deliberation, the process of participation, decision-making and the context in which deliberation takes place. Finally, **output choices** concern the political (or relevant decision-maker's) response to the assembly's recommendations. **Each of these elements, i.e., the qualities and the categorisation, will then be deployed to inform the trade-offs and design choices that will be required in the project's development of an intersectionality-oriented citizens' assembly.** Finally, it should be noted that intersectionality is further embedded in all stages of the above framework, which must remain iterative and adaptable to the relevant context to ensure that intersectionality remains the project's analytical and normative thread.

The analytical and normative dimension provided by Deliverable 2.2 is further facilitated by the categorisation of the stages of a citizens' assembly developed in the same deliverable, as well as the operationalising models developed in Deliverable 2.3, which thereby extends the project's framework for an intersectional analysis. The purpose of Deliverable 2.3 was, therefore, to consider and develop further the analytical and normative models, which will guide in turn the eventual design choices (Deliverable 3.4) that will be tested in the project's pilot Citizens' Assemblies (Work Package 4).

A full account of the various theoretical models can be found in Deliverable 2.3, but as a reminder:

- **Model 1:** Descriptive representation, concerns inclusion of marginalised groups as participants or organisers within a citizens' assembly i.e., ensuring intersectional representativeness;
- **Model 2:** Discursive representation emphasises inclusion of diverse knowledge, perspectives and discourses by moving beyond identity-based 'representation';
- **Model 3:** Subaltern counterpublics seek to provide dedicated or protected spaces in which the perspective of marginalised groups can be articulated;
- **Model 4:** Power sharing focuses on overcoming imbalances in popular control, governance and community-driven design;
- **Model 5:** Agonistic pluralism involves the facilitation of conflicting opinions and perspectives;

- Finally, **Model 6: Relationality and interdependence**, seeks to emphasise commonalities and relationships between participants, their communities and broader society.

These models, while emphasising different design features and attributes, should not be viewed as discrete or siloed. Rather, many of the models overlap or draw inspiration from each other, and do not stand on their own as complete practical operationalisation tools. As also explained in Deliverable 2.3, the models present complementary yet potentially conflicting priorities and values alongside challenges and limitations, particularly with regards to practical implementation. The choice of which design features to emphasise, test, and evaluate as part of our pilots will further be guided by reference back to the qualities of intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation and by centring the concept of ‘power relations’ in our understanding of intersectionality.

It can be seen that dimensions 1 to 3 of the framework inform the design of the pilots to be tested, while dimension 4 evaluates the pilots that will have been conducted and makes our overall recommendations (in Work Package 5) as to the design of an intersectionality-oriented (EU) Citizens’ Assembly.

Taken together, then, each of the above dimensions constitute the overarching EU-CIEMBLY framework for an intersectionality-oriented citizens’ assembly (Figure 5). This framework will be used to: (1) identify and diagnose; and (2) mitigate, exclusion and marginalisation within citizens’ assemblies caused by overlapping and dynamic power relations.

The first step, therefore, is to use the analytical and normative dimension of our intersectionality framework (as developed in Deliverable 2.2) to assess and understand the weaknesses and opportunities within existing approaches to citizens’ assemblies. This is the challenge taken up by the present Deliverable 3.3, which seeks (ex post) to apply an intersectional analytical lens to existing citizens’ assemblies. The focus throughout this deliverable, and indeed throughout Work Package 3, is on the empirical and practical operation of citizens’ assemblies as well as their engagement with intersectionality concepts in practice, which stands in contrast to the theoretical and normative emphasis of Work Package 2.

III. Analysis of Qualitative Interviews with Organisers and Facilitators of Existing Citizens' Assemblies

In order to further our objective of integrating intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation into citizens' assembly practice, we undertook interviews with a range of people who have been involved in the organisation and facilitation of citizens' assemblies across the world. Through these interviews we evaluate existing citizens' assembly practices against the intersectional analytical framework developed in Deliverable 2.2. This section of this report focuses on the findings of those interviews, analysing the extent to which intersectionality is considered and integrated into citizens' assemblies. Therefore, in line with Deliverable 2.2 and the project's intersectionality framework set out in Figure 5, the analysis in this part of the report is undertaken around three core criteria: intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation.

In this part of the deliverable, we focus on identifying and problematising *how far* intersectionality is evident in practice, through our qualitative interviews with citizens' assembly organisers and facilitators. These interviews offer empirical insights on the design, implementation and evaluation of assemblies, extending and complementing the literature-based insights developed in Work Package 2.

Whilst we have acknowledged that intersectionality has rarely been explicitly operationalised in citizens' assemblies, these interviews allow us to explore whether and how intersectional considerations emerge in practice, even at an implicit level.

It should be noted that the interviews do not aim to provide a representative sample of all citizens' assemblies. Instead, when collecting the interviews, we focused on offering a diverse set of experiences, so that we could test the applicability of our analytical framework and identify opportunities for embedding intersectionality systematically in citizens' assemblies. This section presents the findings from these interviews organised around the 'categorising dimension' of our conceptual framework, which concerns key stages of the assembly process: input, throughput, and output. In what follows we will first elaborate further on our methodological approach to conducting the interviews.

1. Methodology

1.1. Data Collection Approach

The qualitative interviews aimed to understand and qualitatively analyse the practical operation of citizens' assemblies, with a focus on exploring the way that intersectionality or intersectionality-related concepts have been incorporated into citizens' assemblies **in practice**. In what follows, we summarise our ethics-driven approach to designing and conducting the interviews.³ The dataset of the anonymised interview transcripts and an Explanatory Note with the full methodology can be found on [the project's community profile in Zenodo](#).⁴ The interviews for the project received ethical approval from the University of Essex (decision number ETH2324-0311), and more details of the ethical approach can be found in Deliverable 3.1.

We undertook a total of 15 semi-structured interviews with individuals who were involved in the organisation of at least one citizens' assembly at the local, national, or transnational level. Most of the interviewees fulfilled more than one role within the relevant citizens' assemblies and were involved with the organisation (deciding topics, location, managing logistics etc), facilitation (ensuring fair discussion and deliberation throughout the process), and/or evaluation (designing and carrying out surveys or interviews with participants on their experiences) of citizens' assemblies.

In order to ensure that we engaged the interviewees in responses that would be useful for the project, the wider project team conducted an iterative approach to design the semi-structured interview guide (see Deliverable 3.1). We adopted a narrative approach through open-ended questions, so that the participants could explain their background, their role in citizens' assemblies, their experiences and their reflections on those experiences. The guide was divided according to the categories of citizens' assembly design characteristics outlined in Deliverable 2.2, which were: (1) Governance and Organisation; (2) Selection and Recruitment; and (3) Facilitation and Deliberation.

³ The full methodology can be found in Karatzia, A., O'Connor, N., Woodward, S., Noles, S., & Jensen, E. (2025). *Dataset of Empirical Results - Explanatory Note*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16573648> as part of Deliverable 3.1.

⁴ See Deliverable 3.1 and Karatzia, A., O'Connor, N., Woodward, S., Noles, S., & Jensen, E. (2025). *Dataset of Empirical Results - Explanatory Note*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16573648>. This Explanatory Note accompanies Deliverable 3.1 and explains in detail the methodology behind the empirical research conducted to support Deliverable 3.3. Some information from this Note has been used in the current Deliverable 3.3 to assist the reader in following the methods behind the data collection process.

In our exploration and mapping of existing citizens' assemblies under Task 3.1, we found that intersectionality did not explicitly appear in most of the reports on citizens' assemblies. In some cases, there was a limited reference to intersectionality, which did not form a key role in the design or execution of the citizens' assembly. This informed our decision to design the interview guide around exploring the implicit rather than explicit use of intersectionality in practice. Therefore, as explained in Deliverable 3.1, we avoided prejudicing or influencing the discussion and the responses given by the interviewees by focusing on the qualities of inclusion, equality, and diversity as values informing the design of citizen's assemblies, to allow themes of intersectionality to emerge organically through the interviewers' prompts during the interview. We ensured, through this approach, that the interview was led by the participants' experience and understanding, using terminology informed by their own practice (Staller, 2022).

1.2. Recruiting Interviewees

In order to recruit interviewees, we drew on the mapping of citizens' assemblies from Task 3.1. We examined a total of 106 citizens' assemblies from 17 EU Member States, five non-EU countries, and from transnational practice, focusing in particular on those that showed interesting characteristics relevant to the project, narrowing down our focus through this approach.⁵ Characteristics included references to inclusion, equality or intersectionality considerations, engagement or recruitment of particular social groups, or innovative design features that aimed to encourage participation. We then identified key individuals involved in those assemblies through publicly available information. From this mapping exercise, we contacted 35 potential interviewees which resulted in 12 interviews. From these 12 interviews, we were able to use a snowball sampling approach to recruit a further 3 interview participants.

In line with the aim of the interviews to understand experiences of organisers and facilitators of citizens' assemblies, we adopted a semi-structured interview approach. This led to recruiting interviewees who had a range of experiences and roles from citizens' assemblies of varying sizes and with different topics. Each of the 15 semi-structured interviews was conducted in English, lasting between 60 and 90 minutes. Prior to the start of each interview, the interviewer gave a brief overview and answered any questions or concerns to build rapport between the interviewer and interviewee (Yow, 2016). The interviewer also conducted preliminary research to direct the interview and narrow down the interview guide during the

⁵ For a detailed explanation of the mapping exercise from Task 3.1, see Karatzia, A., O'Connor, N., Woodward, S., Noles, S., & Jensen, E. (2025). *Dataset of Empirical Results - Explanatory Note*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16573648>.

interview. Interviewer discretion was used when asking open questions, engaging the interviewee in particular areas of interest, and asking follow up questions (Wengraf, 2001). All the interviews were conducted using Zoom, and the application's automatic audio transcription was used to create the initial transcripts of the interviews which were then corrected by the interviewee to ensure accuracy. Despite the interviews being anonymised, Figure 6 below gives an overview of the assemblies that the interviewees were involved in, demonstrating the breadth and depth of experience of the interviewees, many of whom were involved in more than one citizens' assemblies and often fulfilled multiple roles within the citizens' assemblies such as organisers, facilitators, and sometimes also evaluators:

PSEUDONYMISATION OF INTERVIEWS				
Citizens' Assembly	Interview	Key features for analysis		
		Location (EU/non-EU)	Scale	Number of participants
Alpha	2	Non-EU	Local	1-50
Beta	2	Non-EU	Local	1-50
Gamma	2	Non-EU	Local	1-50
Delta	3	EU	Local	1-50
Epsilon	3	EU	Local	1-50
Zeta	4	EU	Transnational	150-200
Eta	5	EU	National	150-200
Theta	5	EU	Local	1-50
Iota	6	EU	Local	1-50
Iota	7	EU	Local	1-50
Zeta	7	EU	Transnational	151-200

Kappa	7	EU	Transnational	151-200
Lambda	8	EU	Local	1-50
Mu	9	EU	National	101-150
Nu	10	EU	Local	51-100
Nu	11	EU	Local	51-100
Xi	12	Non-EU	Local	1-50
Omicron	13	Non-EU	National	1-50
Pi	13	Non-EU	National	101-150
Rho	13	Non-EU	Local	1-50
Sigma	13	Non-EU	Local	1-50
Tau	13	Non-EU	Local	1-50
Upsilon	13	Non-EU	National	1-50
Phi	14	Non-EU	Local	1-50
Chi	14	Non-EU	Local	1-50
Psi	14	Non-EU	Local	1-50
Omega	15	Non-EU	National	200+
Sampi	1	Non-EU	Local	1-50

Figure 6. Pseudonymisation of interviews

Where interviewees referenced organisations, these were pseudonymised with a corresponding letter of the Latin alphabet, as shown in Figure 7. Descriptors of the organisations have been added to offer additional relevant context on the nature of the organisation while ensuring the highest possible level of anonymity for interviewees. As shown by Figure 7, multiple organisations were referred to in some of the interviews.

PSEUDONYMISATION OF ORGANISATIONS		
Interview	Organisation	Descriptor
1	B	Nonprofit
2	A	Public
3	C	Private
3	D	Agency
3	E	Public authority
3	F	Private

4	G	Commissioning body
4	H	Public authority
5	I	Private
6	J	Public
6	K	Research institution
6	L	Public authority
7	K	Private
7	L	Public authority
7	G	Commissioning body
7	M	Private
7	J	Public
9	N	Private
9	O	Private
9	P	Research institute
9	Q	Public
10	R	Advocacy
10	S	Public authority
10	T	Nonprofit
12	U	Social enterprise
12	V	Nonprofit
13	W	Nonprofit
13	X	Public
14	T	Nonprofit

Figure 7. Pseudonymisation of organisations

2. Analysis

To analyse the interview data, the research team drew on their experience of undertaking qualitative data analysis and immersed themselves in the transcripts, reading them multiple times with guidance from the project's developing framework. The first stage involved analysis based on themes emerging from the interviews. Each researcher analysed the interview transcripts individually, and the team then agreed on a set of themes. The first stage of the analysis process was deductive, involving a close reading of the transcripts against the predetermined themes outlined in the interview guide, which was derived from the project's developing framework. The second stage adopted a more inductive approach, engaging in an

open reading of the transcripts to identify emergent themes and patterns that extended beyond the initial framework. This approach ensured that the analysis captured both the predefined themes and new insights arising from participants' experiences.

For this deliverable, we focused on sections of the interviews most relevant to inclusion, equality, and good deliberation. To do so, we collaboratively discussed and workshopped key quotes to develop the analysis. **As we discerned in Deliverables 2.1 and 2.2, intersectionality is often not addressed explicitly, so we looked for individual design choices that may not be explicitly defined as intersectional by interviewees but exhibit intersectional-like qualities.** This led us to engage with the following practical themes, which we then categorised under input, throughput and output stages, i.e., the categorising dimension of the project's framework for intersectionality in citizens' assemblies:

INPUT CHOICES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Topic and agenda setting
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Selection and recruitment of participants <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Invitation approach ○ Barriers to inclusion
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Information presented before and during the assembly
THROUGHPUT CHOICES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Running the assembly
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Deliberation and consensus
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Engaging with politics and involving politicians
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Including different perspectives
OUTPUT CHOICES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Developing inclusive recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The impact on participants
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The impact on public decision-making processes

Across the practical themes that emerged—both from the interviewees' lived experiences and from those themes identified earlier in the project—we engaged in an iterative and reflective process (Udayanga, 2025). This involved moving back and forth between the emerging themes and the dimensions of our conceptual framework, allowing us to connect new insights with existing concepts and explore additional issues. Through several team meetings during the analysis, we discussed the data, identified key lessons, reviewed emerging findings, and

developed recommendations to ensure consistency and coherence in our approach. This process deepened our understanding of how assemblies operate in practice and what their practical operation reveals about the presence—or absence—of intersectionality considerations in existing practices.

Following the same approach adopted for the interview guide, the analysis of the interviews is structured according to the input, throughput, and output categorising dimensions described in Deliverable 2.2. Across each of the themes, we explored the nuance and lived experience of each of the interviewees, noting that each of these themes held both similarities and contradictions, which we will unpack in the following analysis.

In what follows, we present the quotes that best illustrate the key findings from the interview data. These quotes were reviewed in a dedicated workshop where the research team systematically discussed each theme, examined the associated quotes, and agreed on which ones to include. This process ensured that the selected quotes accurately reflected the themes, maintained consistency across the analysis, enabled discussion of the ways that they reinforced or challenged our impressions from earlier deliverables, and strengthened the validity of the findings. At the end of each sub-section, we offer recommendations based on our learning and understanding from the interviews, some of which will then feed into the design of the EU-CIEMBLY pilots which will take place in the next work package of the project.

2.1. Input Choices

As stated in Deliverable 2.2, the input stage concerns who deliberates, the topic of deliberation and the information or materials provided to participants to deliberate on (Reuchamps & Suiter, 2016). As such, this section covers specific aspects of citizens' assemblies, including; topic and agenda setting; selection and recruitment of participants; information presented before and during the assembly.

2.1.1. Topic and agenda setting

Most of the interviews described a similar process of appointing an advisory board to aid in setting the agenda of the citizens' assemblies. The membership of advisory boards often included experts in citizen participation, as well as subject-specific experts, depending on the topic of the assembly. Some interviews described experts being recommended by the commissioning authority of the citizens' assembly (Interview 14).

While many interviews focused on citizens' assemblies that had been commissioned, and therefore the topic was pre-determined, interviewees stressed the importance of capturing the interest of citizens through topic selection and giving participants space to choose or engage in direct discussions and pick the topics, so participants would feel a 'sense of agency' (Interview 2). Interviewee 12 also echoes this:

'The topic that we explore through a process is one that is going to make a difference, because maybe it's linked to certain decisions that are coming up. But at the same time, we want to make sure that citizens are able to choose something that they're really interested in talking about (...) We really like the idea of it being entirely the citizen's choice'. (Interview 12)

The interviewee also described wanting to engage citizens with topics in which they were interested but highlighted a trade-off: the topics that hold the most interest may not always link to the remit of the commissioning authority of citizens' assemblies:

'(...) But then that might mean that they end up not talking about something that could influence a decision that's in the pipeline from decision-makers. But we don't want to just say to them, you need to talk about this, because that's the decision that needs to be made. So the way that we manage that trade-off is that we usually encourage the commissioner to set a, to agree, quite a broad question'. (Interview 12)

Interview 13 describes the way that they approached this trade-off, which was a common approach across interviewees:

'[The commissioning authority] needs to know what they want the assembly to inform and so I would start there so, what is it that you know, what are you wanting? This or that? (...) What decisions is this assembly going to inform [then we get] wider feedback on the question, I would say, at very least from interested organisations, but ideally kind of more broadly, with a particular emphasis on groups who are less heard. I would say at that point to make sure that the question itself kind of mirrors people's concerns and isn't exclusionary to start with'. (Interview 13)

This interviewee confirms that considerations about inclusion/exclusion should start from the design phase - already from the topic selection phase.

In the examples where citizens' assemblies were not commissioned by decision-makers, shared by Interviewees 5, 14 and 15, the interviewees discussed dialogue events and listening activities with local communities to inform the topic selection. Interview 14 described the process of determining a topic of a 'bottom-up' citizens' assembly:

'(...) in the development ones they're decided by communities. So there's engagement delivered beforehand, could be dialogue events, could be on street conversations, could be online stuff and then depending on what comes out of that is the starting point for okay, how do we develop these buildings for the community, with the community, and by them'. (Interview 14)

Topic selection in citizens' assemblies plays a critical role in shaping inclusion, equality, and deliberation. While many assemblies are commissioned with pre-determined topics, interviewees emphasised the importance of giving participants a sense of agency by allowing them to influence or choose discussion areas. This creates a trade-off between aligning with institutional decision-making and engaging citizens on issues they care about. Practitioners often address this by framing broad questions and consulting with less-heard groups to ensure relevance and avoid exclusion. In bottom-up assemblies, topics typically emerge from community engagement activities, which can better reflect diverse lived experiences. These findings highlight that considerations of inclusion and intersectionality should begin at the design stage, starting with topic selection.

Interview Recommendation 1: Use broad framing questions for agenda setting and involve less-heard groups early in the design process.

2.1.2. Selection and recruitment of participants

Recruitment and selection are vital parts of developing an intersectionality-oriented assembly, with aspirations of including a diverse range of people being at the forefront of many interviewees' responses. However, there are also many challenges in making this happen in practice. With the exception of Interview 15, all of the interviews described using a two-stage civic lottery process as their primary method of recruitment and selection for legitimacy and representativeness in citizens' assemblies. Whilst this method does support demographic

diversity, in the following discussion we unpack the limitations that it holds in terms of intersectional inclusion.

The following interviewees argued that whilst not explicitly adopting an intersectional approach to recruitment, intersections emerge organically through the two-stage civic lottery process:

‘(...) we'll give them the criteria, the target population that we need, but we don't really say there must be somebody who's got these types of intersection. But it does sort of come out in that process.’ (Interview 14)

‘The way I think about an assembly is that it's an assembly that is broadly representative of the city that's trying to create many different intersectional experiences and considering the whole person, you know, the cognitive diversity, identity diversity, all these different types of diversity. But that, it's trying to reflect a diversity, a broad diversity of the city. But in my view, the assembly isn't trying to create representation for each specific, you know, group that exists within the city. Because I think that that's where other parallel processes are actually better because they're more relationship based. You know, within an assembly, you form the assembly and then it dissolves and then all those relationships dissolve’. (Interview 1)

These interviewees suggest that, even though they did not rely on intentional design to capture intersections, statistical representativeness does lead to diversity that mirrors the diversity in a given context. Whilst they value diversity, intersectionality is treated incidentally rather than centrally. However, without making intersectionality explicit in recruitment and selection, there is a risk that structural inequalities that shape participation, and which are usually not relevant in representative models, are overlooked, raising questions about whether organic emergence is sufficient to address systematic exclusion. Interviewee 1 suggests prioritising demographic breadth over targeted inclusion, but also that there is a need to take a relationship-based approach, especially for marginalised groups. This is important for us to examine further when exploring intersectionality in our pilot citizens' assemblies as there is a tension highlighted between the type of inclusivity that we may aspire to and the implementation of those aspirations in practice.

While the majority of interviews described the two-stage civic lottery process as their primary method of recruitment and selection for citizens' assemblies, some raised criticisms and alerted to trade-offs to be aware of over the ability of the process to identify and recruit a fully

inclusive and equal pool of participants for a citizens' assembly. Trade-offs included considerations of perceived legitimacy from the use of statistics to calculate the participants needed for the process to be demographically representative as well as the risk of tokenism, where an individual's experience may be considered representative of a collective social group's experience.

One interviewee highlighted the trade-off involved with the apparent legitimacy of recruitment of a statistically representative participant pool compared to the wellbeing of participants from minority backgrounds within the citizens' assembly:

'(...) this is really tricky, isn't it? Because - so there's a massive trade off here, isn't there? I remember doing a climate change jury in a town in the Northwest, and the local MP was on the oversight panel, and we were talking about, should we over recruit certain groups of people. And he said, "if you start manipulating the data, then I'm going to withdraw from the process, because it will no longer be a scientifically valid sample", and others were saying, "well, if we follow the local stats, then it means that there's going to be one person of colour. And that's it. So that's not appropriate. That's tokenistic. And that experience could be really negative for them"'. (Interview 12)

Interviewee 12 is highlighting here the tension between how certain statistical practices are considered legitimate by the commissioning authority (scientific validity/legitimacy of the procedure - methodological neutrality), on the one hand, and social substantive representativeness and inclusion, on the other hand. Whilst statistical representativeness may align with demographics to achieve legitimacy, it can also lead to tokenistic representation, as discussed in Deliverable 2.3. When legitimacy is defined as statistical validity, intersectional inclusion, substantive equality, and lived experience are deprioritised.

To avoid tokenism, Interviewee 1 described the importance of adapting the selection process to ensure that individuals were not acting as representatives of a social group, by making sure that at least two people from a particular language group were included so that representative weight was not being placed on one person:

'And, you know, the way we spoke to assembly members is you're not here representing, you know, like, a certain thing. You're here representing your whole person'. (Interview 1)

Moreover, some of the interviews noted that official statistics could not be relied upon for all social groups, and that they were dependent on the types of data collected in each country and the rules and regulations on data collection. For example, Interviewee 11 described adding categories to the registration form so that they could account for gender in addition to sex within their citizens' assembly. Interviewee 3 described a similar experience and utilising self-reporting for categories such as religion, disability, and income status. We have to consider, though, that some countries will hold data regulations that prevent recruiting on the basis of ethnicity.

Practically, increasing the number of criteria needed in the recruitment process has cost implications by increasing the number of individuals or households that need to be contacted to ensure a representative sample. Moreover, Interviewees 5 and 8 described the challenges of recruiting across a range of criteria and differing response rates between social groups, for example:

'(...) I mean the fact that we had this high response rate gave us the opportunity to make a fairly good sample, I think. So we asked for additional information, of course, we asked for educational background, language skills. All this kind of stuff and that helped us. But at some point, I have to say it is still a problem that most of the people who do reply have a higher education'. (Interview 8)

Interviewee 5 adopted an approach to try to recruit in a staggered way:

'(...) in some other project we just did rolling inscriptions, so you first say yes to the already confirmed for the first 10%, and you confirm for the next 10. So you go up but in the end you have the challenge of, maybe you have 80% of your citizens, your participants together but then for the last 20%, you have a real difficulty to recruit people, because then you need people with migration background, with low education background. (...) I mean the hardest criteria. You will have to find them in the end, which will make it really hard to fulfil the last criteria. So it has its advantages, because you can confirm people quicker. But then in the end you will just have a hard time. Probably to finding the people you will still need in your according to yeah, the representative sample. So, yeah, we have to weigh the options'. (Interview 5)

Additionally, interviewees expressed concern over the feasibility and legitimacy of a process that recruited with too many criteria or intersections within a two-stage civic lottery process, ultimately pointing to the need to make decisions about which criteria would be focused on:

‘How many criteria you can have, how can you stand it up? And if there are kind of, really, a lot of different intersections that are important to what you’re doing [then] is it possible to specify all of them? And if you can’t, how do you justify the ones that you are going for? Which doesn’t mean you shouldn’t do it - it’s just the sort of thing that you think about.’ (Interview 13)

Interview Recommendation 2: Limit the recruitment selection criteria for feasibility; keep registration forms for recruitment simple and engaging.

2.1.3. Invitation approach

As part of the civic lottery process, interviewees discussed the use of different modes of invitation to encourage potential participants to sign up to the assembly. These modes included postal and telephone invitations, as well as door-knocking, both as a form of invitation and follow-up to encourage individuals to sign up to the citizens’ assembly. However, challenges with these modes of invitation, particularly postal invitations, were raised in multiple interviews. Interview 3 also identified that while receiving a postal invitation, not all demographics were likely to engage in the same way, leading to gaps in the recruitment that needed to be filled using other methods.

‘It’s actually in the invitation process that I think the main problem is, because we usually get way too few young people signing up to be able to make a good sortition within this group fairly. Often we just reach the number that we actually need to meet the youth quota so I would do more about the invitation process, having people go out to where young people are, and telling them that they’ve been invited. I would like to do more door knocking also within, like vulnerable communities that we know are less likely to sign up.’ (Interview 3)

Building on this, Interview 12 described the need to simplify the application process once potential participants decide to respond to the invitation. They described offering individuals options to self-identify, rather than creating lengthy processes that may become a barrier to participation.

'So the trade-off there is how do we make sure that it's not daunting? And then some people like, I'll solve this, I'm not gonna do this versus having quite a sophisticated selection process. That means we get a lot of diversity based upon different elements of the profile. So we will, for example, ask a question such as (...) do you identify as disabled something like that, or having a disability. But the temptation is to make sure that we list a whole load of different disabilities but then we're worried that that will mean that people spend much longer and or will be put off. So they end up not registering their interest'. (Interview 12)

In response to these challenges, Interviews 6 and 9 stressed the importance of relationship building through the recruitment process to encourage individuals to sign up, either through telephone invitations or a combination of postal invitations with door-knocking. Through this approach, both interviewees described being able to directly address the needs of potential participants and practice inclusion, reassuring potential participants about the process and directly addressing any concerns they may have, so that they can commit to participating.

'(...) [A]round a third of people who say I can't come won't ever come, for reasons that can't be addressed. So they have a wedding, they have to work that weekend or they get sick like on short-term notice, or they have to take care of a relative or a child and don't have anyone to take care of that person. But we found that around 60 to 70% of 'nos' could actually be addressed with the right conditions. So I'd say the largest case here was actually for example, elderly, that are not mobile enough anymore who could then come, provided they have a taxi that drives them. I think childcare did work pretty well in some cases, or would help in many cases'. (Interview 6)

Interview 13 similarly described the process they follow when organising citizens' assemblies, to arrange phone calls with participants following the selection process and ask open-ended questions, such as 'what do we need to put in place to make it easier for you to take part?' to ensure participants feel comfortable and their support needs can be addressed.

In addition to finding methods of supporting the two-stage lottery process, such as door-knocking, a third of the interviews described supplementing the two-stage lottery process as a way to ensure equality and inclusion.

'I think I think our favourite approach is yes, we should probably use a sortition random selection process, so that it has the legitimacy of the idea that people have

an equal opportunity to take part. But we need to recognise that not everybody is going to go, “yippee! I've got this letter through. That's for me. I'm going to forget all the discrimination and systemic oppression I've faced for decades and fill out this lovely form”. We need to recognise that we need to make lots of efforts to reach other groups. So, for example, for [Citizens' Assembly Xi], we worked through [a local charity campaigning against racism] to identify some more people of colour, after we saw that we weren't reaching our targets. We ran some processes in [another town], and we worked with the local food bank and organisation that supports homeless people to recruit some people onto the process as well. So it's a kind of a combination of the classic sortition process, but also supplemented with some targeted recruitment, as well'. (Interview 12)

Interviewee 12 highlights a critical tension between the idea of equal opportunity and the realities of systematic inequality in recruitment for citizens assemblies. Whilst sortition may bring perceived scientific and representative legitimacy to the process from the perspective of commissioning authorities, this claim to legitimacy ignores the context of historical discrimination and systematic oppression, challenging claims to neutrality in random selection and highlighting the structural barriers of participation. Practically, the interviewee supplements sortition with targeted outreach through trusted community-based organisations to mitigate against inequalities and aim for more substantive inclusion, highlighting the need to go beyond procedural fairness by acknowledging intersectional inequality. Interviewees 13 and 14 similarly noted that, while sortition is the primary recruitment method, additional outreach—such as working with local councils and voluntary sector organisations—was often necessary to engage marginalised groups and support their participation in the process.

'I think there's a sort of limited discussion about the criteria that the sortition process sometimes don't hit. And I think, particularly if you're working in a local area, there's the opportunity to reach out to community where there's not [...] different areas have different, different levels of civil society. But there's possibly the opportunity there to reach out through different schemes that [are] being run by the council through different groups, to get people to talk to people about the process and applying and support them to fill out the form'. (Interview 13)

'(...) [T]he other thing we do in those development ones is we do a lot of voluntary sector advocacy outreach there. So, we would then say to them, so if you've got refugees or asylum seekers that they're working with, or people that are feeling really quite marginalised in there, and they've got a group advocating for them.

Then we would go there and say, “can you make sure, if, firstly, if this lands on their doormat, that it's legitimate, they can really earn £500 from coming to this. And secondly, if you know of people that aren't getting it on their doormat but meet these criteria, could you speak to us, and we'll see if we can get them signed up for it”’. (Interview 1)

As well as considering the best methods to engage potential participants in a citizens' assembly, language was an important element identified in the interviews that impacted whether individuals felt included. For citizens' assemblies that incorporated multiple languages, interviewees described translating invitations into multiple languages to encourage inclusivity and participation, even if the whole of the process could not be offered in multiple languages:

‘(...) in the civic lottery, we included an insert that had the, I think, the eight most common languages spoken in [the city] and a paragraph, you know, essentially saying what the assembly was about. (...) Our budget didn't allow for, operation in languages other than English, but we made sure that participants were aware, that, you know, if they needed a whisper translator or, you know, just a little bit of support, that that was available to them and that they could indicate that to us, you know, if they had those needs (...) there was a few people who flagged, you know, sort of, like, that their English wasn't great. Nobody wanted a whisper translator, but we did have a lot of conversations about, okay. Do we need to slow down a little bit so that people can catch up? Or and I don't know that we ever got that perfect because there's always that design tension of trying to serve a big group that all has different needs. But those were live conversations’’. (Interview 1)

Interviewee 1 added that, although no participants requested a whisper interpreter, the organisers of Citizens' Assembly Sampi held ongoing conversations throughout the process to ensure sessions were inclusive, paying attention to factors such as maintaining an accessible speaking pace.

In addition to sending invitations in multiple languages, Interviewee 8 described including a QR code on invitations that potential participants could scan and watch a video offering a more personable invitation to the citizens' assembly process:

‘We sent out invitations via mail, and what we also did, because we know for immigrants it's often when they get, like, official looking letters (...) they are very

sceptic, and they throw it away very quickly. So, we decided to also put on it a QR code. And with the QR code and the website they were led to a website where we had videos and we had a Farsi and an Arabic and a Ukrainian person speaking on this video explaining the project and repeating the invitation like, in a personal way'. (Interview 8)

Interview Recommendation 3: Supplement lottery recruitment with targeted outreach and relationship-building.

2.1.4. Barriers to inclusion

As described in Deliverable 2.2, some provisions, such as childcare, have become standard best practice to widen access to participatory mechanisms. As with many of the elements previously discussed, trade-offs were identified in many of the logistical decisions. For example, Interviews 2 and 10 discussed rotating venues to bring the citizens' assembly to different areas of the city or region. While this improved access for some participants, Interview 10 described the logistics as a 'nightmare', as the rotation of venue involved facilitating the 'participants, transportation, accommodation, catering' and meeting the needs of participants across different venues was challenging and resulted in the team hiring a travel agency to support the process. Interview 2 similarly identified the process of changing venues as challenging and that venues differed in terms of acoustics, seating arrangements or available space.

Hosting parts or whole citizens' assembly processes online came with similar trade-offs. The interviews described capturing the needs of participants as part of the recruitment process to understand what support they may need, such as equipment or training, to ensure that they are able to participate fully in online sessions. Interview 14 described how giving training and support for people who did not usually have access to digital technology or online services was 'empowering' for participants, but that the support extended to online activities beyond the citizens' assembly. Interview 11 also highlighted the disparity of access to digital technologies and the service of support that they offered to 'older participants'. However, the same interviewee described being 'surprised because older people really connected by themselves and did not need any other support'. They described offering proactive support through the sessions of Citizens' Assembly Nu, which was used by one participant who was a recent immigrant, highlighting the importance of not making assumptions as to where the digital divide lies within a group of participants. It is important to note that the impact on participants of switching from in-person to online needs to be considered by citizens' assembly

organisers, as described in Interview 11. Hosting one session online in Citizens' Assembly Nu had a negative impact on group discussions, as discussions in breakout rooms 'sort of broke the interactive dynamics among the whole group' (Interview 11). This challenge could be mitigated by paying greater attention to inclusive dialogue and facilitation techniques.

Across the interviews, interviewees discussed a range of ways that they worked with participants to address concerns and support individuals to participate in citizens' assemblies, but it was not possible to address every need ahead of the citizens' assembly. However, Interview 14 stressed that while the onboarding process may not capture everything, a human-centred approach by the interviewees organising the citizens' assembly was paramount:

'You get in your onboarding, but you can never get everything, and you know, when people turn up and you've done the first session then just making sure you've got good debriefs factored into your team. So at the end, you know, like, okay, has anyone got any challenges they're having to deal with. And then, as a team working out what feels the most human centred way to do that'. (Interview 14)

Overall, recruitment and selection are critical for creating intersectional citizens' assemblies, but there are tensions and challenges when attempting to achieve diversity and inclusion in practices that go beyond statistical representativeness and tokenism. Here the interviewees show that whilst a two-stage civic lottery approach has been relied upon, intersectionality only emerges incidentally from this approach, risking the exclusion of marginalised groups. This means that, as a project team, we have to consider a number of trade-offs and tensions to bring intersectionality to the forefront of assembly design. There are particular strategies to ensure that we improve inclusion, such as targeted outreach, relationship building, careful and accessible communication and digital inclusion, and we need to tackle persistent barriers and constraints of participation. We highlight that interviewees emphasised a human-centred approach, continuous adaptation, and balancing trade-offs between fairness, feasibility, and intersectional inclusion.

Interview Recommendation 4: Treat intersectionality as a continuous practice, not a recruitment checkbox. Provide multilingual materials, logistical support (childcare, transport, digital training) and adaptive check-ins.

2.1.5. Information presented before and during the assembly

A key aspect of citizens' assemblies is engaging participants with expert knowledge and information, either through having experts join the assembly to share their expertise and/or preparing information for participants to review. As outlined throughout, it is important not to hold a narrow view of expertise:

'It was a very low information approach to the citizens' assembly. We did have short readings, or sometimes there was like a report that folks were invited to review beforehand. It wasn't hugely essential for them to like. Get through all that information. Then we would have, like usually a short staff presentation. But it was like maybe twenty min[ute] presentations and thirty min[ute] QA. Because again, it was, it wasn't a municipal scale. So we weren't tackling, you know, end of life care, things like that where you obviously need very rigorous expertise and a variety of perspectives. But in this case, we actually really focused more on surfacing the lived experience of participants'. (Interview 2)

Interviewee 2 shares that in some cases lived experience and storytelling are prioritised with a low information approach but acknowledges that in some cases more rigorous levels of expertise would be needed through the example of end-of-life care. Interviewee 2 goes on to give another example of expert information that they shared in an assembly:

'We were able to give them a report that the city had already created about it (...) that had identified a number of intersectional challenges around climate change. And we were like, this is the information that already exists. We gave a brief overview of it, and then we just did storytelling circles in a "fishbowl" model with different folks with different lived experiences. So first we had youth at the centre, then we had seniors at the centre. Then folks who had experiences of mental health and physical disabilities, and we had one with people of colour and Indigenous people and we just heard their stories for four hours, and the stuff that came out of those stories were so different than what was in the reports. I'm sure that information is somewhere in another report out there in the world, but I think I just mentioned this, because in the end, like there is wisdom in the group that can kind of surface if we give it enough time. And I think that's kind of the trade-off. When we have sometimes too much information, we lose time to surface (...) lived experiences, and all of that information that is sometimes not caught in a report, in an existing report. And so I think that would be again like where I feel like that's innovative is just finding a different way of accessing knowledge and creating

conditions where that knowledge can surface which sometimes is just talking for four hours about people's stories'. (Interview 2)

This reflects a key tension focused on how much expert input is necessary without overshadowing citizens' voices. If too much technical detail is shared, then deliberation may be reduced to repeating expert or technical knowledge or opinions:

'Sometimes there's like cognitive load that comes with a lot of new information. Or I've definitely read from the literature on assemblies the risk of people just kind of repeating what the experts said. And how I'm, like, [thinking of] different strategies to avoid that. And I think, kind of, the low information is one way. I don't think...again... It's not a good fit for all topics, but I think for some topics, and depending on the objective, it might not be a bad option'. (Interview 2)

Another issue when considering how much information should be presented is the timing and format of information sharing:

'It's always, always a decision. Do you give them information beforehand? And account for that, only half of them, read them? Or do you plan for them to come without any additional information so they have an even playing ground. And so, what we did was, during the deliberation phase and between the sessions of the citizen assembly, provide them with information, mainly with written down things, with handouts. And, during vital parts of the deliberation, there were experts present at the tables. And they could change tables also so that, if one table needed an expert for legal affairs, and, he or she was present at another table so that they could change'. (Interview 9)

Through a different approach, Interviewee 10 did invest in written materials but acknowledges uncertainty about whether participants engaged with the materials shared.

'In terms of contents before the assembly we work with experts and also scientific journalists to design different materials in terms of contents, but I don't know how many participants read all the documents. It was quite an effort. Anyway, for us was important to establish the different proposals of experts and the different reasons they give for their solutions. And then we design with them, like some debates among experts where participants could also interact with the experts, so they had the materials'. (Interview 10)

In these cases, and as Interviewee 2 suggests above, there may be a high cognitive burden if participants are asked to engage in extensive reading alongside deliberation tasks:

'The participants were very happy with it, but we believe that maybe it could have been more useful in the consolidation of knowledge and learning, if the formats were more digitalised or even gamified, because now we are very used to consuming content in this way. And we basically provided them with informatic kits that were, in plain language, very accessible, very easy to read. But in the end they were pretty extensive, and they had to, on top of having the task of solving the dilemma and listening to all the speakers, having to deliberate in separate rooms, small groups. They had to read that, and it was pretty demanding, you know, so maybe in different formats, it would be better for them, and maybe the content consolidation would have been improved a little slightly. But this is speculation'. (Interview 11)

'It's a 50-page long sort of report, but also, it's very visual, because it has many colours, has pictures, has infographics as it has already been curated in a way that anyone who reads it can understand it. But the thing is that the participants are already given the task to attend all the sessions to pay attention carefully to everything that they're being said or told to deliver it in a quality manner. They're following so many rules, and they're coming with this, with this passion to help to solve, so that once they're finished this whole because it's like a job they stay there for the whole day and on top of that, telling them you have to read this'. (Interview 11)

Here the interviewees suggest some digital and gamified formats to improve engagement. These insights point to a trade-off in the designing of citizens assemblies: ensuring informed deliberation without overwhelming participants. Whichever approach is taken, it is important that we adapt to diverse learning needs, styles and knowledge levels:

'I think one of the main challenges for climate assemblies is about information, contents and learning. How, what type of activities work for people with very different backgrounds, because the masterclass doesn't work. Masterclasses don't work, but debates among experts work (...) these guys don't agree on the solution. So it's sort of this kind of fight. But then you see how they focus their attention. But when there's a guy just talking, okay, climate change this and this.

And (...) I'm not sure, some people say that you have to work with emotion, but it will. You work too much with emotion? Then there's no reason there. Maybe you don't want to get in a fight. Maybe building scenarios. It's something that we are also considering building scenarios in the beginning with experts because it helps participants to see what kind of image could be the future depending on how we act. I think there's a big room for improvement on this content and learning process and activities'. (Interview 10)

Interviewee 10 identifies that expert debates and scenario building work to capture attention. Interviewee 14 similarly advocates for differentiated learning strategies including visuals, role play and participatory challenges:

'(...) generally making sure everybody can engage the challenges, the bright sparks, who think they know everything compared to the people who don't, and making sure those people are all involved on an equal basis, and they don't feel like I don't know anything. And that's where things like appreciative inquiry come in. It's a really great leveller for people, visuals, role play, all of those different activities which just stop people from being able to use words to make their sort of position elevate their position'. (Interview 14)

'We try, where possible, to avoid heavy written materials (...) So we use a diverse range of tools. We use appreciative inquiry techniques. We use participatory budgeting techniques. We use other sorts of creative visual generally, if you can [use] techniques to make sure that they get involved in that when it comes to neurodiversity. I mean, that's such a broad spectrum that it's quite - you really need to understand that [at] the onboarding stage'. (Interview 14)

These examples and experiences suggest that pedagogical design is as critical as content in supporting inclusive deliberation. Interviewees identify that assemblies increasingly use interactive formats to integrate expert input. Interview 14 also suggests other interactive methods to strengthen deliberation during the learning phase. One approach was goldfish bowl discussions, where experts share perspectives in small groups while participants observe and then ask questions, ensuring fairness and engagement. Another was role play, which helped participants move beyond dialogue into active deliberation, supported by tools like appreciative inquiry to bring diverse perspectives together. These methods aim to shift learning from passive to active engagement, supporting both comprehension and deliberation. Interviewee 14 also underscores the importance of onboarding to assess participants' needs

and tailor information presented to ensure that neurodiversity, preferred learning formats, and equitable participation are addressed.

In sum, for an inclusive citizens' assembly it is important that we engage with inclusive knowledge design that sees expertise as plural through combining lived experience and technical expertise. It is also important that information shared must be sufficient for informed decisions, but also accessible and presented in formats that reduce cognitive strain. The methods for sharing information should be pedagogically innovative, including debates, role play and appreciative enquiry to enhance engagement and equity. All of this content will need to be tailored, and methods of engagement need to ensure that they prevent exclusion and reinforce fairness.

Interview Recommendation 5: Design knowledge-sharing strategies that are accessible, interactive, and tailored to diverse learning needs.

2.2. Throughput Choices

Throughput design choices offer insight into not only intersectional approaches to equality and inclusion, but also an intersectional approach to deliberation through the running, facilitation, and deliberative stages of the citizens' assemblies. Throughput choices have to do with the nature of the deliberation, how the process of participation is organised (including the applicable rules), how the group makes its decisions, and in what context the participation takes place. This takes us beyond recruitment and selection, and towards inclusion during the deliberative phase of the citizen's assembly, as Interviewee 10 highlights:

'[Diversity] is one of the concerns of some of our partners, too, but, in my opinion, the civic lottery process already allows you to have this diversity and this inclusiveness. It's precisely one of the advantages of these mini-public mechanisms, right? It's not that they are coming, just the stakeholders or people more interested. With more resources in your design, you can already establish all the profiles you are interested in. Maybe you are not able to get every profile you want, because, of course, it's not mandatory for people receiving an invitation (...) If you give the time to the civic lottery process, and you design different profiles like, I think you can get at least a better diverse project compared to many other participatory projects and the challenge for me is to involve all of them properly into the discussions of the assembly'. (Interview 10)

In what follows, we will focus on five key themes that emerged when focusing on the ‘throughput’ stage of citizens’ assemblies: running the assembly, the role of facilitators, deliberation and consensus, engaging with politics and involving politicians, and including different perspectives in the assembly.

2.2.1. Running the assembly

Throughout the interviews, the interviewees spoke about an array of practices that they commonly used to gain a range of engagement from the assembly participants. For example, roundtables were a commonly cited method to encourage engagement and deliberation while running the assembly, intermixed with physical activities, so that participants are moving around and engaging in different ways:

‘I’m a fan of, just like the classical small round tables with citizens in small groups. It depends. There can be yeah, 6 to 8, maybe 10 maximum people. I like involving physical activities like, so you make people stand up and position themselves to show where, on the spectrum of, like the position or the opinion spectrum, they are located. So it’s a nice way to engage them, and also to make, to show how different the opinions are in the circle in the round. But just generally, I think the classical round tables do work quite well, and even though they are not new and innovative’. (Interview 5)

We were able to identify many elements of inclusive best practice that we can build on when running the pilot assemblies, including:

- Using post-its to share thoughts rather than having to share verbally (Interview 2);
- Ensuring equal lengths of time for speaking between participants (Interview 5);
- Silent rounds of working and expression (Interview 5);
- Switching people around in group work (Interview 3);
- Rounds to make sure everyone speaks (Interview 3);
- Submitting anonymous written questions to experts or getting the facilitator to read questions submitted by the participants (Interview 13);
- Drawing to express perspectives and views (Interview 13 and 14);
- Movement-based activities (Interview 13);
- Working in pairs (Interview 13);
- Mixture of small and big group discussions (Interview 2);
- Quiet rooms for participants to use as needed (Interview 2 and 13);

- Weaving trust⁶ style of relationship building between participants (Interview 15);
- One-to-one conversations between participants (Interview 15); and,
- Fidget toys (Interview 13).

Each of these methods is important for us to consider and engage with because they are utilised in practice to create inclusive spaces and build assemblies into the types of environments where participants feel included and feel that they can participate; to gain a range of perspectives and voices during the assembly process; and to lead towards an intersectional mode of deliberation. Engaging in a range of activities is important to keep the assembly active and fun, whilst making sure that the voices of the participants are heard:

‘I can tell you what I think are some of the things I think are really important in designing and managing a process, and I think one of them is about having fun. And I’m reluctant to say that’s particularly innovative. But I think it’s really, really important. I think people want to enjoy themselves. I think they want to leave a process feeling like they’ve had their voice heard, but actually it was all right, and at some points it was a bit of a laugh’. (Interview 12)

Another common practice for the interviewees was starting the assembly by collaboratively agreeing on ground rules, which reflects good practice recommended by the OECD:

‘We also use it [OECD principles] as a first step in, like, practicing deliberation. So we’ll usually have them speak in pairs, work in groups, decide in groups what the three most important things are, put them all up in the wall, have them go up and vote, collect them together, and then, next time, have them printed on a nice poster that everyone can see and hanging, and for the rest of the sessions’. (Interview 2)

Interviewees explain that they often start with having some ground rules as non-negotiable (e.g., not using discriminatory language) (Interview 13), and then engage in collaborative design of the ground rules with the participants:

‘We worked with the group to co-create ground rules for how they wanted to have respectful interactions with each other (...) And, we had people commit to those ground rules (...) So it was very, co-created with participants, which always

⁶ Weaving trust is a type of relational experience i.e., short local workshops run by Leaders and/or Organisers of Citizens UK to create opportunities for people from different organisations to meet. For more information see: <https://www.citizensuk.org/leadership-training/organising-together-across-difference/> [accessed on 13 October 2025].

creates, you know, some broader sense of ownership than just if we do that or dictate them ourselves'. (Interview 1)

These ground rules are largely concerned with being respectful, polite, and not interrupting, but they rarely touch on engaging with or reflecting on privilege and power, which in turn would position the participants on equal footing (akin to the Model 6 approach developed in Deliverable 2.3). Therefore, a challenge from an intersectional perspective is how we make these inequalities visible in the process of setting ground rules. We will continue to explore these more complex aspects of setting ground rules as we develop our pilots.

Interview Recommendation 6: Adopt inclusive design features: collaborative ground rules, creative engagement tools and relational trust-building.

2.2.2. Facilitators

As the more theoretical work on citizens' assemblies has shown us in Deliverables 2.2 and 2.3, facilitation is a critical aspect in terms of inclusion, equality, and good deliberation. Interviewee 14 shared that they see professional facilitation as vital to the functioning of an assembly, as facilitation requires specialised skills (Interview 2), the ability to manage complex group dynamics and maintain neutrality in the name of legitimacy and avoiding bias (Interview 12).

Interviewee 2 elaborates further on this by focusing on the need for trauma-informed support to participants during facilitation as deliberation can be emotionally charged and challenging. This is particularly relevant when engaging marginalised groups that may have direct lived experience of the topic being discussed. Interviewee 13 adds a further layer to this, by noting the potential need to address micro-aggressions during assembly sessions. This highlights the facilitators' role in safeguarding psychological safety and promoting respectful dialogue, which is even more pertinent in an intersectional assembly that engages marginalised voices.

Moreover, when trying to engage with a range of voices or hear from particular groups, it is important that facilitators challenge power dynamics. Interviewee 12 provides a concrete example of adapting facilitation to amplify young people's voices, describing the creation of a youth-only break-out group to counteract adult-dominated spaces:

'We really want to try to make sure that young people's voices are heard meaningfully. So you know, if you use a sortition process and it's a fairly small

group that you're working with (...) It means you'll get a sprinkling of young people in the room, which is great, and I think too many of us like tick the box "I care about young people's involvement, that's covered", but I think we need to do much, much more to make sure that their voice is meaningfully heard and, and is present. And so, because it's inevitably, it's a kind of adult... maybe not inevitably, but it transpires that it's a kind of adult dominated space and we try and shoehorn young people into that. And we're really aware of that. But we will do things like you know, we'll say and now we're going to go into random groups. But we'll actually have a young people's group. We've randomly selected so that that group is of young people so that they can start to build relationships with each other'. (Interview 12)

This approach reflects the intersectional practices that we are aiming for by acknowledging structural inequalities and directly challenging them by designing interventions to ensure meaningful participation which goes beyond tokenism. This approach also relates to the model in Deliverable 2.3 focused on Subaltern Counterpublics. Ultimately, the broader implication of these experiences of facilitation is that facilitation is not just about process management but also about actively challenging power imbalances that exist within a group of people.

However, there is a balance to strike when engaging with facilitation, again reinforcing the need to have experienced facilitators in assemblies, as it is important that the assembly is not steered too much. Interviewee 3 grapples with the tension between structured facilitation and democratic spontaneity:

'I mean, we don't always have facilitators at each table. Sometimes we have no facilitators at the tables, but, like facilitators walking around and kind of being more looking at, but not directly steering the process at the table'. (Interview 3)

On the one hand, facilitators help to maintain order and inclusivity. On the other hand, too much control risks undermining the democratic educational value of participants learning through negotiation and chaos, as Interviewee 3 continues:

'On the other hand, I do also think that citizen assemblies have, like a democratic educational perspective, and I think you would lose some of that if you had like these like perfect facilitators at every table. So, I think there's also something to be gained from the chaos'. (Interview 3)

The tension explored here suggests that facilitation strategies should be context-specific, and it is important to reflect on the best ways to balance guidance with participant autonomy in facilitation practices. This may suggest needing a particular frame and philosophy for our facilitation approach in the pilots. Interviewee 12 reflects on important foundations of this for our project:

'I think it comes from (...) a very, very basic principle that I'd hope our facilitators hold dear, and that is a fundamental belief in the possibilities of people and a belief that we are fundamentally good, and that we enjoy each other's company largely, and we enjoy collaboration and we are not driven by competition. Unlike the economic system that we're all stuck in. So, I think if you, if you have that at heart, then you will really enjoy and cherish moments when you're with participants. Also, I think a recognition that for a lot of people (...) It can be quite challenging and quite tense just to be in that space, irrespective of what you actually do in that space just getting into the room can be really difficult. So, we've got to try our absolute utmost to try to make people feel relaxed when they are in there. And I think that is about it's about showing that we're human as well. So not trying to cover up if we make mistakes, not making it an over polished kind of conference type process, but instead, one that really leans into the fact that we're all working together to try to achieve this thing, and there'll be mistakes, and there'll be problems, and there'll be great times, and there'll be shit times. But we'll, we'll get there in the end. It's a real belief and love of people'. (Interview 12)

Here Interviewee 12 articulates a facilitation ethos grounded in optimism and relationality, by believing in people's capacity for collaboration, embracing imperfection and fostering a relaxed, human-centred environment. Interviewee 7 reinforces this by stressing the importance of personal rapport and individual attentiveness:

'I think that personal rapport is very important. And then it's again individual... like, if we have people with mobility issues where we make sure that someone always by that side, if they need a hand or whatever. If we see that they're, that some of the youth are really shy. We go up to them and we say, "Hi, how are you doing" like, it's just a being very aware of who's in the room, and how they seem like if they seem like they need something, or they are doing well, and then, usually quite quickly people warm up and they get like they start to trust'. (Interview 7)

These insights frame facilitation as relational work, not just procedural. It is work that requires empathy, adaptability, and trust building. These are all important themes to reflect on when building assemblies focused on intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation. In sum, for facilitation we have to balance skilled facilitation with participatory control so as not to disempower participants; and engage with intersectionality in practice by ensuring that facilitators actively acknowledge and dismantle power hierarchies and create equitable spaces. The emotional and relational dimensions of facilitation need to be put front and centre, while we also ensure flexibility and responsiveness to adapt to group dynamics, logistical constraints, and participants' diversity.

Interview Recommendation 7: Embrace a human-centred approach, treating each participant as an individual and adapting support accordingly. Incorporate open-ended questions during recruitment and facilitation to understand individual needs and build trust.

2.2.3. Deliberation and consensus

Many of the interviewees highlight consensus as a core strength and as an important aspect of the legitimacy of an assembly. There is, however, a significant challenge with regards to those issues that are more controversial than others. Interview 10 observes that participants often avoid contentious topics and gravitate towards common ground recommendations to avoid tackling divisive issues. They give a concrete example of this:

[describing a citizens' assembly that used political dilemmas to structure discussions] It was very interesting because we saw how participants tended to avoid controversial issues, they tended to go for the common ground. The common ground recommendations, and many times that meant that it was not impactful recommendations, because, of course, a communication campaign, everyone agrees on that. But when you talk about, if we should limit the meat consumption and production in [this region]. When this is one of the main economic sectors of the agro industry in [this region], which is a major industry in [this region] that becomes more complex and it was very interesting, seeing how they tended or tried to avoid these controversial issues, you know, and we make the comparison between the Parliament and the Assembly in the Parliament. They fight for it, they are opposing views, and they are fighting the whole time. In the Assembly, they avoided that they prefer not to be that aggressive (...) so we

needed to force them to go for the controversial issues where there are trade-offs involved. And then you have to make a recommendation'. (Interview 10)

Pushing participants towards a more agonistic engagement with the issues, so that they are not avoiding tensions but instead engaging with them is central to this issue. Otherwise, as this interviewee articulates, the recommendations become diluted and less impactful. There is a question here for us to consider, as consensus seeking may inadvertently discourage engagement with bold or transformative proposals, which needs to be reflected on, particularly when engaging marginalised groups in a diverse assembly, there needs to be tension and conflict. So, as Interviewee 10 states, there is a need to sometimes force engagement with controversial issues to address real trade-offs instead of only reaching safe compromises.

The tensions surrounding consensus are also discussed by other interviewees. Interviewee 9 describes consensus as an ideal end point, but proposes that final reports should include minority positions if unanimity has not been achieved to ensure that dissenting voices are not erased, and deliberative integrity is maintained:

'The ideal endpoint would have been that, that they reach a consensus, you know, on good measures. But, we also accounted for that there could be minority votes, so to speak, on measures, which are not, not agreed upon by all the members. But the ideal thing would have been that they agreed upon all the measures. Now? And mainly, this, this was successful. Now there were some minority votes, so to speak, that we, accounted for in the citizens report also, but mainly, consensus was reached'. (Interview 9)

Interview 5 proposes a similar approach, highlighting that, while consensus often emerges through the deliberation, alternative mechanisms do exist for areas that are unresolved, so that different opinions are still shared if consensus has not been reached through compromise. For an assembly aiming to take an intersectional approach it is important to consider the ways in which our project will deal with such challenges to create good deliberation and inclusive practices.

Some of the interviewees were involved in assemblies that took a more formalised approach to consensus through voting thresholds:

'In order to be valid, they had to get more than 50% of both of the participants, but actually to be incorporated in the final recommendations, the consensus had to be

at least 60, 66% of the votes. So that was what we did. Yeah. And every recommendation got more than 66%. Of course, there was some people disagreeing with some recommendations. But still, ah, consensus was pretty high’.

(Interview 10)

Interviewee 10 required at least 66% support for recommendations to be included, whilst Interview 9 used majority and super majority thresholds, alongside iterative voting for rephrasing until consensus was reached:

‘We had, in the plenary, the same thing as well. And it’s a kind of voting system, so to speak. Yeah? Everyone could have thumbs ups, thumbs down, or I have a question. Yeah? And then we count it for, we counted for all the phrasing and the wording, as long as it took to reach a consensus of this, of individual measures’.

(Interview 9)

While thresholds may provide clarity, they do not guarantee or may even stifle inclusivity and intersectional deliberation as they risk privileging majority views unless paired with mechanisms that surface and present minority concerns, as discussed in Deliverable 2.3. To combat some of these challenges, Interviewees 2 and 6 spoke about their engagement with Deep Democracy:

‘The Deep Democracy facilitation method is really based on like is everyone in agreement of this? And then you’re not raising your hand. What do you need to come along like? What do we need to add to this or modify so that we get as close to consensus as possible, or so we can surface at least what those tensions or concerns are about, even if they’re not ultimately what the group decides to do. But at least those voices are heard. And so it’s really seeking throughout the process, like, what do you need to come along, or why? What is the resistance that you’re feeling?’. (Interview 2)

Interviewee 6 reflected that deep democracy enabled them, in a more in-depth way, to explore consensus, agreement and disagreement, describing that the method improved group decision-making by focusing on minority or opposing views. The approach assumes that dissent often reflects concerns shared by others, even those who initially agree with the majority. By giving space to these concerns and asking what changes would make opponents accept the decision, the process aims to strengthen decisions and avoid simple majority rule.

This method, therefore, focuses on surfacing resistance and minority perspectives throughout the process, using different tools and methods to adapt proposals and bring people along by accommodating their concerns, improving decisions and reducing polarisation. The method is focused on reframing consensus as a dynamic negotiation rather than only a focus on a binary yes/no outcome. Interviewee 13 draws on a 'like it, love it, loathe it' tool to gauge perspectives and refine proposals, while Interviewee 9 draws on voting signals (thumbs up and down) to iteratively adjust recommendations.

An important point to note around this issue emerges from Interviewee 13, who stresses that legitimacy of consensus is not about the consensus itself or universal agreement, but instead about the fairness of the process, prioritising reason giving and equal voice and not unanimity. Overall, there are some trade-offs that emerge around deliberation and consensus that must be considered when engaging in inclusion, equality, diversity, and intersectionality:

- If we aim for consensus and agreement this may lead to safe, low impact recommendations, so it is important to encourage engagement with controversial issues and trade-offs;
- Voting thresholds may risk marginalising dissent (which may come from those already marginalised) so we need to push towards methods like Deep Democracy;
- Whilst formal voting systems may be clearer and less time consuming, it is important to focus on iterative, dialogic approaches which better capture the complexity of participants' perspectives and experiences.

Interview Recommendation 8: Use iterative, dialogic approaches to consensus that surface minority voices and positions and avoid tokenism.

2.2.4. Engaging with politics and involving politicians

When engaging with politics and politicians in a citizens' assembly, there is potential for problematic power dynamics to be reinforced and perpetuated. We have to consider carefully the way in which we engage with politics and politicians when creating assemblies that are focused on intersectional inclusion, equality, and good deliberation. This necessitates pushing our understanding of 'power relations' beyond considering power relations between social groups or individuals and instead expanding it to consider, and design around, power imbalances with politicians and power holders. For citizens' assemblies to be intersectional spaces then, we need to ensure that they are accessible and meaningful for marginalised groups as opposed to only the already politically engaged citizens. Engaging power-holders can bring this meaning into the space:

'The plenary session was super super great, and people really felt that they were in a dignified space, because this is a place where it's usually it's a government delegation of the [City 4]. So there are many, many political acts and stuff, it's carried out so you could see that that place was important. But the working groups part, which was smaller rooms, they were not really that happy. But us the organisers, they were super super excited. Because political representatives were joining the session in the end to receive their recommendations, to provide them with the roadmap of how are they planning to deploy the citizen mandate?'. (Interview 11)

But it can also have the effect of reinforcing power structures, if those powerholders involved are allowed to dominate deliberation. Politicians are engaged at different stages of the process, depending on the approach: some are engaged through the commissioning authority, some are bought in during the process, and/or often engaged at the end of the process to receive recommendations and engage in dialogue, highlighting the importance and impact of the work that the citizens have done in the assembly, whilst maintaining participant autonomy. Interviewee 14 gives a concrete example of this:

'We allow for a bit of dialogue in that other agencies don't allow that. It's just you present your recommendations. They take [those] away and then they'll respond later. But we didn't do that, we, we present the recommendations, and then we ask those that are receiving them if they've got any questions about those recommendations, and then the assembly members answer their questions based on their conversations that they've had. So, we allow time for a bit of that dialogue before they leave that room. I think that. I mean, we've always done that. So, you know, I think everybody else is doing it. But they're not... apparently that doesn't get done elsewhere. So, I think that's something you might want to think about making sure you factor in the time'. (Interview 14)

This approach aims to mitigate the risks of tokenism and reinforce the principle that the deliberation and recommendations belong to citizens and are being shared with political elites/powerholders. At the same time, allowing for interaction, during the assembly, between the assembly participants and politicians potentially mitigates the risk that the latter will simply not follow-up on the recommendations.

In addition, it is important throughout that the potential impact of the recommendations is not oversold, and instead there is a focus on long term relationship building between citizens and institutions, as policy-making cannot be changed quickly:

'So one change is our stronger focus on relationship and relationship building and mutual understanding trust building vice versa to or as opposed to recommendations policy recommendations. So, we kind of started with the idea [that] we can use the one-day format as a feedback tool for parliamentarians where they can get short term feedback for a complex topic. And we realised that's not possible. It's only one day and individual parliamentarians are structurally not able to decide on anything alone so they're not the right ones to address. When it comes to recommendations, they can just take it back into their party and kind of influence there, but giving people the idea they can influence political decision-making (...) through a one-day format would be just naïve'. (Interview 6)

There is an important shift highlighted here. Interviewee 6 is advocating for a move away from transactional recommendation delivery and toward relational engagement and mutual understanding, which aligns with our intersectionality principles as it prioritises empowerment over symbolic participation or box ticking exercises. In other words, the citizens' assembly can be the opportunity to reflect on potential recommendations and solutions, but maybe even more, to reflect on how to build long-term relationships to jointly cope with the issues discussed and work together with decision makers in long term relationships of accountability. This implies using the citizens' assembly as the basis for a future interactive approach for addressing issues in a way that also takes into account the most marginalised social groups.

When engaging with politicians, Interviewees 5 and 15 stress the importance of engaging in a non-partisan approach, to bring in a range of perspectives:

'The Knowledge Committee should be composed of people [with] which all the political parties in the Parliament can agree on. So, what we did - [in Citizens' Assembly Theta] was that every political party of the Municipality Board could propose one candidate for the Knowledge Advisory Board, for example, like that. So, it really should make sure that also the opposition party has a say in (...) who's becoming member of that board, so that they can't say in the end this was a biased or only leading political party project. Again, perspectives should be balanced, so having different views on it. And, as I said, I have a pro con, or maybe ones who are depends on the topic. Right? Is it someone who is more, maybe

environmentally oriented, someone who's more business oriented. In our last advisory board, we made sure we had at least one nature conservation representative or NGO representative, someone from agriculture, someone from business, someone from science, a university. So just to make sure that there's also a good mix between practitioners and people who work in a more theoretical setting'. (Interview 5)

According to the quote above, including diverse political, sectoral and expert perspectives strengthens the credibility of the assembly.

In sum, when involving those holding power in an intersectional citizens' assembly it is important to:

- challenge traditional hierarchies;
- centre citizens' voices;
- avoid political co-optation;
- engage politicians without undermining the citizens' deliberative autonomy;
- build relationships and trust between citizens and power holders; and,
- ensure balanced representation.

Interview Recommendation 9: Engage politicians carefully: maintain citizen autonomy, ensure balanced representation of perspectives, and prioritise relationship-building.

2.2.5. Including different perspectives

To create a diverse and inclusive assembly, we need to find ways to ensure that different perspectives are included throughout the entire assembly. A significant part of inclusive practice is recruitment, but to reach inclusion there needs to be a provision for multiple entry points for citizens to engage beyond recruitment. Interviewee 13 identifies that there are other ways to bring different perspectives into the assembly, not limiting this to recruitment quotas:

'But there are, there are potentially other ways of bringing intersectionality into the processes in terms of who's speaking, that's a very formulaic way of getting evidence. But like, yeah, in [Citizens' Assembly Tau], we had different community groups come in. So we had a group of people, one of the most effective in the group of people. The disability group people, disabled people's organisation with people with various different types of disability. And there were quite a lot of

intersectionalities within that group and tabled how we structure people table by table, going and just chatting to that group about their experiences. And so there are other ways of bringing in specific intersectionalities. And it isn't just about recruitment. But recruitment is obviously an important area'. (Interview 13)

Interviewee 14 also highlights the importance of these conversations during the assembly:

'(...) there were people in that room who were also, you've got the intersectionality between disability and gender. So there was lots of conversation there about what it means to be a woman in a wheelchair and other disabilities there'. (Interview 14)

Interviewee 13 gives some examples here of how to integrate different perspectives through inviting community groups to share lived experiences during deliberations. Another way of doing this would be to ensure that those most affected by the issue contribute to agenda setting:

'You can run a workshop, you can go and run a workshop or go to those people [organisations that represent those most affected by the issue] and talk about the process, and talk about the question, and ask for their feedback and that would be my preferred way of doing it (...) You just ask the organisation what they think and you hope that they're in touch with [and] (...) properly in tune with the people that they're purporting to represent'. (Interview 13)

Interviewee 13 also proposes that assemblies should start by acknowledging participants' existing knowledge and experiences:

'I would now, anyway, for a few years would have started any assembly with ways of people discussing the part of the issue or kind of their attitude to the issue, or something before you give them any information in order to try and get across this point, that you're validating their own knowledge and their own experience that they're bringing to the process. It's not just about giving them new information, and everything that they thought or felt before is not relevant'. (Interview 13)

By doing this, the facilitators signal respect for experiential knowledge, and encourage sharing personal and community insights, enriching the deliberation process. This can also happen when participants bring in indirect experiences from families and friends, expanding the range of experiences shared:

'(...) People talk to the family and friends about the experiences. And then, obviously, there's an interaction there and then they're bringing that back into the room as well and just to flag that, too. So definitely, for example, had examples of people talking about the experience of their neighbour with who has a certain sort of disability, for example, and kind of how would you meet that?'. (Interview 13)

These approaches move beyond tokenistic inclusion towards participation and embedding marginalised voices throughout the process. Interviewee 1 takes these examples further by sharing their experience running public workshops, online surveys and open community sessions (what they call 'satellite' or 'parallel' processes) alongside the assembly:

'We were running the assembly and a few other, satellite processes or parallel processes that fit into the Assembly. And the City at the same time was also running its sort of general public engagement. So, online surveys about the [city-wide] plan, public workshops that anybody could attend. For the Assembly, you know, the things that we did that were more sort of standard practice. You know, we had an evening where anybody from the community could come and meet with the Assembly and, you know, talk around small tables and sort of have those generate ideas that the Assembly could choose to take forward or not'. (Interview 1)

These approaches broaden participation beyond only the selected citizens' assembly participants. Similarly, Interview 15 emphasises story telling as a tool for empowerment:

'It's very much about storytelling and the people that are closest to the problem being able to communicate the solution like we, we believe that. But the people that are most impacted by things know what needs to change. So we don't like to just tell someone else's story. We like to develop their leadership skills and their ability to tell their own story and have agency to bring about change in their scenario (...) You know there's no shame in talking about these issues. The shame is in the systemic problem. It's not in the people who are experiencing these things. And we find that the more we can encourage and equip people to share their own story, the more they find that there are other people in exactly the same boat, and then they build up this agency and this power to do something about it'. (Interview 15)

Interviewee 15 describes their position that the people most affected by the issue should be in the room and articulate their experiences, building their agency and collective power, reframing participants as knowledge holders rather than passive consultees. However, this inclusion of diverse experiences has to be approached carefully:

'You know, for instance, there was lots of, because one Assembly member was vision impaired, one was in a wheelchair. You know, like, you can see their voices directly in the recommendations, in a way that really had an impact. The flip side of that is that in some cases, having diversity in the room where there wasn't sufficient awareness within broader society about certain groups' experiences also puts a lot of pressure on somebody in that room who's in a deep minority. And, you know, for instance, during the assembly, there was one process where somebody made a [comment that another participant found hurtful about who counted as a community member]. And so that's the flip side of the you know, like, people who bring diversity into this assembly, I've seen in many different cases, have enriched the assembly's outputs. But sometimes there's a burden on that person'. (Interview 1)

Through this example, Interviewee 1 explains that while diversity and inclusion enrich recommendations and impact, it can also place an excessive burden on individuals who are representing the 'deep minority' position, giving the example of a micro-aggression which occurred in a past assembly. This reiterates the need for trauma-informed facilitation and safeguarding in the space.

To ensure inclusion, Interviewee 8 also identifies that it is important that the facilitation team itself is diverse and inclusive:

'What worked really well was that my team was as inclusive as the body, the sample, our participants. That was interesting also for me, because I did it for a practical reason. I just needed people who spoke the languages. And I realised that is something very interesting. (...) as the person responsible for a huge event with lots of people involved. I mean, we were at the end 50 or 60 people in the room (...) for example, we had a situation where the Ukrainians got really excited about something, and then I saw that my team member, my translator. She just handled the situation, and I do speak (...) Slavic languages. So, I understood more or less what she was saying, and I realise that she's handling it. Otherwise, I would have had to step in right at some point and say, people calm down (...) And she

did it quite well, but she also did it in a very Ukrainian way. I would not have. Yeah, I would have spoken differently to Germans. I have lots of experience with people in the Slavic countries. So, that was interesting that, like my team, that they handled situations in their way, because they know their people'. (Interview 8)

This quote highlights the value of multilingual and culturally diverse facilitation teams that match the diversity of the group so that they can de-escalate tensions, foster trust, and enhance responsiveness, aligning with the intersectional principles of our project. This observation connects to the recognition in Deliverable 2.2 of the need to consider and reflect on our own positionality as project team members.

Interviewee 6 and 15 expand the idea of creating a safe and trusting space:

'Another one is active listening, which runs on different terms as well, but just trying to make us listen differently than we do. Normally, we're just waiting for the other one to pause to make our own opinion. So, we always try to or we always sit people together in groups of two, in the beginning to get to know each other and to just share their own experiences on the topic over the course of 10 minutes. Only one person can ask, and the other person can answer, and the first person who asks is writing things down and really just trying to understand more and summarise what he or she has understood. And this sets a mood for the whole assembly, or for the whole for the whole day, that people kind of learn to actively listen from the beginning'. (Interview 6)

'The key part of community organising is the one-to-one conversation (...) where you can get to know one another's interests (...) often, there's little ways of drip feeding little parts of community organising training, like encouraging someone to think a bit more deeply about what they're really wanting and why they're in this role (...) what are you passionate about? (...) trying to have a conversation which helps people to just reconnect with who they really are and what they really want to see change is really helpful'. (Interview 15)

These interviewees highlight practices like active listening exercises and one-to-one conversations as key tools to build trust and empathy among participants, set a tone of mutual respect, navigate differences and address power imbalances. These relational strategies are critical for intersectional inclusion as they actively reduce barriers for meaningful contributions across participants.

Overall, this leads to some key findings. Intersectionality should be seen as an ongoing process and journey in the citizens' assembly rather than a tick box exercise. To do this there needs to be a range of strategies to engage a range of perspectives during agenda setting, diverse people engage in facilitation, range of testimonies shared and several forms of engagement throughout. It is important that participants are given power and agency throughout the process via sharing lived experience and becoming involved early on to ensure that those most affected by decisions are central to the process. However, we also have to factor in the risks and responsibilities that these forms of engagement raise as diversity can create vulnerability, so organisers and facilitators must anticipate this possibility and mitigate harm. We should try to create a relational infrastructure throughout the assembly to engage in trust building practices to engage in intersectionality-oriented deliberation.

Interview Recommendation 10: Broaden participation through parallel processes and storytelling, while mitigating risks of burden on participants from marginalised groups.

2.3. Output Choices

Finally, the output-dimension of designing a citizens' assembly demonstrates the results and effectiveness of the various approaches adopted by the interviewees, focusing first on developing inclusive recommendations and then on ensuring that those recommendations have an impact on relevant power-holders.

2.3.1. Developing inclusive recommendations

Across the interviews, the goal of each of the citizens' assemblies was to develop recommendations as the primary output in various formats. Although some of the recommendations were described as guidelines or visions for the future, all of them were developed with the intention of informing the relevant powerholders who could then influence policy based on the evidence from the citizens' assembly. Importantly, many of the interviewees reflected on the importance of 'public voice' and involvement of the public in decision-making processes.

'Well, I mean, I'll describe some of our goals for the assembly and then, you know, the most obvious direct one is to influence the City's policies, and to provide

enhanced public voice amongst all the other pressures on decision makers. (...) We were building on [a] legacy of past collaboration with them that had been quite successful at the time. And so one of my goals was to try to, both deepen [the city's] internal capacity for doing this sort of work and commissioning and responding to this type of work. Because it's a city that doesn't have a framework for how it does public participation'. (Interview 1)

Some of the interviews described introducing explicit methods of ensuring that powerholders heard the voices of participants directly, rather than implicitly through the recommendations produced by the citizens' assembly. These methods can be seen as an attempt to bridge the gap between those with the power to make decisions and those without, giving voice to the public's wishes and hopes which go beyond a list of recommendations, as described in Interview 5.

'And then in some assembly, we also asked the citizens to write a like a foreword or something like so we have a, like, a letter that the citizens write to the policy-makers (...) that could include, however, their experience of working together. That puts together like, again, their overarching goals and wishes and hopes which is also nice and again (...) includes more these overarching goals.' (Interview 5)

While ensuring the voices of participants are heard by decision-makers is one aspect of addressing power imbalances, this does not ensure that decision-makers are held accountable for listening to or implementing recommendations from citizens' assemblies, which is an ongoing challenge for citizens' assemblies more broadly.

Interview Recommendation 11: Design outputs and engagement strategies that amplify marginalised voices and challenge power imbalances. Include participant-authored elements (e.g., letters, forewords) alongside recommendations to convey overarching goals, lived experiences, and minority positions.

2.3.2. Having an Impact

Some of the interviews described the follow-ups that were built into the process of the citizens' assembly to ensure that recommendations were delivered on, or if they could not be, to offer an explanation to participants as to why this had not been possible.

'The recommendations were delivered last summer, and it's now going through a follow through process that we build into our assemblies where the City delivers how it acted on the on the recommendations of the assembly and gives that written report back to the assembly, we then have the assembly give another piece of feedback back to the City. So trying to create a lot of iteration within the process in order to deal with some of the challenges of follow[-up] that exist within the assembly world'. (Interview 1)

Alternatively, Interview 6 describes selecting six participants to form an oversight group that represented the citizens' assembly. The group continued to be involved in the implementation process following the assembly. However, not all citizens' assemblies are able to build follow-up into the process or continue to support participants beyond the assembly. When asked what interviewees would do with unlimited resources, this continued engagement formed part of some of the responses.

'It might be something about support afterwards for participants. And what you can do with that. Yeah, I mean, I'd start, I'd start - a proper evaluation that comes back a year on and 2 years on and sees what the impact has been. And if the budget's unlimited, trying to disentangle the impact of the assembly from other things that may have impacted on that policy area for sure and tracking the participant impact on the participants like everything evaluation that doesn't happen very often'. (Interview 13)

Not all citizens' assemblies have a built-in process to ensure the impact of recommendations on policy. Some of the interviewees described not being able to specifically track the impact of the process (Interview 7) or that a change in government following the citizens' assembly complicated the process (Interview 10). While acknowledged as a challenge, holding the decision-makers to account and tracing the impact of the outputs of citizens' assembly processes was highlighted as being important to participants.

'I mean, I've run about 40 of these processes over the years, I suppose, and without fail, every single one at the end people say, "oh, we don't want to go anywhere (...)", at least like two-thirds of them want to carry on, because they're hugely knowledgeable. They've committed lots of time and energy and they want to make sure their recommendations are taken seriously so they want to push for change'. (Interview 12)

As demonstrated by Interview 12, an outcome reported in some of the interviews was that participants felt more engaged in democratic processes. Several interviews described the ‘transformational’ experience for participants who have taken part in a citizens’ assembly process. Additionally, Interview 14 described how for some participants, the experience they gained within the citizens’ assembly was able to help them gain employment or go into further study and how practitioners promoted skills used and gained within the process, giving participants certificates to evidence the experience that they had gained.

‘(...) we do a matrix. And they answer which of those [skills] they think they've used in this. And the reason we do that is we can send certificates to them as well to say they've used these skills. And so, as I said right at the beginning, we're all for the people that don't normally get involved in things, and if they don't normally get involved in things, not always, but for some of those who have got no qualifications this has been a hugely enjoyable and educational process. And you get people saying they want to go back to study again or this looks really interesting, how do we do this? So we would give them a certificate of participation which they can then use to get jobs or to give them an edge on their next job [interview and] shows a bit of civic duty, civic engagement. And just thinking about that actually, there is normally someone who we help get a job out of this process. Out of every process there's normally one person at least, that says “I found this fascinating, can you help me?”’. (Interview 14)

In addition to the matrix described in Interview 14, the interviews outlined the methods usually implemented to capture the experiential data of participants through interviews or surveys, examples of which can be found in Section IV of this deliverable (i.e., the secondary analysis of evaluation data from existing citizens’ assemblies). Most of the interviews mentioned conducting pre- and post-assembly surveys with participants. Interview 6 recommended giving participant’s time within the citizens’ assembly to complete surveys and that from their experience, it encouraged a high participation rate. However, some of the interviewees discussed using evaluations throughout the process to help guide their practice and so that they could adapt as needed to best support participants.

‘At the end of the first phase of the assembly, around the midpoint, and then at the end. And after we received feedback in those two sort of developmental evaluations that we did during the process, we sat with folks, and we had an open conversation about, “okay, here are the themes that we heard from you”. Here are some of the specific comments from specific individuals. That included at least

one person who felt like, you know, we asked people, did they feel like the discussion materials were biased or unbiased? And all these different questions. And our numbers are really good as far as, you know, like, if you look at you know, I think we're in the 90 percent for many of the different areas as far as people feeling like we were meeting their needs and unbiased, etcetera. But we also address the tails. You know, like, if there was one person who really felt that the materials were biased, we invited conversation about that. We said, "please come and talk to us if there's something that you're concerned about". (Interview 1)

Similarly, Interview 15 described attempting to build a 'culture of learning' through practice, using evaluation throughout the process to reflect on practice and ensure inclusivity and good deliberation and to inform changes in practice, as needed.

'We'll do an evaluation, you know how generally we start with, how are we feeling? Because that's so important, like, you know. How does a meeting make us feel? How does an action make us feel and trying to be aware of? Am I feeling strengthened? Am I feeling empowered? Am I feeling like we're moving, or do I feel like we're going backward? Do I feel like that? Was a waste of time? Do I feel like that? I wasn't heard, you know, like just being genuinely in touch with how it feels because if people haven't been heard and we're not moving forward, then we need to. We need to learn from that. And also, it's just trying to build in this culture of learning. That we're all learners. It's not that you've got the organisers or the leaders of the organisation who know how to do it and everyone else in the organisation doesn't know. We can all learn this stuff and we're all constantly learning' (Interview 15).

Overall, the interviews demonstrate that the success of citizens' assemblies depend not only on outputs or recommendations that are inclusive of the range of views with the process, but also the mechanisms that ensure participants' voices are heard, valued, and acted upon. While assemblies often promote public voice in decision-making, challenges remain in holding decision-makers to account to ensure that outputs have demonstrable impact on policy. This is particularly important in the application of intersectionality as citizens' assemblies offer the opportunity to subvert traditional power structures by amplifying voices that are not traditionally involved in the decision-making process. Despite challenges related to accountability, citizens' assemblies have been shown to be transformational for some participants, whether through civic engagement or personal and professional opportunities. As shown through the

interviewees' approach to evaluation, the practice is continuously evolving, so we should continue to explore different methods and approaches.

Interview Recommendation 12: Foster a culture of learning among organisers and participants, emphasising reflection and responsiveness. Ensure evaluation frameworks capture experiences of PMIMG and identify barriers to exerting influence.

3. Discussion and Conclusion

By analysing these interviews through the lens of intersectionality, focusing on equality, inclusion and good deliberation, we identified several key findings across the dimensions of input, throughput and output choices.

In terms of agenda setting and topic selection, whilst most assemblies were commissioned with pre-determined topics, the topics have also been somewhat shaped by advisory boards. As the interviewees identify, it is important for participants to feel that they have agency in topic selection, and we purport that this is even more vital when engaging in a citizens' assembly that aims to operationalise intersectionality. We find that inclusion should start at the design stage, ensuring less-heard groups are included throughout.

Commonly in recruitment and selection, the two-stage civic lottery approach was dominant, being valued for its representativeness and legitimacy. Intersectionality has not yet been drawn on as a selection and recruitment design criteria, but interviewees claim that diversity often emerged incidentally, leaving room in future citizens' assemblies for a more directed and explicit intersectional focus in selection and recruitment including tackling barriers to participation, which is the focus of the project. Interviewees highlight some key methods that could be drawn upon to take an intersectional approach, including targeted outreach, multilingual invitations, relationship building, logistical support and online formats.

It is also important that intersectionality is considered when deciding on the information that will be presented to participants in citizens' assemblies, ensuring that information shared is plural, combines technical knowledge with lived experiences, and uses a range of formats and methods to share information and tailor content to a range of needs and learning styles.

When moving to throughput choices, interviewees identify the importance of inclusive practices through a range of different tools and methods that are important to consider in terms

of inclusivity and good deliberation. In particular, we find that collaborative ground rules, which is a common practice, foster respect and inclusion, but the interviewees have not yet directly addressed privilege and power, a key area for us to explore.

Facilitation is also important to inclusion and good deliberation as it can be relevant for managing challenging dynamics during the assembly. For an intersectional assembly, facilitators should actively challenge power hierarchies, via drawing on adaptive, relationship building, and flexible strategies. However, the role of the facilitators should also be balanced with enabling participants to engage in democratic exploration. The trade-offs in this process were highlighted by the interviewees when they considered methods for deliberation and the importance of consensus. We find that whilst consensus is valued for legitimacy it may produce safe recommendations and marginalise dissent from those who are already marginalised. Interviewees highlight methods like deep democracy and iterative tools as important for surfacing minority perspectives, loosening the focus on consensus, to ensure inclusivity and voice.

Power dynamics also need to be considered when engaging with political actors, as an intersectionality-oriented assembly should actively challenge hierarchical dynamics yet bringing power holders into the space can create hierarchical tensions. Therefore, the interviews identify that citizens' autonomy should be maintained, tokenistic engagement should be avoided, long term relationship building should be created to avoid transactional recommendation delivery, and non-partisan involvement should be adopted to ensure balanced representation.

Another way to tackle power dynamics in citizens' assembly design and implementation is about how diverse perspectives are included in the assembly beyond recruitment. For example, interviewees suggest strategies of including community groups, storytelling, parallel engagement processes and ensuring that there is continued validation of participants' existing knowledge, to ensure equality and inclusion throughout the assembly.

Moving to output choices, and the steps that take place after the assembly is finished, we find that citizens' assemblies aim to produce recommendations for policy influence, but there are limited mechanisms for measuring this impact. We see this as a key sight for further exploration in a citizens' assembly, identifying that the follow up is a vital part of legitimacy when engaging marginalised voices. In other words, if citizens do not see the impact that their work will have there is limited reason for them to take part. It is important that public voice is amplified in decision-making and that assemblies play a key role in bridging gaps between

citizens and powerholders. This impact also could occur in a range of ways, not just focusing on elected officials and commissioners but also other power holders and using different methods for engaging such power holders that subvert traditional power structures.

Beyond creating output in the form of recommendations, assemblies are also impactful on participants. In terms of participant experience, assemblies can be transformational because they foster civic engagement, personal growth, employability, and skills development. It is important that these impacts are evaluated through different methods so that continuous learning can take place on assemblies, and concerns can be addressed to continuously improve (intersectional) equality, inclusivity, and good deliberation.

IV. Secondary Analysis of Evaluation Data on Participants of Existing Citizens' Assemblies

One of the aims of the EU-CIEMBLY project is to provide procedural and methodological innovations for any organisers of citizens' assemblies (including the EU), that maximise intersectional- equality, inclusion, and good deliberation. With that goal in mind, we conducted a secondary data analysis of two citizen assembly participant evaluation datasets that collected and linked demographic data to participant experience data, revealing notable methodological findings, as well as patterns and trends in how people belonging to multiple intersecting marginalised groups experienced different elements of the citizens' assemblies. Our final result over-delivers on our original task description by gathering data on a maximum of 153⁷ participants (tripling our baseline aim of 50 survey respondents), and by analysing demographic differences across gender, age, ethnicity, place of birth, language, and education level. These insights will inform the design, development, implementation, and evaluation of our three EU-CIEMBLY pilot assemblies, to be held in 2026.

To conduct this analysis, we used data from Scotland's Climate Assembly and the Citizens' Assembly for the Climate of Catalonia both of which fall under our category of 'local' citizens' assembly, in that they are held at a regional level below the nation state. The full methodology is described in Deliverable 3.1, including details on steps taken to ensure compliance with the project's Data Management Plan (Deliverable 1.3), the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and consent for use of the data. It is important to note that Scotland and Catalonia are regions with above-average income compared to the average for Europe, and that both assemblies were on the topic of climate change. Catalonia's GDP per capita is approximately €34,500 (Eurostat, 2025), clearly above Spain's national average of about €27,000, and slightly lower than Scotland (€38,400) (Office for National Statistics, 2025), placing it clearly above the EU average (around €32,000) (Eurostat, 2025).

In higher-income regions, participants may be more likely to have prior experience with civic engagement, access to digital tools, and the time and resources to fully participate - factors that can influence participation and experience in citizens' assemblies. Additionally, both

⁷ Some results tables' totals do not amount to 153. This is because not all participants responded to every survey question (including demographic questions), resulting in some sample size inconsistency.

assemblies were part of a growing ecosystem of climate-related citizens' assemblies⁸, benefiting from a broader community of practice that may have informed design choices, facilitation models, and participant support. These features may not be as readily available or transferable to less wealthy contexts, where structural barriers to participation may be more pronounced. As such, we do not suggest that our substantive findings are generalisable to all citizens' assemblies, particularly those outside the climate domain or in settings with fewer resources. However, our analysis does offer transferable insights into how intersecting social groups shape participant experiences in structured deliberative processes. These findings provide a basis for improved methodological practices in future evaluations and support the broader EU goal of enhancing inclusive and equitable democratic innovation.

1. Research Questions that Guided the Secondary Data Collection

With this part of our empirical research, we sought to assess the perceptions and experiences of citizens' assembly participants, particularly those belonging to marginalised social groups, including their experience or perception of equality, inclusion, and deliberation. Given the limitations discussed above concerning the 'direct' translation of our intersectional analytical lens to existing practices, but also beyond that, it was necessary to develop more specific research questions to achieve the aims of this secondary evaluation of experience-related data:

How are the experiences of PMIMG (people belonging to multiple, intersecting, marginalised groups) different to those of participants belonging to other social groups?

This includes the following sub-questions:

RQ 1. How were different elements (such as facilitation, deliberation, governance, etc.) of Citizens' Assemblies perceived by participants from different social groups?

RQ 2. How inclusive were Citizens' Assemblies, in terms of representation, process, outputs and outcomes, from the perspectives of participants belonging to different social groups?

⁸ See, e.g., the Knowledge Network On Climate Assemblies (KNOCA): <https://www.knocca.eu/> [accessed on 29 October 2025].

<p>RQ 2.A. Representation (diversity as an indication of inclusivity): Includes level of agreement with comments and perception statements about the socio-demographic make-up of the Assembly; if certain types of people dominated conversations; if participants felt like there was a diverse range of experts; if participants felt like there was a diverse range of facilitators.</p>
<p>RQ 2.B. Process: Inclusive in terms of (i) design/organisation (ii) recruitment / selection, (iii) facilitation and deliberation, (iv) effectiveness of mechanisms for accommodating different language needs from the perspective of participants.</p>
<p>RQ 2.C. Outputs: Do PMIMG participants feel their perspectives are included in citizens' assembly outputs? Do these participants feel a sense of co-ownership of citizens' assembly outputs?</p>
<p>RQ 2.D. Outcomes: Do PMIMG feel a personal impact (e.g., a change in attitude or view on a topic, confidence, or sense of political agency), as a result of participation in the citizens' assembly?</p>
<p>RQ 3. What was the impact of technology on participants' perception of the Citizens' Assembly? Were there differences in experiences based on online versus face-to-face formats? Was the use of technology experienced differently by different social groups?</p>
<p>RQ 4. What are the drivers of non-participation in citizens' assemblies by potential participants from different social groups? (by non-participation we mean citizens declining to participate in the citizens' assembly at all, and citizens not engaging while in the citizens' assembly, and citizens dropping out of the citizens' assembly).</p>

2. Methodology

Here, we outline the methodology used to conduct secondary analysis of evaluation data from existing citizens' assemblies.

2.1. Sampling and Data Management

To address the research questions, a wide sample of 33 citizens' assemblies across Europe conducted within the last 5-10 years were scoped for suitability. Factors assessed included: sample size, extent and relevance of member experience data collected, extent of demographic data collected, evaluation quality (e.g., if pre- and post- measures were utilised

to measure participant outcomes rather than only post), availability of a publicly downloadable dataset, and accessibility of organiser contact details. Of the 33 citizens' assemblies scoped, 29 met the minimum range of demographic variables identified as relevant by the project team to move on to scoping member experience variables. These variables included gender, age, ethnicity, nationality, education level, physical ability, work status, home ownership, and the possibility of objective household income and inferred social class. Of these 29 citizens' assemblies that met the minimum range of demographic variables, 14 citizens' assemblies contained participant experience surveys with questions and timeframes suitable to the purposes of this research. However, for cross tabulation, access to the attached demographic data of the participants was required. This required direct requests to these 14 dataset holders.

Of these 14 citizens' assemblies, we were able to successfully collect anonymised evaluation survey datasets from organisational data holders across three countries: Scotland, Spain, and Denmark. Organisational representatives for all three were provided with a Participant Information Sheet and were asked to return a signed Consent Form. These can be found in Appendix 4 and 5 of Deliverable 3.1, respectively.

However, the datasets from We Do Democracy-run citizens' assemblies in Denmark did not link any demographic data to individual assembly members' responses about their experience, meaning this dataset was not ultimately included in our analysis. This meant that our secondary analysis ultimately focused on two datasets, namely those related to the Citizens' Assembly for the Climate of Catalonia, and the Scotland Climate Assembly.

As a result of this work, two anonymised evaluation survey datasets were collected from organisational data holders across two distinct locations: Scotland (part of the UK) and Catalonia (part of Spain). The datasets were standardised and prepared to ensure compatibility for statistical analysis. Full details on variables and cases in each dataset and the associated codebooks are provided in the Deliverable 3.1 [Zenodo](#) submission. Below, we provide an overview of each assembly's topic, sampling and recruitment approach, and assembly process.

2.1.1 Scotland's Climate Assembly

Topic. Scotland's Climate Assembly focused on informing government decision-making on the climate crisis in line with Scotland's Climate Change Act from 2019. The specific question posed to the Assembly was decided by a Stewarding Group through a facilitated deliberation

process: 'How should Scotland change to tackle the climate emergency in an effective and fair way?'

Sampling and recruitment. The goal for Scotland's Climate Assembly's recruitment process was to gain a set of participants that reflected the demographic diversity of the Scottish population. To ensure a representative sample of the Scottish population, the Scotland Climate Assembly used a civil lottery method led by the Sortition Foundation. A total of 20,000 households were randomly selected from the Royal Mail's Postal Address File, with 80% drawn from across Scotland and 20% from more deprived areas to counteract typical biases in registration. From 878 registrations (a 4.4% response rate), 105 participants over the age of 16 were selected to match demographic targets based on gender, age, geography, ethnicity, disability status, income, and climate views. The final participant group closely aligned with population targets across these categories, ensuring the Assembly reflected the diversity of the Scottish public (Sortition Foundation, 2020). During the process, 7 replacements were added, and 102 citizens completed the process. Each member received a gift of £200 per weekend, and was provided technical equipment and training where necessary.

Assembly process. The assembly was held online (Zoom) across seven weekends. Participants were given access to an Online Hub in which learning resources (videos and documents), and a discussion board were provided. Weekends 1 and 2 focused on education, after which members were divided into 3 workstreams: Diet and Lifestyle; Homes and Communities; Work and Travel. Workstreams engaged with over 100 experts and advocates to consider key challenges via video, question and answer sessions, and facilitated breakout room discussions (using Jamboard, Google Docs), and subsequently drafted recommendations. During weekends 6 and 7, the full assembly shared, reviewed, redrafted, and voted on the workstream recommendations (using SurveyMonkey).

2.1.1. Citizen's Assembly for the Climate of Catalonia

Topic. Catalonia's climate assembly focused on the topics of energy and agri-food, decided as a result of a 'political dilemmas' framing approach. This narrowed the focus to topics for which there is a scientific consensus amongst policy-makers but require value-based decision-making regarding trade-offs and public priorities.

Sampling and recruitment. 100 citizens were drawn from the sample population that responded to the initial call for participation. Participants were selected to be representative of

Catalonia in terms of gender, age, level of education, territory and origin. Travel and accommodation was covered for participants, and they were also paid € 65 per meeting. In addition, care services were made available to participants with dependents which led to a provision of childcare.

Assembly process. There were six meetings, five of which were held in person and one online. The in-person meetings were held across different cities in Catalonia. Participants were divided into workstreams on energy and agri-food, were presented with written materials, expert proposals and interactive debates with experts. Participants deliberated in shifting small groups which were professionally facilitated. Recommendations were arrived at through a collective prioritisation and refinement process.

2.2. Quantitative Analysis Approaches

To conduct secondary analysis of evaluation data from existing citizens' assemblies, we employed two main methods of quantitative analysis. Both methods used descriptive statistics (summaries of data such as percentages, means, or distributions). The available sample size, particularly at this detailed intersectional level (e.g., combining age and gender at the independent variable level) was too limited to support multivariate inferential statistics (i.e., techniques that test relationships between several variables to generalise findings beyond the sample). Consequently, our analyses focused on descriptive statistics to identify emerging trends in PMIMG experiences of citizens' assemblies, which will inform the next deliverables of the project. The full descriptive statistical detail developed for this work is available in the open datasets published on [Zenodo](#).

Aggregate analysis. First, an aggregate analysis combined data from evaluation datasets for Scotland's Climate Assembly and the Citizens' Assembly for the Climate of Catalonia. This approach allowed for three-way crosstabulations to be generated, providing cross-contextual insights into different demographic experiences of citizens' assemblies. A three-way crosstabulation is a method used to examine the relationship between three categorical variables simultaneously. We have used three-way crosstabulations to explore how citizens' assembly experience varied not only by gender but also across different age groups. This approach enabled us to identify whether patterns in experiences in the assemblies differed within specific gender–age combinations. For example, instead of comparing experiences by gender alone, we could observe whether men, women and those identifying in another way within the same age group (e.g., 29 and under, 30-44, 45-64, 65+) reported similar or different ratings of their experiences. Conversely, we could also examine whether experience varied

by age group within each gender category. This layered analysis provides greater insight into how perceptions differed across demographic intersections, helping to avoid overly general conclusions that might overlook important subgroup variation.

In order to implement this approach, both datasets were cross-referenced to identify where the same demographic and member experience variables were asked, so the data could be merged. Demographic data relating to gender and age were collected for both evaluations. In terms of member experience variables, 11 topic areas were identified for which similar survey questions were utilised across both evaluations. Given that the evaluation surveys were developed independently across different citizens' assemblies, some questions varied slightly in wording or context. Nevertheless, where items measured conceptually similar constructs, we treated them as comparable indicators. This approach involved accepting minor contextual differences in exchange for a broader and more robust analytical base. In order to merge the data from both evaluations to conduct aggregate analysis, some data transformation was required. Table 1 below shows the recoding that was implemented, grouping the variables from both evaluations by the core concept they measure.

Core concept	Scotland wording (item code)	Catalonia wording (item code)	Scotland original response options	Catalonia original response options	New dichotomised categories
Gender	Gender (GEN)	Gender (GEN)	Man	Male	Man
			Woman	Female	Woman
			In another way		In another way
Age	Age group (AGE)	Age (AGE)	19-24, 25-29	16-24, 25-29	29 and under
			30-44	30-44	30-44
			45-64	45-64	45-64
			65-74, 75+	65-74, 75+	65+
Diversity and representation	“The Assembly is diverse enough to ensure a broad range of perspectives are considered” (ASB_DIV_MED)	“Do you think the people in the Assembly reflect the social diversity of Catalonia?” (ASB_SOC_DIV)	Strongly disagree Tend to disagree	Not at all, Little	Negative
			I don't know, Neither agree nor disagree		Exclude
			Tend to agree Strongly agree	Quite a bit, A lot	Positive

Equal chance to speak	“I have had ample opportunity in the small-group discussions to express my views” (GRP_DISC_MED)	“During the debate, do you think everyone had the opportunity to speak and participate?” (DEB_OPP)	Tend to agree Strongly agree	Not at all, Little	Negative
			I don't know, Neither agree nor disagree		Exclude
			Strongly disagree Tend to disagree	Quite a bit, A lot	Positive
Feeling that contributions were listened to	How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the Assembly as a whole, and about your experience as a whole?: I feel that my contributions have been listened to by the other Assembly members (CONTR_LIST)	Are you satisfied with your level of participation during the debate/work sessions? (PART_SAT)	Tend to agree Strongly agree	Not at all, Little	Negative
			I don't know, Neither agree nor disagree		Exclude
			Strongly disagree Tend to disagree	Quite a bit, A lot	Positive

Facilitator neutrality	<p>“The break-out room facilitator sometimes tried to influence the group with their own ideas”</p> <p>(FAC_INFL_MED)</p>	<p>“Do you think the facilitation team remained neutral?”</p> <p>(FAC_TEAM_NEUT)</p>	Tend to agree Strongly agree	Not at all, Little	Negative
			I don't know, Neither agree nor disagree		Exclude
			Strongly disagree Tend to disagree	Quite a bit, A lot	Positive
Facilitator encouragement of debate	<p>"The break-out room facilitator made sure that opposing arguments were considered"</p> <p>(FAC_ARG_MED)</p>	<p>"Did the facilitation team help and encourage the debate?";</p>	Tend to agree Strongly agree	Not at all, Little	Negative
			I don't know, Neither agree nor disagree		Exclude
			Strongly disagree Tend to disagree	Quite a bit, A lot	Positive
Information fairness & balance	<p>“The information I have received during the Assembly weekend has been fair and balanced between different viewpoints”</p> <p>(ASB_FAIR)</p>	<p>“Do you think there are relevant perspectives ... that were not covered in the training sessions?”</p> <p>(TRN_PER_MIS)</p>	Strongly disagree Tend to disagree	Quite a bit, A lot	Negative
			I don't know, Neither agree nor disagree		Exclude
			Tend to agree Strongly agree	Not at all, Little	Positive

Contribution reflected in recommendations	How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the Assembly as a whole, and about your experience as a whole?: My views are reflected in the finalised goals and recommendations (GRP_GOREC_T7)	“Do you think your opinions have been included in the final recommendations?” (OPN_INC)	Tend to agree Strongly agree	Not at all, Little	Negative
			I don't know, Neither agree nor disagree		Exclude
			Strongly disagree Tend to disagree	Quite a bit, A lot	Positive
Clarity of purpose/process	“The purpose of the weekend was well explained” (WK_PURP_MED)	“Were the objectives of the debate sessions clear?” (DEB_OBJ_CLR)	Tend to agree Strongly agree	Not at all, Little	Negative
			I don't know, Neither agree nor disagree		Exclude
			Strongly disagree Tend to disagree	Quite a bit, A lot	Positive

Confidence in uptake of recommendations	“I am confident that the Assembly report will be taken seriously by Parliament and political parties” (REP_SER)	“Do you think the Assembly’s recommendations will be adopted by the Government of Catalonia?” (REC_GOV_ADOPT)	Tend to agree Strongly agree	Not at all, Little	Negative
			I don't know, Neither agree nor disagree		Exclude
			Strongly disagree Tend to disagree	Quite a bit, A lot	Positive
Interest in future participation	“To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements: Taking part in this citizens' assembly has made me want to be more involved in other aspects of Government decision making” (GOV_INVOL_T8)	Would you be willing to participate in another citizens' Assembly? (PART_NEXT_ASB)	Tend to agree Strongly agree	Not at all, Little	Negative
			I don't know, Neither agree nor disagree		Exclude
			Strongly disagree Tend to disagree	Quite a bit, A lot	Positive

Assessments of speaker quality	How helpful did you find the following activities for your learning about climate change and how to tackle it across the Assembly as a whole?: Presentations by speakers (SPK_PRES)	Did the speakers and trainers explain the discussed topics well? (SPK_TRN_EXP)	Tend to agree Strongly agree	Not at all, Little	Negative
			I don't know, Neither agree nor disagree		Exclude
			Strongly disagree Tend to disagree	Quite a bit, A lot	Positive

Table 1: Comparable variables and recoding approach across Scotland’s Climate Assembly and Citizen’s Assembly for Climate of Catalonia evaluation datasets

Bivariate analysis. Second, bivariate analysis is applied separately for each citizens' assembly dataset using two-way crosstabulations. This involves examining the relationship between one demographic variable (e.g., gender, age, or ethnicity) and one member experience variable (e.g., their rating of how inclusive they perceived the facilitation process to be). These two-way crosstabulations allowed for the identification of patterns and differences across the full range of demographic characteristics each dataset captured (gender, age, and ethnicity for Scotland's Climate Assembly; gender, age, place of birth, education level, and language for the Citizens' Assembly for the Climate of Catalonia) to explore differences in experiences and perceptions among various social groups participating in the assemblies. Unlike three-way crosstabulations (which incorporate a third variable to reveal more complex subgroup patterns), two-way tables provide a more straightforward view of relationships between two variables at a time.

2.3. Dataset Limitations

2.3.1. Scotland's Climate Assembly

While data related to participants' geography, ethnicity, disability status, and income was collected at the sampling stage in order for the final participant group to reflect the demographic diversity of Scotland, the demographic data included in the evaluation dataset provided to us was limited to **gender, age group, and ethnicity**. As such, our analysis could only examine intersections across gender, age group and ethnicity. While this has still yielded important insights, a more comprehensive intersectional analysis would have been possible had the recruitment-stage demographic data been retained. This limitation highlights a broader methodological gap in existing evaluation practices, where potentially valuable demographic information collected at the recruitment stage is not systematically used to assess participants' experiences. See Secondary Evaluation Key Finding 2 for more details.

While 102 participants completed the Assembly process, only 85 responded to the evaluation, and not all participants responded to every survey question. The table below sets out the difference in response rates across demographic categories.

Demographic variable	Category	Target N (informed by census data)	Confirmed N (participated in assembly)	Maximum N from evaluation dataset	Response rate
Gender	Men	49.7	49	30	61.2%
	Women	52.3	54	38	70.4%
	In another way	2	2	2	100%
Age	16-18	5.8	5	0	0%
	19-24	10.4	10	5	50%
	25-29	6.4	6	4	66.7%
	30-44	23.3	25	22	88%
	45-64	34.5	34	26	76.5%
	65+	24	25	16	64%
Ethnicity	BAME	8	8	4	50%
	White	96	97	71	73.2%

Table 2. Evaluation response rates by demographic category

These results point to notable underrepresentation of Black and minority ethnic (BAME) participants and participants aged between 16-25 in Scotland's Climate Assembly evaluation data, with both categories only achieving a 50% response rate. This not only represents a limitation to the generalisability of our findings, but highlights an important consideration for the practice of survey-based citizens' assembly evaluations in terms of groups least likely to respond.

While differences in how demographic groups responded to questions were identifiable, the small sample sizes in several groups e.g., n=2 people identifying their gender 'in another way', only n=5 or fewer people aged 19-24, 25-29, or 75+, and only n=4 non-White participants, mean that the strength of conclusions about these groups on the basis of this data is limited.

2.3.2. Citizens' Assembly for the Climate of Catalonia

The demographic variables available were **language, age, gender,⁹ achieved education, and place of birth**. As such, our analysis is limited to exploring different experiences based on these factors alone.

While 100 participants were recruited for the Assembly, the maximum number of participants at any one meeting was 97, while the lowest was 81. 83 participants attended the final Assembly meeting. 68 participants responded to the evaluation, which represents a 68% response rate compared to the number of people recruited. Not all participants responded to every survey question. The table below sets out the difference in response rates across demographic categories, compared to the number of people recruited.

Demographic variable	Category	Target N (informed by census data)	Recruited N¹⁰	Maximum N from evaluation dataset	Response rate
Gender	Male	49	46	34	73.9%
	Female	50	54	34	63%
	Non-binary	1	0	0	N/A
Age	16-29 years old	18	20	8	40%
	30-44 years old	25	26	14	53.8%
	45-59 years old	28	30	17	56.7%
	60+ years old	26	29	19	65.5%
Place of birth	Spain	83	83	57	68.7%
	Other EU countries	4	5	3	60%

⁹ While a third gender category beyond 'male' and 'female' was provided, no one belonging to this gender category participated.

¹⁰ Actual Assembly attendance rates (rather than recruitment rates) separated by demographic categories were not visible in the data supplied to us.

	Non-EU countries	13	12	8	66.7%
Achieved education	Highly educated	32	41	36	87.8%
	Secondary studies	51	48	28	58.3%
	No studies or primary studies	17	11	4	36.4%

Table 2. Evaluation response rates by demographic category¹¹

These results point to notable underrepresentation in the evaluation data of several groups, particularly those with no studies or primary studies (36.4% response rate), and those aged 16-29 years old (40% response rate).

While differences in how demographic groups responded to questions were identifiable, the small sample sizes in some groups mean that the strength of conclusions about these groups on the basis of this data is limited.

2.4. Criteria for Selecting Member Experience Variables on which to run Analyses

The primary aim guiding the selection of member experience variables on which to conduct analyses in each dataset was to ensure a spread of valid insights that respond to the research questions, and sub-questions within them (10 in total) for this task. To ensure this, a set of criteria for variables to be included was established:

- Variable has relevance to any of the 10 themes in the research questions;
- Variable draws out insights at the level of the assembly as a whole, rather than a specific session or day; and,
- Variable overlaps in meaning with another variable in a different dataset, opening up potential for aggregate analysis.

¹¹ Catalonia's citizens' assembly recruitment data and evaluation dataset use different variables and categories, so some data transformation and recoding was required to produce this table.

Variables in each citizens' assembly evaluation dataset were then screened and coded based on these criteria.

3. Results

3.1. Aggregate Analysis

Here, we integrate variables from across the Scotland and Catalonia datasets to run analyses revealing demographic patterns in member experiences.

3.1.1. RQ 1: How were different elements of Citizens' Assemblies perceived by participants from different social groups?

Clarity of Assembly purpose and process

		29 and under			30-44			45-64			65+			Total
		Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	
Negative	n	0	3	0	0	2	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	9
% within		0%	30%	0%	0%	9.1%	N/A	11.1%	6.2%	N/A	0%	0%	N/A	6.5%
Positive	n	9	7	2	17	20	0	16	30	0	20	8	0	129
% within		100%	70%	100%	100%	90.9%	N/A	88.9%	93.8%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	93.5%
Total	n	9	10	2	17	22	0	18	32	0	20	8	0	138
% within		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	100%

Overall, responses regarding the clarity of the Assembly purpose and process were predominantly *positive* (93.5%; n=134). While satisfaction was high across most intersectional groups, a **notable divergence appeared among women aged 29 and under**, where 30% (n=3) expressed *negative* views. In comparison, other groups exhibited higher *positivity*. Though the difference within this younger group is notable, caution is advised given

the relatively small subgroup size. Generally, the findings suggest broad agreement across diverse identities regarding clarity.

Assessments of speaker quality

		29 and under			30-44			45-64			65+			
		Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Total
Negative	n	0	0	0	3	1	0	2	0	0	1	1	0	8
% within		0%	0%	0%	16.7%	4.5%	N/A	11.1%	0%	N/A	5%	12.5%	N/A	5.8%
Positive	n	7	9	2	15	21	0	16	33	0	19	7	0	129
% within		100%	100%	100%	83.3%	95.5%	N/A	88.9%	100%	N/A	95%	87.5%	N/A	94.2%
Total	n	7	9	2	18	22	0	18	33	0	20	8	0	137
% within		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	100%

Responses regarding the assessments of speaker quality were overwhelmingly positive (94.2%; n=129). All participants aged 29 and under, across all gender categories, reported entirely *positive* assessments (100%). Among older groups, small numbers reported *negative* assessments, most notably men aged 30-44 (16.7%, n=3). Despite these minor variations, **high positivity was consistent across most intersectional social groups, suggesting broadly satisfactory perceptions of speaker quality.**

Sufficiency of the diversity of assembly members

		29 and under			30-44			45-64			65+			
		Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Total
Negative	n	2	2	0	1	2	0	2	3	0	2	0	0	14
% within		22.2%	20%	0%	5.6%	10%	N/A	10.5%	9.1%	N/A	10.5%	0%	N/A	10.2%

								%			%			%
Positive	n	7	8	2	17	18	0	17	30	0	17	7	0	123
% within		77.8%	80%	100%	94.4%	90%	N/A	89.5%	90.9%	N/A	89.5%	100%	N/A	89.8%
Total	n	9	10	2	18	20	0	19	33	0	19	7	0	137
% within		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	100%

There were few notable differences in views on the sufficiency of the diversity of Assembly members by intersectional social groups combining age and gender. **Overall, a substantial majority expressed positive views** (89.9%, n=123), though some nuanced variations emerged. Younger participants (29 and under) identifying as in another way unanimously expressed positive views (100%, n=2). Positive perceptions were similarly high among older women (65+) (100%, n=7) and adults aged 30-44 (90%, women: n=18; men: n=17) and 45-64 (90.9%, women: n=30; men: n=17). **Negative responses were not highly concentrated within any age/gender group.** However, younger men and women (29 and under) displayed slightly higher *negativity* (22.2% within men 29 and under: n=2; 20% within women 29 and under: n=2) compared to other groups, potentially highlighting younger participants' somewhat higher critical perspective.

Information fairness & balance

		29 and under			30-44			45-64			65+			
		Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Total
Negative	n	1	5	0	7	3	0	8	7	0	5	2	0	38
% within		11.1%	50%	0%	38.9%	15%	N/A	44.4%	21.2%	N/A	29.4%	28.6%	N/A	28.4%
Positive	n	8	5	2	11	17	0	10	26	0	12	5	0	96
% within		88.9%	50%	100%	61.1%	85%	N/A	55.6%	78.8%	N/A	70.6%	71.4%	N/A	71.6%
Total	n	9	10	2	18	20	0	18	33	0	17	7	0	134

% within	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	100%
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Though the majority of participants across Scotland and Catalonia's citizens' assemblies responded *positively* regarding the level of fairness and balance in the information provided to them, there were some notable differences between demographic profiles. **Women aged 29 and under were the most divided in their perceptions of information fairness.** In this group, 50% (n=5) gave a *negative* response, while the other 50% (n=5) were *positive*. A notable portion of men aged between 45-64 also responded *negatively* (44.4%, n=8). In contrast, other groups showed much higher levels of positive responses overall - such as women aged 30-44 with 85% (n=17), and women aged 45-64 with 78.8% (n=26). No participants in the *in another way* category gave a *negative* response, though the small sample size should be taken into consideration here.

3.1.2. RQ 2b: How inclusive was the Citizen Assembly process, in terms of facilitation and deliberation?

Equal chance for assembly members to speak

		29 and under			30-44			45-64			65+			
		Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Total
Negative	n	0	2	0	3	3	0	4	2	0	1	0	0	15
% within		0%	20%	0%	16.7%	14.3%	N/A	22.2%	6.1%	N/A	5.6%	0%	N/A	10.9%
Positive	n	9	8	2	15	18	0	14	31	0	17	8	0	122
% within		100%	80%	100%	83.3%	85.7%	N/A	77.8%	93.9%	N/A	94.4%	100%	N/A	89.1%
Total	n	9	10	2	18	21	0	18	33	0	18	8	0	137
% within		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	100%

Overall, attitudes towards an equal chance for assembly members to speak were broadly positive across intersectional social groups, with 89.1% (n=122) responding positively.

However, minor variations emerge that merit cautious attention. **Younger men (29 and under, 100%, n=9) and those identifying in another way in this age group (100%, n=2) reported uniformly positive responses regarding equal chances for assembly members to speak, whereas younger women (29 and under), men aged 30-44, and men aged 45-64 exhibited somewhat less positivity (80%, n=8).** Participants aged 30-44 showed relatively consistent positive responses across genders (men: 83.3%, n=15; women: 85.7%, n=18), while participants aged 45-64 and 65+ displayed strong positivity, especially among older women (65+, 100%, n=8). While these subtle differences are notable, it is important not to overstate their significance, considering the overall high positivity and the small sample sizes in each subgroup involved.

Satisfaction with personal ability to participate

		29 and under			30-44			45-64			65+			
		Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Total
Negative	n	2	1	0	1	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	7
% within		33.3%	11.1%	0%	5.9%	9.5%	N/A	5.9%	0%	N/A	0%	0%	N/A	5.4%
Positive	n	4	8	2	16	19	0	16	32	0	18	8	0	123
% within		66.7%	88.9%	100%	94.1%	90.5%	N/A	94.1%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	94.6%
Total	n	6	9	2	17	21	0	17	32	0	18	8	0	130
% within		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	100%

There were some notable differences in satisfaction with personal ability to participate, although overall *positive responses* were high (94.6%, n=123). Specifically, **younger men (29 and under) expressed somewhat greater dissatisfaction (33.3%, n=2 negative) compared to their peers. In contrast, women aged 45 and older reported universally positive experiences (100% positive, n=32 for ages 45-64; n=8 for ages 65+).** Although other groups had small numbers reporting negative experiences (approximately 10%), these differences are cautious observations due to small sample sizes.

Facilitator neutrality

		29 and under			30-44			45-64			65+			Total
		Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	
Negative	n	2	0	0	2	2	0	2	1	0	1	2	0	12
% within		25%	0%	0%	11.8%	10%	N/A	12.5%	3.1%	N/A	5.3%	25%	N/A	9.3%
Positive	n	6	8	1	15	18	0	14	31	0	18	6	0	117
% within		75%	100%	100%	88.2%	90%	N/A	87.5%	96.9%	N/A	94.7%	75%	N/A	90.7%
Total	n	8	8	1	17	20	0	16	32	0	19	8	0	129
% within		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	100%

Perceptions of facilitator neutrality were broadly positive across all age and gender groups, though there was some variation. **Women aged 65 and over were more likely to report negatively compared to other subgroups.** 25% (n=2) of both women aged 65+ and men aged 29 and under gave a *negative* response, as did 12.5% (n=2) of men aged 45–64. In contrast, 96.9% (n=31) of women aged 45–64 and 94.7% (n=18) of men aged 65+ gave *positive* responses, suggesting generally strong perceptions of facilitator neutrality among mid-to-older age groups.

Facilitator encouragement of debate

		29 and under			30-44			45-64			65+			Total
		Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	
Negative	n	1	1	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	5
% within		12.5%	10%	0%	0%	0%	N/A	11.1%	3.1%	N/A	0%	0%	N/A	3.7%
Positive	n	7	9	2	17	21	0	16	31	0	19	7	0	129

% within		87.5%	90%	100%	100%	100%	N/A	88.9%	96.9%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	96.3%
Total	n	8	10	2	17	21	0	18	32	0	19	7	0	134
% within		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	100%

Overall, there were **few striking differences regarding facilitator encouragement of debate**, with consistently *positive* responses across most groups (n=129; 96.3%). The maximum proportion of any group giving a negative response was very small (10%).

3.1.3. RQ 2c: Outputs: Do PMIMG participants feel their perspectives are included in Citizens' Assembly outputs? Do these participants feel a sense of co-ownership of Citizens' Assembly outputs?

Contributions reflected in final recommendations

		29 and under			30-44			45-64			65+			
		Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Total
Negative	n	0	0	0	4	2	0	3	3	0	1	1	0	14
% within		0%	0%	0%	23.5%	10%	N/A	18.8%	9.1%	N/A	5.6%	12.5%	N/A	10.8%
Positive	n	7	9	2	13	18	0	13	30	0	17	7	0	116
% within		100%	100%	100%	76.5%	90%	N/A	81.2%	90.9%	N/A	94.4%	87.5%	N/A	89.2%
Total	n	7	9	2	17	20	0	16	33	0	18	8	0	130
% within		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	100%

Responses regarding whether assembly members' contributions were reflected in the final recommendations were predominantly *positive* (89.2%, n=116). Participants aged 29 and

under universally reported *positive* perceptions across all gender identities (100%). **Slightly lower positivity appeared among older groups, with notably 23.5% of men aged 30-44 (n=4) and 18.8% of men aged 45-64 (n=3) expressing negative perceptions.** A similar, though less pronounced trend was present among women in these age groups (10%, n=2 and n=3 respectively). While these small variations warrant cautious attention, broadly positive perceptions persisted across most intersectional social groups, indicating general satisfaction with the representation of contributions.

Confidence in uptake of recommendations

		29 and under			30-44			45-64			65+			Total
		Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	
Negative	n	4	4	0	8	4	0	10	11	0	5	2	0	48
% within		57.1%	50%	0%	50%	25%	N/A	76.9%	42.3%	N/A	41.7%	25%	N/A	44.9%
Positive	n	3	4	1	8	12	0	3	15	0	7	6	0	59
% within		42.9%	50%	100%	50%	75%	N/A	23.1%	57.7%	N/A	58.3%	75%	N/A	55.1%
Total	n	7	8	1	16	16	0	13	26	0	12	8	0	107
% within		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	100%

Regarding *confidence in the uptake of recommendations*, the overall responses were moderately positive (55.1%, n=59), but meaningful variation was observable across groups. **Particularly, men aged 45-64 expressed considerable negativity (76.9%, n=10), while those aged 29 and under (both men at 57.1%, n=4, and women at 50%, n=4) also showed notable scepticism.** Conversely, the group aged 30-44, especially women, were more optimistic (75% positive, n=12). Although the sample sizes here limit definitive conclusions, these differences do suggest cautious exploration of age and gender-based disparities in optimism about assembly impact.

3.1.4. RQ 2d: Outcomes: Do PMIMG feel a personal impact (e.g., a change in attitude or view on a topic, confidence, or sense of political agency), as a result of participation in the Citizens' Assembly?

Interest in future participation

		29 and under			30-44			45-64			65+			
		Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Man	Woman	In another way	Total
Negative	n	1	2	0	0	1	0	5	2	0	1	2	0	14
% within		14.3%	25%	0%	0%	7.7%	N/A	27.8%	8%	N/A	6.7%	50%	N/A	13.7%
Positive	n	6	6	1	11	12	0	13	23	0	14	2	0	88
% within		85.7%	75%	100%	100%	92.3%	N/A	72.2%	92%	N/A	93.3%	50%	N/A	86.3%
Total	n	7	8	1	11	13	0	18	25	0	15	4	0	102
% within		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	100%	100%	N/A	100%

Regarding *interest in future participation*, attitudes were generally highly positive (86.3%; n=88). However, subtle variations emerged. **Particularly notable is that women aged 65 and older showed evenly split responses (50% positive; n=2 out of 4), representing lower enthusiasm compared to most other groups.** Additionally, men aged 45-64 were slightly less positive (72.2%; n=13). Conversely, the youngest group, particularly those identifying *in another way*, expressed unanimous positivity, though sample sizes were small. These findings warrant cautious consideration of potential age and gender-based nuances in sustained engagement with assembly activities.

4. Synthesis of Insights

Here, we synthesise results from the aggregate analysis and the bivariate cross-tabulations. The Annex - Results on Individual Social Groups - Secondary Analysis Results Tables, which has been submitted with this Deliverable, provides the secondary analysis results tables relating to individual social groups as well as methodological details for the Citizens' Assemblies under investigation. The results of the analysis and the bivariate cross-tabulations

are presented under each individual research question, and key themes are drawn out for EU-CIEMBLY to consider in the design and implementation of the pilot Citizens' Assemblies.

4.1.1. RQ 1: How were different elements of Citizens' Assemblies perceived by participants from different social groups?

This section synthesises participant responses relating to key Citizens' Assembly elements, such as clarity of purpose, methodology, and training materials, with a focus on how experiences varied across intersecting and individual social groups. By analysing patterns across demographic groups, we aim to understand how design features may be experienced differently by participants based on their social group.

Clarity of Assembly purpose and process

Insights on intersecting social groups

Both Scotland and Catalonia's Citizens' Assembly evaluations asked questions relating to the *clarity of Assembly purpose and process* - Scotland's evaluation asked *To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statement: The purpose of the weekend was well explained* while Catalonia's evaluation asked participants *were the objectives of the debate sessions clear?* Looking at their data combined with the distribution of responses separated by gender and age combined, responses were broadly positive (90%; n=134), with a small divergence amongst women aged 29 and under, where 30% (n=3) expressed negative views.

Insights on individual social groups

For Catalonia, postgraduates were notably less likely than other education groups to have felt there was *a lot* of clarity regarding the *objectives of the debate sessions*, and more likely than other education groups to say there was *little* clarity. This highlights the challenge for citizens' assemblies to address the different levels of explanation that may be needed for assembly participants to sufficiently address their diverse cognitive needs when it comes to task instructions. Interestingly, participants born in South America expressed notably higher clarity (*a lot*, 50%, n=3; the only other place of birth group with any *a lot* responses was Catalonia, 26%, n=13), compared to other place of birth groups, though the sample size for South America-born participants was small (n=6).

Taking the Scotland data alone, there were no notable trends regarding ethnicity - all groups *strongly agreed* or *tended to agree* that *the purpose of the weekend was well explained* in broadly similar proportions.

Satisfaction with assembly methodology

Insights on individual social groups

Overall, minimal differences were identifiable between demographic groups in terms of satisfaction with *the balance between task-based discussions and open discussions in my small groups across the assembly weekends as a whole*. The strongest differences in experience can be seen in terms of gender - women were more likely to say they were *satisfied* or *very satisfied* with the balance (n=34, 94.5%) compared to men (n=23, 85.1%). The only evidence from the full evaluation report from Scotland's Climate Assembly that might shed light on this is the fact that 'there were challenges in balancing time for evidence with time for deliberation and completing small group tasks, and in completing small group tasks within session time. Work was often rushed and at times overran into breaks' (Andrews et al. 2022, p.50), indicating that men perhaps experienced more dissatisfaction than women when it came to how time was balanced between *task-based discussions and open discussions* in small groups. A similar trend of men expressing slightly less agreement (70.3%, n=19) than women (83.3%, n=30) when it came to liking *the way we developed the overarching statements in my small group*. The youngest (19-24) and oldest (75+) groups also showed slightly more disagreement or uncertainty.

For Catalonia, broader questions were asked regarding the methodology used throughout the Assembly - specifically, whether it *allowed [participants] to learn what was necessary to debate the dilemmas*, and whether it was *appropriate to achieve the objectives of the working sessions*. For both measures, there was strong consensus across all groups that the methodology was appropriate and allowed them to learn what was needed, with minor variation by age and gender. In terms of responses by education groups, undergraduates and postgraduates were the most likely to criticise the appropriateness of the methodology to *achieve the objectives of the working sessions* and select *little*, while those with compulsory secondary education were most likely to praise it by selecting *a lot*. For both questions, place of birth notably affected the spread of participant responses: South American-born participants reported higher satisfaction compared to other birthplace groups. In terms of language, Catalan speakers were more likely than Spanish speakers to perceive the helpfulness of the methodology to *learn what was necessary to debate the dilemmas* as *a lot* helpful, whereas those who spoke Spanish were more likely to rate the methodology's *appropriateness to achieve the objectives of the working sessions* higher (*a lot*) compared to Spanish speakers.

Perceptions of training activities, content and materials

Insights on intersecting social groups

Both Scotland and Catalonia's citizens' assembly evaluations asked questions regarding the quality of speakers presenting information and evidence to the assembly. Responses were overwhelmingly positive, with a small divergence of 20% (n=3) of men aged 30-33 giving a negative assessment. While this is a small subgroup, the proportion of negative responses is notable compared to other groups. One tentative interpretation is that this demographic may have had higher expectations regarding speaker expertise or delivery style, or may have been more critical of the framing of evidence. However, given the small sample size, this finding should be treated cautiously and considered a potential signal for further exploration rather than a definitive pattern.

Insights on individual social groups

Catalonia's citizens' assembly evaluation asked three further questions regarding training content and materials. In terms of *satisfaction with the training sessions*, 88.2% (n=60) of all Assembly members were *quite a bit* or *a lot* satisfied. Women, those aged 75+, those with compulsory secondary education and South American-born participants were more likely than their demographic counterparts to be the most satisfied (*a lot*), while participants aged 45-64 and postgraduates showed the least strength in their satisfaction. Similar patterns along the lines of gender and age were observed for the extent to which *topics covered in the training were appropriate for the assembly's objectives* - women were more likely than men to rate the training topics as highly (*a lot*) appropriate, alongside those aged 75+. In terms of how *clear and appropriate supporting materials for the sessions* were, the most notable finding was that postgraduate respondents were less positive than other education groups, with 44.4% (n=4) selecting *little* rather than *quite a bit*, which was the most common response across most other education groups. This underscores the idea that those with higher levels of education are likely to have different standards of clarity and appropriateness of information to those who have lower levels of education.

Scotland's citizens' assembly evaluation asked more detailed questions regarding the helpfulness of different formats of learning activities. In terms of gender, for all formats, (*small group discussions, time with speakers in breakout rooms, transcripts of speakers' presentations, written summaries of speakers' presentations, and visual graphics of evidence*) women and those identifying in another way were more likely to rate these as *very helpful* compared to men, who showed a wider spread of responses.

Clear trends by ethnicity emerged for the helpfulness level of different learning formats. Ethnic minority participants rated *small group discussions* unanimously as at least *quite helpful*, while ratings of them only being *a little* or *somewhat helpful* came exclusively from White Scottish/British respondents. Participants from ethnic minority backgrounds were more likely to rate all learning formats - *transcripts of speakers' presentations*, *written summaries of speakers' presentations*, *visual graphics of evidence*, *time with speakers in breakout rooms* and *live Q&A with experts* - as *very helpful* compared to White Scottish/British respondents.

There were varied patterns by age for learning formats. *Written summaries of speakers' presentations* showed the strongest cross-age appeal, with a majority in every group rating them as *very helpful* and few negative responses. *Transcripts*, and *visual graphics* were the most polarising formats, with younger and older participants often rating them highly while middle-aged groups were more variable or less enthusiastic.

Participants in the 19-24 age group were consistently enthusiastic about all formats, with only *live Q&A sessions* drawing a more mixed response. Those aged 25-29 followed similar trends, giving uniformly positive ratings to *small group discussions* and *presentations by speakers*, while *live Q&A sessions with experts* drew a more varied response. The 30-44 age group were most likely to find *live Q&A sessions very helpful* (70%, n=14), along with broad support for *small group discussions* (72.7%, n=16 *very helpful*). This was the most critical age group for *presentations by speakers*, with only half saying they were *very helpful* and 18.1% (n=4) saying they were only *a little helpful* or *not helpful at all*. Less than half found transcripts *very helpful*, and two participants rated *written summaries* as *not at all helpful*. *Visual graphics* drew a range of responses. Participants aged 45-64 were the least consistently positive. While two-thirds rated *small group discussions* and *presentations* as *very helpful*, they were the least enthusiastic age group about *transcripts of speaker presentations* (only 35%, n=8 *very helpful*) and *visual graphics* (45.8%, n=11 *very helpful*). Participants aged 45-64 were generally positive about *written summaries* but gave the largest proportion of the *somewhat helpful* rating (20.8%, n=5), and just over half (52.2%, n=12) found Q&A sessions *very helpful*.

4.1.2. RQ 2a: How inclusive were Citizens' Assemblies in terms of representation (diversity as an indication of inclusivity): Includes comments and perceptions about the socio-demographic make-up of the assembly; if certain types of people dominated conversations; if participants felt like there was a diverse range of experts; if participants felt like there was a diverse range of facilitators.

This section explores participants' perceptions of the representativeness of the assemblies, including the socio-demographic make-up of fellow members, the presence or absence of dominant voices, and the fairness of the information provided. Insights are examined through both intersecting social groups and individual demographic variables to assess whether inclusion was experienced equitably across social groups.

Socio-demographic make-up of the assembly

Insights on intersecting social groups

Both Catalonia and Scotland's citizens' assembly evaluations included questions on the perceived social diversity of the assembly, offering insights into assembly members' perceptions of citizens' assembly organisers' attempts to maximise representativeness. In Scotland, participants were asked whether the assembly was *diverse enough to ensure a broad range of perspectives are considered* while for Catalonia, participants were asked if the *Assembly reflected the social diversity of Catalonia*. It is worth highlighting the relative ambiguity in both of these survey questions regarding what is included in the term 'Assembly', meaning respondents could have been rating the diversity of Assembly participants, the experts, and/or the organisers of the citizens' assembly. Despite this limitation, these variables are taken as more likely to be referring to the socio-demographic make-up of the assembly participants, as more specific questions regarding experts and information presented were asked separately.

Most participants across both assemblies perceived the Citizens' Assemblies as diverse and inclusive in terms of its social representativeness. Negative responses were not highly concentrated within any age/gender group. This suggests that, overall, the assemblies' recruitment strategies were broadly accepted by participants as successful in achieving a socially diverse composition. The lack of concentrated dissatisfaction in any particular subgroup may indicate that perceptions of representativeness were widely shared across demographic lines. However, when participants in Catalonia were probed specifically on visible exclusion or over-inclusion of certain groups, additional trends emerged (see below).

Insights on individual social groups

For Catalonia's Citizens' Assembly, 83.9% (n=57) thought at least *quite a bit* or *a lot* that *the people in the assembly reflect the social diversity of Catalonia*, with no concentration of disagreement amongst any particular social group. A further 88.3% (n=60) agreed that *the diversity of people in the assembly helped to achieve results*. Similarly, for Scotland, 89.8% (n=70) people agreed that the assembly was *diverse enough to ensure a broad range of perspectives are considered*, and there were no major differences in perceptions between genders, ages or ethnicities. Given that a traditional sortition method (random stratified selection method) was used for the sampling and recruitment for both of these citizens' assemblies, this demonstrates a broad level of acceptance from participants for this method - at least in terms of its effectiveness for producing a group that itself feels representative of the population.

However, when Catalonia Citizens' Assembly participants were probed more specifically regarding any potential under- or overrepresentation of particular groups, different attitudes emerged amongst different demographic groups. Women were notably more likely than men to believe both that *a group or collective was not represented in the Assembly* (54.5% of women, n=18, responded *yes*, compared to 38.2% of men, n=13), and that *a group or collective was overrepresented in the Assembly* (32.4% of women, n=11, answered *yes*, compared to 12.1% of men, n=4). In terms of age, the youngest participants (aged 16-24) were the most likely to report that a group was overrepresented, with 66.7% (n=4) answering *yes*, sharply contrasting with the responses of older groups. This contrasts with results from Scotland's Citizens' Assembly, where there were no major differences between genders, ages or ethnicities in perceptions of whether the Assembly was *diverse enough to ensure a broad range of perspectives*.

Dominance in small group dynamics

Also relevant to the question of representation is that of group dynamics, which recognises that beyond PMIMG being present throughout a citizens' assembly, their meaningful inclusion in group settings is affected by "existing inequalities, power imbalances, and historical and ongoing injustices" (Deliverable 2.2, p. 56). This may result in certain types of people with non-marginalised identities taking up more space in a group setting than others.

Insights on individual social groups

Shedding light on this, Scotland's Citizens' Assembly evaluation included a question regarding the extent to which *one or more of the people in [their] small group tended to dominate the*

discussions. While there were no clear gender-based trends in response to this question, notably a plurality of men *neither agreed nor disagreed* (44.1%, n=15), while women were more evenly split across *agreement* and *disagreement*, with at least 14% of women providing each response option except *strongly agree*. In terms of age, younger and older groups reported the most *strong agreement* with the statement, while middle-aged groups (30-44, 45-64) were more likely to *disagree* or be neutral. There were some differences across ethnic groups in perceptions of dominance in small group discussions, but no clear pattern emerged to make an overall conclusion.

Information fairness and balance

Insights on intersecting social groups

The majority of participants across Scotland and Catalonia's citizens' assemblies responded positively regarding the level of fairness and balance in the information provided to them. Looking at the data from both citizens' assemblies combined in terms of age and gender, women aged 29 and under were the most divided in their perceptions of information fairness. 50% (n=5) of this specific demographic group responded negatively to a question about the balance of information provided. While this subgroup is small and interpretations should be made tentatively, the divergence is proportionally notable, particularly when contrasted with the overwhelming positive responses across most other groups. The finding underscores the importance of examining how different intersections of identity can influence not just experience, but perceptions of throughput legitimacy - a key dimension of inclusivity in deliberative processes.

Insights on individual social groups

For Scotland, the only clear difference by gender, age or ethnicity was that women and people identifying in another way were more likely than men to *strongly agree that the information they received during the assembly weekends has been fair and balanced between different viewpoints*, while men showed more mixed results, with 15.6% (n=6) *disagreeing* compared to only 2.4% (n=1) women. For Catalonia, no substantial differences were observed across gender. Younger age groups (especially 25-29), those with only compulsory secondary education, and participants from the rest of Spain were slightly more likely to believe perspectives were missed.

4.1.3. RQ 2b: How inclusive was the citizens' assembly process, in terms of its design and organisation?

This section examines how participants in the Scottish Citizens' Assembly¹² perceived the inclusiveness of procedural elements of the Citizens' Assemblies, such as logistical support, communication, organisation, and opportunities to influence the design of the citizens' assembly itself, such as speaker and content decisions. Overall, satisfaction with logistical aspects was high, but there were nuances in how participants of different identities experienced agency within the process - particularly concerning influence over speaker and content selection.

Logistics and organisation

Insights on individual social groups

Participants in the Scottish citizens' assembly reported consistently high levels of satisfaction with the design and delivery of the process, particularly in relation to logistical and organisational aspects. Support from organisers (Involve), communications in the lead-up to the weekend, and the overall organisation of the event were rated positively by the vast majority of participants, regardless of gender, age, or ethnicity. Women were consistently more likely than men to rate these aspects as *very satisfactory*, with 76.2% (n=32) of women choosing this option for support from organisers, compared to 64.7% (n=22) of men. Participants identifying in another way gave uniformly high ratings, with 100.0% (n=2) selecting *very satisfactory*. Across age groups, satisfaction was also high, though slightly lower proportions of *very satisfactory* responses were observed among the youngest (19–24) and oldest (75+) participants - 33.3% (n=2) and 25.0% (n=1), respectively - compared to higher rates among mid-age groups, such as 75.0% (n=3) among 25–29s and 77.3% (n=17) among 30–44s. Ethnic minority participants, including Asian and Black respondents, reported particularly strong satisfaction, with 100.0% (n=2 per group) selecting *very satisfactory* for support from Involve. Only one respondent from the White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other group gave a response lower than *satisfied*.

Opportunities for Assembly members to influence citizens' assembly design and delivery

Insights on individual social groups

Despite this strong procedural satisfaction, participants across all demographic groups reported limited perceived influence over key aspects of the Assembly's agenda and content

¹² No member experience variables were available in the Climate Assembly of Catalonia dataset to address this research question.

delivery. Notably, no participants - regardless of gender, age, or ethnicity - selected *tend to agree* or *strongly agree* when asked whether they *had influence over the choice of speakers that presented information this weekend*. Strong disagreement increased with age, from 40.0% (n=2) among 19–24s to 100.0% (n=2) among those aged 75 and over. Among women, 52.9% (n=18) selected *strongly disagree*, compared to 57.7% (n=15) of men. The two participants identifying *in another way* selected either *tend to disagree* or *neither agree nor disagree*, but neither expressed agreement.

Perceived *opportunity to influence decisions about the content of the information presented* during the assembly was somewhat higher, though still modest. Participants identifying *in another way* were most likely to feel included in content decisions, with 50.0% (n=1) selecting *strongly agree*. Among women, 34.3% (n=12) selected *strongly agree*, compared to 25.0% (n=7) of men. Men were also more likely than women to choose neutral or negative responses. Across all age groups, at least 60.0% of participants agreed to some extent, with *tend to agree* being the most common response. For example, 50.0% (n=3) of those aged 19–24 and 25.0% (n=1) of those aged 25–29 selected *strongly agree*. Ethnic differences were less pronounced in this question, though again all Asian respondents (100.0%, n=2) selected either *tend to agree* or *strongly agree*, and a clear majority of White Scottish/British participants (71.5%, n=40) also selected one of these two options.

In sum, while participants widely praised the organisational and communicative aspects of the Scottish Citizens' Assembly, there was a consistent perception of limited influence over speaker selection and, to a lesser extent, over information content.

4.1.4. RQ 2b: How inclusive was the citizens' assembly process, in terms of facilitation and deliberation?

Participants across both the Scottish and Catalanian citizens' assemblies generally reported positive experiences of facilitation and deliberation, with high levels of agreement across key indicators such as feeling heard, respected, and able to contribute. However, variations in the strength of agreement across gender, age, and ethnic groups revealed patterns that merit further attention.

Opportunities for Assembly members to speak and participate

Insights on intersecting social groups

Both Scotland and Catalonia's citizens' assembly evaluations assessed the extent to which Assembly members felt they had an opportunity to speak. In Scotland, participants were asked how much they agreed that they had *ample opportunity in the small-group discussions to express [their] views*, while for Catalonia, participants were asked during the debate, *do you think everyone had the opportunity to speak and participate?* Taking both data together, while responses were broadly positive, a slightly lower rate of positivity (80%, n=8) was observed amongst women under the age of 29 compared to men in that age group (100%, n=9). While based on small subgroup sizes, this difference may suggest that younger women were somewhat more likely to feel constrained or less fully included in group discussions. Possible explanations could include dynamics of confidence, group composition, or subtle power imbalances. However, the limited number of respondents means this should be interpreted cautiously - as a potential area of concern rather than a definitive conclusion.

Insights on individual social groups

Looking at the Scotland citizens' assembly data alone, ethnic minority participants were more likely to select *strongly agree* compared to other groups, though sample sizes for non-white respondents were small.

Other trends identified in the Catalonia Citizens' Assembly evaluation was that participants from Other countries were more likely to express higher satisfaction, with 40% (n=2) selecting *a lot*, while smaller proportions of other birthplaces chose this option.

Feeling listened to and satisfaction with participation efforts

In addition to questions assessing whether participants had sufficient opportunity to speak, both assembly evaluations assessed the extent to which their efforts to participate translated into feeling listened to and satisfaction with the process. The Scottish evaluation asked *how much participants agreed that their contributions [had] been listened to by the other Assembly members*, while Catalonia's evaluation asked if *they were satisfied with [their] level of participation during the debate/work sessions*.

Insights on intersecting social groups

Taking both citizens' assemblies data together, while overall positive responses were high (90%, n=123), younger men (29 and under) expressed slightly greater dissatisfaction (30%,

n=2 negative) compared to their peers. There were no further strong trends in each individual dataset beyond gender and age.

Insights on individual social groups

Scotland's Citizens' Assembly evaluation asked additional questions which shed more light on their perceptions of other Assembly members, and how those perceptions impacted their experience. Notably, men were more cautious than women in their agreement with the statement, 'my fellow participants respected what I had to say, even when they didn't agree with me' - only 35.3% (n=12) of men strongly agreed, compared to 52.4% (n=22) of women. Men were also more likely to agree that they didn't always feel free to raise [their] views and ideas, for fear of others' reactions - reported by 11.8% (n=4) of men compared to just 2.4% (n=1) of women. While the available data does not allow for a definitive explanation, one tentative interpretation is that this pattern may reflect the influence of other intersecting factors not captured by the evaluation, such as education level or socio-economic background. Alternatively, it could suggest a form of self-censorship among men - who, as a group, often hold greater systemic power¹³ - driven by a conscious awareness of not wanting to dominate discussion spaces. This possibility highlights how inclusion dynamics are not only shaped by structural marginalisation, but also by individuals' internalised norms about participation and space-taking. The only other notable demographic difference in responses to this question was that the 65-74 age group were the most likely to strongly disagree with this statement.

Facilitator encouragement of debate

Insights on intersecting social groups

The extent to which facilitators encouraged debate was measured in both assembly evaluations, with Scotland's survey asking participants how much they agreed that *the breakout room facilitator made sure that opposing arguments were considered* while Catalonia's participants were asked *did the facilitation team help and encourage the debate?* Taking both results together, there were few striking differences across age and gender regarding facilitator encouragement of debate, with consistently positive responses across most groups (n=135; 96%). This high and relatively uniform level of satisfaction suggests that facilitation practices were broadly effective in creating space for differing views to be expressed and explored.

Insights on individual social groups

¹³ For a discussion on the role of sex and gender in the work on inclusivity within citizens' assemblies design features see Deliverable 2.2 pp. 75, 103-105.

Taking Catalonia's evaluation data alone, no further major differences between positivity and negativity were observed across other demographic lines, though participants with undergraduate or postgraduate degrees were slightly more moderate in their positivity of the facilitators' efforts to help and encourage the debate than other education groups.

Looking at Scotland's data individually, while again there was no demographic group that expressed significant negativity, there were some differences across ethnic groups in their perceptions of the facilitator's success in making sure opposing arguments were considered. Black and White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other were more likely to select *strongly agree*, whereas other groups showed slightly more varied responses. However, small sample sizes in the non-White Scottish/British respondents mean these results should be interpreted with caution.

Facilitatory neutrality

Insights on intersecting social groups

Both Scotland and Catalonia's citizens' assembly evaluations assessed the extent to which Assembly members felt the facilitators were sufficiently neutral. The Scottish Citizens' Assembly evaluation asked for agreement levels to the negatively framed statement *the breakout room facilitator sometimes tried to influence the group with their own ideas*, while the Catalonia Citizens' Assembly asked participants directly if they thought *the facilitation team remained neutral*. After aggregating the results from both datasets, women aged 65 and over were slightly more likely to report negatively compared to other gender/age subgroups. Although based on a small number of respondents, this pattern may reflect a greater sensitivity among older women to perceived bias or imbalance in facilitation. This could stem from prior civic experiences, expectations of impartiality, or generational differences in interpreting facilitator behaviour. Given the limited scale of this divergence, it should not be overinterpreted, but it highlights the value of continuing to monitor how different social groups perceive neutrality within deliberative processes.

Insights on individual social groups

There were no strong trends in the Scotland dataset beyond age and gender. In the Catalonia evaluation, participants with postgraduate degrees were the most hesitant about the facilitator's neutrality, with less than half of each category selecting *a lot* and a small share (22.2%, n=2) respondents selecting *little*, suggesting modest uncertainty in this higher education bracket.

4.1.5. RQ 2d: Outputs: Do PMIMG participants feel their perspectives are included in citizens' assembly outputs? Do these participants feel a sense of co-ownership of citizens' assembly outputs?

This section examines whether participants felt their views were reflected in the final outputs of the Assemblies and whether different social groups experienced a sense of co-ownership. We analyse which groups felt most or least heard in the recommendations, and explore how factors such as gender, education, ethnicity, and place of birth may have influenced those perceptions.

Contributions reflected in final recommendations

Insights on intersecting social groups

Across both citizens' assembly evaluations, the extent to which assembly members' felt their contributions throughout the process were reflected in the final recommendations was assessed. Scotland's Citizens' Assembly evaluation asked how much participants agreed that their *views are reflected in the finalised goals and recommendations*, while Catalonia asked if participants thought their *opinions have been included in the final recommendations*. While responses were broadly *positive* (90%, n=116), it was notable that most negativity could be accounted for by men in the 30-44 and 45-64 age groups (20% of men in both age groups, n=4 and n=3 respectively). This may reflect higher expectations among this group regarding influence or impact, potentially shaped by their societal positioning as historically more empowered decision-makers. In contexts where the deliberative process distributes influence more equally, these participants may experience a perceived reduction in relative influence, leading to a stronger critical stance on the final recommendations.

Insights on individual social groups

However, this interpretation is complicated by the fact that when looking at the Catalonia data in isolation, men were more likely than women to feel their views were fully reflected, with 70.6% (n=24) selecting *a lot*, compared to 58.8% (n=20) of women. This could suggest a national or cultural difference in how co-ownership is interpreted or expressed across genders. Alternatively, it may reflect variations in facilitation quality, cultural norms of voice/assertiveness, or comfort levels in the deliberative setting that influenced men's perceptions more positively in Catalonia.

Looking at the Scotland data in isolation, a striking difference by ethnicity was observed: White Scottish/British participants were the only ethnic group that selected *tend to disagree* (11.9%, n=7) and *neither agree nor disagree* (10.2%, n=6), while ethnic minority groups universally at least *somewhat agreed*. While this may suggest that ethnic minority participants felt their voices were included, the small sample sizes mean caution is warranted. Another possibility is that ethnic minority participants were less willing to express dissent in a formal evaluative setting, especially if they were unsure whether criticism would be acted upon or welcomed. This could reflect broader patterns of civic under-empowerment, where people from marginalised backgrounds are less likely to publicly critique processes they were invited into. Further qualitative data would be needed to validate this possibility.

Taking the Catalonia data alone, perceptions of opinion inclusion declined slightly with education level. Primary school educated-participants reported the highest perception of full inclusion (*a lot*, 66.7%, n=2) compared to university undergraduates (*a lot*, 29.6%, n=8) who were the most likely age group to select *little* (14.8%, n=4). This may point to a pattern where more formally educated participants have more critical or complex expectations of what it means for one's views to be reflected in the final recommendations.

Separating responses by place of birth revealed that participants from other places felt their opinions were included strongly (*a lot*) at the highest rate (80.0%, n=4) compared to only 18.0% (n=9) from Catalonia. This suggests that participants with migration backgrounds may have experienced a stronger sense of co-ownership. In terms of different experiences of different language groups, Catalan speakers were more likely than Spanish people to report a high level of inclusion (34.4%, n=11 compared to 19.4%, n=7), and less likely to say their opinions were only included *a little* (6.3%, n=2 compared to 13.9%, n=5). This may reflect linguistic familiarity with the process, or a closer alignment between Catalan civic culture and the deliberative environment. Spanish speakers, who may be more often associated with recent migration or different cultural-political positioning in Catalonia, were more likely to feel that their views were only partially included. This could suggest a subtle linguistic-cultural barrier to full co-ownership, even within a broadly inclusive process.

Confidence in uptake of recommendations

Insights on intersecting social groups

Both citizens' assemblies' evaluations explored whether assembly participants felt recommendations would be taken forward by the governments in Scotland and Catalonia. Scotland's citizens' assembly evaluation asked how much participants agreed that they were

confident that the Assembly report will be taken seriously by Parliament and political parties, while Catalonia asked if participants thought *the Assembly's recommendations will be adopted by the Government of Catalonia*. This question drew more negative responses than any other measure examined in this report. Men aged 45-64 expressed considerable negativity (80%, n=10), while those aged 29 and under (both men at 60%, n=4, and women at 50%, n=4) also showed notable scepticism. Conversely, the group aged 30-44, especially women, were more optimistic (80% positive, n=12). This finding points to generational and gendered differences in political trust or expectations of impact.

4.1.6. RQ 2d: Outcomes: Do PMIMG feel a personal impact (e.g., a change in attitude or view on a topic, confidence, or sense of political agency), as a result of participation in the citizens' assembly?

This section reviews whether participation in the Assembly had a personal impact on members' political confidence, deliberative comfort, and future engagement intentions. By examining changes in attitudes across gender, age, and other social categories, we assess whether the Assembly experience affected individuals' sense of agency and voice differently depending on their background.

Interest in future participation

Insights on intersecting social groups

Both citizens' assemblies asked about the extent to which Assembly members were interested in participating in future political initiatives. In Scotland's evaluation, they asked participants to rate their level of agreement with the statement *taking part in this citizens' assembly has made me want to be more involved in other aspects of Government decision making*, while Catalonia's evaluation asked participants if *they would be willing to participate in another citizens' assembly*. While the majority of participants expressed positivity, 50% (n=2) of older women (aged 65 and over) gave negative responses, and similarly men aged 45-64 were not as broadly enthusiastic (30%, n=5 negative responses) as other groups. These results could reflect generational differences in expectations of political involvement, or perhaps a greater sense of fatigue or disengagement following the Assembly process. Conversely, the youngest group, particularly those identifying in another way, expressed unanimous positivity, though sample sizes were small.

Changes in deliberative confidence

Insights on individual social groups

Scotland's Climate Assembly evaluation asked a range of other questions both before and after the Assembly process in order to track any attitudinal changes that may have developed as a result of the experience.

Across all participants, a majority (59.0%) reported no change in agreement with the statement *I think my opinion is as valid as anyone else's*, but notable gender differences emerged. Women were more likely to report a positive shift in confidence: 31.8% (n=7) recorded an increase of +1, compared to only 5.9% (n=1) of men. Men were more variable, with 11.8% (n=2) reporting a decrease of -3, a level of decline not seen among women. This may suggest that the assembly bolstered women's sense of voice slightly more, while men's responses were more polarised.

Gender again played a role in changes in agreement with the statement *I feel comfortable challenging someone's opinion during a conversation*. While most men (47.1%, n=8) and women (34.8%, n=8) reported no change, increased comfortability challenging someone's opinion was more prevalent among women: 26.1% (n=6) recorded an increase of +1, compared to 11.8% (n=2) of men. Conversely, decreased comfortability challenging someone's opinion (-1) was more common among men (35.3%, n=6) than women (26.1%, n=6). These results may indicate that the Assembly environment was slightly more empowering for women, or that men began with a higher baseline and thus had less room for perceived improvement.

Older participants (75+, n=3) were the only group to report uniform declines in comfortability challenging someone's opinion, all experiencing a decrease of -1, while younger and mid-aged groups were more mixed. For example, participants aged 25-29 showed the highest rate of a +1 change (50.0%, n=1). Overall, this suggests confidence gains were modest and not evenly distributed, with older adults potentially feeling less affirmed by the process.

Differences in gender were particularly striking in changes in agreement with the statement *I feel nervous speaking in front of a group*. Women were more likely than men to report increased nervousness, with 22.7% (n=5) recording +1 and 13.6% (n=3) +2, compared to just 5.9% (n=1) of men reporting +1. In contrast, 29.4% (n=5) of men experienced a decrease of -1, compared to only 9.1% (n=2) of women.

By age, the strongest reductions in nervousness were found among those aged 65-74 (66.7%, n=4) and 45-64 (18.8%, n=3), indicating increased ease in speaking over time. In contrast, younger groups such as 19-24 and 30-44 had higher instances of increased nervousness, including one 19-24 participant who recorded a +3 increase.

Across all demographics, participants generally reported stable or improved confidence in political engagement, measured through agreement with the statement *I feel more confident to engage in political decision-making as a result of being involved in this citizens' assembly*. Women leaned more toward agreement, with 46.4% (n=13) tending to agree, compared to 36.4% (n=8) of men. Older participants showed the strongest agreement: 65–74 (71.5%, n=5) and 75+ (66.7%, n=2), suggesting that the assembly may have been particularly empowering for older adults.

No ethnic group reported disagreement. Among White Scottish/British participants, 42.2% (n=19) tended to agree and 20.0% (n=9) strongly agreed, showing a strong overall sense of empowerment across all ethnic groups.

4.1.7. RQ 3: What was the impact of technology on participants' perception of the citizens' assembly? Were there differences in experiences based on online versus face-to-face formats? Was the use of technology experienced differently depending on social groups?

This section analyses participants' perceptions of the technological aspects of Scotland's Climate Assembly. We explore whether barriers or benefits associated with technology - such as platform usability, session length, and device access - were experienced differently across age, gender, and ethnic groups, highlighting how digital format design may affect inclusion. It should be recalled here that the Scotland's Climate Assembly took place entirely online.

Insights on individual social groups

Participants across all gender groups in Scotland's Climate Assembly reported high satisfaction with the technological aspects of the assembly. Use of the online learning platform was well received to similar degrees across gender groups, with no one expressing dissatisfaction. Regarding the usefulness of the Online Hub, which was described above under the information about the Assembly, women were slightly more positive: 37.9% (n=11) found it *very helpful* compared to 25.0% (n=6) of men.

In terms of barriers, women rejected the idea that distractions, devices, or connection difficulties reduced participation to a slightly stronger extent than men. For example, 76.2% (n=32) of women *strongly disagreed* that connection issues were a barrier, compared with 55.9% (n=19) of men. Women were also slightly more likely to *strongly disagree* that online session length reduced participation (69.0%, n=29) compared with men (50.0%, n=17), while men were more likely to *tend to disagree* (41.2%, n=14 vs. 19.0%, n=8).

Older participants consistently reported the highest levels of satisfaction and the fewest barriers related to technology use. For example, among those aged 65–74, 83.3% (n=20) *strongly disagreed* that their device limited participation, and the same proportion *strongly disagreed* that platform difficulties were a barrier. In the 75+ group, *strongly disagree* responses remained high across most questions - for example, 75% (n=3) regarding distractions and connection difficulties, and 100.0% (n=4) regarding session length. By contrast, younger participants (under 30) were more likely to express ambivalence or mild disruption. Neutral responses were more frequent in this group: 33.3% (n=2) were *neutral* about distractions, and one participant (16.7%) selected *neutral* regarding platform use. Among 25–29s, similar trends were observed - only 25.0% (n=1) *strongly disagreed* about session length being a barrier, and 50.0% (n=2) *strongly disagreed* with statements about platform difficulties.

On connection issues, 83.3% (n=18) of 65–74s and 75.0% (n=3) of 75+ *strongly disagreed* they were affected, compared with only 33.3% (n=2) of 19–24s. Notably, *tend to disagree* was selected more often by 30–44s (22.7%, n=5) and other younger groups, suggesting a more moderate experience of stability.

Participants across all ages found the Online Hub useful. In the 65-74 group, 50.0% (n=5) found it *quite helpful* and 40.0% (n=4) *very helpful*. Among 19-24s, 40.0% (n=2) selected each of those options, with 20.0% (n=1) choosing *somewhat helpful*.

Differences by ethnicity were minimal, though sample sizes were small in minoritised social groups. Among White Scottish/British participants, satisfaction with the online learning platform was high, with 45.3% (n=29) *very satisfied* and 43.8% (n=28) *satisfied*. Across all questions, the majority in this group selected *strongly disagree* when asked whether technology limited participation. For example, 75.0% (n=48) *strongly disagreed* that their device reduced participation; 70.3% (n=45) *strongly disagreed* that platform difficulties were a barrier.

Among the White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other group, results followed a similar pattern, though with more variability: 60.0% (n=3) were *satisfied* and 20.0% (n=1) *very satisfied* with the platform; one respondent (25.0%) chose each of the usefulness levels for the Online Hub (from *a little helpful* to *very helpful*), reflecting no strong consensus.

For Asian and Black Scottish/British participants, sample sizes were too small for definitive conclusions (n=2 per group), but responses were largely positive or neutral. Both respondents in the Asian group selected *neutral* when asked about the online learning platform, and neither selected dissatisfaction. Both Black respondents reported satisfaction with the Hub and no barriers related to devices, connection, or distractions.

4.1.8. RQ 4: What are the drivers of non-participation in citizens' assemblies by potential participants from different social groups? (by non-participation we mean citizens declining to participate in the citizens' assembly at all, and citizens not engaging while in the citizens' assembly, and citizens dropping out of the citizens' assembly)

This section makes use of the data available to us to examine potential factors affecting non-participation in citizen assembly processes. While specific data to directly draw out factors driving non-participation are not available, we examined the data detailing target recruitment quotas, confirmed recruitment, subsequent drop-off during the assembly processes, and response rates to evaluation surveys to provide some indirect insights to answer this research question.

Insights on individual social groups

In Catalonia, the number of participants attending dropped from 100 recruited to a low of 81 during the process, with 83 attending the final meeting. While attendance data is not disaggregated by social group, the evaluation response data shows people aged 16-29 were the least likely to complete the evaluation. This trend of underrepresentation of younger participants in evaluation was also identified within the Scotland evaluation response data. In Scotland, response rates for those aged 16–18 and 19–24 were 0% and 50% respectively, while in Catalonia, only 40% of participants aged 16–29 responded to the evaluation.

Similarly, those with the lowest levels of formal education (no studies or primary only) had the lowest response rate in Catalonia (36.4%) compared to 87.8% among highly educated participants. In Scotland, there was also an underrepresentation of Black and minority ethnic participants in evaluation data (50% response rate).

While this data does not capture reasons for disengagement, it suggests that younger participants, those with less educational experience, and historically marginalised groups may be less likely to complete follow-up evaluations - a pattern that may also reflect broader disengagement or barriers to sustained participation within the process itself.

5. Summary of Key Findings

Here, we summarise the key methodological and substantive findings from our secondary evaluation data analysis before presenting the full results further below.

5.1. Findings Related to Intersectional Social Groups

Here, we set out key exploratory findings about the experience of intersectional subgroups (i.e., that combine age and gender) that emerged from the secondary data analysis. Given the small sample sizes available for specific intersections, these results should be interpreted as indicative rather than generalisable. While the analyses yield valuable insights into potential patterns in participants' experiences across gender, age, and ethnicity, they are not sufficient to support evidence-based recommendations about assembly design or facilitation practices. **Instead, their primary contribution lies in illustrating how intersectional analysis can uncover meaningful differences even within limited datasets, thereby highlighting the value of collecting, retaining, and analysing richer demographic data in future assemblies to inform more robust recommendations at later stages of the project.**

Secondary Evaluation Key Finding 1: Young women were more likely to express negative views about the clarity of the Assembly's purpose (RQ 1)

While responses regarding the clarity of the Assembly's purpose and process were broadly positive across both assemblies, **intersectional analysis revealed a small divergence amongst women aged 29 and under, who expressed negative views about the clarity of the Assembly's purpose** (see 4.1.1 *Clarity of Assembly purpose and process* for details). This result should be treated as an **indicator worth exploring in the EU-CIEMBLY pilot assemblies** rather than a definitive finding. It also highlights the value of disaggregating data by intersectional social groups to alert citizens' assembly organisers of trends which might otherwise go unnoticed in univariate analyses.

Secondary Evaluation Key Finding 2: Young women were the most divided group in perceptions of information fairness (RQ 2a)

While the majority of participants across Scotland and Catalonia's citizens' assemblies responded positively regarding the level of fairness and balance in the information provided to them, **50% of women aged 29 and under gave negative responses**. While interpretations should be made tentatively, the divergence is proportionally notable, particularly when contrasted with the overwhelming positive responses across most other groups (e.g., women aged 30-44 with 85% positive responses, men aged 29 and under with 88.9%. See 4.1.1 *Information fairness and balance* for details). The finding underscores the importance of examining how different intersections of identity can influence not just experience, but perceptions of (throughput) legitimacy, which is a key dimension of inclusivity in deliberative processes.

Secondary Evaluation Key Finding 3: Young women and men aged 30-44 and 45-64 reported lower agreement that everyone had the opportunity to speak (RQ 2b)

Negative responses to questions about the level of opportunity to speak and participate in both citizens' assemblies were minimal. However, notable proportions of women aged 29 and under, men aged 30-44, and men aged 45-64 responded negatively to the statement that everyone had equal opportunities - slightly higher than rates of disagreement compared to other subgroups. The fact that these differences were only minor, and based on small sample sizes, limits the strength of these findings. However, **taking key findings 1, 2 and 3 together could suggest that younger women may face unique barriers to inclusion, including navigating group dynamics or interpreting information under pressure.**

Secondary Evaluation Key Finding 4: Older women and young men were slightly more critical of facilitator neutrality (RQ 2b)

Across both datasets, **women aged 65+** and **men aged 29 and under** were **more likely to question the neutrality of facilitators**. Both subgroups expressed negativity towards facilitator neutrality levels, which could suggest that these intersectional groups may have perceived subtle biases in group dynamics or facilitation choices, despite overall positive trends.

Secondary Evaluation Key Finding 5: Men under 30 and men aged 45–64 were most sceptical of the uptake of recommendations (RQ 2c)

Confidence that recommendations would be taken seriously was lowest among **men aged 45–64**, and **men under 30**. Compared to other findings in this report, this result stands out due to the large proportional differences observed, making it one of the stronger divergences identified in the combined dataset. While these groups may not be structurally marginalised, the result could suggest that **their intersection of gender and age may have shaped stronger cynicism or higher expectations of political responsiveness**.

Secondary Evaluation Key Finding 6: Older women and men aged 45-64 were the least interested in future participation in deliberative democracy (RQ 2d)

While the majority of participants across Scotland and Catalonia’s climate assemblies expressed positivity regarding interest in participating in future political initiatives, 50% of older women (aged 65 and over) gave negative responses, and similarly men aged 45-64 were not as broadly enthusiastic as other groups. Conversely, **the youngest group, particularly those identifying in another way**, expressed unanimous positivity, though sample sizes were small. **This may indicate that the transformative potential of citizens’ assemblies is uneven** and may need targeted reinforcement.

5.2. Findings Related to Individual Social Groups

This section summarises key findings related to gender, age, and ethnicity separately. Although our primary focus is on intersectional rather than homogenous social group experiences, examining each social group individually provides context for interpreting the intersectional patterns identified above. The purpose of this section is also to help synthesise key trends in relation to the project’s research questions, serving as a bridge between the detailed intersectional analyses presented earlier and the broader synthesis of insights provided earlier in the report. The statistical detail for these findings can be found in the ‘Annex - Results on Individual Social Groups - Secondary Analysis Results Tables’, which has been submitted together with this Deliverable Report.

Secondary Evaluation Key Finding 7: Ethnic minority participants rated deliberative tools and formats more positively than White participants (RQ 2b)

In Scotland, ethnic minority participants **unanimously rated all learning formats as at least quite helpful**, and were **more likely** than White Scottish/British participants **to rate formats like small group discussions, transcripts, and breakout rooms as very helpful**. This may reflect a greater appreciation of inclusive facilitation techniques when provided, or contrasted with more exclusionary civic experiences elsewhere.

Secondary Evaluation Key Finding 8: Educational background shaped how clear and appropriate participants found citizens' assembly content and methodology (RQ 2b)

Postgraduates in Catalonia were consistently **less satisfied with clarity and content** than those with lower levels of education, particularly on debate objectives and training materials. This suggests that **designing for diverse cognitive styles and expectations** is essential to support equitable understanding and engagement.

Secondary Evaluation Key Finding 9: Most participants felt the Assemblies were socially diverse enough, but women and young people were more likely to identify gaps in representation. (RQ 2a)

In Catalonia, while overall perceptions of representativeness were positive, **54.5% of women believed there were some groups not sufficiently represented, and 66.7% of participants aged 16–24** believed some groups were overrepresented - compared to lower rates among men and older participants. This suggests that **surface-level diversity may not be experienced equally**, and some groups remain more attuned to exclusion.

Secondary Evaluation Key Finding 10: Women and ethnic minority participants were more likely to rate learning formats and facilitation positively (RQ 2b)

In Scotland, **women and those identifying in another way** rated all facilitation formats as more helpful than men, which could suggest that these groups may have experienced the space as **more supportive or empowering**.

Secondary Evaluation Key Finding 11: Women reported greater increases in deliberative confidence than men in Scotland's Climate Assembly (RQ 2d)

Evidence from Scotland's Climate Assembly suggests the deliberative process may have had a more consistently empowering effect on women than men. **A much higher proportion of**

women reported increases in measures of deliberative confidence than men. Similarly, women were more likely to report increased comfort challenging others' opinions. These patterns could suggest that the Assembly experience may have strengthened women's deliberative confidence more reliably, while men's responses were **more polarised**, possibly reflecting differing baselines or expectations around voice and influence.

Secondary Evaluation Key Finding 12: Technology was not a major barrier overall, but younger participants were more likely to report mild disruption (RQ 3)

Older adults (65+) reported **the highest satisfaction with online tools** and **fewest perceived barriers**, while younger groups (under 30) expressed more ambivalence or occasional connection issues. This underscores the need to **tailor tech support not only to older users**, but also to **expectations and usage patterns among younger participants**.

Secondary Evaluation Key Finding 13: South American-born participants were less critical of assembly proceedings compared to other birthplace groups (RQ 1)

In the Citizens' Assembly for the Climate of Catalonia, participants born in South America consistently reported higher satisfaction levels than participants born in the rest of Spain or other countries. This trend was **identified across 13 variables**, including **clarity/appropriateness of supporting materials, overall satisfaction with training sessions and speaker presentations**, and **inclusive representation within the assembly's socio-demographic make-up**. This could indicate higher baseline expectations for the assembly amongst participants born in the rest of Spain and other countries compared to those born in South America.

Secondary Evaluation Key Finding 14: Native Catalan speakers consistently expressed higher satisfaction with Assembly proceedings compared to Spanish speakers (RQ 2b)

In Catalonia's Citizens' Assembly, both Catalan- and Spanish-speaking participants reported very positive overall experiences. However, Catalan speakers tended to express slightly higher satisfaction with specific aspects of the process, including **training quality, methodological helpfulness, and clarity of materials**. Language support provided to Spanish speakers included simultaneous translation for the plenary sessions, and assistance from facilitators during the working groups. These results **do not suggest stark divisions in**

participant experience based on language, and could suggest that the language support provided was largely successful, given the lack of explicitly negative responses from Spanish speakers. However, they do indicate that despite best efforts to cater for non-native language speakers, **small variations in satisfaction and critical perception were evident between the two groups.**

5.3. Methodological Findings

While our efforts were primarily focused on addressing these research questions, challenges encountered during the data collection and analysis stage led to several important methodological findings. These findings are important both for understanding the limitations of the data in the context of our project, and for exploring the possibility and prospects of future efforts in intersectional analysis of member experiences in citizens' assemblies. As such, we provide recommendations in this section following on from each methodological finding, which are both for the EU-CIEMBL Y project and for organisers of citizen assemblies that also have the goal of evaluating their approaches to participant inclusion through an intersectional lens.

Secondary Evaluation Key Finding 15: Sortition-based approaches may lead to tokenistic participation of PMIMG

A key limitation of our analysis lies in **the small numbers of people belonging to marginalised social groups (e.g., ethnic minorities, people of non-conforming gender identities, people with less formal education)**, which restricts the strength and generalisability of findings related to those groups. For example, in Scotland's Climate Assembly, only two participants identified their gender as 'in another way', and just four participants identified as non-White. Similarly, in the Citizens' Assembly for the Climate of Catalonia, only one participant had 'no formal education', three had 'primary education' only, and fewer than ten participants fell into birthplace categories such as 'Rest of Spain', 'South America', or 'Other'. While differences observed within these subgroups are notable and warrant further exploration, the validity and reliability of conclusions drawn from such small numbers is inherently limited. This constraint is not only a methodological concern but also highlights a structural issue with traditional sortition-based recruitment, which, although designed to ensure representativeness, often results in very small numbers of people with particular minoritised or structurally excluded identities (e.g., ethnic minorities, gender non-conforming individuals, or people with lower levels of formal education). As sortition remains the standard approach in citizens' assemblies, this limitation is likely to apply to any future attempt to analyse intersectional patterns within such processes.

Secondary Evaluation Recommendation 1: Explore non-sortition based approaches to ensure higher numbers of PMIMG participants

Of primary concern to EU-CIEMBLY is the exploration of PMIMG experiences in our pilot citizens' assemblies. If a traditional sortition approach to sampling and recruitment was implemented in any of the three pilots, we would reproduce the tokenistic nature of PMIMG participation, due to their minoritised position in population samples, and be highly limited in drawing any strong, generalisable conclusions about their experiences. Therefore, the EU-CIEMBLY project should set out to pilot non-sortition based approaches to sampling and recruitment, in order to explore if this ensures high enough numbers of people with multiple overlapping minoritised identities that can result in valid and more generalisable evaluation data. This approach is also reflective of our 'substantive' understanding of intersectional equality and inclusion, which permits more favourable treatment of marginalised social groups. **While there is no 'one size fits all' methodology for intersectional recruitment and decisions must be made depending on the citizens' assembly topic, locale, and the specific goals of the assembly, our pilots should innovate on past practices to explore how different sampling and recruitment methods offered by the theoretical models explored in Deliverable 2.3 lead to different levels of participation, experiences, and outcomes for PMIMG.**

Secondary Evaluation Key Finding 16: Current evaluation approaches to citizens' assemblies limit the potential for analysing experiences through the lens of intersectionality

Regarding the limitations that have transpired and which concern the possibility and prospects of future efforts at intersectional analysis of member experiences in citizens' assemblies, three key observations are relevant here.

Firstly, **our understanding from our dataset scoping efforts is that it does not seem to be essential standard practice to link demographic data to participants' assessments** of the citizens' assemblies experience in any way. That is, demographic data are completely separated from the experience data. While there can be legitimate reasons to aggregate demographic categories to protect respondent privacy (e.g., when there are a low number of respondents in a given category), there are well-established methods of mitigating this concern. An example would be combining categories, which would have allowed for at least a minimum level of differentiation. By way of contrast, a complete aggregation of responses in this way appears excessive to protect privacy. Moreover, it precludes basic analysis of

experiences and outcomes based on demographic characteristics, let alone a more complex intersectional analysis.

As such, the dominant approach to evaluating participant experience of citizens' assemblies, to our knowledge, is limited to reporting experiences or outcomes at the aggregate/univariate (examining one variable at a time) level, rather than differentiated by demographics. This undifferentiated approach is contrary to the European Commission guidelines ([European Commission, 2021](#)) on data collection to allow for evaluation of equality and inclusion. This approach has been identified in nearly all of citizen assemblies we scoped, including The National Assembly for Wales Citizens (2019), the Oxford Citizens' Assembly on Climate Change (2019), the London Borough of Camden Citizen Assembly on Climate Change (2019), the London Borough of Brent Climate Assembly (2020), the Citizens' Assembly on Gender Equality (Ireland, 2021), the Devon Climate Assembly (2021), the Lambeth Citizens' Assembly (2022), the Belgian Citizens' Assembly (KBR Report, 2023), the Barcelona Citizens' Climate Assembly (2023), and the Biergerkomitee Lëtzebuerg 2050. The only evidence of multivariate analysis technique application (i.e., techniques that test relationships between several variables to generalise findings beyond the sample) on the evaluation data from citizens' assembly participants that we could identify was limited to the Citizens' Assembly of Scotland (2022) (distinct from Scotland's Climate Assembly). However, this analysis was not reported systematically in the research report, and we did not receive a response to our dataset sharing request.

Secondly, even where demographic data were collected, there was **unfortunately little consistency in the types, number, and response options within the demographic variables included in evaluations**, limiting the possible scope of our intersectional analysis. This is illustrated in Figure 8, below.

Location	Gender	Age	Ethnicity	Region	Nationality	Education level	Marital status	Physical Ability	Work status	House ownership	Household income (objective)	Social class (inferred)
UK	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
UK	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>					
UK	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
UK	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
UK	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
UK	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				
UK	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
UK	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
UK	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
UK	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
UK	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
UK	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
UK	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Luxembourg	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Luxembourg	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Ireland	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Ireland	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Spain	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Spain	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Spain	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Spain	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Spain	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
EU	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
EU	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
EU	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
EU	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
EU	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
EU	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Canada	<input type="checkbox"/>											
EU	<input type="checkbox"/>											
Denmark	<input type="checkbox"/>											
Belgium	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Figure 8. Types of demographic data available across the scoped citizens' assemblies

For example, while both the datasets that we were able to access and use in our secondary analysis used a diverse set of demographic criteria to recruit participants (e.g., disability status, socio-economic background) these characteristics were not reported in either evaluations at the level of individual responses. This prevented us from being able to maximise the value of the data that had originally been collected at the sampling and recruitment phase.

Secondary Evaluation Recommendation 2: Design evaluation processes with intersectional analysis requirements in mind.

As we set out in Deliverable 3.1, our aim for this secondary data analysis work was to gather a large enough dataset on which multivariate statistical analysis techniques could be applied to explore patterns in experiences of PMIMG. However, the small numbers of PMIMG represented in the datasets we were given access to, lack of alignment in survey items across evaluations, gaps in demographic variables collected and disconnection from participant experience data has revealed a need for improvements and consistency in citizens' assembly evaluation practice in order to improve the potential for large scale intersectional analysis efforts in the future. In order for participant experiences in citizens' assemblies to be analysed and evaluated through an intersectional lens (as is the aim for EU-CIEMBLY, and should be an aim for other citizen assembly initiatives focused on evaluating their approach to inclusion), several key steps are required. These are detailed in Secondary Evaluation Recommendations 2a, 2b, and 2c.

Secondary Evaluation Recommendation 2a: Utilise standardised participant experience evaluation questions across citizens' assembly practice.

In order for the benefits of intersectional analysis methods to be realised (e.g., an ability to draw out statistically significant trends about demographic subgroups, and understand if they are limited to specific assembly processes or are pervasive across different contexts), common survey items for demographic variables and key participant experience variables would be required. This would allow for streamlined dataset merging processes, both in order to build datasets large enough for multivariate analysis techniques to be appropriate and to allow for straightforward comparison between datasets. In terms of participant experience variables, the OECD has provided a strong set of recommended survey items in Annex C of their Evaluation Guidelines for Representative Deliberative Processes, covering process design integrity, deliberative experience, and pathways to impact (OECD, 2021). Since 2021 the Annex C survey items have been adopted frequently in the deliberative democracy arena, especially for major citizens' assemblies and climate forums. Encouragingly, the trend is

toward wider adoption, with Europe leading the way, and other regions gradually following suit.

Secondary Evaluation Recommendation 2b: Gather early and appropriate consent for personal data collection and management.

The current practice of collecting extensive demographic data to inform sampling and recruitment processes for citizens' assemblies while not linking these data to evaluation results represents missed opportunities for improving understanding about how different intersectional groups experience deliberative processes. As such, citizens' assembly organisers should gather early and appropriate consent for the collection and management of participants' anonymised personal data for future research efforts, as well as for the purpose of the citizens' assembly itself. Unique IDs, rather than names, could be used to link data together to preserve anonymity, in addition to aggregation where necessary to mitigate re-identification risks.

Secondary Evaluation Recommendation 2c: Consider a wider variety of socio-demographic variables that reflect forms of power or marginalisation

Evaluations could also go deeper than collecting the standard demographic variables in order to collect other information that more deeply reflects the forms and levels of power they hold in deliberative settings and how this might affect their experience. For example, forms of neurodivergency, housing status and/or residential stability, specific migration or refugee background including recency, or levels of expertise on specific citizens' assembly topic areas could be included as optional survey questions to gather a more nuanced picture of forms of power assembly members may hold in deliberative settings.

Secondary Evaluation Key Finding 17: Lower evaluation engagement among younger, less formally educated, and minoritised participants may signal wider barriers to participation (RQ 4)

Across both the Scotland and Catalonia citizens' assemblies, evaluation response rates were notably lower among participants aged under 30, those with lower levels of formal education and minoritised ethnic groups. While this data does not directly capture reasons for non-participation, the patterns could suggest these groups may face structural or procedural barriers to engagement, both in terms of responding to evaluations and participation in the

assembly processes. These gaps highlight the importance of intersectionally inclusive design and targeted follow-up strategies to ensure representative voices are not only recruited, but retained and heard throughout. Established means of addressing this kind of evaluation participation challenge include: (1) application of evidence-based social science methods in the survey design and participant communication; (2) participatory approaches to evaluation design that involve co-design with underrepresented groups; and (3) pilot testing with a sample of people from typically under-represented groups prior to the main citizens' assembly evaluation data collection.

Secondary Evaluation Recommendation 3: Diversify evaluation approaches beyond traditional post-event surveys

Citizens' assemblies could also adopt multi-point, inclusive evaluation processes to better capture feedback from participants who may be less likely to participate in traditional end-of-process surveys. This could include incorporating focus groups involving rotating groups of participants after each assembly day, supported by varied feedback formats. This approach would reduce reliance on a single post-event survey, help identify emerging participation barriers in real time, and ensure that younger, less formally educated, and minoritised participants are supported to provide feedback and have equitable opportunities to contribute to evaluation of the process.

6. Conclusion

This secondary analysis of evaluation data from Scotland's Climate Assembly and the Citizens' Assembly for the Climate of Catalonia provides new insights into how people with different intersecting social groups experience participation in citizens' assemblies. While both assemblies were generally well-received across most demographic groups, our intersectional analysis reveals subtle yet important patterns that would likely be obscured in univariate reporting. In particular, young women and older men stood out as groups who were more likely to express dissatisfaction or scepticism around elements such as clarity of process, fairness of information, and confidence in uptake of recommendations. Women, ethnic minority participants, and those identifying in another way, were more likely to report positive experiences with facilitation and deliberative formats, suggesting that inclusive practices, when implemented, may be especially beneficial to participants belonging to marginalised groups.

However, this analysis also exposed serious **methodological limitations** that hamper more in-depth and more generalisable intersectional insights. In particular, sortition-based recruitment practices in both assemblies resulted in very low numbers of participants belonging to marginalised groups, undermining the statistical power to detect meaningful trends across multiple intersecting social groups. Furthermore, (unintentional) inconsistencies in the design of evaluation tools and the absence of standardised demographic variables limited our ability to merge or compare datasets systematically. These limitations are not unique to the two assemblies analysed but appear to reflect a broader pattern in citizens' assembly evaluation practices across Europe.

To address these limitations, we recommend three key improvements for the evaluation of future assemblies: (1) using recruitment strategies that ensure higher representation of PMIMG (people belonging to multiple intersecting marginalised social groups); (2) collecting and linking detailed demographic data to experience measures while ensuring appropriate consent; and (3) aligning evaluation designs around a shared core of standardised survey items that incorporate intersectionality considerations, building on those proposed in the OECD's Evaluation Guidelines for Representative Deliberative Processes. These changes would significantly enhance the field's ability to conduct robust intersectional evaluations.

Overall, this evaluation offers both substantive findings and methodological recommendations that will inform the design and evaluation of the upcoming EU-CIEMBLY pilot citizens' assemblies and potentially future citizens' assembly practices. It affirms the value of disaggregated analysis and highlights the need for structural adjustments if deliberative democratic innovations are to be both inclusive and equitable in practice.

V. Evaluation of Existing European Union Citizens' Assembly Practices

This final Section of Deliverable 3.3 provides a case study of existing assembly-like practices at the European Union level, namely the EU Citizens' Panels (hereafter 'the Panels'). It aims to identify current EU practices, as well as gaps and opportunities that arise thereof from an intersectionality point of view. In this way, the case study aims to contribute to the overall aim of the project to make recommendations for how intersectionality can advance current citizens' assembly practices including those organised by the EU institutions.¹⁴

Although they are not called 'assemblies' as such, the Panels are the closest EU-level participatory mechanism to a citizens' assembly. This is seen in their composition and procedure: they bring together randomly selected citizens from all 27 EU Member States to discuss key, upcoming policy proposals. Like a citizens' assembly, the Panels take place across a number of days (over three full weekends), and participants work together in small groups of around 12 people, and all together in plenaries. A facilitation team provides support and the goal for the group is to discuss and 'make recommendations for the European Commission to consider when defining policies and initiatives'.¹⁵ The Panels, therefore, stand in stark contrast to other EU-level participatory mechanisms, which operate differently albeit still aiming to include citizens in EU public life, such as the European Citizens' Initiative, EU Youth Dialogues, Public Consultations, the European Citizens' Engagement Platform, and petitions to the European Parliament.¹⁶

The current Panels originate from the Conference on the Future of Europe, which was the first time that European Citizens' Panels took place. The (then) European Citizens' Panels was one of the four pillars of the Conference, which also included a Multilingual Online Platform; National Citizens' Panels and events organised in the framework of the Conference; and the Conference Plenaries. The establishment of a more permanent form of Citizens' Panels was, in fact, one of the recommendations of the Conference. Specifically, the European Citizens' Panel 2 on 'European democracy/Values and rights, rule of law, security', Stream 5 on

¹⁴ Having said that, it should also be noted that it is not the purpose of the current case study to propose recommendations or modifications to the EU's practices at this stage.

¹⁵ All the information about the European Citizens' Panels, including the Information Kits, Factsheets, and other supporting material referenced in this section can be found in the European Commission's website on the European Citizens' Panels (https://citizens.ec.europa.eu/european-citizens-panels_en) as well as the websites of the individual panels: Tackling Hatred in Society Panel (https://citizens.ec.europa.eu/european-citizens-panels/tackling-hatred-society-panel_en); New European Budget Panel (https://citizens.ec.europa.eu/european-citizens-panels/european-citizens-panel-new-european-budget_en) and the Young Citizens Assembly on Pollinators (https://citizens.ec.europa.eu/young-citizens-assembly-pollinators_en) [all accessed on 29 October 2025].

¹⁶ For an overview see 'Participate, interact and vote in the European Union' available here: https://european-union.europa.eu/live-work-study/participate-interact-vote_en

‘Strengthening citizen participation’ recommended that the EU holds citizens’ assemblies (European Union, 2022, p. 140). Since then, six Panels have taken place on the policy topics of food waste, shaping virtual worlds, fostering learning mobility, improving energy efficiency, tackling hatred in society, and deciding the priorities of the new EU budget. A Panel on Intergenerational fairness and a Young Citizens’ Assembly on Pollinators are currently underway.

Against this background, an evaluation of the Panels is pertinent because, according to the recommendations of the Conference on the Future of Europe European Citizens’ Panel 2, mentioned above, the EU should be ‘[h]olding Citizens’ assemblies periodically, on the basis of legally binding EU law’. Although some experience with Panels has accumulated over the last few years, a formal codification has not happened yet, which leaves open the question of *whether* and *in what form* the Panels should be codified. This observation takes us back to a point made earlier in this project (notably, Deliverable 2.2), i.e., that the rise of more formalised, institutionalised, and systematised citizens’ assemblies across Europe and in the EU provides a unique opportunity to ensure that intersectionality informs the development of these innovations with a view to enhancing their inclusiveness.

This evaluation mainly draws on three sources of information. The first is the Commission’s Communication ‘Putting Vision Into Concrete Action’, which can be seen as the basis for the establishment of the current European Citizens’ Panels after the Conference for the Future of Europe (Commission Communication, 2024). The second source is the Commission’s ‘Corporate Guidance on Citizen Participation’ (European Commission, 2025, hereafter ‘Corporate Guidance’). This is an internal document of the Commission, which—according to its description—aims to ‘bring more consistency, visibility and corporate ownership of citizen engagement activities, as part of the Commission’s policymaking process’ (p. 7). Although the Guidance should not be considered as representing the EU Commission’s official position,¹⁷ it explains how the Commission implements citizen involvement in its own processes and is particularly valuable for us in the absence of any other relevant legal or non-legal EU act on the operation of the Panels. The European Citizens’ Panels is one of the forms of citizen involvement that the Guidance describes (pp. 32-36). In this sense, the Guidance can provide information both on the cross-cutting considerations that are considered when designing the Panels (pp. 16-24), and on the methodology of the Panels themselves (pp. 32-34).

¹⁷ See disclaimer at the beginning of the Corporate Guidance.

The third source of information used for our discussion is the body of available information for the two latest Panels, namely the ‘Tackling Hatred in Society’ Panel and the ‘New European Budget’ Panel. The former took place from April-May 2024, and the latter from March-May 2025, allowing us to paint the most accurate picture of how the Panels currently work in practice in comparison e.g., to choosing one of the first Panels, as there might have been changes in practice since then. We will see that some practices differ even between these two panels—this can be seen, for instance, in the more detailed information regarding recruitment for the ‘New European Budget’ Panel. In addition, where relevant, the discussion will also refer to the first ‘Youth Assembly’, which is taking place at the EU level while this deliverable is being written: the ‘Young Citizens Assembly on Pollinators’. This Youth Assembly matches a form of citizens’ assembly identified in the follow-up communication to the Conference on the Future of Europe, which sets out the possibility to convene Citizens’ Panels composed exclusively of young people whose deliberations could serve as a ‘youth test’ and which is of particular relevance given that age is one of the social groups being considered in the EU-CIEMBLY pilots (Corporate Guidance, p. 12). Given that this assembly is ongoing, our evaluation will refer only to the methodology around its design as this can be seen through publicly available documents.

In line with the objectives of Deliverable 3.3, this case-study evaluation of the European Citizens’ Panels attempts to identify how the existing approach of the European Commission to the design of the European Citizens’ Panels corresponds to our definitions of intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation. It should be noted here that we have not found any explicitly stated considerations of intersectionality in the publicly available information on the design of the Panels under consideration. Intersectionality is mentioned in the ‘Tackling Hatred in the EU’ Panel but as related to the topic of the discussions rather than the Panel itself (see pp. 8-9 of the relevant Information Kit). It thus appears that existing practices around the Panels have not been designed with intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation (as defined by our project) in mind. For the purposes of our evaluation, therefore, we examined both whether the Panels show efforts to embed intersectionality considerations in their design (even though this may not be explicitly stated), and whether the Panels show efforts to embed ‘intersectionality-like’ concepts, namely efforts at ‘general’ equality, inclusion, and good deliberation. In this way, the discussion follows the same rationale as the empirical research that supports Sections II and III of this deliverable.

However, by way of contrast to the discussion (in Sections II and III) of the empirical findings of Tasks 3.2 and 3.3, the case study elaborated here does not start from identifying design features alongside the categorising dimensions of input, throughput, and output choices (see

Section II) or from identifying the experiences of the Panels' participants (see Section III). Instead, it takes a step back by being grounded on 'Dimension 1: Analytical and Normative Dimension' of the EU-CIEMBLY conceptual framework. Although the discussion of the design features along 'Dimension 2: Categorising Dimension' is of course part and parcel of the framework, the purpose of this evaluation is not to delve into the design features of the Panels *per se* but instead to assess and understand the rationale behind the existing design of the Panels and the relevant opportunities and weaknesses that are presented thereof from an intersectionality point of view.

To this effect, the current case study seeks to answer the following question and sub-questions, which are related to our understanding of intersectional equality, inclusion and good deliberation respectively:

How do the European Citizens' Panels currently fare vis-à-vis the qualities of intersectional equality, intersectional inclusion, and intersectional (good) deliberation?

- Do the Panels make any effort to depart from procedural or formal conceptions of equality towards more substantive conceptions which recognise that structurally marginalised groups need more favourable treatment to participate in the Panels (intersectional equality)?
- Do the Panels challenge the idea of strict representativeness, i.e., that they need to mirror the citizenry of the polity (intersectional inclusion)?
- Has the deliberation process of the Panels been designed in ways that consider power dynamics and/or structural marginalisation to ensure equality of voice among participants by addressing structural biases (intersectional deliberation)?

Put together, the research on whether and how the Panels embody the three qualities set out above will illustrate the current state of the art regarding intersectionality in EU citizens' assembly-like practices. It will also shed light on the potential for our team to offer recommendations on how existing practices can be taken forward.

Before looking at each of the three elements in turn, it is important to frame the discussion by breaking down the stated aims of the European Citizens' Panels at the EU level. The novelty of the Panels as a form of citizens' participation in EU policy-making and decision-making, as well as their scale and the organisational effort behind their implementation, cannot be doubted. Yet, what is the ultimate purpose of the Panels? This can be discerned along two lines. The first seems to be to enhance citizens' participation in the EU policy-making process

or, in other words, to make citizens' voices heard in the decision-making process at the EU level. As stated in the Corporate Guidance, the concept of citizen participation refers to the various ways in which citizens are involved in democratic decision-making and policy-making processes, with a special focus on the efforts made by public institutions 'to enable citizens' informed and autonomous participation and to hear their perspectives in between elections' (p. 5).

The second purpose behind the Panels relates more closely to the quality of the decision-making process. Here, the Panels are seen as an addition to the consultations that take place in the context of EU decision-making processes. This second purpose is highlighted more than the first, both in the Corporate Guidance and in the Information Kits provided to the participants. The Corporate Guidance states that 'citizen engagement reinforces the traditional consultation mechanisms [and] aims to associate citizens to policymaking in the form of collaboration, *even though the responsibility for the final decision rests with the public authority*' (Corporate Guidance, 2025, p. 5). Along similar lines, the 'New European Budget' Panel Information Kit states that '[y]ou, as a European citizen, will enrich the institutional process with the intention to lead to better decisions' and similarly emphasises that the Panels precede the EU's actual decision-making processes: '[t]hose decisions will be made by the bodies that represent the 450 million European citizens: the European Commission, the European Parliament and the Council of the EU' (European Commission, 2025, p. 4). According to the Information Kit for the 'Tackling Hatred in Society' Panel, the objective of the discussions during the Panels is to 'develop recommendations that the European Commission will *take into consideration* in the preparation of its policies' (European Commission, 2023, p. 4).

From the above, we can distil a consultative role for the Panels, which adds to the other channels of consultation that are available to the EU. It is clear that the Panels are seen as one of many parts of the policy-making and decision-making process of the European Union, whereby the EU institutions will always have the first word. This view is not surprising insofar as it matches the Commission's approach towards the European Citizens' Initiative as another form of EU participatory mechanism (Karatzia, 2017). Under the current EU Treaties, where the Commission has the monopoly of legislative initiative, the Council and the European Parliament are co-legislators in the ordinary legislative process, and the European Council steers the policies and priorities of the Union, the recommendations of the Panels are highly unlikely to have a legally binding force. Of course, this does not mean that they cannot have any influence on the EU institutions' policy-making and lawmaking processes. It does mean that such an influence is highly dependent on the discretion and appetite of the EU institutions

that receive the recommendations of the Panels. This ‘disclaimer’ sets the context for the subsequent discussion on the role of the Panels within the EU institutional balance, and what this role means in terms of the design and implementation of such citizens’ assembly-like practices at the EU level.

1. Intersectional Equality and the European Citizens’ Panels

Do the Panels make any effort to depart from procedural or formal conceptions of equality towards more substantive conceptions which recognise that structurally marginalised groups need more favourable treatment to participate in the Panels (intersectional equality)?

To explore the above question, we need to ask: how is the notion of equality operationalised in the design of the European Citizens’ Panels? The Corporate Guidance states that ‘inclusiveness and representativeness’ are key principles guiding the participatory processes. Notably, equality is not on that list. Instead, it is mentioned under ‘inclusiveness and representativeness’, regarding the recruitment of participants. Equality is said to come from citizens having an equal chance to be selected to participate in the Panels, no matter their walks of life (Corporate Guidance, p. 16). As the Guidance explains: ‘[i]n the great majority of cases, citizens must be recruited randomly in a manner that is representative of both demographic and geographic diversity, from the publics of concern, even if the citizen engagement process concerns a specific community affected by or affecting the policy issue’ (p. 16).

Notably, the Guidance uses the phrase: ‘representative of diversity’, as ‘the sortition of small groups of around 100 citizens does not allow pure representativeness’ (p. 16). The Factsheet of the ‘Tackling Hatred in Society’ Panel reiterates this language by stating that ‘The citizen participants are randomly selected by phone interview, using number generation technology. The final selection is representative of diversity of the EU population based on the Eurostat (...) One out of three citizens of this Panel is 16-25 years old’. The Information Kit of the ‘New European Budget’ similarly tells the participant: ‘[y]ou will join 149 other randomly selected citizens, from all Member States and representative of EU diversity, of which one-third are younger than 29 years old, to ensure good discussions between generations’. Intersectionality is not mentioned in any of the documents that we examined, while diversity seemed to be reliant on—or even automatically result from—the diversity of the geographic location from which each participant was recruited. Representativeness itself takes a different form than the conventional standard of demographic representation, which is usually employed in deliberative mini-publics: the required standard here is a Panel that is representative of

diversity, and which oversamples from the young population of the European Union (16-25; and younger than 29 years old for each Panel, respectively).

The notions of equality and inclusion vis-à-vis the recruitment method of the Panels is discussed further below under 'Intersectional Inclusion and the European Citizens' Panels'. The Panels seem to acknowledge, even indirectly, the need to make an extra attempt to include the younger generation of Europeans by oversampling on the basis of age. Beyond this, there does not seem to be an acknowledgment of any structural or societal barriers to equality, which require structural strategies and interventions to overcome them—something we had pointed out as inherent in the definition of an intersectional approach to equality under the project's conceptual framework.¹⁸

Beyond the words of the Corporate Guidance, the 'New European Budget' Panel recognises and accommodates the need to support the participants in the process. For instance, persons providing support to participants with special needs have the possibility to attend as listeners and can join the social meetings that take place in the evenings after the Panels. There is also ad hoc support available for participants with practical issues, medical conditions, or even to participants who are having difficulties with the process. In addition, participants were given the possibility to report any illegal misconduct to an 'inclusion officer' during or in-between the Panel sessions.

More generally speaking, the Information Kit that is given to the participants at the beginning of the process is written in plain language and is user-friendly, reassuring the participants that they do not need to have expertise on the topic of the discussion to take part in the deliberations. Travel and accommodation costs are reimbursed, and a compensation fee is provided.¹⁹ The Information Kit provides supporting information regarding arrival, accommodation, departure, dress code, tourism information, and where to seek help if needed, while stating that members of the team were available to welcome participants upon arrival. The location of the Panels, i.e., the premises of the European Commission, are fully accessible for people with disabilities, and participants were asked to indicate any special needs and dietary requirements upon registering online.²⁰ The same observations hold true for the 'Young Citizens' Assembly on Pollinators', as seen from the Information Kit for the participants.

¹⁸ See Deliverable 2.2 version 2, p. 85.

¹⁹ For the 'Tackling Hatred in Society' Panel, a compensation fee of 90 euros per session and/ or travel day was provided, paid following the sessions after participation was confirmed through an attendance list.

²⁰ This information can be found in the 'Tackling Hatred in Society' Panel Information Kit. An Annex with Practical Information was also attached in the 'New European Budget' Panel, but it is not accessible online.

2. Intersectional Inclusion and the European Citizens' Panels

Do the Panels challenge the idea of strict representativeness, i.e., that the Panels need to mirror the citizenry of the polity (intersectional inclusion)?

In the context of the Panels, inclusion has a dual meaning. First, it refers to the fact that the Panels aim to include citizens in EU policy-making. As a new—for the EU—deliberative format, the Panels aim to better include citizens in 'priority and ambition setting, as well as in designing and making policies at the European level' (Commission Communication, p. 5). As a continuation of the panels that took place during the Conference on the Future of Europe, the Panels are seen as a way in which citizens are more closely included in EU policy-making. This is a rather generic view of inclusion, one that describes ambition for an increased role for ordinary citizens in the broader EU policy-making circle, rather than a view of inclusion along the lines of internal / external inclusion, which focus on who is given the opportunity to join the deliberation, and how included they feel during the deliberation.

The two factors of internal and external inclusion can be linked to the second meaning of inclusion in the Panels and can be seen in their design features and the principles guiding the choice of those features. The Commission Communication, for instance, states that the Conference European Citizens' Panels sought the views of 'the hardest to reach'. At first sight, this reference might imply considerations around the inclusion of persons belonging to marginalised groups or even to the intersections of multiple marginalised groups. In existing academic research, the term 'hard-to-reach' is used particularly in public health research to describe sub-groups of the population that may be difficult to reach or to involve in research or public health programmes (Shaghghi et al., 2011) while the term also appears in public engagement processes to signal those that are more difficult to contact and engage through traditional engagement methods.²¹

Yet, in the Communication, those that are 'the hardest to reach' are defined as 'those who rarely engage with politics or perhaps have not voted in previous European elections' (p. 5). There is no further reference to structural marginalisation or to people belonging to multiple intersecting marginalised groups. The Communication goes on to say that the more

²¹ According to the US-based public engagement consulting firm Public Participation Partners, for example, 'these groups may include people with limited English proficiency, immigrants, religious minorities, indigenous groups, senior citizens, people with disabilities, renters, new residents in a community, or those that are not a part of organized groups. Hard-to-reach groups may also include minority populations that are disproportionately affected by project impacts, and therefore hearing their perspectives is critical to minimize adverse impacts as much as possible.' Available at <https://publicparticipationpartners.com/reaching-the-hard-to-reach/> [accessed 29 October 2025].

permanent European Citizens' Panels (i.e., the current Panels) should be composed of participants that are randomly selected and who reflect Europe's diversity and demography, with one third of the participants being young people, i.e., below 29 years old. This oversampling of young people may be considered as adding to the concept of 'representative of diversity' to the extent that the recruitment method does not seek to accurately reflect the underlying EU demographics as such and might even consider young people in the definition of 'the hardest to reach'. In any case, the oversampling of young people itself challenges the idea of strict representativeness.

One way in which the Panels embed considerations around inclusion is through their design on language. Both in the Corporate Guidance and in the design of the actual Panels, language is seen as an avenue for inclusion. The Guidance mentions that 'a citizen engagement process cannot claim to be truly inclusive if citizens do not have the possibility to express themselves in their native language' (p. 23). From a design point of view, the process needs to allow the audience to follow any written documentation provided to them, as well as to express themselves in their own language (p. 23). The 'Tackling Hatred in Society' Panel indeed provided interpretation in the 24 official EU languages while the 'New European Budget' Panel welcomed the participants by noting that a team of professional interpreters will allow each of them to speak the language they are most comfortable with.

Following the Communication, the Guidelines also highlight diversity as one of the strengths of Citizens' Panels. This diversity comes from using random selection for the recruitment of participants. Random selection allows for the inclusion of people in policy-making 'who are not familiar with European issues or public affairs in general, or pertain to vulnerable communities, as anybody can be potentially selected' (Corporate Guidance, p. 6). This reference implies that there is some consideration of including citizens that are in a marginalised position and adds to the concept of inclusion the dimension of 'vulnerable communities.' It does not, however, provide a definition or explain whether any special steps are taken to ensure the inclusion of such communities. It is implied in this recruitment methodology that people who do not tend to participate in EU public life (i.e., those unfamiliar with European issues or public affairs) and those belonging to vulnerable communities, will be included because of the random selection process. There is thus no acknowledgment, at least at this level of design, of barriers to participation and how those affect the possibility of citizens to be included.

The design of the 'Tackling Hatred in Society' European Citizens' Panel follows a similar conceptualisation of 'inclusion'. The participants were randomly selected by phone interview, using number generation technology. The final selection did not aim to be representative of

the EU Member States but instead **representative of diversity of the EU population** based on the Eurostat.²² Participants were recruited along five criteria: age, gender, place of residence (rural/city), education, and socio-economic background, while 1/3 of the participants were young persons (16-25 years old). These criteria indicate a departure from the concept of strict representativeness or being a 'mini-public'. Representation was translated here into 'representation of diversity', and not representation of the polity or of the citizenry of the European Union.

However, it seems that the methodology has changed in the run-up to the most recent, 'New European Budget' Panel, which appears to have employed a more sophisticated recruitment strategy than the 'Tackling Hatred in Society' Panel. Participants in the 'New European Budget' Panel were recruited by Sortition Europe via the democratic lottery method (Sortition Foundation, 2025a). According to Sortition Europe, '[t]he Panel invited 150 citizens from all 27 EU member states selected by democratic lottery to reflect Europe's demographic diversity in terms of age, gender, geography, socio-economic background, education level, and attitude towards the EU'. A new criterion for recruitment was, therefore, added for the most recent panel: attitude towards the EU i.e., whether the individual had a positive, negative, or neutral attitude towards the EU.

The methodology for recruitment has also changed (Sortition Foundation, 2025b). The process for the democratic lottery starts by selecting locations. Through the use of population and urban-rural data from Eurostat, the Sortition Foundation selects through lottery 150 places across the EU including cities, towns, and rural areas, weighted by population and geographic diversity. Once the locations are selected, trained local recruiters from Sortition's partner network go door-to-door, inviting residents to register their interest in participating. As part of this exercise, the recruiters engage with the residents: they offer reassurance and explain that no special knowledge or expertise is needed, 'just a willingness to listen, share, and deliberate'. The process seems to explicitly acknowledge that there are barriers that often limit participation, and that the recruitment method takes steps to make participation accessible for everyone, for example by supporting communication in all European languages and offering in-person, over the phone, and digital registration options. The aim of this step is to collect a pool of around 750-1000 potential participants, meaning five times the number needed.

²² 'Tackling Hatred in Society' European Citizens' Panel Factsheet. There is no further explanation of the recruitment process but a breakdown of participants per country is provided in the factsheet.

In turn, a sample is chosen from the large pool. A representative sample of 150 participants is selected via lottery through an open-source software. The software picks a group that matches specific demographic, geographic, and attitudinal targets: gender, age, education, occupation, region, urban/rural balance, and views on the EU. A reserve list is also put together, to replace those who withdraw with others with a matching profile. According to the Sortition Foundation, the result is 'a mini-public that mirrors the broader population of the EU'.²³ The process is said to prioritise equal chance, equity, transparency, and trust.

Similarly to what was mentioned above, equality seems to be manifested here as an equal chance for every citizen to be selected. Yet equity is also mentioned in the sense that the recruiters are going the extra mile to include people who might otherwise be left out. The process is also said to build trust through face-to-face conversations at the doorstep, which help to establish people's confidence in an unfamiliar process (Sortition Foundation, 2025b). This view is close to the definition of intersectional inclusion employed by EU-CIEMBL Y, which acknowledges that formal or procedural equality has been insufficient for the meaningful participation of marginalised groups, and that there is a need to actively take measures to include people from disadvantaged social groups in deliberative processes.²⁴ It is also closer to the rationale behind intersectional inclusion than the recruitment methodology of the previous three Panels, which was explained above, and which has been criticised in the literature for predominantly including participants with pro-European views and for failing to ameliorate self-selection bias (Gjaldbæk-Sverdrup E. et al, 2023).

Having said that, the process does not specify further how 'the people who might otherwise be left out' are to be identified or whether other strategies beyond door-to-door recruitment are employed. There is no explanation, for instance, of any further consideration of the role of barriers whether structural, historical, or social, or how those lead to the marginalisation of citizens from democratic processes either at Member State level or at EU level. There is a focus, as we have seen, on including young people and those from across socio-economic backgrounds, but the role of ethnicity, gender, or age beyond youth is not acknowledged and presumably not addressed in the recruitment strategy of the Panels. Except for young people, there are no quotas of reserved seats for marginalised individuals. Although both the Commission Communication and the Corporate Guidance refer to including those unfamiliar with EU issues or public affairs (e.g., the non-voters) and vulnerable communities, there are

²³ Sortition Europe is also coordinating the two upcoming panels, namely the Panel on Intergenerational Fairness and the Youth Assembly on Pollinators, and so it can be expected that the criteria and methodology will remain the same. See: https://www.sortitionfoundation.org/ecps_2025 [accessed on 29 October 2025].

²⁴ See Deliverable 3.3 p. 89.

no definitions and no reserve quotas for such groups. Of course, steps may be taken in practice that have not been documented, and the priorities guiding the process of the Sortition Foundation are laudable. The picture of the Panels as painted through publicly available information, though, does not show an engagement with issues surrounding structural inequalities or current or historical discrimination that could be considered in designing the Panels' composition.

An evaluation of the Panels vis-à-vis intersectional inclusion would be incomplete without a reference to the extent to which marginalised groups or the interests of marginalised groups have been included in the set-up of the Panels themselves. Who has the decision-making powers to set-up the process, and to decide the experts and facilitators? Who is included in the set-up of the Panels themselves? The 'Tackling Hatred in Society' Panel provides information both on who organises the Panel, and who is a member of the Knowledge Committee, i.e., a group of experts who, according to the Information Kit, will provide the group with the knowledge needed to grasp the topic and develop recommendations. The European Commission's Directorate-General for Communication, and the Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers are both listed as the organisers of the Panel. There is no similar note in the 'New European Budget' Pilot, but the 'Young Citizens Assembly on Pollinators' includes even more information about the different teams involved: from the Commission these are the Directorates-General for Environment and Communications, the Joint Research Centre, Agriculture, and Health and Food Safety; a Methodology and Facilitation Team, a Knowledge and Information Centre that includes experts from within and outside the EU Institutions, an External Evaluation Group, a group of observers, and a logistics team. There is no further information on how the teams or the experts were selected, although previous Panels were criticised for their top-down organisation structure and the lack of a role for Civil Society Organisations in the process (Gjaldbæk-Sverdrup E. et al, 2023).

3. Intersectional Deliberation and the European Citizens' Panels

Has the deliberation process of the Panels been designed in ways that consider power dynamics and/or structural marginalisation to ensure equality of voice among participants by addressing structural biases (intersectional deliberation)?

Corresponding to the need for substantive equality as part of designing an assembly with intersectionality in mind, the deliberative aspect of such an assembly should recognise that more active interventions may be required to ensure the genuine inclusion of diverse voices in the deliberation process. In this sense, an intersectional view of deliberation recognises that

at the informational or educative phase participants are not neutral vessels waiting to be filled with knowledge. Instead, they bring their own biases to processing information both at the point of listening to others or receiving knowledge on a subject. As explained in Deliverable 2.2, this recognition means that specific design features are needed to ameliorate biases and power imbalances in the context of an assembly to ensure equitable expression in deliberation or, otherwise, an intersectionality-oriented deliberative process.²⁵

A notable characteristic of the Panels is that they involve professional facilitators. According to the Information Kit of the 'New European Budget' Panel, the role of the facilitation team is 'to ensure that each participant feels comfortable in the process. It will have an eye on the timing and progression of each session. It will help to make the group work more dynamic, to get the best out of each individual contribution and of the group. It will also provide you with a range of tools for collaborative work and collective decision-making.' Similar phrasing is used in the Information Kit of the 'Tackling Hatred in Society' Panel: '[p]anellists will be supported by a facilitation team. This team is made up of experts in supporting group work. They will help to make the group work more dynamic, to get the best out of each individual's contribution and of the group as a whole. They will also provide citizens with a range of tools for collaborative work and collective decision-making.'

In addition, a noteworthy disclaimer appears in the Information Kit of the 'Tackling Hatred in the EU' Panel. Under 'Deliberating About a Sensitive Topic', the Kit explains that it is the responsibility of the Panel's organisers to make the Panel 'a safe space that allows all panellists and invited contributors to talk freely and be heard, as long as they respect the perspectives and experiences of others'. The disclaimer recognises the importance of acknowledging and respecting the lived experiences both of the panellists and of those who have suffered and are suffering from hatred. It continues by explaining that the organisers apply the 'no harm' principle 'to reduce as much as possible the chance of psychological harm to participants attending (such as causing violence and conflict, triggering trauma or mental health issues) (p. 5)'. According to the Kit, it is the role of the professional facilitators team to meet and uphold this principle throughout the sessions. It appears that this disclaimer is directly linked to the topic of the particular panel, rather than the process as a whole, as there is no similar disclaimer in the Information Kit of the subsequent 'New European Budget' Panel.

The most elaborate insight into facilitation is given in the 'Young Citizens' Assembly on Pollinators' Information Kit where a section (Chapter 3) is devoted to the topic of 'What you

²⁵ See Deliverable 2.2 v.2 pp. 91-95.

need to know to ensure a successful deliberation'. The Section highlights the significance of diversity in the deliberation. It starts by noting that an assembly is a gathering of very diverse people, who 'come together with their own stories, perspectives, characters and communication styles' (p. 10). Diversity will help the participants 'develop impactful recommendations that speak to a broad spectrum of young European citizens and take into consideration many different needs and preferences'. High engagement and a respectful, curious attitude are said to be crucial to benefit from the diversity in the room. In the Information Kit, these are oriented towards 'the development of better solutions', which can be said to align with the rationale of the Panels to contribute to better policy-making, discussed in the Introduction to this case-study.

The 'Young Assembly on Pollinators' Information Kit provides a number of 'discussion rules and principles' for the deliberation of the Panel, which can be seen as attempting to achieve equality of voice among participants in an environment where not everyone comes from the same starting point in terms of feeling able to express themselves freely and having their views heard in democratic deliberation. Three points are particularly noteworthy here: point 1 on 'I will be present'; point 3 on 'I will make and take space'; and point 6 on 'I will not discriminate'. Under Point 1, the participants are asked to actively listen to other members of the Assembly and refrain from interrupting when others are speaking, and refrain from multi-tasking. Under point 3, participants are asked to be aware of their own positionality in the group in comparison to others. If they notice that they are talking more than others, they are to be stepped aside to give others the opportunity to contribute to the discussion. They will 'muster the courage' to speak up, even if unsure of how their ideas will be received. Finally, point 6 asks participants not to discriminate on the basis of gender, age, race, (dis)ability, sexuality, class, ethnicity, education, religion, and any other grounds. Participants are asked to recognise that all other members are as worthy as themselves of contributing to the discussion and, notably for our evaluation, 'to be aware of their own privileges'.

The above addition to the Information Kit, which does not appear in the kits of the previous Panels, is particularly welcome from an intersectional point of view. The three points reiterated here signal an awareness on behalf of the organising and the facilitating team regarding concepts of power, privilege, and positionality, all of which are central also to intersectionality as an analytical lens. They can be seen as examples of active interventions to ensure the inclusion of diverse voices during the citizens' assembly deliberations. They also operate as an addition to the role of facilitator in enabling good deliberation, insofar as the Kit also states: 'Don't worry, a group facilitator will be there to help you apply these principles and rules, and the Advisory Committee will be available in case a conflictual situation arises'.

Moving slightly away from the role of the facilitator as such, a final question arises when reviewing current Panel practices, which is about the starting point from which citizens are meant to participate in the deliberation and, specifically, the question of who they are representing during the discussions. Is it the participants themselves and their experiences, their countries, or their communities? On the one hand, the supporting documentation examined here, the concept of ‘representing the EU’s diversity’, and the oversampling of young people who make up 1/3 of the panel, all point out to a notion of representation that does not strictly adhere to the idea of demographic (or descriptive) representation that has traditionally been considered one of the core characteristics of deliberative mini-publics (Curato et. al, 2021). On the other hand, the EU Commission’s website on the European Citizens’ Panels, refers both to ‘representation of the EU’s diversity’ based on geography (urban/rural), gender, age,²⁶ education, socioeconomic background, and image of the EU (i.e., attitude towards the EU)²⁷ but also mentions that the random selection process ‘ensures that recruitment is representative’. It then continues to mention that participants from each Member State are recruited in proportion to its population, while ensuring proportional representation across different groups. A minimum of two participants per Member State are recruited ‘to guarantee that even the smallest countries are represented’. Although it is not possible to reflect all socio-demographic categories within a single country’s delegation, this is mitigated by the diversity of categories across the panels as a whole.

The language of the Panels, therefore, seems to be a mix of seeking ‘representation of the EU’s diversity’ and ‘representation of the EU’s Member States’. In fact, after the above explanation of the link between participants and Member States, the website returns to the language of representing diversity, by saying that ‘recruiting panels that represent diversity is essential to facilitate vibrant discussions and ensure that those discussions reflect a wide variety of perspectives and opinions’. It may be that both types of representation are sought. It may also be that recruitment from across all EU Member States is a way to ensure the diversity sought for the achievement of vibrant discussions. It does raise the question: if the ultimate aim is diversity of participants, is recruiting on the basis of demographics per Member State the best or the only way to achieve it?

²⁶ The definition of age seems to be inconsistent across the panels: as seen in the discussion of this session, while some define ‘young people’ as 16-25, others define it as ‘under 26’ and the website talks about ‘16-29 years old’.

²⁷ The recruitment targets are based on Eurobarometer, the annual European Union public opinion survey, and Eurostat, the EU’s statistics office. Occupation is also taken into account.

Conclusion

This deliverable constitutes the EU-CIEMBLY project's move from engagement with theoretical conceptions of intersectionality towards more practical applications of that concept, namely through the application of the project's framework for intersectionality in citizens' assemblies. The more immediate objective of the deliverable was to evaluate current citizens' assembly practices through an intersectional analytical lens as already elaborated in the first dimension of the framework developed in Deliverable 2.2. To facilitate the examination of existing citizens' assembly practices, this deliverable also applies the second dimension of this framework, namely the categorising dimension which employs the concepts of input, throughput, and output to categorise design choices.

This deliverable thereby constituted a mixed methods assessment of the strengths and shortcomings of existing practices within citizens' assemblies from an intersectionality perspective based on the project's analytical framework, assessing the space for increased consideration and integration of intersectionality issues into existing citizens' assembly practices. It will be recalled from the project's framework that the qualities of intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation are the three criteria against which current practices were reviewed and evaluated. In so doing, the present Deliverable 3.3 represents an application of the first function of intersectionality as an analytical lens, namely to diagnose or identify existing gaps within citizens' assembly practices from an intersectionality perspective.

This objective was achieved in three ways: (1) through the evaluation by means of qualitative interviews of the experiences of citizens' assembly organisers and facilitators; (2) through understanding by way of secondary data analysis, the experience of participants in citizens' assemblies; and (3) through an evaluation of existing EU practices in the design of citizens' assemblies. The latter consisted of an intersectional assessment of existing EU-level practices in the form of the EU Citizens' Panels with the aim of identifying deficiencies and opportunities – from an intersectionality point of view – within these existing EU practices. The rationale behind this choice was guided by one of the project's objectives of making recommendations for an intersectionality-oriented EU Citizens' Assembly.

The overarching findings of the analysis above reinforce our initial assessment derived from Work Package 2 that intersectionality has not yet been systematically or consistently integrated or operationalised into the practice of citizens' assemblies, even though there is evidence of welcome (though we would argue incomplete from an intersectionality perspective) efforts at enhancing the more general qualities of

equality, inclusion, and good deliberation in the design and delivery of citizens' assemblies, across all levels. We do not claim, however, to have provided a conclusive overview of the wealth of practices that exists in citizens' assembly organisation, conduct, and evaluation given that our evaluation was necessarily selective. Our intention was rather to attempt to capture the role of intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation (which constitute the key analytical dimension of our framework) within existing practices. Finally, it should be noted that the eventual application of our framework to our own efforts will necessarily differ from those experiences in that we will be explicitly designing our pilots with the qualities of intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation in mind.

Having conducted this assessment of existing practices and having tested the application of the project's analytical framework, the next deliverable (Deliverable 3.4) will address the second function of intersectionality, namely to address the problems or gaps identified at the diagnostic stage. To achieve this objective, Deliverable 3.4 will draw on the operationalising dimension of the project framework to design the three pilots that are to be tested by the project team in Work Package 4 at a local, national, and transnational level.

The particular added value of Deliverable 3.3 to the EU-CIEMBLY project, beyond the wider insights that it provides into existing citizens' assembly practices, is that it has offered a testbed for the application (albeit ex-post) of the project's intersectional analytical framework within the context of real-life examples from across the three levels of interest to us (local, national, and transnational), drawing on interviews with those who were involved, surveys of participant experiences, and a case study assessment of existing EU practices. This allowed us to move from thinking about intersectionality (in citizens' assemblies) in the abstract or from a theoretical perspective, towards an approach that is practically and empirically grounded and which serves as a bridge between the project's theorisation (Work Package 2) and operationalisation (Work Package 3) of intersectionality in citizens' assemblies as we lay the ground for the pilot assemblies to be tested in the next stages of the project (Work Package 4).

Summary of Recommendations

The following is a summary of the recommendations from the above analysis of the findings of our empirical research. The design choices have been classified using the categorisation dimension of our framework for intersectionality in citizens' assemblies, which groups choices according to the stages of input, throughput, and output while recognising that there may be

overlap between categories and that particular choices may be relevant to and fall within more than one category. The below also sets out the recommendations relating to the evaluation dimension of the project's framework. These recommendations will be considered at the stage of designing the project's citizens' assembly pilots and may also be of wider relevance to those conducting or evaluating citizens' assemblies in practice.

DESIGN CHOICES FOR THE INPUT STAGE

- **I1. Use broad framing questions for agenda setting and involve less-heard groups early in the design process.**
- **I2. Explore non-sortition based approaches to ensure higher numbers of PMIMG participants.**
- **I3. Limit the recruitment selection criteria for feasibility; keep registration forms for recruitment simple and engaging.**
- **I4. Supplement lottery recruitment with targeted outreach and relationship-building.**
- **I5. Treat intersectionality as a continuous practice, not a recruitment checkbox. Provide multilingual materials, logistical support (childcare, transport, digital training) and adaptive check-ins.**
- **I6. Design knowledge-sharing strategies that are accessible, interactive, and tailored to diverse learning needs.**

DESIGN CHOICES FOR THE THROUGHPUT STAGE

- **T1. Adopt inclusive design features: collaborative grounds rules, creative engagement tools and relational trust-building.**
- **T2. Embrace a human-centred approach, treating each participant as an individual and adapting support accordingly. Incorporate open-ended**

questions during recruitment and facilitation to understand individual needs and build trust.

- T3. Use iterative, dialogic approaches to consensus that surface minority voices and positions and avoid tokenism.
- T4. Engage politicians carefully: maintain citizen autonomy, ensure balanced representation of perspectives, and prioritise relationship-building.
- T5. Broaden participation through parallel processes and storytelling, while mitigating risks of burden on participants from marginalised groups.

DESIGN CHOICES FOR THE OUTPUT STAGE

- O1. Design outputs and engagement strategies that amplify marginalised voices and challenge power imbalances. Include participant-authored elements (e.g., letters, forewords) alongside recommendations to convey overarching goals, lived experiences, and minority positions.
- O2. Foster a culture of learning among organisers and participants, emphasising reflection and responsiveness. Ensure evaluation frameworks capture experiences of PMIMG and identify barriers to exerting influence.

RECOMMENDATIONS REGARDING THE EVALUATION STAGE

- E1. Design evaluation processes with intersectional analysis requirements in mind.
- E2. Utilise standardised participant experience evaluation questions across citizens' assembly practice.
- E3. Gather early and appropriate consent for personal data collection and management.

- E4. Consider a wider variety of socio-demographic variables that reflect forms of power or marginalisation.

- E5. Diversify evaluation approaches beyond traditional post-event surveys.

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Annex to EU-CIEMBLY Deliverable 3.3

Annex - Results on Individual Social Groups - Secondary Analysis Results Tables

I. SCOTLAND'S CLIMATE ASSEMBLY

Methodological details

To evaluate Scotland's Climate Assembly, participants were asked to respond to a survey with standardised questions after each assembly weekend, as well as completing a pre- and post- Assembly survey so organisers could track any attitudinal changes or the development of personal outcomes. For the questions that were asked after each assembly weekend, our analysis uses an average (median) of participants' responses to identify overarching patterns. Results generated using this approach (creating a new 'median' variable), are marked in the footnotes. Full details of the data transformation that took place for this dataset can be found in the supplementary material (Scotland CA codebook, available on Zenodo).

For the questions that were just asked pre- and post-assembly, the pre-assembly value was subtracted from the post-assembly value to create a 'change level' variable, to explore if there were any patterns in the levels of change in attitudes across different demographic groups.

While data related to participants' geography, ethnicity, disability status, and income was collected at the sampling stage in order for the final participant group to reflect the demographic diversity of Scotland, the demographic data included in the evaluation dataset was limited to **gender, age group, and ethnicity**. As such, our analysis is limited to exploring different experiences based on these factors alone.

While 102 participants completed the Assembly process, only 85 responded to the evaluation, and not all participants responded to every survey question. The table below sets out the difference in response rates across demographic categories.

Table 1. Evaluation response rates by demographic category

Demographic variable	Category	Target N (informed by census data)	Confirmed N (participated in assembly)	Maximum N from evaluation dataset	Response rate
Gender	Men	49.7	49	30	61.2%
	Women	52.3	54	38	70.4%
	In another way	2	2	2	100%
Age	16-18	5.8	5	0	0%
	19-24	10.4	10	5	50%
	25-29	6.4	6	4	66.7%
	30-44	23.3	25	22	88%
	45-64	34.5	34	26	76.5%
	65+	24	25	16	64%
Ethnicity	BAME	8	8	4	50%
	White	96	97	71	73.2%

These results point to notable underrepresentation of Black and minority ethnic participants and participants aged between 16-25 in Scotland's Climate Assembly evaluation data, with both categories only achieving a 50% response rate. This not only represents a limitation to the generalisability of our findings, but highlights an important consideration for the practice of survey-based CA evaluations in terms of groups least likely to respond.

While differences in how different demographic groups responded to questions were identifiable, the small sample sizes in several groups - e.g. n=2 people identifying their gender 'in another way', only n=5 or fewer people aged 19-24, 25-29, or 75+, and only n=4 non-White participants - mean that the strength of conclusions about these groups on the basis of this data is limited.

Results

RQ: How were different elements of Citizens' Assemblies (CAs) perceived by participants from different social groups?

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: The purpose of the weekend was well explained

- Women were more likely to *strongly agree* than men or those identifying in another way.
- Older and younger participants were more likely to report lower levels of *strong agreement* compared to middle-aged groups.
- By ethnicity, all groups *strongly agreed* or *tended to agree* in broadly similarly proportions.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Agreement level: The purpose of the weekend was well explained	Strongly disagree	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	2.9%	0%	1.3%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	2	1	3
	% within Gender		0%	5.9%	2.4%	3.9%
	Tend to agree	Count	2	15	14	31
	% within Gender		100%	44.1%	33.3%	39.7%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	16	27	43
	% within Gender		0%	47%	64.3%	55.1%
	Total	Count	2	34	42	78
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were notable differences in gender regarding perceptions of how well the weekend's purpose was explained. **The majority of all genders *strongly agreed* or *tended to agree*, but women were more likely to *strongly agree* than men or**

those identifying in another way. For instance, 64.3% (n=27) of women *strongly agreed*, compared to 47.1% (n=16) of men.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: The purpose of the weekend was well explained	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	1	2	0	0	3
	% within Age group		0%	0%	4.6%	8%	0%	0%	4.1%
	Tend to agree	Count	3	1	9	8	5	3	29
	% within Age group		50%	25%	40.9%	32%	41.7%	75%	39.7%
	Strongly agree	Count	3	3	12	15	7	1	41
	% within Age group		50%	75%	54.6%	60%	58.3%	25%	56.2%
	Total	Count	6	4	22	25	12	4	73
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were clear differences in how well participants of different ages felt the purpose of the weekend was explained. **Older and younger participants were more likely to report lower levels of *strong agreement* compared to middle-aged groups.** Among those aged 75+, only 25% (n=1) selected *strongly agree*, while 75% (n=3) chose *tend to agree*. A similar pattern appeared among 19–24-year-olds, with 50% (n=3) selecting *strongly agree* and 50% (n=3) *tend to agree*. In contrast, *strongly agree* was chosen by 60% (n=15) of those aged 45–64 and 58.3% (n=7) of those aged 65–74, suggesting that older middle-aged groups felt more clearly informed.

Ethnicity		
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			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	Total
Agreement level: The purpose of the weekend was well explained	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	0	3	3
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	4.7%	4.1%
	Tend to agree	Count	2	0	2	25	29
	% within Ethnicity		100%	0%	40%	39%	39.73%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	2	3	36	41
	% within Ethnicity		0%	100%	60%	56.3%	56.2%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	64	73
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Ethnic differences were subtle concerning whether the purpose of the weekend was well explained. **However, all groups *strongly agreed* or *tended to agree* broadly similarly, suggesting consistent positive communication effectiveness across ethnicities.** Most notably, 100% (n=2) of Black Scottish/British/African/African Caribbean respondents *strongly agreed*, compared to 56.3% (n=36) of White Scottish/British respondents.

SQ: How satisfied or dissatisfied are you with the following aspects: The balance between task-based discussions and open discussions in my small groups across the Assembly weekends as a whole

- Overall, minimal differences were identifiable between demographic groups for this participant experience variable.
- The strongest differences in experience of the balance between discussion types can be seen in terms of gender. Women were more likely to say they were *satisfied* or *very satisfied* with the balance (n=34, 94.5%) compared to men (n=23, 85.1%).

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Satisfaction level: The balance between task-based discussions and open discussions in my small groups across the Assembly weekends as a whole	Very dissatisfied	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	3.7%	0%	1.5%
	Dissatisfied	Count	0	1	1	2
	% within Gender		0%	3.7%	2.8%	3.1%
	Neutral	Count	0	2	1	3
	% within Gender		0%	7.4%	2.8%	4.6%
	Satisfied	Count	2	10	11	23
	% within Gender		100%	37%	30.6%	35.4%
	Very satisfied	Count	0	13	23	36
	% within Gender		0%	48.1%	63.9%	55.4%
	Total	Count	2	27	36	65
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were notable differences between gender groups in how they rated their satisfaction with the balance between task-based and open discussions during the Assembly weekends. A majority of women (63.9%, n=23) reported being *very satisfied*, compared to 48.1% of men (n=13) and 0% of those identifying "in another way." Conversely, only 30.6% of women (n=11) were *satisfied*, while a higher proportion of men (37%, n=10) chose this option, and 100% of respondents identifying in another way (n=2) selected it. **Notably, only men reported being very**

dissatisfied (3.7%, n=1) or dissatisfied (3.7%, n=1), suggesting some gendered divergence in experience or expectations around discussion formats.

			Age group					Total	
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74		75+
Satisfaction level: The balance between task-based discussions and open discussions in my small groups across the Assembly weekends as a whole	Very dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	% within Age Group		0%	0%	0%	4.5%	0%	0%	1.5%
	Dissatisfied	Count	0	0	1	1	0	0	2
	% within Age Group		0%	0%	5.3%	4.5%	0%	0%	3.1%
	Neutral	Count	0	0	1	1	0	1	3
	% within Age Group		0%	0%	5.3%	4.5%	0%	25%	4.6%
	Satisfied	Count	3	3	7	9	6	1	29
	% within Age Group		60%	75%	36.8%	40.9%	54.5%	25%	44.6%
	Very satisfied	Count	2	1	10	10	5	2	30
	% within Age Group		40%	25%	52.6%	45.5%	45.5%	50%	46.2%
	Total	Count	5	4	19	22	11	4	65
% within Age Group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	

Looking at results for this question in terms of age groups, general satisfaction is high, with 90.8% overall reporting being either “Satisfied” (44.6%) or “Very satisfied” (46.2%). **Overall, younger and older age groups tended to report the highest satisfaction, with mid-age groups showing slightly more mixed experiences.** The only groups showing any dissatisfaction were ages 30-64, and even there it was minimal (one or two individuals per group).

	Ethnicity				Total
	Asian, Asian Scottish/British	Black, Black Scottish/British, African or	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other	White Scottish/British	

			African Caribbean				
Satisfaction level: The balance between task-based discussions and open discussions in my small groups across the Assembly weekends as a whole	Very dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	1.8%	1.5%
	Dissatisfied	Count	0	1	0	1	2
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	0%	1.8%	3.1%
	Neutral	Count	0	0	0	2	2
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	3.6%	3.1%
	Satisfied	Count	2	0	3	23	28
	% within Ethnicity		100%	0%	60%	41.1%	43.1%
	Very satisfied	Count	0	1	2	29	32
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	40%	51.8%	49.2%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	56	65
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Most ethnic groups expressed strong satisfaction, though small sample sizes in non-White groups limit firm conclusions. **Overall, satisfaction was high across most groups, but the Black ethnic group showed a markedly lower positivity rate, albeit based on a very small sample.** The mixed responses among Black participants—50% (n=1) *dissatisfied*, 50% (n=1) *very satisfied*—suggest a divergent experience within that small group, which may warrant further exploration.

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: I liked the way we developed the overarching statements in my small group

- Overall, all demographic groups expressed majority *agreement* with this statement.
- The most notable difference can be seen in terms of gender, with women more likely to express *agreement* (n=30, 83.3%), than men (n=19, 70.3%).
- In terms of age, the youngest (19-24) and oldest (75+) groups showed more *disagreement* or uncertainty.

			Gender			
			In another way	Man	Woman	Total
Agreement level: I liked the way we developed the overarching statements in my small group	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	1	1
	% within Gender		0%	0%	2.8%	1.5%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	3	1	4
	% within Gender		0%	11.1%	2.8%	6.2%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	5	4	9
	% within Gender		0%	18.5%	11.1%	13.8%
	Tend to agree	Count	2	10	12	24
	% within Gender		100%	37%	33.3%	36.9%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	9	18	27
	% within Gender		0%	33.3%	50%	41.5%
	Total	Count	2	27	36	65
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were notable differences between genders in how they felt about the way overarching statements were developed in their small group. **Overall, women were more likely than men to express *strong agreement*, while men showed a broader spread across response categories.** Among women, 83% (n=30) gave a positive response—50% (n=18) *strongly agreed* and 33% (n=12) *tended to agree*. Among men, 68% (n=19) responded positively, split between 32% (n=9) *strongly agree* and 36% (n=10) *tend to agree*. However, men were also more likely to respond neutrally (18%, n=5) or negatively—11% (n=3) *tended to disagree*. All respondents identifying their gender in another way (n=2) gave positive responses, both selecting *tend to agree*. These results suggest that while most participants responded positively, women were more strongly positive overall.

			Age group						
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	Total
Agreement level: I	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1

liked the way we developed the overarching statements in my small group	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	4.5%	0%	0%	1.5%
	Tend to disagree	Count	1	0	0	0	1	1	3
	% within Age group		20%	0%	0%	0%	8.3%	25%	4.6%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	3	3	2	1	9
	% within Age group		0%	0%	16.7%	13.6%	16.7%	25%	13.8%
	Tend to agree	Count	3	1	7	9	4	0	24
	% within Age group		60%	25%	38.9%	40.9%	33.3%	0%	36.9%
	Strongly agree	Count	1	3	8	9	5	1	27
	% within Age group		20%	75%	44.4%	40.9%	41.7%	25%	41.5%
	Total	Count	5	4	18	22	12	4	65
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were notable differences across age groups in agreement with liking the way overarching statements were developed in small groups. **Overall, participants aged 30-64 were the most consistently positive, while the youngest (19-24) and oldest (75+) groups showed more *disagreement* or uncertainty.** Among 30-44 year-olds, 83.3% (n=15) gave a positive response (38.9% *tend to agree*, 44.4% *strongly agree*), and among 45-64 year-olds, 81.8% (n=18) were similarly positive. Participants aged 25-29 were the most positive overall, with 100% *agreement*—75% (n=3) *strongly agree* and 25% (n=1) *tend to agree*. However, responses among the 19-24 group were more mixed: while 80% (n=4) were positive, one person (20%) *tended to disagree*. The 75+ group had the lowest positive response rate at 25% (n=1), with the remaining 75% (n=3) split between neutral or negative views. These findings suggest a dip in agreement among the youngest and oldest age groups.

	Ethnicity				Total
	Asian, Asian Scottish/British	Black, Black Scottish/British,	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other	White Scottish/British	

				African or African Caribbean			
Agreement level: I liked the way we developed the overarching statements in my small group	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	1.8%	1.2%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	4	4
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	7%	4.9%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	1	7	8
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	20%	12.3%	9.8%
	Tend to agree	Count	2	1	2	19	24
	% within Ethnicity		100%	50%	40%	33.3%	29.3%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	1	2	25	28
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	40%	43.9%	34.1%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	57	66
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were **few notable differences** between ethnic groups in their agreement with how the overarching statements were developed. These results reflect broadly positive sentiment overall, with the only *tend to disagree* or *strongly disagree* responses coming from the White Scottish/British group (n=5, 8.8%).

SQ: How helpful did you find the following activities for your learning about climate change and how to tackle it across the Assembly as a whole?: Small group discussions

- Overall, all participants reported small group discussions as at least *a little* helpful.

- Women and participants identifying in another way were more likely than men to rate small group discussions as *very helpful*, with men showing a wider spread of responses.
- Younger and middle-aged groups (19-44) reported higher levels of helpfulness of small group discussions, while older participants were slightly more mixed in their views.
- Ratings of small group discussions only being *a little* or somewhat helpful came exclusively from White Scottish/British respondents, while ethnic minority participants rated them unanimously as at least *quite helpful*.

			Gender			
			In another way	Man	Woman	Total
Helpfulness level: Small group discussions	Not at all helpful	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	2	3	5
	% within Gender		0%	6.9%	7.9%	7.2%
	Somewhat	Count	0	5	0	5
	% within Gender		0%	17.2%	0%	7.2%
	Quite helpful	Count	0	7	11	18
	% within Gender		0%	24.1%	28.9%	26.1%
	Very helpful	Count	2	15	24	41
	% within Gender		100%	51.7%	63.2%	59.4%
	Total	Count	2	29	38	69
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were notable differences between genders in how helpful they found the small group discussions. **Overall, women and those identifying in another way were more likely than men to rate small group discussions as very helpful, with men showing a wider spread of responses.** Most women (63.2%, n=24) and all participants identifying "in another way" (n=2) rated the discussions as *very helpful*, compared to 51.7% of men (n=15). Concomitantly, men also had more responses in mid-range categories: 24.1% (n=7) rated small group discussions as *quite helpful*

and 17.2% (n=5) said *somewhat helpful*, while 6.9% (n=2) rated them only *a little helpful*. In contrast, 28.9% of women (n=11) said small group discussions were *quite helpful*, and 7.9% (n=3) rated them as *a little helpful*.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Helpfulness level: Small group discussions	Not at all helpful	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	0	1	2	2	0	5
	% within Age group		0%	0%	4.5%	8.3%	16.7%	0%	7.2%
	Somewhat	Count	0	0	1	1	1	2	5
	% within Age group		0%	0%	4.5%	4.2%	8.3%	50%	7.2%
	Quite helpful	Count	0	0	4	5	7	2	18
	% within Age group		0%	0%	18.2%	20.8%	58.3%	50%	26.1%
	Very helpful	Count	4	3	16	16	2	0	41
	% within Age group		100%	100%	72.7%	66.7%	16.7%	0%	59.4%
	Total	Count	4	3	22	24	12	4	69
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were subtle differences across age groups in how helpful participants found small group discussions. **Overall, younger and middle-aged groups (19-24, 25-29, 30-44) reported higher levels of helpfulness of small group discussions, while older participants were slightly more mixed in their views.** All participants aged 19-24 (n=4) and 25-29 (n=3) rated discussions as *very helpful*. Among the 30-44 and 45-64 age groups, large majorities also responded positively: 72.7% (n=16) and 66.7% (n=16), respectively, rated them as *very helpful*. In contrast, only 16.7% (n=2) of 65-74 year-olds and none of the 75+ group rated discussions *very helpful*; instead, 50% of each group said *quite helpful*, and others selected *somewhat* or *a little*. Older participants showed a broader range of responses, suggesting a less consistently positive experience.

Ethnicity		
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			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/ Gypsy/ Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	Total
Helpfulness level: Small group discussions	Not at all helpful	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	0	0	5	5
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	8.3%	7.2%
	Somewhat	Count	0	0	0	5	5
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	8.3%	7.2%
	Quite helpful	Count	1	0	1	16	18
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	20%	26.7%	26.1%
	Very helpful	Count	1	2	4	34	41
	% within Ethnicity		50%	100%	80%	56.7%	59.4%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	60	69
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some notable differences across ethnic groups in how helpful participants found the small group discussions. **Ratings of small group discussions only being a *little* or *somewhat* helpful came exclusively from White Scottish/British respondents** (n=10, 16.6%), while the remaining 56.7% (n=34) rated the discussions *very helpful* and 26.7% (n=16) *quite helpful*. All five responses from White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other participants were positive. Black/Black Scottish/British, African or African Caribbean participants (n=2) were unanimously positive, with both saying small group discussions were *very helpful* (100%). Asian/Asian Scottish/British participants (n=2) were split evenly between *very* and *quite helpful*.

SQ: How helpful did you find the following activities for your learning about climate change and how to tackle it across the Assembly as a whole?: Presentations by speakers

- Women were more likely than men to rate the presentations as very helpful.
- Younger (under 30) and older (65+) participants were more likely to find presentations very helpful, while middle-aged groups showed more variation.
- White Scottish/British participants gave more mixed responses compared to ethnic minority participants, who overwhelmingly rated the presentations as *quite* or *very helpful*.

			Gender			
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Helpfulness level: Presentations by speakers	Not at all helpful	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	3.4%	0%	1.4%
	A little	Count	0	4	1	5
	% within Gender		0%	13.8%	2.6%	7.2%
	Somewhat	Count	0	2	0	2
	% within Gender		0%	6.9%	0%	2.9%
	Quite helpful	Count	1	7	6	14
	% within Gender		50%	24.1%	15.8%	20.3%
	Very helpful	Count	1	15	31	47
	% within Gender		50%	51.7%	81.6%	68.1%
	Total	Count	2	29	38	69
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were notable differences between genders in how helpful they found the presentations by speakers. Overall, **women were much more likely than men to rate the presentations as very helpful** - 81.6% (n=31) selected *very helpful*, compared to 51.7% of men (n=15). Men were more likely to respond with lower ratings: 13.8% (n=4) rated the presentations as *a little* helpful, 6.9% (n=2) *somewhat* helpful, and 3.4% (n=1) *not at all helpful*. Among those identifying in another way

(n=2), responses were split evenly between *quite* and *very helpful*. These results show a gendered difference in perceived speaker effectiveness.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Helpfulness level: Presentations by speakers	Not at all helpful	Count	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	4.5%	0%	0%	0%	1.4%
	A little	Count	0	0	3	1	1	0	5
	% within Age group		0%	0%	13.6%	4.2%	8.3%	0%	7.2%
	Somewhat	Count	0	0	2	0	0	0	2
	% within Age group		0%	0%	9.1%	0%	0%	0%	2.9%
	Quite helpful	Count	0	0	5	7	2	0	14
	% within Age group		0%	0%	22.7%	29.2%	16.7%	0%	20.3%
	Very helpful	Count	4	3	11	16	9	4	47
	% within Age group		100%	100%	50%	66.7%	75%	100%	68.1%
	Total	Count	4	3	22	24	12	4	69
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some differences in perceived helpfulness of presentations across age groups. **Overall, younger (under 30) and older (65+) participants were more likely to find presentations *very helpful*, while middle-aged groups showed more variation.** The 19-24 and 25-29 groups were unanimous in rating presentations *very helpful* (100%, n=4 and n=3, respectively). Among 65-74 year-olds, 75% (n=9) said *very helpful*, as did 100% (n=4) of the 75+ group. In contrast, only 50% of 30-44 year-olds (n=11) and 66.7% of 45-64 year-olds (n=16) gave this top rating. Other responses in these groups included quite helpful and somewhat helpful, showing a slightly less enthusiastic response.

		Ethnicity				Total
		Asian, Asian Scottish	Black, Black Scottish/	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	

			h/British	British, African or African Caribbean			
Helpfulness level: Presentations by speakers	Not at all helpful	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	1.7%	1.4%
	A little	Count	0	0	0	5	5
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	8.3%	7.2%
	Somewhat	Count	0	0	0	2	2
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	3.3%	2.9%
	Quite helpful	Count	1	0	2	11	14
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	40%	18.3%	20.3%
	Very helpful	Count	1	2	3	41	47
	% within Ethnicity		50%	100%	60%	68.3%	68.1%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	60	69
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some notable differences across ethnic groups in how helpful they found the speaker presentations. **Overall, White Scottish/British participants gave more mixed responses compared to ethnic minority participants, who overwhelmingly rated the presentations as quite or very helpful.** Among White Scottish/British respondents, 13.3% ($n=8$) selected *not at all helpful*, *a little helpful*, or only *somewhat helpful*. In contrast, of the 5 minority ethnic participants combined: *Asian* respondents were split (50% *very helpful*, 50% *quite helpful*), *Black* respondents ($n=2$) both selected *very helpful*, and the remaining groups gave a mix of *quite* and *very helpful*.

SQ: How helpful did you find the following activities for your learning about climate change and how to tackle it across the Assembly as a whole?: Time with speakers in breakout rooms

- There was a broad sense that time with speakers in breakout rooms was helpful for assembly participants across different demographics.
- The two youngest age groups (19-24, 25-29) unanimously agreed the sessions were at least quite helpful, while participants aged 65-74 group were the most likely to rate time with speakers in breakout rooms as very helpful.
- Women were more likely than men to rate the time as very helpful, while men gave more mixed responses.
- Participants from ethnic minority groups gave exclusively high ratings, while White Scottish/British participants offered a broader mix of views.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Helpfulness level: Time with speakers in breakout rooms	Not at all helpful	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	5	2	7
	% within Gender		0%	17.2%	5.3%	10.1%
	Somewhat	Count	0	4	1	5
	% within Gender		0%	13.8%	2.6%	7.2%
	Quite helpful	Count	2	8	12	22
	% within Gender		100%	27.6%	31.6%	31.9%
	Very helpful	Count	0	12	23	35
	% within Gender		0%	41.4%	60.5%	50.7%
	Total	Count	2	29	38	69
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were notable differences in how helpful different genders found the breakout time with speakers. **Overall, women were more likely than men to rate the time as very helpful, while men gave more mixed responses.** Among women, 60.5% (n=23) rated the sessions *very helpful*, while only 41.4% of men (n=12) said the same. Participants identifying "in another way" (n=2) all selected *quite helpful*, indicating positive but moderate approval.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Helpfulness level: Time with speakers in breakout rooms	Not at all helpful	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	0	4	1	1	1	7
	% within Age group		0%	0%	18.2%	4.2%	8.3%	25%	10.1%
	Somewhat	Count	0	0	2	3	0	0	5
	% within Age group		0%	0%	9.1%	12.5%	0%	0%	7.2%
	Quite helpful	Count	2	2	5	10	2	1	22
	% within Age group		50%	66.7%	22.7%	41.7%	16.7%	25%	31.9%
	Very helpful	Count	2	1	11	10	9	2	35
	% within Age group		50%	33.3%	50%	41.7%	75%	50%	50.7%
	Total	Count	4	3	22	24	12	4	69
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some notable differences across age groups in how participants rated breakout sessions with speakers. **The two youngest age groups (19-24, 25-29) unanimously agreed the sessions were at least *quite helpful*, while participants aged 65-74 group were the most likely to rate time with speakers in breakout rooms as *very helpful*, with 75% (n=9) of those aged 65-74 selecting this response.** Only 10.1% participants across all ages (n=7) found the sessions only a *little helpful*, and none selected *not at all helpful*, indicating generally positive views of breakout time across the sample.

	Ethnicity				Total
	Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African	White Irish/Poli sh/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	

			Caribbean				
Helpfulness level: Time with speakers in breakout rooms	Not at all helpful	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	0	0	7	7
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	11.7%	10.1%
	Somewhat	Count	0	0	0	5	5
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	8.3%	7.2%
	Quite helpful	Count	0	0	1	21	22
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	20%	35%	31.9%
	Very helpful	Count	2	2	4	27	35
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	80%	45%	50.7%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	60	69
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were notable differences** in how helpful participants from different ethnic groups found the time with speakers in breakout rooms. **Overall, participants from ethnic minority groups gave exclusively high ratings, while White Scottish/British participants offered a broader mix of views.** All respondents from *Asian, Black, and White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other* backgrounds ($n=9$) rated the time as either *quite* or *very helpful*, with the proportion indicating breakouts were *very helpful* ranging from 80-100%. In contrast, among *White Scottish/British* participants ($n=60$), only 45% ($n=27$) selected *very helpful*. This suggests a consistently strong appreciation from ethnic minorities, although based on smaller sample sizes.

SQ: How helpful did you find the following activities for your learning about climate change and how to tackle it across the Assembly as a whole?: Transcripts of speakers' presentations

- Women and those identifying in another way were much more likely than men to rate transcripts as very helpful, while men showed a more even split across categories.
- Participants under 30 and those 75+ were most likely to rate transcripts as very helpful, while 45-64 year-olds gave the least enthusiastic responses.
- Participants from minority ethnic backgrounds were more likely to rate transcripts as very helpful, while White Scottish/British participants were more evenly split across options.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Helpfulness level: Transcripts of speakers' presentations	Not at all helpful	Count	0	2	0	2
	% within Gender		0%	7.1%	0%	3.1%
	A little	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Somewhat	Count	0	9	5	14
	% within Gender		0%	32.1%	14.7%	21.9%
	Quite helpful	Count	0	9	11	20
	% within Gender		0%	32.1%	32.4%	31.2%
	Very helpful	Count	2	8	18	28
	% within Gender		100%	28.6%	52.9%	43.8%
	Total	Count	2	28	34	64
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were notable differences** between genders in how helpful participants found the transcripts of speaker presentations. **Overall, women and participants identifying in another way were much more likely than men to rate transcripts as very helpful, while men showed a more even split across categories.** Among women, 52.9% ($n=18$) found them *very helpful*, and 23.7% ($n=9$) *quite helpful*, while 14.7% ($n=5$) found them only *somewhat helpful*. For men, only 28.6% ($n=8$) selected

very helpful, 32.1%, (n=9) rated them as somewhat helpful, and 7.1% (n=2) rated them not at all helpful. All respondents identifying "in another way" (n=2) said very helpful.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Helpfulness level: Transcripts of speakers' presentations	Not at all helpful	Count	1	0	1	0	0	0	2
	% within Age group		25%	0%	4.8%	0%	0%	0%	3.1%
	A little	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Somewhat	Count	0	0	5	6	2	1	14
	% within Age group		0%	0%	23.8%	26.1%	18.2%	25%	21.9%
	Quite helpful	Count	0	0	6	9	5	0	20
	% within Age group		0%	0%	28.6%	39.1%	45.5%	0%	31.2%
	Very helpful	Count	3	1	9	8	4	3	28
	% within Age group		75%	100%	42.9%	34.8%	36.4%	75%	43.8%
	Total	Count	4	1	21	23	11	4	64
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were notable differences in how age groups rated the usefulness of transcripts. Overall, participants under 30 and those 75+ were most likely to rate transcripts as very helpful, while the mid-age groups gave the least enthusiastic responses. The one respondent aged 25-29 and all those aged 75+ (n=4) rated transcripts as very helpful, along with 75% of 19-24s (n=3). Among those aged 30-44, said very helpful, compared to just) of 45-64s. Less than half of those aged 30-44 and 45-64 said very helpful (42.9%, n=9; 34.8%, n=8 respectively), were more likely to select somewhat or quite helpful, with one not at all helpful response in both the 30-44 and 45-64 groups.

Ethnicity		
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			Asian, Asian Scottis h/Britis h	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbea n	White Irish/Poli sh/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	Total
Helpfulne ss level: Transcript s of speakers' presentati ons	Not at all helpful	Count	0	0	0	2	2
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	3.6%	3.1%
	A little	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Somewhat	Count	1	0	0	13	14
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	0%	23.2%	21.9%
	Quite helpful	Count	0	1	0	19	20
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	0%	33.9%	31.2%
	Very helpful	Count	1	1	4	22	28
	% within Ethnicity		50%	50%	100%	39.3%	43.8%
	Total	Count	2	2	4	56	64
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were notable differences** across ethnic groups in their assessment of transcript helpfulness. **Overall, participants from minority ethnic backgrounds were more likely to rate transcripts as very helpful, while White Scottish/British participants were more evenly split across options.** All participants from *Asian, Black, and White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other* backgrounds rated transcripts positively, with the proportions indicating *very helpful* ranging from 80-100% in each group. Among *White Scottish/British* participants, 58.3% (n=35) said *very helpful*, 28.3% (n=17) *quite helpful*, and the rest gave lower scores—two (3.3%) rated them *not at all helpful*. This indicates stronger perceived usefulness of transcripts among minority ethnic participants.

SQ: How helpful did you find the following activities for your learning about climate change and how to tackle it across the Assembly as a whole?: Written summaries of speakers' presentations

- Women and those identifying in another way were more likely to give the highest rating, while men had a more varied response.
- There were only minor differences across age groups in how participants rated written summaries.
- In terms of ethnicity, minority ethnic participants were more likely to rate summaries as very helpful, while White Scottish/British participants expressed more moderate views.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Helpfulness level: Written summaries of speakers' presentations	Not at all helpful	Count	0	2	0	2
	% within Gender		0%	6.9%	0%	2.9%
	A little	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Somewhat	Count	0	5	2	7
	% within Gender		0%	17.2%	5.3%	10.1%
	Quite helpful	Count	0	8	9	17
	% within Gender		0%	27.6%	23.7%	24.6%
	Very helpful	Count	2	14	27	43
	% within Gender		100%	48.3%	71.1%	62.3%
	Total	Count	2	29	38	69
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were notable differences** between genders in how helpful they found the written summaries. **Overall, women and those identifying in another way were more likely to give the highest rating, while men had a more varied response.** Among women, 71.1% (n=27) rated the summaries *very helpful*, compared to 48.3% (n=14) of men. Men also had a higher rate of mid-range responses—27.6% (n=8) said *quite helpful* and 17.2% (n=5) *somewhat*. Only men rated summaries *not at all*

helpful (n=2, or 6.9%). Both respondents identifying "in another way" (n=2) said *very helpful*.

			Age group					Total	
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74		75+
Helpfulness level: Written summaries of speakers' presentations	Not at all helpful	Count	0	0	2	0	0	0	2
	% within Age group		0%	0%	9.1%	0%	0%	0%	2.9%
	A little	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Somewhat	Count	0	0	0	5	2	0	7
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	20.8%	16.7%	0%	10.1%
	Quite helpful	Count	0	1	4	8	3	1	17
	% within Age group		0%	33.3%	18.2%	33.3%	25%	25%	24.6%
	Very helpful	Count	4	2	16	11	7	3	43
	% within Age group		100%	66.7%	72.7%	45.8%	58.3%	75%	62.3%
	Total	Count	4	3	22	24	12	4	69
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were few notable differences** across age groups in how participants rated written summaries. A majority of all age groups rated written summaries as *very helpful*, with the next highest proportions in all age groups selecting *quite helpful*. The only *not at all helpful* responses came from the 30-44 age group (n=2, 9.1%), while the only *somewhat helpful* responses came exclusively from the 45-64 and 65-74 age range.

	Ethnicity				Total
	Asian, Asian Scottish /British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	

			African Caribbean				
Helpfulness level: Written summaries of speakers' presentations	Not at all helpful	Count	0	0	0	2	2
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	3.3%	2.9%
	A little	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Somewhat	Count	0	0	1	6	7
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	20%	10%	10.1%
	Quite helpful	Count	0	0	0	17	17
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	28.3%	24.6%
	Very helpful	Count	2	2	4	35	43
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	80%	58.3%	62.3%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	60	69
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were notable differences** across ethnic groups in how helpful participants found the written summaries. **Overall, minority ethnic participants were more likely to rate summaries as very helpful, while White Scottish/British participants expressed more moderate views.** Every participant from *Asian, Black, and White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other* groups selected either *very* or *quite helpful*, with the proportion in each group giving the top rating ranging from 80-100%. Among *White Scottish/British* participants (n=60), 58.3% (n=35) rated them *very helpful*, 28.3% (n=17) *quite helpful*, and 10% (n=6) gave lower ratings (*somewhat* or *not at all helpful*). The findings suggest a slightly stronger appreciation of written summaries among minority groups.

SQ: How helpful did you find the following activities for your learning about climate change and how to tackle it across the Assembly as a whole?: Visual graphics of evidence

- Women and participants identifying in another way were much more likely than men to rate the graphics as very helpful

- Overall, the youngest and oldest age groups were more likely to find visual graphics helpful
- Participants from minority ethnic backgrounds rated the graphics more positively than White Scottish/British respondents

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Helpfulness level: Visual graphics of evidence	Not at all helpful	Count	0	2	0	2
	% within Gender		0%	6.9%	0%	2.9%
	A little	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Somewhat	Count	0	5	2	7
	% within Gender		0%	17.2%	5.3%	10.1%
	Quite helpful	Count	0	8	9	17
	% within Gender		0%	27.6%	23.7%	24.6%
	Very helpful	Count	2	14	27	43
	% within Gender		100%	48.3%	71.1%	62.3%
	Total	Count	2	29	38	69
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were notable differences** between genders in how helpful they found visual graphics of evidence. **Overall, women and participants identifying in another way were much more likely than men to rate the graphics as very helpful, while men showed a broader spread of responses.** Among women, 71.1% (n=27) said the graphics were *very helpful*, compared to 48.3% of men (n=14). Additionally, 27.6% (n=8) of men rated the graphics as *somewhat helpful*, and 17.2% (n=5) rated them as *a little helpful*. Both participants identifying "in another way" (n=2) rated the graphics as *very helpful*, suggesting very strong approval overall.

			Age group					Total	
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74		75+
Helpfulness level:	Not at all helpful	Count	0	0	2	0	0	0	2

Visual graphics of evidence	% within Age group		0%	0%	9.1%	0%	0%	0%	2.9%
	A little	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Somewhat	Count	0	0	0	5	2	0	7
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	20.8%	16.7%	0%	10.1%
	Quite helpful	Count	0	1	4	8	3	1	17
	% within Age group		0%	33.3%	18.2%	33.3%	25%	25%	24.6%
	Very helpful	Count	4	2	16	11	7	3	43
	% within Age group		100%	66.7%	72.7%	45.8%	58.3%	75%	62.3%
	Total	Count	4	3	22	24	12	4	69
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Visual graphics were seen as *very helpful* by the majority of all age groups except those in the 45-64 bracket (45.8%, n=11). **Overall, the youngest and oldest age groups were more likely to find visual graphics helpful**, with 100% of those under 30 and 75+ exclusively rating visual graphics as *quite* or *very helpful*. There was more variation amongst those aged 30-44, 45-64, and 65-74.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/ Polish/ Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	
Helpfulness level: Visual graphics of evidence	Not at all helpful	Count	0	0	0	2	2
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	3.3%	2.9%
	A little	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Somewhat	Count	0	0	1	6	7

% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	20%	10%	10.1%
Quite helpful	Count	0	0	0	17	17
% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	28.3%	24.6%
Very helpful	Count	2	2	4	35	43
% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	80%	58.3%	62.3%
Total	Count	2	2	5	60	69
% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were clear differences** across ethnic groups in perceptions of the helpfulness of visual graphics. **Overall, participants from minority ethnic backgrounds rated the graphics more positively than White Scottish/British respondents.** Every non-White participant gave a *very helpful* rating (100% across both groups, n=4 total). Among *White Scottish/British* participants, only 58.3% (n=35) gave the top rating, while 28.3% (n=17) said *quite helpful*, and 13.3% (n=8) gave lower responses including *somewhat* or *not at all helpful*. While all groups expressed overall approval, the responses suggest stronger enthusiasm among participants from ethnic minorities.

SQ: How helpful did you find the following activities for your learning about climate change and how to tackle it across the Assembly as a whole?: Live Q&A with experts

- Women were more likely to rate these sessions as *very helpful*, while men had a wider spread of views.
- Participants aged 30-44 and 65-74 were the most likely to rate them as very helpful, while younger and older groups gave more mixed responses.
- Minority ethnic participants gave consistently positive ratings, while White Scottish/British participants showed more variation.

			Gender			
			In another way	Man	Woman	Total
Helpfulness level: Live	Not at all helpful	Count	0	1	0	1

Q&A with experts	% within Gender		0%	3.4%	0%	1.5%
	A little	Count	0	5	0	5
	% within Gender		0%	17.2%	0%	7.6%
	Somewhat	Count	0	4	1	5
	% within Gender		0%	13.8%	2.9%	7.6%
	Quite helpful	Count	2	6	10	18
	% within Gender		100%	20.7%	28.6%	27.3%
	Very helpful	Count	0	13	24	37
	% within Gender		0%	44.8%	68.6%	56.1%
	Total	Count	2	29	35	66
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were notable differences** between genders in how they rated live Q&A sessions with experts. **Overall, women were more likely to rate these sessions as very helpful, while men had a wider spread of views.** Among women, 68.6% ($n=24$) said *very helpful*, compared to 44.8% ($n=13$) of men. Additionally, 20.7% of men ($n=6$) said *quite helpful*, while 31% ($n=9$) selected mid-to-low ratings (*somewhat, a little, or not at all helpful*). In contrast, women had fewer lower ratings—only one selected *somewhat*, and none chose *a little* or *not at all helpful*. Both respondents identifying "in another way" ($n=2$) said *quite helpful*, showing moderate but positive sentiment.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Helpfulness level: Live Q&A with experts	Not at all helpful	Count	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	% within Age group		25%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	1.5%
	A little	Count	0	0	2	2	1	0	5
	% within Age group		0%	0%	10%	8.7%	8.3%	0%	7.6%
	Somewhat	Count	0	1	0	2	1	1	5
	% within Age group		0%	33.3%	0%	8.7%	8.3%	25%	7.6%
	Quite helpful	Count	3	1	4	7	2	1	18

% within Age group		75%	33.3%	20%	30.4%	16.7%	25%	27.3%
Very helpful	Count	0	1	14	12	8	2	37
% within Age group		0%	33.3%	70%	52.2%	66.7%	50%	56.1%
Total	Count	4	3	20	23	12	4	66
% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were notable differences** in how helpful different age groups found the Q&A sessions. **Overall, participants aged 30-44 and 65-74 were the most likely to rate them as very helpful, while younger and older groups gave more mixed responses.** Among 30-44 year-olds, 70% (n=14) selected *very helpful*, alongside 66.7% (n=8) of 65-74s. In contrast, only 52.2% (n=12) of 45-64 year-olds, 50% of 75+ (n=2), 33.3% of 25-29s (n=1) gave this top rating.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/British	Black, Black Scottish/British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other	White Scottish/British	
Helpfulness level: Live Q&A with experts	Not at all helpful	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	1.8%	1.5%
	A little	Count	0	0	0	5	5
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	8.8%	7.6%
	Somewhat	Count	0	0	1	4	5
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	20%	7%	7.6%
	Quite helpful	Count	2	0	1	15	18
	% within Ethnicity		100%	0%	20%	26.3%	27.3%
	Very helpful	Count	0	2	3	32	37

	% within Ethnicity		0%	100%	60%	56.1%	56.1%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	57	66
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were notable differences** between ethnic groups in their views on the helpfulness of live Q&A sessions. **Overall, minority ethnic participants gave consistently positive ratings, while White Scottish/British participants showed more variation.** Every respondent from Asian, Black, and White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other backgrounds (n=9) selected either *very helpful* or *quite helpful*. For example, 100% of Black respondents (n=2) said *very helpful*, while 100% of Asian respondents (n=2) said *quite helpful*. Among White Scottish/British respondents (n=57), 56.1% (n=32) gave the top rating, 26.3% (n=15) said *quite helpful*, and the remainder selected lower options, including one *not at all helpful*. This pattern suggests broader appreciation across all groups, with stronger consistency among minority ethnic respondents.

RQ: How inclusive was the CA in terms of representation?

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: The Assembly is diverse enough to ensure a broad range of perspectives are considered¹

- There were no major differences between genders, ages or ethnicities in perceptions of whether the assembly was diverse enough to ensure a broad range of perspectives.

			Gender			
			In another way	Man	Woman	Total
Agreement level: The Assembly is diverse enough to ensure a broad range of perspectives are	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	2	1	3
	% within Gender		0%	5.9%	2.4%	3.8%
	Neither agree	Count	0	2	3	5

¹ Median variable used, averaging participants' responses across the Assembly weekends

considered	nor disagree					
	% within Gender		0%	5.9%	7.1%	6.4%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	17	17	35
	% within Gender		50%	50%	40.5%	44.9%
	Strongly agree	Count	1	13	21	35
	% within Gender		50%	38.2%	50%	44.9%
	Total	Count	2	34	42	78
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were no major differences** between genders in perceptions of whether the assembly was diverse enough to ensure a broad range of perspectives. **Overall, responses were highly positive across all genders.** Exactly half of respondents in each group selected *strongly agree* (50% of those identifying "in another way", 38.2% of men, and 50% of women), and 44.9% of the total sample *tended to agree*. Neutral and negative responses were low across all groups, with just 5.9% of men (n=3) and 2.4% of women (n=1) *tending to disagree*. This indicates broad confidence in the assembly's diversity across gender lines.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: The Assembly is diverse enough to ensure a broad range of perspectives are considered	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	1	1	1	0	3
	% within Age group		0%	0%	4.5%	4%	8.3%	0%	4.1%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	2	0	2	0	4
	% within Age group		0%	0%	9.1%	0%	16.7%	0%	5.5%
	Tend to agree	Count	3	3	8	10	4	3	31
	% within Age group		50%	75%	36.4%	40%	33.3%	75%	42.5%
Strongly agree	Count	3	1	11	14	5	1	35	

% within Age group		50%	25%	50%	56%	41.7%	25%	47.9%
Total	Count	6	4	22	25	12	4	73
% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were some differences** across age groups regarding perceptions of assembly diversity, but no strong patterns were identifiable. Participants aged 30-64 were slightly more likely to *strongly agree*, while younger and older groups leaned more toward general *agreement*. *Strong agreement* peaked among 45-64s (56%, n=14) and 30-44s (50%, n=11), compared to just 25% (n=1) of 25-29s and 25% (n=1) of 75+. Conversely, 75% of both 25-29s and 75+ participants chose *tend to agree*. Neutral and negative views were rare, with only 3 participants across all age groups (4.1%) choosing *tend to disagree*.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/British	Black, Black Scottish/British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other	White Scottish/British	
Agreement level: The Assembly is diverse enough to ensure a broad range of perspectives are considered	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	3	3
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	4.7%	4.1%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	2	2	4
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	40%	3.1%	5.5%
	Tend to agree	Count	2	0	2	27	31
	% within Ethnicity		100%	0%	40%	42.2%	42.5%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	2	1	32	35

% within Ethnicity		0%	100%	20%	50%	47.9%
Total	Count	2	2	5	64	73
% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were some differences** between ethnic groups in how diverse they perceived the assembly to be, **but no strong patterns were identifiable**. Half of White Scottish/British participants (n=32) selected *strongly agree*, compared to just 20% (n=1) of the White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other group. Among this latter group, 40% (n=2) said *neither agree nor disagree*, and the remaining 60% were evenly split between *tend to agree* and *strongly agree*. Asian participants leaned toward *tend to agree* (100%, n=2), while Black participants (n=2) exclusively said *strongly agree*. Negative responses were rare and only appeared among White Scottish/British participants.

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the Assembly as a whole, and about your experience as a whole?: The information I have received during the Assembly weekends has been fair and balanced between different viewpoints²

- Women and people identifying in another way were more likely than men to *strongly agree* that the information was fair and balanced, while men showed more mixed responses.
- There were some differences across age groups in perceptions of information balance, but no strong patterns overall.
- Participants from ethnic minorities tended to be more positive than White Scottish/British participants, who expressed more critical views.

			Gender			
			In another way	Man	Woman	Total
Agreement level: The information I have received	Strongly disagree	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	2.9%	0%	1.3%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	5	1	6

² Median variable used, averaging participants' responses across the Assembly weekends

during the Assembly weekend has been fair and balanced between different viewpoints	% within Gender		0%	14.7%	2.4%	7.7%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	4	5	9
	% within Gender		0%	11.8%	11.9%	11.5%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	17	23	41
	% within Gender		50%	50%	54.8%	52.6%
	Strongly agree	Count	1	7	13	21
	% within Gender		50%	20.6%	31%	26.9%
	Total	Count	2	34	42	78
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were notable differences** between genders in how they rated the fairness and balance of information during the assembly weekend. **Overall, women were more likely than men to express *strong agreement*, while men showed more mixed responses.** Among women, 31% ($n=13$) selected *strongly agree*, compared to 20.6% ($n=7$) of men. Men were also more likely to express negative or neutral views—14.7% ($n=5$) *tended to disagree* and 11.8% ($n=4$) were neutral. In contrast, only 2.4% ($n=1$) of women *tended to disagree*. All participants identifying "in another way" ($n=2$) responded positively.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: The information I have received during the Assembly weekend has been fair and balanced between different viewpoints	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	4.5%	0%	0%	0%	1.4%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	2	3	1	0	6
	% within Age group		0%	0%	9.1%	12%	8.3%	0%	8.2%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	2	2	3	1	8
	% within Age group		0%	0%	9.1%	8%	25%	25%	11%
	Tend to agree	Count	3	3	12	12	6	2	38

% within Age group		50%	75%	54.5%	48%	50%	50%	52.1%
Strongly agree	Count	3	1	5	8	2	1	20
% within Age group		50%	25%	22.7%	32%	16.7%	25%	27.4%
Total	Count	6	4	22	25	12	4	73
% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were some differences** across age groups in perceptions of information balance, but **no strong patterns overall**. Participants aged 30-44 were most positive, while 45-64 year-olds were more critical. Among 30-44 year-olds, 54.5% ($n=12$) said *tend to agree* and 22.7% ($n=5$) *strongly agree*. In contrast, the 45-64 group had the highest share of *disagreement*—12% ($n=3$) *tended to disagree* and 4% ($n=1$) *strongly disagreed*. *Agreement* levels were consistent but slightly lower among 65-74 and 75+ age groups. Younger age groups (under 30) were largely positive, with 75% selecting *tend to agree* or *strongly agree*.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	
Agreement level: The information I have received during the Assembly weekend has been fair and balanced between different viewpoints	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	1.6%	1.4%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	6	6
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	9.4%	8.2%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	2	6	8
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	40%	9.4%	11%

s	Tend to agree	Count	2	1	2	33	38
	% within Ethnicity		100%	50%	40%	51.6%	52.1%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	1	1	18	20
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	20%	28.1%	27.4%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	64	73
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were notable differences** between ethnic groups in how fair and balanced they found the assembly's information. **Overall, participants from ethnic minorities tended to be more positive than White Scottish/British participants, who expressed more critical views.** 100% of *Asian* and *Black* participants selected either *tend to agree* or *strongly agree*, and *White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other* participants were also highly positive, with 40% *tending to agree* and 20% *strongly agree*. In contrast, *White Scottish/British* respondents were more divided: while 28.1% (n=18) *strongly agreed*, 9.4% (n=6) *tended to disagree* and another 9.4% (n=6) were neutral. Only 1.6% (n=1) said *strongly disagree*, and this was also from the *White Scottish/British* group.

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the Assembly as a whole, and about your experience as a whole?: Overall, I am happy with the choice of speakers

- Women and those identifying in another way were more likely to positively rate their satisfaction with the choice of speakers, while men showed a broader spread of views, including all negative responses.
- There were clear differences across age groups in satisfaction with the assembly's speakers. Younger participants (under 30) and those aged 75+ expressed the highest approval, while the 30-64 age range included more mixed responses.
- Minority ethnic participants gave uniformly positive responses, while *White Scottish/British* participants showed a wider range, including the only negative ratings.

	Gender			Total
	In another	Man	Woman	

			way			
Agreement level: Overall, I am happy with the choice of speakers	Strongly disagree	Count	0	2	0	2
	% within Gender		0%	6.9%	0%	3%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	4	1	5
	% within Gender		0%	13.8%	2.8%	7.5%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	3	2	5
	% within Gender		0%	10.3%	5.6%	7.5%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	8	16	25
	% within Gender		50%	27.6%	44.4%	37.3%
	Strongly agree	Count	1	12	17	30
	% within Gender		50%	41.4%	47.2%	44.8%
	Total	Count	2	29	36	67
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were notable differences** between gender groups in how satisfied participants were with the choice of speakers. **Overall, women and those identifying in another way were more likely to respond positively, while men showed a broader spread of views, including all negative responses.** Half of those identifying *in another way* and 47.2% of women selected *strongly agree*, compared to 41.4% of men. Meanwhile, all *strongly disagree* and *tend to disagree* responses came from men, with 20.7% expressing some level of dissatisfaction or neutrality.

			Age group						
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	Total
Agreement level: I am happy with the choice of speakers that presented information	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	2	0	0	0	2
	% within Age group		0%	0%	9.5%	0%	0%	0%	3%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	3	2	0	5
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	13%	16.7%	0%	7.5%
	Neither	Count	0	0	3	0	0	2	5

on this weekend	agree nor disagree								
	% within Age group		0%	0%	14.3%	0%	0%	50%	7.5%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	3	5	10	5	1	25
	% within Age group		25%	100%	23.8%	43.5%	41.7%	25%	37.3%
	Strongly agree	Count	3	0	11	10	5	1	30
	% within Age group		75%	0%	52.4%	43.5%	41.7%	25%	44.8%
	Total	Count	4	3	21	23	12	4	67
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were clear differences** across age groups in satisfaction with the weekend's speaker selection. **Overall, younger participants (under 30) and those aged 75+ expressed the highest approval, while the 30-44 and 45-64 age ranges included more mixed responses.** Among 19-24s, 75% (n=3) said *strongly agree*, and 100% of 25-29s (n=3) *agreed* at some level. For the 30-44 and 45-64 age groups, positive sentiment was still high - over 85% gave a positive rating - but included the only *strongly disagree* (n=2) and *tend to disagree* responses (n=5).

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	
Agreement level: I am happy with the choice of speakers that presented information	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	2	2
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	3.4%	3%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	5	5
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	8.6%	7.5%

n this weekend	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	0	5	5
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	8.6%	7.5%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	0	4	20	25
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	80%	34.5%	37.3%
	Strongly agree	Count	1	2	1	26	30
	% within Ethnicity		50%	100%	20%	44.8%	44.8%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	58	67
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were some differences** across ethnic groups in satisfaction with the choice of speakers. **Overall, minority ethnic participants gave uniformly positive responses, while White Scottish/British participants showed a wider range, including the only negative ratings.** Every respondent from *Asian, Black, and White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other* groups ($n=9$) gave positive responses, with 50-100% choosing *strongly agree*. Among *White Scottish/British* participants ($n=58$), 44.8% ($n=26$) said *strongly agree*, but they also included all *strongly disagree* ($n=2$), *tend to disagree* ($n=5$), and *neutral* ($n=5$) responses.

SQ: *How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: One or more of the people in my small group tended to dominate the discussions³*

- Women were slightly more likely than men to agree that someone dominated, but also more likely to disagree, while men were more likely to be neutral.
- In terms of age, middle-aged groups (30-64) were more likely to disagree or be neutral, while younger and older groups reported higher levels of dominance.
- There were some differences across ethnic groups in perceptions of dominance in small group discussions, but no clear pattern emerged to make an overall conclusion.

	Gender	
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³ Median variable used, averaging participants' responses across the Assembly weekends

			In another way	Man	Woman	Total
Agreement level: One or more of the people in my small group tended to dominate the discussions	Strongly disagree	Count	0	2	6	8
	% within Gender		0%	5.9%	14.3%	10.3%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	8	11	19
	% within Gender		0%	23.5%	26.2%	24.4%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	15	11	27
	% within Gender		50%	44.1%	26.2%	34.6%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	9	12	22
	% within Gender		50%	26.5%	28.6%	28.2%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	2	2
	% within Gender		0%	0%	4.8%	2.6%
	Total	Count	2	34	42	78
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were notable differences** between genders in whether they felt someone dominated the small group discussions. **Overall, women were slightly more likely to agree that someone dominated, but also more likely to disagree, while men were more likely to be neutral.** Among women, 40.5% (n=17) *disagreed*, compared to 29.4% of men (n=10). 33.4% of women (n=14) *agreed* that someone dominated, compared to 26.5% of men (n=9). Men were more likely (44.1%, n=15) to *neither agree nor disagree*—significantly more than the 26.2% of women (n=11) who selected the same. Those identifying "in another way" (n=2) split between *neither agree nor disagree* and *tend to agree*.

			Age group						
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	Total
Agreement level: One or more of the people in my small group	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	1	3	3	1	8
	% within Age group		0%	0%	4.5%	12%	25%	25%	11%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	8	8	2	1	19

tended to dominate the discussions	% within Age group		0%	0%	36.4%	32%	16.7%	25%	26%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	3	1	6	7	5	2	24
	% within Age group		50%	25%	27.3%	28%	41.7%	50%	32.9%
	Tend to agree	Count	3	3	6	7	2	0	21
	% within Age group		50%	75%	27.3%	28%	16.7%	0%	28.8%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	4.5%	0%	0%	0%	1.4%
	Total	Count	6	4	22	25	12	4	73
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were some notable differences** across age groups in whether participants felt one person dominated small group discussions. **Overall, middle-aged groups (30-64) were more likely to disagree or be neutral, while younger and older groups reported higher levels of dominance.** Among 30-44 and 45-64 year-olds, the majority either *tended to disagree* (36.4%, n=8 and 32%, n=8 respectively) or *neither agreed nor disagreed* (27.3%, n=6 and 28%, n=7). In contrast, among 65-74s, 25% (n=3) *strongly disagreed*, and 41.7% (n=5) *tended to agree*. Similarly, 50% of those aged 75+ (n=2) were *neither agreed nor disagreed*. Younger respondents (19-29) leaned toward *agreement* or *neutrality*, with none expressing *strong disagreement* or *strong agreement*.

	Ethnicity				Total
	Asian, Asian Scottish/British	Black, Black Scottish/British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other	White Scottish/British	

Agreement level: One or more of the people in my small group tended to dominate the discussions	Strongly disagree	Count	0	1	0	7	8
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	0%	10.9%	11%
	Tend to disagree	Count	1	0	2	16	19
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	40%	25%	26%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	0	1	22	24
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	20%	34.4%	32.9%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	1	1	19	21
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	20%	29.7%	28.8%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	1	0	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	20%	0%	1.4%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	64	73
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were some differences** across ethnic groups in perceptions of dominance in small group discussions, but no clear pattern emerged to make an overall conclusion. **Overall, White Scottish/British participants were more likely to express disagreement or neutrality, suggesting they experienced less perceived dominance.** Among this group, 70% either *disagreed* or were *neutral*, with only 29.7% ($n=19$) saying they *tended to agree* and none selecting *strongly agree*. In contrast, responses from minority ethnic groups were more mixed, but due to small sample sizes, no clear trend emerged.

RQ: How inclusive was the CA process, in terms of its design and organisation?

SQ: Can you let us know your views about the arrangements leading up to and during this weekend?: The support and assistance provided by the organisers at Involve⁴

- Overall satisfaction was very high across all gender groups, though women and those identifying in another way slightly more likely to be *very satisfied*.

⁴ Median variable used, averaging participants' responses across the Assembly weekends

- There were no strong differences between age groups or ethnicities in satisfaction with the support from the organisers at Involve.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Satisfaction level: The support and assistance provided by the organisers at Involve	Very dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Neutral	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	2.9%	0%	1.3%
	Satisfied	Count	0	11	10	21
	% within Gender		0%	32.4%	23.8%	26.9%
	Very satisfied	Count	2	22	32	56
	% within Gender		100%	64.7%	76.2%	71.8%
	Total	Count	2	34	42	78
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were no notable differences** between genders in satisfaction with support from the organisers at Involve. **Overall satisfaction was very high across all gender groups, with over 64% of each group reporting they were very satisfied.** Women (76.2%, n=32) and those identifying in another way (100%, n=2) were slightly more likely than men (64.7%, n=22) to report being *very satisfied*.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Satisfaction level: The support and assistance provided by the organiser	Very dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Neutral	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1

s at Involves as a whole	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	4%	0%	0%	1.4%
	Satisfied	Count	0	0	7	6	4	2	19
	% within Age group		0%	0%	31.8%	24%	33.3%	50%	26%
	Very satisfied	Count	6	4	15	18	8	2	53
	% within Age group		100%	100%	68.2%	72%	66.7%	50%	72.6%
	Total	Count	6	4	22	25	12	4	73
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were no major differences** across age groups in how participants rated the support from Involve. **High satisfaction was reported across all ages, with at least half in each group rating the support as very satisfactory.** *Very satisfied* responses ranged from 50% (75+) to 100% (under 30), indicating widespread approval.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/B ritish	Black, Black Scottish/B ritish, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polis h/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/B ritish	
Satisfac ion level: The support and assistance provided by the organisers at Involve as a whole	Very dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Neutral	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	1.6%	1.4%
	Satisfied	Count	1	0	1	17	19
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	20%	26.6%	26%
	Very satisfied	Count	1	2	4	46	53
	% within Ethnicity		50%	100%	80%	71.9%	72.6%

	Total	Count	2	2	5	64	73
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were no meaningful differences** between ethnic groups in satisfaction with the support from Involve. The majority across all ethnicities—71.9% of *White Scottish/British* and 100% of *Black* and *Asian* respondents—selected *very satisfied*. **Satisfaction levels were uniformly high, with every respondent across all groups reporting either *satisfied* or *very satisfied***, except 20% (n=1) of *White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other* respondents.

SQ: Can you let us know your views about the arrangements leading up to and during this weekend?: The communications about the arrangements, in the lead-up to the weekend⁵

- While the vast majority of participants were positive about the communications about weekend arrangements, women were more likely to be *very satisfied* than men, while men were slightly more likely to be *satisfied* than women.
- While all age groups showed strong satisfaction, the 30-44 and 25-29 age groups were the most likely to select *very satisfied*.
- There were no significant differences in satisfaction across ethnic groups regarding communications in the lead-up to the weekend.

			Gender			
			In another way	Man	Woman	Total
Satisfaction level: The communications about the arrangements, in the lead-up to the weekend	Very dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Neutral	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	2.9%	0%	1.3%
	Satisfied	Count	1	13	9	23

⁵ Median variable used, averaging participants' responses across the Assembly weekends

	% within Gender		50%	38.2%	21.4%	29.5%
	Very satisfied	Count	1	20	33	54
	% within Gender		50%	58.8%	78.6%	69.2%
	Total	Count	2	34	42	78
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were modest differences** in satisfaction with pre-weekend communications. **Overall, women were more likely to be very satisfied, while men were slightly more likely to be satisfied rather than very satisfied.** Among women, 78.6% (n=33) said *very satisfied*, compared to 58.8% (n=20) of men and 50% (n=1) of those identifying in another way.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Satisfaction level: The communications about the arrangements, in the lead-up to the weekend	Very dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Neutral	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	4%	0%	0%	1.4%
	Satisfied	Count	2	1	5	7	4	2	21
	% within Age group		33.3%	25%	22.7%	28%	33.3%	50%	28.8%
	Very satisfied	Count	4	3	17	17	8	2	51
	% within Age group		66.7%	75%	77.3%	68%	66.7%	50%	69.9%
	Total	Count	6	4	22	25	12	4	73
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were no notable differences** across age groups in satisfaction with communications before the weekend. **All age groups showed strong satisfaction, with the proportion in each group selecting *very satisfied* ranging from**

50-77.3%. The highest proportions came from the 30-44 group (77.3%, n=17) and the 25-29 group (75%, n=3).

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/B ritish, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polis h/Gypsy Traveller/O ther	White Scottish/B ritish	
Satisfaction level: The communications about the arrangements, in the lead-up to the weekend	Very dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Neutral	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	1.6%	1.4%
	Satisfied	Count	1	0	2	18	21
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	40%	28.1%	28.8%
	Very satisfied	Count	1	2	3	45	51
	% within Ethnicity		50%	100%	60%	70.3%	69.9%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	64	73
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were no significant differences** in satisfaction across ethnic groups regarding communications in the lead-up to the weekend. **All groups reported high levels of satisfaction, with 60-100% choosing very satisfied.** Only one *White Scottish/British* respondent selected *neutral*; no one reported dissatisfaction.

SQ: Can you let us know your views about the arrangements leading up to and during this weekend?: Organisation of the weekend⁶

- Women were more likely to say they were *very satisfied*, while men gave a more mixed response.
- While the vast majority of all age groups were at least satisfied, the oldest (75+) and youngest (19-24) participants were the least likely to say they were very satisfied.
- There were no notable differences across ethnic groups in satisfaction with how the weekend was organised.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Satisfaction level: Organisation of the weekend	Very dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Dissatisfied	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	2.9%	0%	1.3%
	Neutral	Count	0	3	1	4
	% within Gender		0%	8.8%	2.4%	5.1%
	Satisfied	Count	2	16	13	31
	% within Gender		100%	47.1%	31%	39.7%
	Very satisfied	Count	0	14	28	42
	% within Gender		0%	41.2%	66.7%	53.8%
	Total	Count	2	34	42	78
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were notable differences** between genders in satisfaction with the overall organisation of the weekend. **Women were more likely to say they were very satisfied, while men gave a more mixed response.** 66.7% (n=28) of women chose *very satisfied*, compared to 41.2% (n=14) of men; 8.8% (n=3) of men also selected *neutral*, and one (2.9%, n=1) said *dissatisfied*.

⁶ Median variable used, averaging participants' responses across the Assembly weekends

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Satisfaction level: Organisation of the weekend	Very dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	4%	0%	0%	1.4%
	Neutral	Count	0	0	1	1	1	1	4
	% within Age group		0%	0%	4.5%	4%	8.3%	25%	5.5%
	Satisfied	Count	4	1	9	8	4	2	28
	% within Age group		66.7%	25%	40.9%	32%	33.3%	50%	38.4%
	Very satisfied	Count	2	3	12	15	7	1	40
	% within Age group		33.3%	75%	54.5%	60%	58.3%	25%	54.8%
	Total	Count	6	4	22	25	12	4	73
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were some notable differences** across age groups in how they rated the weekend's organisation. While the vast majority of all age groups were at least *satisfied*, the oldest (75+) and youngest (19-24) participants were the least likely to say they were *very satisfied* (25%, n=1 and 33.3%, n=2 respectively). In comparison, proportions of mid-age groups (25-29, 30-44, 45-64, 65-74) ranged from 54.5-75%.

	Ethnicity				Total
	Asian, Asian Scottish/ British/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/ Polish/ Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	

Satisfaction level: Organisation of the weekend	Very dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	1.6%	1.4%
	Neutral	Count	0	0	0	4	4
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	6.2%	5.5%
	Satisfied	Count	2	0	2	24	28
	% within Ethnicity		100%	0%	40%	37.5%	38.4%
	Very satisfied	Count	0	2	3	35	40
	% within Ethnicity		0%	100%	60%	54.7%	54.8%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	64	73
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were no notable differences** across ethnic groups in satisfaction with how the weekend was organised. **High satisfaction was consistent across all groups, with most respondents selecting either *satisfied* or *very satisfied*.** The only *dissatisfied* response came from a *White Scottish/British* participant.

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: I had influence over the choice of speakers that presented information this weekend

- Most participants across all genders felt they had little or no influence, with women slightly more likely to express stronger disagreement.
- Older participants felt less influence, with stronger disagreement increasing with age.
- There were no substantial differences between ethnic groups in perceived influence over speaker choice.

			Gender			
			In another way	Man	Woman	Total
Agreement level: I had influence over the choice of	Strongly disagree	Count	0	15	18	33
	% within Gender		0%	57.7%	52.9%	53.2%

speakers that presented information this weekend	Tend to disagree	Count	1	10	7	18
	% within Gender		50%	38.5%	20.6%	29%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	1	9	11
	% within Gender		50%	3.8%	26.5%	17.7%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	2	26	34	62
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were clear differences** in perceived influence over the choice of speakers. **Most participants across all genders felt they had little or no influence, with women slightly more likely to express stronger *disagreement*.** 52.9% (n=18) of women and 57.7% (n=15) of men *strongly disagreed*, while 50% (n=1) of those identifying *in another way tended to disagree* or were *neutral*. No one across any gender group selected *tend to agree* or *strongly agree*.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: I had influence over the choice of speakers that presented information this weekend	Strongly disagree	Count	2	1	8	11	8	2	32
	% within Age group		40%	33.3%	44.4%	55%	66.7%	100%	53.3%
	Tend to disagree	Count	1	1	6	7	3	0	18
	% within Age group		20%	33.3%	33.3%	35%	25%	0%	30%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	2	1	4	2	1	0	10
	% within Age group		40%	33.3%	22.2%	10%	8.3%	0%	16.7%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	5	3	18	20	12	2	60
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were clear differences** across age groups in perceived influence over speaker selection. **Overall, older participants felt less influence, with stronger *disagreement* increasing with age.** For example, *strongly disagree* responses rose from 40% (n=2) amongst 19-24s to 100% (n=2) amongst 75+s, while *neutral* responses were highest among younger groups (40%, n=2 among 19-24s). No one in any age group *agreed* that they had influence.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish /British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	
Agreement level: I had influence over the choice of speakers that presented information this weekend	Strongly disagree	Count	2	1	1	28	32
	% within Ethnicity		100%	50%	25%	53.8%	53.3%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	1	2	15	18
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	50%	28.8%	30%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	1	9	10
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	25%	17.3%	16.7%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	0	0	0

	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	2	2	4	52	60
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were no substantial differences** between ethnic groups in perceived influence over speaker choice. **Across all groups, most participants *disagreed*, with *strongly disagree* the most common response.** 100% (n=2) of *Asian* respondents and 53.8% (n=28) of *White Scottish/British* participants said *strongly disagree*, while smaller groups varied but showed *no agreement*.

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the Assembly as a whole, and about your experience as a whole?: I had the opportunity to influence decisions about the content of the information presented to us

- Those identifying their gender in another way were most likely to agree, while men and women were more mixed.
- There were no strong differences between age groups in perceived influence over content.
- There were no major differences across ethnic groups in perceived opportunity to influence content.

			Gender			
			In another way	Man	Woman	Total
Agreement level: I had the opportunity to influence decisions about the content of the information presented to us	Strongly disagree	Count	0	2	0	2
	% within Gender		0%	7.1%	0%	3.1%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	3	4	7
	% within Gender		0%	10.7%	11.4%	10.8%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	4	6	10
	% within Gender		0%	14.3%	17.1%	15.4%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	12	13	26
	% within Gender		50%	42.9%	37.1%	40%

	Strongly agree	Count	1	7	12	20
	% within Gender		50%	25%	34.3%	30.8%
	Total	Count	2	28	35	65
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were moderate differences** between gender groups in perceived opportunity to influence content decisions. **Those identifying in another way were most likely to agree, while men and women were more mixed.** 50% (n=1) of those identifying in another way selected *strongly agree*, compared to 25% (n=7) of men and 34.3% (n=12) of women. Men were more likely to select neutral or negative responses than women.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: I had the opportunity to influence decisions about the content of the information presented to us	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	1	1	0	0	2
	% within Age group		0%	0%	4.8%	4.3%	0%	0%	3.1%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	3	2	1	1	7
	% within Age group		0%	0%	14.3%	8.7%	10%	25%	10.8%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	1	3	2	2	1	10
	% within Age group		25%	33.3%	14.3%	8.7%	20%	25%	15.4%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	2	7	10	5	1	26
	% within Age group		25%	66.7%	33.3%	43.5%	50%	25%	40%
	Strongly agree	Count	2	0	7	8	2	1	20
	% within Age group		50%	0%	33.3%	34.8%	20%	25%	30.8%
	Total	Count	4	3	21	23	10	4	65
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were no strong differences** between age groups in perceived influence over content. **Across all ages, the majority gave positive responses, with at least**

60% in each group agreeing to some extent. *Strongly agree* responses ranged from 25% (25-29s) to 50% (19-24s), and *tend to agree* was the most common response across groups.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish /British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Poli sh/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	
Agreement level: I had the opportunity to influence decisions about the content of the information presented to us	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	2	2
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	3.6%	3.1%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	1	1	5	7
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	20%	8.9%	10.8%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	1	9	10
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	20%	16.1%	15.4%
	Tend to agree	Count	2	0	2	22	26
	% within Ethnicity		100%	0%	40%	39.3%	40%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	1	1	18	20
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	20%	32.1%	30.8%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	56	65
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were no major differences** across ethnic groups in perceived opportunity to influence content. **All groups expressed mostly positive views, with a majority selecting *tend to agree* or *strongly agree*.** For example, 100% (n=2) of *Asian* respondents and 71.5% (n=40) of *White Scottish/British* selected one of the two *agreement* options.

RQ: How inclusive was the CA process, in terms of facilitation and deliberation?

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: I didn't always feel free to raise my views and ideas, for fear of others' reaction⁷

- Notably, men made up the vast majority of those *agreeing* that they didn't always feel free to raise their views and ideas, while women were more likely to *strongly disagree*.
- While the 65-74 age group was the most likely to *strongly disagree*, there were no other notable patterns across age groups.
- There were no strong differences in whether participants felt free to raise their views, though levels of agreement varied by group.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Agreement level: I didn't always feel free to raise my views and ideas, for fear of others' reaction	Strongly disagree	Count	0	13	21	34
	% within Gender		0%	38.2%	50%	43.6%
	Tend to disagree	Count	2	15	16	33
	% within Gender		100%	44.1%	38.1%	42.3%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	2	4	6
	% within Gender		0%	5.9%	9.5%	7.7%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	4	1	5
	% within Gender		0%	11.8%	2.4%	6.4%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	2	34	42	78
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were some differences by gender** in whether participants felt free to raise ideas. **Overall, women were slightly more likely to report feeling free to speak, with 50% saying they *strongly disagreed* that fear held them back, and just 2.4% (n=1) *tending to agree*.** Those identifying in another way were more likely to

⁷ Median variable used, averaging participants' responses across the Assembly weekends

tend to disagree (100%). In contrast, only 38.2% (n=13) of men *strongly disagreed* that they didn't always feel free to raise their views or ideas, while 11.8% (n=4) *tended to agree*.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: I didn't always feel free to raise my views and ideas, for fear of others' reaction	Strongly disagree	Count	3	0	11	9	8	2	33
	% within Age group		50%	0%	50%	36%	66.7%	50%	45.2%
	Tend to disagree	Count	3	3	8	12	3	1	30
	% within Age group		50%	75%	36.4%	48%	25%	25%	41.1%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	1	2	2	0	1	6
	% within Age group		0%	25%	9.1%	8%	0%	25%	8.2%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	0	1	2	1	0	4
	% within Age group		0%	0%	4.5%	8%	8.3%	0%	5.5%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	6	4	22	25	12	4	73
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were some differences but no strong overall pattern** across age groups in whether participants felt free to share ideas. **The 65-74 age group were the most likely to *strongly disagree* with the statement** (66.7%, n=8), indicating greater confidence. Other age groups were consistently more varied in their responses.

		Ethnicity				Total
		Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British,	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	

			African or African Caribbean				
Agreement level: I didn't always feel free to raise my views and ideas, for fear of others' reaction	Strongly disagree	Count	0	1	3	29	33
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	60%	45.3%	45.2%
	Tend to disagree	Count	2	1	1	26	30
	% within Ethnicity		100%	50%	20%	40.6%	41.1%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	0	6	6
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	9.4%	8.2%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	0	1	3	4
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	20%	4.7%	5.5%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	64	73
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were no strong differences** in whether participants felt free to raise their views, though levels of agreement varied by group. **Most participants across all ethnicities disagreed with the statement, indicating they generally felt comfortable speaking.** *Strongly disagree* was most common among *White Scottish/British* (45.3%) and *White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other* (60%), while *Asian* participants leaned more toward *tend to disagree* (100%).

SQ: *How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: My fellow participants respected what I had to say, even when they didn't agree with me⁸*

- While agreement was high across genders, women and those identifying in another way were more likely to *strongly agree* than men.

⁸ Median variable used, averaging participants' responses across the Assembly weekends

- All age groups reported high agreement, but the youngest participants were most likely to select *strongly agree*.
- No notable differences were observed across ethnic groups.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Agreement level: My fellow participants respected what I had to say, even when they didn't agree with me	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	4	4	8
	% within Gender		0%	11.8%	9.5%	10.3%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	18	16	35
	% within Gender		50%	52.9%	38.1%	44.9%
	Strongly agree	Count	1	12	22	35
	% within Gender		50%	35.3%	52.4%	44.9%
	Total	Count	2	34	42	78
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were some notable differences** across genders in feeling respected by fellow participants. While *agreement* was high across genders, with 90% or more in each group saying they felt respected, **women (52.4%, n=22) and those identifying in another way (50%, n=1) were more likely to strongly agree**, compared to 35.3% (n=12) of men who were more cautious in their *agreement*.

			Age group					Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	
Agreement level: My fellow participants respected what I	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0

had to say, even when they didn't agree with me	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	3	2	0	1	6
	% within Age group		0%	0%	13.6%	8%	0%	25%	8.2%
	Tend to agree	Count	2	3	8	11	8	1	33
	% within Age group		33.3%	75%	36.4%	44%	66.7%	25%	45.2%
	Strongly agree	Count	4	1	11	12	4	2	34
	% within Age group		66.7%	25%	50%	48%	33.3%	50%	46.6%
	Total	Count	6	4	22	25	12	4	73
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There **were slight differences** across age groups in feeling respected, but no strong overall pattern. **Overall, all age groups reported *high agreement*, but the youngest participants were most likely to select *strongly agree*.** For example, 66.7% (n=4) of 19-24s said *strongly agree*, while the proportion of all other age groups selecting *strongly agree* ranged between and 50-25%.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	
Agreement level: My fellow participants respected what I had to say, even	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

when they didn't agree with me	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	0	6	6
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	9.4%	8.2%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	1	1	30	33
	% within Ethnicity		50%	50%	20%	46.9%	45.2%
	Strongly agree	Count	1	1	4	28	34
	% within Ethnicity		50%	50%	80%	43.8%	46.6%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	64	73
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

No notable differences were observed across ethnic groups. Participants from all ethnic backgrounds overwhelmingly *agreed* that they felt respected by others during the assembly discussions. Between 80-100% of respondents in each group either *tended to agree* or *strongly agreed* that fellow participants respected what they had to say, even when there were disagreements. No participants selected *tend to disagree* or *strongly disagree*, suggesting a strong shared experience of mutual respect irrespective of ethnicity.

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: I liked the way we prioritised the themes in my small group

- There was broad agreement across genders that participants liked the way themes were prioritised in their small group, though men were slightly less emphatic in their agreement than women.
- No notable age-based differences were found in how participants viewed theme prioritisation; disagreement was minimal and scattered across age groups.
- Most ethnic groups showed similarly high levels of agreement with how themes were prioritised.

	Gender			Total
	In another way	Man	Woman	

Agreement level: I liked the way we prioritised the themes in my small group	Strongly disagree	Count	0	1	1	2
	% within Gender		0%	3.7%	2.8%	3.1%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	2	1	3
	% within Gender		0%	7.4%	2.8%	4.6%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	5	3	9
	% within Gender		50%	18.5%	8.3%	13.8%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	13	17	31
	% within Gender		50%	48.1%	47.2%	47.7%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	6	14	20
	% within Gender		0%	22.2%	38.9%	30.8%
	Total	Count	2	27	36	65
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

Overall, there was **broad agreement across genders** that participants liked the way themes were prioritised in their small group, with notable gender variation in the strength of agreement. A majority of women either *tended to agree* (n=17, 47.2%) or *strongly agreed* (n=14, 38.9%), totalling 86.1% *agreement* (n=31). Among men, most also *tended to agree* (n=13, 48.1%), though fewer *strongly agreed* (n=6, 22.2%), and one in five *neither agreed nor disagreed* (n=5, 18.5%). Overall, **men were slightly less emphatic in their agreement than women**. Only a small number of participants *tended to disagree* or *strongly disagreed* across all gender categories (n=3 and n=2 respectively, 7.7% combined), suggesting a generally positive response to this aspect of the process.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: I liked the way we prioritised the themes in my small	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	2	0	0	0	2
	% within Age group		0%	0%	10.5%	0%	0%	0%	3.2%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	1	2	0	3
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	5%	16.7%	0%	4.8%

group	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	0	3	2	3	0	9
	% within Age group		20%	0%	15.8%	10%	25%	0%	14.5%
	Tend to agree	Count	3	2	8	9	4	3	29
	% within Age group		60%	66.7%	42.1%	45%	33.3%	100%	46.8%
	Strongly agree	Count	1	1	6	8	3	0	19
	% within Age group		20%	33.3%	31.6%	40%	25%	0%	30.6%
	Total	Count	5	3	19	20	12	3	62
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

No notable age-based differences were found in how participants viewed theme prioritisation. Levels of *agreement* were high across all age groups, with 100% of respondents aged 75+ (n=3) and 80% of 19-24-year-olds (n=5) expressing *agreement*. Even among the lowest *agreeing* group (ages 65-74), 58% *tended to agree* or *strongly agreed*. *Disagreement* was minimal and scattered across age groups. This indicates that the prioritisation process was broadly acceptable to participants of all ages.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	
Agreement level: I liked the way we prioritised the themes in my small	Strongly disagree	Count	1	0	0	1	2
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	0%	1.9%	3.2%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	3	3

group	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	5.6%	4.8%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	0	1	7	9
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	25%	13%	14.5%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	1	2	26	29
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	50%	48.1%	46.8%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	1	1	17	19
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	25%	31.5%	30.6%
	Total	Count	2	2	4	54	62
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

No strong differences were found between ethnic groups. Most ethnic groups showed similarly high levels of *agreement* with how themes were prioritised. For example, 75% (n=3) of White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other participants and 100% (n=2) of Black/Black Scottish/British respondents *agreed*. Only one *strongly disagree* response was recorded.

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: I liked the way we discussed proposals for change in my small group

- No notable gender differences emerged in how participants evaluated the discussions around change proposals in their small groups.
- Some differences were observed between age groups, but no consistent pattern emerged.
- No notable differences across ethnic groups were observed; agreement levels were consistently high across all categories.

			Gender			
			In another way	Man	Woman	Total
Agreement level: I liked the way we discussed proposals for change in my small group	Strongly disagree	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	3.8%	0%	1.7%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	1	2	3
	% within Gender		0%	3.8%	6.2%	5%

	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	2	3	5
	% within Gender		0%	7.7%	9.4%	8.3%
	Tend to agree	Count	2	13	14	29
	% within Gender		100%	50%	43.8%	48.3%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	9	13	22
	% within Gender		0%	34.6%	40.6%	36.7%
	Total	Count	2	26	32	60
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

No notable gender differences emerged in how participants evaluated the discussions around change proposals in their small groups. *Agreement* levels were consistently high: 84.4% (n=27) of women and 84.6% (n=22) of men either *tended to agree* or *strongly agreed*. Negative responses were rare, and there was no evidence that any gender felt significantly less included in proposal discussions.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: I liked the way we discussed proposals for change in my small group	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	5.6%	0%	0%	0%	1.7%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	2	1	0	0	3
	% within Age group		0%	0%	11.1%	4.5%	0%	0%	5%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	1	1	2	1	0	5
	% within Age group		0%	25%	5.6%	9.1%	11.1%	0%	8.3%
	Tend to agree	Count	4	1	10	10	3	1	29
	% within Age group		80%	25%	55.6%	45.5%	33.3%	50%	48.3%
	Strongly agree	Count	1	2	4	9	5	1	22
	% within Age group		20%	50%	22.2%	40.9%	55.6%	50%	36.7%

Total	Count	5	4	18	22	9	2	60
% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Some differences were observed between age groups, but no consistent pattern emerged. *Agreement* was universal among the youngest age group (19-24, n=5), while all other age groups had a wider spread of responses. The only *tend to disagree* or *strongly disagree* responses came from the 30-44 and 45-64 age groups. These fluctuations suggest some age-related variation in experience, though not enough to indicate a structural issue.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	
Agreement level: I liked the way we discussed proposals for change in my small group	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	2%	1.7%
	Tend to disagree	Count	1	0	0	2	3
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	0%	3.9%	5%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	1	4	5
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	20%	7.8%	8.3%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	0	4	24	29
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	80%	47.1%	48.3%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	2	0	20	22
	% within Ethnicity		0%	100%	0%	39.2%	36.7%
Total	Count	2	2	5	51	60	

	% within Ethnicity	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
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No notable differences across ethnic groups were observed. *Agreement* levels were consistently high across all categories, with 80% or more of participants in each group reporting that they either *tended to agree* or *strongly agreed*. The White Scottish/British group had the highest rate of *strongly agree* responses (39%, n=20).

SQ: How satisfied or dissatisfied are you with the following aspects: The way in which participants' questions have been handled/answered over the Assembly weekends as a whole

- *Very satisfied* responses were more common among women than men, and negative responses were more frequent among men than women.
- There were some differences by age group, but no consistent trend.
- Though based on small sample sizes, Asian and Black participants were exclusively very satisfied or satisfied with the way participants' questions had been answered, while the only disagreement came from White participants.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Satisfaction level: The way in which participants' questions have been handled/answered over the Assembly weekends as a whole	Very dissatisfied	Count	0	3	1	4
	% within Gender		0%	11.1%	2.8%	6.2%
	Dissatisfied	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	3.7%	0%	1.5%
	Neutral	Count	0	4	4	8
	% within Gender		0%	14.8%	11.1%	12.3%
	Satisfied	Count	2	12	17	31
	% within Gender		100%	44.4%	47.2%	47.7%
	Very satisfied	Count	0	7	14	21
	% within Gender		0%	25.9%	38.9%	32.3%
	Total	Count	2	27	36	65
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

Some differences were present between genders, although overall *agreement* remained high. 86.1% (n=31) of women and 70.3% (n=19) of men were either *very satisfied* or *satisfied* with how questions were handled. *Very satisfied* responses were more common among women (38.9%, n=14) than men (25.9%, n=7), and negative responses (e.g., *strongly disagree*) were more frequent among men (11.1%, n=3) than women (2.8%, n=1). These figures suggest a slightly more positive experience for women, but without extreme divergence.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: The way in which participants' questions have been handled/answered over the Assembly weekend as a whole	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	1	2	1	0	4
	% within Age group		0%	0%	5.3%	9.1%	9.1%	0%	6.2%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	5.3%	0%	0%	0%	1.5%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	2	4	1	1	8
	% within Age group		0%	0%	10.5%	18.2%	9.1%	25%	12.3%
	Tend to agree	Count	4	2	10	8	5	2	31
	% within Age group		80%	50%	52.6%	36.4%	45.5%	50%	47.7%
	Strongly agree	Count	1	2	5	8	4	1	21
	% within Age group		20%	50%	26.3%	36.4%	36.4%	25%	32.3%
	Total	Count	5	4	19	22	11	4	65
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some differences by age group, but again no consistent trend. Participants aged 19-24 and 25-29 were the most positive (100% *agreement*, n=5 and n=4 respectively), whereas those aged 45-64 and 30-44 had slightly lower *agreement* levels (72.8%, n=16 and 78.9%, n=15, respectively). While younger participants tended to be more uniformly positive, older groups still reported strong overall satisfaction.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	
Agreement level: The way in which participants' questions have been handled/answered over the Assembly weekends as a whole	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	4	4
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	7.1%	6.2%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	1.8%	1.5%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	1	7	8
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	20%	12.5%	12.3%
	Tend to agree	Count	2	1	2	26	31
	% within Ethnicity		100%	50%	40%	46.4%	47.7%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	1	2	18	21
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	40%	32.1%	32.3%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	56	65
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

While high *agreement* was seen across all groups, **there was exclusively very satisfied or satisfied responses from Asian and Black participants**. In contrast, lower proportions of 78.5% (n=44) White Scottish/British respondents and 80% (n=4) White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other expressed satisfaction with the way questions had been handled. The only *strongly disagree* or *disagree* responses came from White participants.

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the Assembly as a whole, and about your experience as a whole?: I feel that my contributions have been listened to by the other Assembly participants

- Agreement was similarly high across all gender groups, though men were slightly more likely to *neither agree nor disagree*.
- There were some small variations across age groups, but no strong overall pattern.
- There were no strong differences across ethnic groups, with high agreement across the board, though the most variation in response came from White Scottish/British respondents.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Agreement level: I feel that my contributions have been listened to by the other Assembly participants	Strongly disagree	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	3.6%	0%	1.5%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	1	1	2
	% within Gender		0%	3.6%	2.6%	2.9%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	4	2	6
	% within Gender		0%	14.3%	5.3%	8.8%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	9	15	24
	% within Gender		0%	32.1%	39.5%	35.3%
	Strongly agree	Count	2	13	20	35
	% within Gender		100%	46.4%	52.6%	51.5%
	Total	Count	2	28	38	68
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no notable differences between gender groups in how listened to participants felt by other assembly participants, though men were slightly more likely to *neither agree nor disagree*. A strong majority across all gender categories agreed that their contributions were heard, with 51.5% *strongly agreeing* overall. Women were slightly more likely than men to *strongly agree* (52.6%, n=20

vs. 46.4%, n=13), while respondents identifying in another way all *strongly agreed*, but the count here was very small (n=2).

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: I feel that my contributions have been listened to by the other Assembly participants	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	4.2%	0%	0%	1.5%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	2	0	0	0	2
	% within Age group		0%	0%	9.1%	0%	0%	0%	2.9%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	2	2	1	1	6
	% within Age group		0%	0%	9.1%	8.3%	8.3%	25%	8.8%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	2	8	9	4	1	24
	% within Age group		0%	100%	36.4%	37.5%	33.3%	25%	35.3%
	Strongly agree	Count	4	0	10	12	7	2	35
	% within Age group		100%	0%	45.5%	50%	58.3%	50%	51.5%
	Total	Count	4	2	22	24	12	4	68
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some small variations across age groups, but no strong overall pattern. All age groups showed high levels of *agreement*, with more than 70% either *tending to agree* or *strongly agreeing*. The proportion *strongly agreeing* increased steadily from 45.5% (n=10) in the 30-44 group to 58.3% (n=7) in the 65-74 group, but numbers were small in the youngest and oldest brackets, so conclusions should be drawn cautiously.

		Ethnicity				Total
		Asian, Asian	Black, Black Scottish/	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other	White Scottish/British	

			Scottish/ British	British, African or African Caribbean			
Agreement level: I feel that my contributions have been listened to by the other Assembly participants	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	1.7%	1.5%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	2	2
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	3.4%	2.9%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	0	6	6
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	10.2%	8.8%
	Tend to agree	Count	2	0	2	20	24
	% within Ethnicity		100%	0%	40%	33.9%	35.3%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	2	3	30	35
	% within Ethnicity		0%	100%	60%	50.8%	51.5%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	59	68
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no strong differences across ethnic groups, with high agreement across the board. Over 80% of participants in each group either *tended to agree* or *strongly agreed*. The most variation in response can be seen in the White Scottish/British ethnic group, with 10.2% (n=6) *neither agreeing nor disagreeing*, and 5.1% (n=3) *disagreeing* to some extent.

SQ: Thinking about your facilitator this weekend, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: The breakout room facilitator made sure that opposing arguments were considered⁹

- There were no notable differences between gender groups

⁹ Median variable used, averaging participants' responses across the Assembly weekends

- There were modest differences by age - younger participants (19-24, 25-29) were more likely to report *stronger agreement* than those in all older age groups.
- There were some differences across ethnic groups - all Black respondents selected *strongly agree*, whereas other groups showed slightly more varied responses

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Agreement level: The breakout room facilitator made sure that opposing arguments were considered	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	4	4	8
	% within Gender		0%	11.8%	9.5%	10.3%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	10	12	22
	% within Gender		0%	29.4%	28.6%	28.2%
	Strongly agree	Count	2	20	26	48
	% within Gender		100%	58.8%	61.9%	61.5%
	Total	Count	2	34	42	78
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no notable differences between gender groups in *agreement* that the breakout room facilitator made sure opposing arguments were considered. **The majority of participants across all groups selected *strongly agree*.** For instance, 61.9% (n=26) of women and 58.8% (n=20) of men chose this response, with only minor variation in the proportion selecting *tend to agree*.

			Age group					Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	
Agreement level:	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0

The breakout room facilitator made sure that opposing arguments were considered	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	1	2	2	2	0	7
	% within Age group		0%	25%	9.1%	8%	16.7%	0%	9.6%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	0	6	9	2	2	20
	% within Age group		16.7%	0%	27.3%	36%	16.7%	50%	27.4%
	Strongly agree	Count	5	3	14	14	8	2	46
	% within Age group		83.3%	75%	63.6%	56%	66.7%	50%	63%
	Total	Count	6	4	22	25	12	4	73
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were modest differences by age. **Younger participants (19-24, 25-29) were more likely to report stronger agreement than those in all older age groups.** Specifically, 83.3% (n=5) of 19–24-year-olds and 75% (n=3) of 25–29-year-olds selected *strongly agree*, compared to 56% (n=14) of those aged 45–64. In the 30–44 age group, 27.3% (n=6) selected *tend to agree*, and 9.1% (n=2) chose *neither agree nor disagree*, reflecting a slightly more mixed pattern.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	
Agreement level: The	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0

breakout room facilitator made sure that opposing arguments were considered	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	0	7	7
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	10.9%	9.6%
	Tend to agree	Count	2	0	1	17	20
	% within Ethnicity		100%	0%	20%	26.6%	27.4%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	2	4	40	46
	% within Ethnicity		0%	100%	80%	62.5%	63%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	64	73
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some differences across ethnic groups. **All Black respondents selected *strongly agree*, whereas other groups showed slightly more varied responses.** For example, 100% (n=2) of Black participants and 80% (n=4) of the White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other group selected *strongly agree*, compared with 62.5% (n=40) of White Scottish/British respondents. A quarter of the latter group (26.6%, n=17) selected *tend to agree*, indicating a broader distribution of views. Small sample sizes in the non-White Scottish/British respondents mean these results should be interpreted with caution.

SQ: Thinking about your facilitator this weekend, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: The break-out-room facilitator sometimes tried to influence the group with their own ideas¹⁰

- Women were notably more likely to *strongly disagree* than men that facilitators tried to influence the group with their own ideas.
- Clear differences emerged across age groups regarding facilitator influence. Older age groups tended to *strongly disagree* more than younger ones.

¹⁰ Median variable used, averaging participants' responses across the Assembly weekends

- White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other respondents were more likely to *strongly disagree* compared to other groups.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Agreement level: The break-out-room facilitator sometimes tried to influence the group with their own ideas	Strongly disagree	Count	0	12	27	39
	% within Gender		0%	35.3%	64.3%	50%
	Tend to disagree	Count	1	11	8	20
	% within Gender		50%	32.4%	19%	25.6%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	6	6	13
	% within Gender		50%	17.6%	14.3%	16.7%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	5	0	5
	% within Gender		0%	14.7%	0%	6.4%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	1	1
	% within Gender		0%	0%	2.4%	1.3%
	Total	Count	2	34	42	78
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

Gender showed a distinct pattern regarding perceptions of facilitator neutrality. **Women were notably more likely to *strongly disagree* than men that facilitators tried to influence the group with their own ideas.** 64.3% (n=27) of women *strongly disagreed*, compared to 35.3% (n=12) of men.

			Age group					Total	
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74		75+
Agreement level: The break-out-room facilitator sometimes tried to influence	Strongly disagree	Count	2	1	11	14	7	1	36
	% within Age group		33.3%	25%	50%	56%	58.3%	25%	49.3%
	Tend to disagree	Count	1	0	6	7	4	2	20
	% within Age group		16.7%	0%	27.3%	28%	33.3%	50%	27.4%

the group with their own ideas	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	2	2	3	4	0	1	12
	% within Age group		33.3%	50%	13.6%	16%	0%	25%	16.4%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	1	1	0	1	0	4
	% within Age group		16.7%	25%	4.6%	0%	8.3%	0%	5.5%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	4.6%	0%	0%	0%	1.4%
	Total	Count	6	4	22	25	12	4	73
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Clear differences emerged across age groups regarding facilitator influence. **Older age groups tended to *strongly disagree* more than younger ones.** For example, 58.3% (n=7) of respondents aged 65-74 *strongly disagreed*, compared to only 25% (n=1) in the 25-29 age group and 33.3% (n=2) in the 19-24 age group.

			Ethnicity				
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	Total
Agreement level: The break-out-room facilitator sometimes tried to influence the group with their own ideas	Strongly disagree	Count	0	1	3	32	36
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	60%	50%	49.32%
	Tend to disagree	Count	1	1	1	17	20
	% within Ethnicity		50%	50%	20%	26.56%	27.4%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	0	1	10	12

% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	20%	15.62%	16.44%
Tend to agree	Count	0	0	0	4	4
% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	6.25%	5.48%
Strongly agree	Count	0	0	0	1	1
% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	1.56%	1.37%
Total	Count	2	2	5	64	73
% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There was a notable difference across ethnicities regarding perceptions that the breakout-room facilitator influenced the group. **White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other respondents were more likely to *strongly disagree* compared to other groups.** Specifically, 60% (n=3) of this group *strongly disagreed*, whereas 50% (n=32) of White Scottish/British respondents and 50% (n=1) of Black Scottish/British/African/African Caribbean respondents *strongly disagreed*.

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: I have had ample opportunity in the small group discussions to express my views¹¹

- Across the board, the most common response for this question was *strongly agree*.
- There were minor differences by gender: women were slightly more likely to report *strong agreement* that they had ample opportunity to express their views
- There were small differences by age: younger participants (under 30) were more likely to select *strongly agree* than middle-aged participants
- Minor variation was evident across ethnic groups, though not large enough to be noteworthy.

	Gender			Total
	In another way	Man	Woman	

¹¹ Median variable used, averaging participants' responses across the Assembly weekends

Agreement level: I have had ample opportunity in the small group discussions to express my views	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	3	1	4
	% within Gender		0%	8.8%	2.4%	5.1%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	3	1	4
	% within Gender		0%	8.8%	2.4%	5.1%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	9	14	23
	% within Gender		0%	26.5%	33.3%	29.5%
	Strongly agree	Count	2	19	26	47
	% within Gender		100%	55.8%	61.9%	60.3%
	Total	Count	2	34	42	78
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were small differences between genders in perceptions of having had the opportunity to express views in small group discussions. **Women were slightly more likely to report strong agreement.** 61.9% (n=26) of women selected *strongly agree*, compared to 55.9% (n=19) of men. Meanwhile, 26.5% (n=9) of men chose *tend to agree*, slightly below the 33.3% (n=14) among women.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: I have had ample opportunity in the small group discussions to express my views	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	1	2	0	0	3
	% within Age group		0%	0%	4.5%	8%	0%	0%	4.1%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	1	1	0	2	4
	% within Age group		0%	0%	4.6%	4%	0%	50%	5.5%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	0	9	7	4	0	21

	% within Age group		16.7%	0%	40.9%	28%	33.3%	0%	28.8%
	Strongly agree	Count	5	4	11	15	8	2	45
	% within Age group		83.3%	100%	50%	60%	66.7%	50%	61.6%
	Total	Count	6	4	22	25	12	4	73
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Differences by age group showed some variation in levels of *agreement*, though at least half of all age groups selected *strongly agree*. **Younger participants (under 30) were more likely to select *strongly agree* than middle-aged participants, who were more likely than the younger age groups selected *tend to agree*.** For example, 83.3% (n=5) of 19-24 year-olds and 100% (n=4) of 25-29 year olds chose *strongly agree*, compared to 50% (n=11) of those aged 30–44. Meanwhile, *tend to agree* was selected by 40.9% (n=9) of 30-44 year olds and 28% (n=13) of 45-64 year-olds, showing a slightly more moderate response pattern in middle age.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	
Agreement level: I have had ample opportunity in the small group discussions to express my views	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	3	3
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	4.7%	4.1%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	0	0	3	4
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	0%	4.7%	5.5%

	Tend to agree	Count	1	0	2	18	21
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	40%	28.1%	28.8%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	2	3	40	45
	% within Ethnicity		0%	100%	60%	62.5%	61.6%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	64	73
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Minor variation was evident across ethnic groups. **Black, Black Scottish/British, African or African Caribbean respondents were more likely to select *strongly agree* compared to other groups, though sample sizes for non-White respondents were small.** Specifically, 100% (n=2) of Black participants chose *strongly agree*, as did 62.5% (n=40) of the White Scottish/British group.

RQ: Outputs: Do PMIMG participants feel their perspectives are included in CA outputs? Do these participants feel a sense of co-ownership of CA outputs?

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: My views are reflected in the themes selected as priority areas from my small group

- There was broad agreement across gender groups that participants' views were reflected in the themes prioritised by their small group, though women and those identifying in another way were more likely to strongly agree.
- Some differences emerged by age, but with no clear directional pattern,
- There were no significant differences by ethnicity; across all ethnic groups, the majority felt their views were reflected.

			Gender			
			In another way	Man	Woman	Total
Agreement level: My views are reflected in the themes selected as priority areas from my small	Strongly disagree	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	3.8%	0%	1.6%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	2	1	3
	% within Gender		0%	7.7%	2.8%	4.7%

group	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	4	3	7
	% within Gender		0%	15.4%	8.3%	10.9%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	11	16	28
	% within Gender		50%	42.3%	44.4%	43.8%
	Strongly agree	Count	1	8	16	25
	% within Gender		50%	30.8%	44.4%	39.1%
	Total	Count	2	26	36	64
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There was broad *agreement* across gender groups that participants' views were reflected in the themes prioritised by their small group, though **women and those identifying in another way were more likely to strongly agree**. Among women and those identifying in another way, 44.4% (n=16) and 50% (n=1) *strongly agreed* respectively, whereas 30.8% (n=8) of men *strongly agreed*. A larger proportion of men also *neither agreed nor disagreed* (15.4%, n=4) compared to women (8.3%, n=3). Negative responses were minimal across all genders. These findings suggest that while *agreement* was high overall, women reported feeling slightly more represented in the priority themes than men.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: My views are reflected in the themes selected as priority areas from my small group	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	8.3%	0%	1.6%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	2	1	0	0	3
	% within Age group		0%	0%	10.5%	5%	0%	0%	4.9%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	1	1	2	3	0	7
	% within Age group		0%	33.3%	5.3%	10%	25%	0%	11.5%
	Tend to agree	Count	2	1	10	8	4	2	27

% within Age group		40%	33.3%	52.6%	40%	33.3%	100%	44.3%
Strongly agree	Count	3	1	6	9	4	0	23
% within Age group		60%	33.3%	31.6%	45%	33.3%	0%	37.7%
Total	Count	5	3	19	20	12	2	61
% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Some differences emerged by age, but with no clear directional pattern, suggesting the extent to which assembly participants felt their views were reflected in the themes selected was not meaningfully influenced by age. Overall, *agreement* was high across all groups.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Poli sh/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	
Agreement level: My views are reflected in the themes selected as priority areas from my small group	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	1.9%	1.6%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	3	3
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	5.7%	4.9%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	0	7	7
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	13.2%	11.5%
	Tend to agree	Count	2	1	2	22	27
	% within Ethnicity		100%	50%	50%	41.5%	44.3%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	1	2	20	23

	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	50%	37.7%	37.7%
	Total	Count	2	2	4	53	61
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were **no significant differences by ethnicity**. Across all ethnic groups, the majority felt their views were reflected, with at least 79.2% either *tending to agree* or *strongly agreeing*. All Asian respondents (n=2) *tended to agree*, while half of the Black respondents *tended to agree* and half *strongly agreed*. Among White Scottish/British participants, 41.5% *tended to agree* and 37.7% *strongly agreed*.

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: The final prioritised themes across the Assembly reflect how I voted

- While similar proportions of men and women *agreed* with this statement, men were slightly more likely to *disagree* to some extent, while women were more likely to *neither agree nor disagree*.
- There were some differences across age groups, though no strong directional pattern.
- *Agreement* levels were fairly consistent across ethnicities, with no major differences.

			Gender			
			In another way	Man	Woman	Total
Agreement level: The final prioritised themes across the Assembly reflect how I voted	Strongly disagree	Count	0	1	1	2
	% within Gender		0%	3.7%	2.9%	3.1%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	4	1	5
	% within Gender		0%	14.8%	2.9%	7.8%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	2	7	10
	% within Gender		50%	7.4%	20%	15.6%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	15	20	35
	% within Gender		0%	55.6%	57.1%	54.7%
	Strongly agree	Count	1	5	6	12
	% within Gender		50%	18.5%	17.1%	18.8%

	Total	Count	2	27	35	64
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some gender differences in whether people felt the final themes reflected their votes. While similar proportions of men (55.6%, n=15) and women (57.1, n=20) *tended to agree*, and *strongly agreed* (18.5%, n=5 for men, 17.1%, n=6 for women), **men were slightly more likely to disagree (14.8%, n=4), while women were more likely to neither agree nor disagree (20%, n=7)**. Participants identifying in another way were more split, with 50% (n=1) *neither agreeing nor disagreeing* and 50% *strongly agreeing*.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: The final prioritised themes across the Assembly reflect how I voted	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	1	0	1	0	2
	% within Age group		0%	0%	5.3%	0%	8.3%	0%	3.2%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	2	2	1	0	5
	% within Age group		0%	0%	10.5%	10%	8.3%	0%	8.1%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	0	3	5	1	0	10
	% within Age group		20%	0%	15.8%	25%	8.3%	0%	16.1%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	3	12	9	6	3	34
	% within Age group		20%	100%	63.2%	45%	50%	100%	54.8%
	Strongly agree	Count	3	0	1	4	3	0	11
	% within Age group		60%	0%	5.3%	20%	25%	0%	17.7%
	Total	Count	5	3	19	20	12	3	62
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some differences across age groups, although the overall trend was one of agreement. Younger participants (under 30) were more likely to *strongly agree* (60%, n=3 among 19-24s), while middle-aged groups (30-44, 45-64) were

more likely to select *tend to agree* (up to 63.2%, n=12 in the 30-44 group). The 75+ group all *tended to agree* (100%, n=3), but no one in that group *strongly agreed*.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Poli sh/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	
Agreement level: The final prioritised themes across the Assembly reflect how I voted	Strongly disagree	Count	1	0	0	1	2
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	0%	1.9%	3.2%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	1	4	5
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	25%	7.4%	8.1%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	1	9	10
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	25%	16.7%	16.1%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	2	2	29	34
	% within Ethnicity		50%	100%	50%	53.7%	54.8%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	0	11	11
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	20.4%	17.7%
	Total	Count	2	2	4	54	62
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Agreement levels were fairly consistent across ethnicities, with no major differences. White Scottish/British respondents were the most likely to *agree* (53.7% *tended to agree* and 20.4% *strongly agreed*). Smaller groups such as Asian and Black respondents showed similar trends: 50% of Asian respondents *tended to agree* and 50% of Black respondents *strongly agreed*, but total numbers here were very low (n=2 for each group).

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: I accept the outcome of the vote this weekend

- There were no strong differences by gender in levels of acceptance of the vote outcome; majorities in all groups either *strongly agreed* or *tended to agree*.
- There were some differences by age group, but no clear pattern.
- There were no notable differences by ethnicity; majorities in all ethnic groups *strongly agreed* or *tended to agree* with the statement.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Agreement level: I accept the outcome of the vote this weekend	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	1	1
	% within Gender		0%	0%	2.6%	1.4%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	4	3	7
	% within Gender		0%	13.3%	7.9%	10%
	Tend to agree	Count	2	11	13	26
	% within Gender		100%	36.7%	34.2%	37.1%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	15	21	36
	% within Gender		0%	50%	55.3%	51.4%
	Total	Count	2	30	38	70
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no strong differences by gender in levels of acceptance of the vote outcome. Majorities in all groups either *strongly agreed* or *tended to agree*, with women slightly more likely to *strongly agree* (55.3%, $n=21$) compared to men (50%, $n=15$) and those identifying in another way (0%, $n=0$). Those identifying in another way showed 100% *agreement* in the *tend to agree* category, but with a very small sample ($n=2$), this should be interpreted cautiously.

	Age group	
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			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	Total
Agreement level: I accept the outcome of the vote this weekend	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	3	3	0	1	7
	% within Age group		0%	0%	15.8%	12.5%	0%	25%	10.4%
	Tend to agree	Count	3	2	4	7	6	2	24
	% within Age group		60%	50%	21.1%	29.2%	54.5%	50%	35.8%
	Strongly agree	Count	2	2	12	14	5	1	36
	% within Age group		40%	50%	63.2%	58.3%	45.5%	25%	53.7%
	Total	Count	5	4	19	24	11	4	67
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some differences by age group, but no clear pattern. *Strong agreement* was relatively high across all age groups except for those aged 75+, where it dropped to 25% (n=1), and was highest among the 30-44 group (63.2%, n=12). The proportion of most other groups selecting the *strongly agree* response ranged between 40-58%. Neutral responses were slightly more common in the 30-64 range (12.5-15.8%).

	Ethnicity				Total
	Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	

			Caribbean			
Agreement level: I accept the outcome of the vote this weekend	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	0	7
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	12.1%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	0	1	22
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	20%	37.9%
	Strongly agree	Count	1	2	4	29
	% within Ethnicity		50%	100%	80%	50%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	58
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no notable differences by ethnicity. Majorities in all ethnic groups *strongly agreed* or *tended to agree* with the statement. *Strongly agree* responses were especially high among Black (100%, n=2) and White Irish/Other participants (80%, n=4), but small subgroup sizes make it difficult to generalise.

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: I was happy with the options presented for voting this weekend

- There were no notable differences by gender; a similarly proportioned majority of each gender group either *strongly agreed* or *tended to agree*.
- Satisfaction with the voting options was high across all age groups, but the 25-29 group stood out with 100% *agreement*.
- There were no strong differences by ethnicity.

	Gender			Total
	In another way	Man	Woman	

Agreement level: I was happy with the options presented for voting this weekend	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	3.3%	0%	1.4%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	5	5	10
	% within Gender		0%	16.7%	13.2%	14.3%
	Tend to agree	Count	2	13	17	32
	% within Gender		100%	43.3%	44.7%	45.7%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	11	16	27
	% within Gender		0%	36.7%	42.1%	38.6%
	Total	Count	2	30	38	70
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no notable differences by gender. A majority of each gender group either *strongly agreed* or *tended to agree* with women slightly more likely to *strongly agree* (42.1%, n=16) than men (36.7%, n=11). People identifying in another way all selected *tend to agree* (n=2), but the numbers are too small for inference.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: I was happy with the options presented for voting this weekend	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	25%	1.5%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	4	3	2	1	10
	% within Age group		0%	0%	21.1%	12.5%	18.2%	25%	14.9%
	Tend to agree	Count	2	3	7	11	5	1	29
	% within Age group		40%	75%	36.8%	45.8%	45.5%	25%	43.3%

	Strongly agree	Count	3	1	8	10	4	1	27
	% within Age group		60%	25%	42.1%	41.7%	36.4%	25%	40.3%
	Total	Count	5	4	19	24	11	4	67
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Satisfaction with the voting options was high across all age groups, but the 25-29 group stood out with 100% agreement—75% (n=3) *tended to agree* and 25% (n=1) *strongly agreed*. In contrast, the 75+ group showed more mixed views, with 25% (n=1) *tending to disagree* and another 25% (n=1) *neither agreeing nor disagreeing*. These findings suggest unanimous approval among younger adults, while older participants expressed slightly more hesitation.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	
Agreement level: I was happy with the options presented for voting this weekend	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	1.7%	1.5%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	0	0	9	10
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	0%	15.5%	14.9%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	0	2	26	29
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	40%	44.8%	43.3%

	Strongly agree	Count	0	2	3	22	27
	% within Ethnicity		0%	100%	60%	37.9%	40.3%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	58	67
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no strong differences by ethnicity. Large majorities across all groups reported being happy with the options, with the vast majority in all but one group *agreeing* to some extent. The exception was Asian participants (n=2), where responses were split between *neither agree nor disagree* and *tend to agree*, though the small sample limits conclusions.

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: My views are reflected in the overarching statements proposed by my small group

- There were no major gender differences, though men were slightly more likely to *neither agree nor disagree* and *disagree*.
- Younger age groups were much more likely to *strongly agree* compared to older age groups.
- While most ethnic groups expressed *agreement* that their views were reflected in the overarching statements, White Scottish/British participants were the most varied in their responses.

			Gender			
			In another way	Man	Woman	Total
Agreement level: My views are reflected in the overarching statements proposed by my small group	Strongly disagree	Count	0	2	0	2
	% within Gender		0%	7.4%	0%	3.1%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	1	1	2
	% within Gender		0%	3.7%	2.9%	3.1%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	5	3	8
	% within Gender		0%	18.5%	8.6%	12.5%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	8	12	21
	% within Gender		50%	29.6%	34.3%	32.8%

	Strongly agree	Count	1	11	19	31
	% within Gender		50%	40.7%	54.3%	48.4%
	Total	Count	2	27	35	64
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no major gender differences. Most participants either *tended to agree* or *strongly agreed*, with **women showing slightly more *strongly agree* responses** (54.3%, n=19) than men (40.7%, n=11). **Men were also slightly more likely to be *neutral or disagree*.**

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: My views are reflected in the overarching statements proposed by my small group	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	1	0	1	0	2
	% within Age group		0%	0%	5.9%	0%	8.3%	0%	3.1%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	1	1	0	0	2
	% within Age group		0%	0%	5.9%	4.5%	0%	0%	3.1%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	2	3	1	2	8
	% within Age group		0%	0%	11.8%	13.6%	8.3%	50%	12.5%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	1	5	7	6	1	21
	% within Age group		20%	25%	29.4%	31.8%	50%	25%	32.8%
	Strongly agree	Count	4	3	8	11	4	1	31
	% within Age group		80%	75%	47.1%	50%	33.3%	25%	48.4%
	Total	Count	5	4	17	22	12	4	64
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were **notable age differences, especially in the proportions *strongly agreeing***. Younger participants (19-24, 25-29) showed high *strongly agree* responses (75%, n=4 and 80%, n=5 respectively), compared to all other older age groups.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	
Agreement level: My views are reflected in the overarching statements proposed by my small group	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	2	2
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	3.6%	3.1%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	2	2
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	3.6%	3.1%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	0	0	7	8
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	0%	12.7%	12.5%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	0	3	17	21
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	60%	30.9%	32.8%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	2	2	27	31
	% within Ethnicity		0%	100%	40%	49.1%	48.4%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	55	64
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Most ethnic groups expressed *agreement* that their views were reflected in the overarching statements. White Scottish/British participants showed the greatest spread, with 80% (n=44) *agreeing* to some extent, 12.7% (n=7) *neither agreeing nor disagreeing*, and 7.2% (n=4) expressing *disagreement*. Asian participants (n=2) were split between *tend to agree* (50%, n=1) and *neither agree nor disagree* (50%, n=1). All Black (n=2) and White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other participants (n=5) expressed *agreement*.

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the Assembly as a whole, and about your experience as a whole?: My views are reflected in the finalised goals and recommendations

- There were noticeable differences by gender in *agreement*: women and those identifying in another way were more likely than men to feel represented in the finalised goals and recommendations.
- While *agreement* was generally high, younger participants were more likely to report *strong agreement*.
- White Scottish/British participants were the only ethnic group that did not unanimously *agree* that their views were reflected.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Agreement level: My views are reflected in the finalised goals and recommendations	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	5	2	7
	% within Gender		0%	17.2%	5.4%	10.3%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	5	1	6
	% within Gender		0%	17.2%	2.7%	8.8%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	8	18	26
	% within Gender		0%	27.6%	48.6%	38.2%
	Strongly agree	Count	2	11	16	29
	% within Gender		100%	37.9%	43.2%	42.6%
	Total	Count	2	29	37	68
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were noticeable differences by gender in *agreement*. Women and those identifying in another way were more likely than men to feel represented in the finalised goals, with 43.2% (n=16) women and 100% people identifying in another way (n=2) *strongly agreeing* and compared to 37.9% among men (n=11). Conversely, men were more likely to express *disagreement*, with 17.2% (n=5) selecting either *tend to disagree* or *neither agree nor disagree* in both categories.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: My views are reflected in the finalised goals and recommendations	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	3	3	1	0	7
	% within Age group		0%	0%	14.3%	12.5%	8.3%	0%	10.3%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	2	2	1	1	6
	% within Age group		0%	0%	9.5%	8.3%	8.3%	25%	8.8%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	1	7	11	5	2	26
	% within Age group		0%	33.3%	33.3%	45.8%	41.7%	50%	38.2%
	Strongly agree	Count	4	2	9	8	5	1	29
	% within Age group		100%	66.7%	42.9%	33.3%	41.7%	25%	42.6%
	Total	Count	4	3	21	24	12	4	68
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some differences across age groups, particularly in levels of *strong agreement*. **While agreement was generally high, younger participants were more likely to report strong agreement:** 100% (n=4) of 19-24s and 66.7% (n=2) of 25-29s *strongly agreed*, compared with 25% (n=1) of those aged 75+. Those aged 30-64 were more mixed, with a *tendency to agree* (e.g. 45.8%, n=11 of 45-64s) rather than *strongly agree*. Only small minorities across all groups selected *neither agree nor disagree* or *disagree*.

		Ethnicity				Total
		Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	

				or African Caribbean			
Agreement level: My views are reflected in the finalised goals and recommendations	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	7	7
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	11.9%	10.3%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	0	6	6
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	10.2%	8.8%
	Tend to agree	Count	2	0	3	21	26
	% within Ethnicity		100%	0%	60%	35.6%	38.2%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	2	2	25	29
	% within Ethnicity		0%	100%	40%	42.4%	42.6%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	59	68
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Across all ethnic groups, the majority *agreed* that their views were reflected in the finalised goals and recommendations, with no participants selecting *strongly disagree*. **The most striking difference was that White Scottish/British participants were the only ethnic group that selected *tend to disagree* (11.9%, n=7) and *neither agree nor disagree* (10.2%, n=6), suggesting that other ethnic groups expressed more consistent or unequivocal *agreement*.**

SQ: *How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the Assembly as a whole, and about your experience as a whole?: My views are reflected in the finalised overarching statements*

- There were notable differences by gender: women were more likely to select positive responses than men, while men were more likely than women to *neither agree nor disagree* or *disagree*.

- Younger age groups (19-24, 25-29) were universal in their *agreement*, while older age groups showed more of a spread of responses.
- There were no notable differences by ethnicity.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Agreement level: My views are reflected in the finalised overarching statements	Strongly disagree	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	3.4%	0%	1.4%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	3	1	4
	% within Gender		0%	10.3%	2.6%	5.8%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	6	0	6
	% within Gender		0%	20.7%	0%	8.7%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	10	24	35
	% within Gender		50%	34.5%	63.2%	50.7%
	Strongly agree	Count	1	9	13	23
	% within Gender		50%	31%	34.2%	33.3%
	Total	Count	2	29	38	69
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were notable differences by gender. Women were more likely to select positive responses, with 63.2% (n=24) *tending to agree* and 34.2% (n=13) *strongly agreeing*. Men were more split: 34.5% (n=10) *tended to agree* and 31% (n=9) *strongly agreed*, but 20.7% (n=6) *selected neither agree nor disagree*. Disagreement was very low overall, but men accounted for most of it (3 out of 4 cases).

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: My views are reflected in the	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	4.2%	0%	0%	1.4%
	Tend to	Count	0	0	3	0	1	0	4

finalised overarching statements	disagree								
	% within Age group		0%	0%	13.6%	0%	8.3%	0%	5.8%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	1	3	1	1	6
	% within Age group		0%	0%	4.5%	12.5%	8.3%	25%	8.7%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	3	11	13	5	2	35
	% within Age group		25%	100%	50%	54.2%	41.7%	50%	50.7%
	Strongly agree	Count	3	0	7	7	5	1	23
	% within Age group		75%	0%	31.8%	29.2%	41.7%	25%	33.3%
	Total	Count	4	3	22	24	12	4	69
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some age-related differences: the 19-24 group showed a stronger inclination toward *strong agreement* (75%, n=3) compared with all other age groups, who were predominantly more likely to *tend to agree*. *Neither agree nor disagree* and *disagree* responses were only selected by participants 30+, indicating more consistent *agreement* amongst younger participants.

			Ethnicity				
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	Total
Agreement level: My views are reflected in the finalised	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	1.7%	1.4%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	4	4

overarching statements	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	6.7%	5.8%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	0	6	6
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	10%	8.7%
	Tend to agree	Count	2	1	4	28	35
	% within Ethnicity		100%	50%	80%	46.7%	50.7%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	1	1	21	23
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	20%	35%	33.3%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	60	69
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no notable differences by ethnicity. *Agreement* was broadly high across all groups, with *tend to agree* and *strongly agree* accounting for most responses. For example, 46.7% of 'White Scottish/British' respondents tended to agree and 35% strongly agreed. There were no cases of strong disagreement outside the 'White Scottish/British' group.

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the Assembly as a whole, and about your experience as a whole?: The goals have been developed in a fair way

- There were notable differences by gender: women were more likely to *strongly agree* than men, while men were more likely than women to *neither agree nor disagree* or *disagree*.
- There were some modest age differences; *disagreement* and *neither agree nor disagree* responses were rare but slightly more common in the 30-44 and 45-64 brackets.
- There were no strong differences across ethnic groups.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Agreement level: The goals have	Strongly disagree	Count	0	2	1	3
	% within Gender		0%	7.4%	2.6%	4.5%

been developed in a fair way	Tend to disagree	Count	0	4	0	4
	% within Gender		0%	14.8%	0%	6%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	1	2	3
	% within Gender		0%	3.7%	5.3%	4.5%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	13	20	34
	% within Gender		50%	48.1%	52.6%	50.7%
	Strongly agree	Count	1	7	15	23
	% within Gender		50%	25.9%	39.5%	34.3%
	Total	Count	2	27	38	67
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some differences by gender. Women were more likely to **strongly agree** (39.5%, n=15) compared to men (25.9%, n=7). However, both genders had high overall *agreement* levels, with 52.6% (n=20) of women and 48.1% (n=13) of men *tending to agree*. *Disagreement* was limited but concentrated among men, who accounted for 6 of the 10 non-positive responses.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: The goals have been developed in a fair way	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	1	2	0	0	3
	% within Age group		0%	0%	4.5%	8.3%	0%	0%	4.3%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	1	1	1	0	3
	% within Age group		0%	0%	4.5%	4.2%	8.3%	0%	4.3%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	4	2	0	2	8
	% within Age group		0%	0%	18.2%	8.3%	0%	50%	11.6%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	2	8	12	7	1	31
	% within Age group		25%	66.7%	36.4%	50%	58.3%	25%	44.9%
	Strongly	Count	3	1	8	7	4	1	24

	agree								
	% within Age group		75%	33.3%	36.4%	29.2%	33.3%	25%	34.8%
	Total	Count	4	3	22	24	12	4	69
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some modest age differences. *Strong agreement* was highest among 19-24-year-olds (75%, n=3) and lowest among people aged 75+ (25%, n=1). However, **across all age bands, the majority agreed**, showing overall positive sentiment. *Disagreement* and *neither agree nor disagree* were rare but slightly more common in the 30-44 and 45-64 brackets.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	
Agreement level: The goals have been developed in a fair way	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	3	3
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	5%	4.3%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	3	3
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	5%	4.3%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	0	0	7	8
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	0%	11.7%	11.6%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	1	3	26	31
	% within Ethnicity		50%	50%	60%	43.3%	44.9%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	1	2	21	24
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	40%	35%	34.8%

Total	Count	2	2	5	60	69
% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no strong differences across ethnic groups. *Agreement* levels were broadly consistent, with *tend to agree* and *strongly agree* combining for majorities in every group. For instance, 60% of the 'White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other' group and 43.3% of the 'White Scottish/British' group *tended to agree*. The only three cases of *strong disagreement* appeared in the largest group, 'White Scottish/British'.

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the Assembly as a whole, and about your experience as a whole?: The recommendations have been developed in a fair way

- There were notable differences by gender: women were more likely to *strongly agree* than men, while men were more likely than women to *neither agree nor disagree* or *disagree*.
- There were limited differences by age, with no strong pattern.
- While *agreement* dominated across all ethnic groups, the White Scottish/British group included a notable minority expressing reservations.

			Gender			
			In another way	Man	Woman	Total
Agreement level: The recommendations have been developed in a fair way	Strongly disagree	Count	0	2	1	3
	% within Gender		0%	7.4%	2.6%	4.5%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	4	0	4
	% within Gender		0%	14.8%	0%	6%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	1	2	3
	% within Gender		0%	3.7%	5.3%	4.5%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	13	20	34
	% within Gender		50%	48.1%	52.6%	50.7%
	Strongly agree	Count	1	7	15	23
	% within Gender		50%	25.9%	39.5%	34.3%
Total	Count	2	27	38	67	

	% within Gender	100%	100%	100%	100%
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There were some differences by gender. Women showed higher rates of **strong agreement** (39.5%, n=15) compared to men (25.9%, n=7). Combined *agreement* (*tend to agree* + *strongly agree*) was over 90% for both groups, but men showed slightly higher rates of *disagreement*: 14.8% *tended to disagree* and 7.4% *strongly disagreed*, compared to none among women.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: The recommendations have been developed in a fair way	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	1	2	0	0	3
	% within Age group		0%	0%	4.5%	8.7%	0%	0%	4.5%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	2	1	1	0	4
	% within Age group		0%	0%	9.1%	4.3%	8.3%	0%	6%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	2	0	0	1	3
	% within Age group		0%	0%	9.1%	0%	0%	33.3%	4.5%
	Tend to agree	Count	2	2	9	13	7	1	34
	% within Age group		50%	66.7%	40.9%	56.5%	58.3%	33.3%	50.7%
	Strongly agree	Count	2	1	8	7	4	1	23
	% within Age group		50%	33.3%	36.4%	30.4%	33.3%	33.3%	34.3%
	Total	Count	4	3	22	23	12	3	67
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were limited differences by age: across all age bands, the majority *agreed*, showing overall positive sentiment. *Disagreement* and *neither agree nor disagree* were rare but slightly more common in the 30-44 (13.6%, n=3 *disagreement*, 9.1%, n=2 *neither agree nor disagree*) and 45-64 brackets (13%, n=3 *disagreement*, 4.3%, n=1 *neither agree nor disagree*).

			Ethnicity				
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	Total
Agreement level: The recommendations have been developed in a fair way	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	3	3
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	5.2%	4.5%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	4	4
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	6.9%	6%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	0	3	3
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	5.2%	4.5%
	Tend to agree	Count	2	1	3	28	34
	% within Ethnicity		100%	50%	60%	48.3%	50.7%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	1	2	20	23
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	40%	34.5%	34.3%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	58	67
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some differences by ethnicity in views on whether the recommendations were developed in a fair way, though overall *agreement* remained high. All ethnic minority respondents *tend to agree* or *strongly agree*. The White Scottish/British ($n=58$), had the widest spread of responses: 48.3% ($n=28$) selected *tend to agree*, 34.5% ($n=20$) *strongly agree* and the remainder selected *neither agree nor disagree* (5.2%) or *disagreed* (11.1%, $n=7$). These figures suggest that **while agreement dominated across all ethnic groups, the White Scottish/British group included a notable minority expressing reservations.**

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the Assembly as a whole, and about your experience as a whole?: The overarching statements have been developed in a fair way

- There were notable differences by gender: women and those identifying in another way were more likely to *strongly agree* than men, while men were more likely than women to *neither agree nor disagree or disagree*.
- *Agreement* was high across all age groups, with over 70% selecting either *tend to agree* or *strongly agree* in each group except those aged 75+.
- There were some differences by ethnicity, though patterns were not entirely consistent.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Agreement level: The overarching statements have been developed in a fair way	Strongly disagree	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	3.4%	0%	1.4%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	4	2	6
	% within Gender		0%	13.8%	5.3%	8.7%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	4	3	7
	% within Gender		0%	13.8%	7.9%	10.1%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	13	16	30
	% within Gender		50%	44.8%	42.1%	43.5%
	Strongly agree	Count	1	7	17	25
	% within Gender		50%	24.1%	44.7%	36.2%
	Total	Count	2	29	38	69
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some differences by gender in perceptions of fairness in how the overarching statements were developed. Women and those identifying in another way were the most likely to *strongly agree* (44.7%, n=17 for women, 50%, n=1 for those identifying in another way), compared to 24.1% (n=7) of men. **Men were also slightly more likely to select *tend to disagree* (13.8%) and *neither agree nor disagree* (13.8%), suggesting some ambivalence.**

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: The overarching statements have been developed in a fair way	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	4.5%	0%	0%	0%	1.4%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	2	3	1	0	6
	% within Age group		0%	0%	9.1%	12.5%	8.3%	0%	8.7%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	3	3	0	1	7
	% within Age group		0%	0%	13.6%	12.5%	0%	25%	10.1%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	1	8	11	7	2	30
	% within Age group		25%	33.3%	36.4%	45.8%	58.3%	50%	43.5%
	Strongly agree	Count	3	2	8	7	4	1	25
	% within Age group		75%	66.7%	36.4%	29.2%	33.3%	25%	36.2%
	Total	Count	4	3	22	24	12	4	69
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were strong differences by age group in views on the fairness of overarching statement development. The **youngest respondents (19-24) were the most likely to strongly agree** (75%, n=3), whereas this dropped to just 25% among those aged 75+ (n=1), suggesting **more uncertainty in the oldest cohort**. The 30-44 and 45-64 age groups had relatively high proportions who chose either *tend to agree* (36.4%, n=4 and 45.8%, n=11 respectively) or *strongly agree* (36.4%, n=4 and 29.2%, n=7). Overall, *agreement* was high across all age groups, with over 70% selecting either *tend to agree* or *strongly agree* in each group except those aged 75+.

		Ethnicity				Total
		Asian, Asian	Black, Black Scottish/British,	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other	White Scottish/British	

			Scottish/ British	African or African Caribbean			
Agreement level: The overarching statements have been developed in a fair way	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	1.7%	1.4%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	6	6
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	10%	8.7%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	0	0	6	7
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	0%	10%	10.1%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	1	3	25	30
	% within Ethnicity		50%	50%	60%	41.7%	43.5%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	1	2	22	25
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	40%	36.7%	36.2%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	60	69
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some differences by ethnicity, though patterns were not entirely consistent. **While agreement was the majority view, there were hints that participants from ethnic minority backgrounds were less emphatic in their responses.** All participants from Asian or Black ethnic backgrounds selected either *neither agree nor disagree* or *tend to agree*, with no one in these groups choosing *strongly agree*. Among White Scottish/British participants, 41.7% (n=25) selected *tend to agree* and 36.7% (n=22) *strongly agree*. Notably, 10% (n=6) in this group selected *neither agree nor disagree*, and 1 person (1.7%) selected *strongly disagree*. Participants identifying as White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other had a similar split between *agreement* levels but were slightly more likely to *strongly agree* (40%, n=2).

SQ: *I support... None of the overarching statements, A few of the overarching statements, Most of the overarching statements, All of the overarching statements (select one)*

- There were some notable differences by gender for supportiveness level for the overarching statements: men were more likely to fall in the middle categories, while women were more polarised toward full support.
- There were some differences by age, though support was generally high.
- There were strong differences by ethnicity in levels of full support: White Scottish/British participants had the widest spread across support levels, while all ethnic minority participants supported at least *most of the overarching statements*.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Supportiveness level: Overarching statements	None of the overarching statements	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	3.4%	0%	1.5%
	A few of the overarching statements	Count	0	7	1	8
	% within Gender		0%	24.1%	2.9%	12.1%
	Most of the overarching statements	Count	1	16	16	33
	% within Gender		50%	55.2%	45.7%	50%
	All of the overarching statements	Count	1	5	18	24
	% within Gender		50%	17.2%	51.4%	36.4%
	Total	Count	2	29	35	66
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some notable differences by gender, particularly in the highest level of support. 50% of those identifying in another way supported *all of the overarching statements*. Among women, 51.4% (n=18) supported *all*, compared to only 17.2% (n=5) of men. Conversely, 24.1% (n=7) of men supported *only a few* of the overarching statements, compared to 2.9% (n=1) of women. **Men were more likely to fall in the middle categories, while women were more polarised toward full support.**

			Age						
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	Total
Supportiveness level:	None of the overarching statements	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	4.3%	0%	0%	1.5%
Overarching statements	A few of the overarching statements	Count	0	0	4	2	2	0	8
	% within Age group		0%	0%	19%	8.7%	18.2%	0%	12.1%
	Most of the overarching statements	Count	3	2	12	9	4	3	33
	% within Age group		75%	66.7%	57.1%	39.1%	36.4%	75%	50%
	All of the overarching statements	Count	1	1	5	11	5	1	24
	% within Age group		25%	33.3%	23.8%	47.8%	45.5%	25%	36.4%
	Total	Count	4	3	21	23	11	4	66
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some differences by age, though support was generally high. The youngest (19-24) and oldest (75+) participants were most likely to support *most* of the overarching statements (75% each, n=1 for 19-24, n=3 for 75+), while middle-aged participants (45-64) had the highest percentage selecting *all* (47.8%,

n=11). The 30-44 group had a more spread distribution, with 19% (n=4) selecting a *few* and 57.1% (n=12) *most*. The age group 25-29 was very positive overall, with 66.7% (n=2) selecting *most* and 33.3% (n=1) *all*.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish /British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	
Supportiveness level: Overarching statements	None of the overarching statements	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	1.8%	1.5%
	A few of the overarching statements	Count	0	0	0	8	8
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	14%	12.1%
	Most of the overarching statements	Count	2	2	1	28	33
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	20%	49.1%	50%
	All of the overarching statements	Count	0	0	4	20	24
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	80%	35.1%	36.4%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	57	66
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were strong differences by ethnicity in levels of full support. None of the Asian or Black participants selected *all of the overarching statements*—100% of them supported *most* instead. Meanwhile, 80% of White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other participants and 35.1% (n=20) of White Scottish/British selected *all*. White

Scottish/British participants had the widest spread across support levels, including all those who selected *a few* (14%, n=8) or *none* (1.8%, n=1).

SQ: *I support... None of the goals, A few of the goals, Most of the goals, All of the goals (select one)*

- There were strong gender differences in support for the goals: women and those identifying in another way were more likely to support *all* the goals than men, who were more likely to only support *most* or *a few of the goals*.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Supportive ness level: Goals	None of the goals	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	A few of the goals	Count	0	7	2	9
	% within Gender		0%	24.1%	5.4%	13.2%
	Most of the goals	Count	0	18	15	33
	% within Gender		0%	62.1%	40.5%	48.5%
	All of the goals	Count	2	4	20	26
	% within Gender		100%	13.8%	54.1%	38.2%
	Total	Count	2	29	37	68
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were strong gender differences in support for the goals. All those identifying in another way (n=2) and the majority of women (54.1%, n=20) supported *all of the goals*, compared to only 13.8% (n=4) of men. Men were most likely to support *most of the goals* (62.1%, n=18), while women were more split between *most* (40.5%, n=15) and *all* (54.1%, n=20).

	Age						Total
	19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	

Supportiveness level: Goals	None of the goals	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A few of the goals	Count	0	0	5	2	2	0	9
	% within Age group		0%	0%	23.8%	8.3%	16.7%	0%	13.2%
	Most of the goals	Count	2	3	8	12	4	4	33
	% within Age group		50%	100%	38.1%	50%	33.3%	100%	48.5%
	All of the goals	Count	2	0	8	10	6	0	26
	% within Age group		50%	0%	38.1%	41.7%	50%	0%	38.2%
	Total	Count	4	3	21	24	12	4	68
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were clear age-related differences in support for *all* goals. Support for *all of the goals* was highest among those aged 65-74 (50%, n=6) and 45-64 (41.7%, n=1). By contrast, no one aged 25-29 or 75+ selected *all*. Middle-aged participants were the most consistent in their support, while younger and older groups had more mixed views. The 30-44 age group had the highest share supporting a *few* (23.8%).

			Ethnicity				
			Asian, Asian Scottish /British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	Total
Supportiveness level: Goals	None of the goals	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A few of the	Count	0	0	0	9	9

goals							
% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	15.3%	13.2%	
Most of the goals	Count	1	2	2	28	33	
% within Ethnicity		50%	100%	40%	47.5%	48.5%	
All of the goals	Count	1	0	3	22	26	
% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	60%	37.3%	38.2%	
Total	Count	2	2	5	59	68	
% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	

There were observable ethnic differences in support for the goals. All minority ethnic participants supported either *most* or *all of the goals*, whereas White Scottish/British participants showed the most diverse distribution, with 15.3% (n=9) selecting *a few*, 47.5% (n=28) *most*, and 37.3% (n=22) *all*. White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other participants were the most likely to support *all of the goals*.

SQ: I support...(select one)

- There were strong differences by gender in levels of support for the recommendations; men were more likely to express lower levels of support than women.
- Though most participants in each age group supported *most* or *all* of the recommendations, the lowest levels of support came from the 30-44 group.
- There were some differences by ethnicity: all respondents across minority ethnic groups supported *most* or *all* of the recommendations while only White Scottish/British respondents expressed support for *a few*.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Supportive ness level:	None of the recommendations	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%

Recommendations	A few of the recommendations	Count	0	8	1	9
	% within Gender		0%	27.6%	2.6%	13%
	Most of the recommendations	Count	0	19	26	45
	% within Gender		0%	65.5%	68.4%	65.2%
	All of the recommendations	Count	2	2	11	15
	% within Gender		100%	6.9%	28.9%	21.7%
	Total	Count	2	29	38	69
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were strong differences by gender in levels of support for the recommendations. A majority of both men and women supported *most of the recommendations*—65.5% (n=19) and 68.4% (n=26), respectively. However, men were more likely to express lower levels of support, with 27.6% (n=8) selecting *a few* and only 6.9% (n=2) selecting *all*. In contrast, 28.9% (n=11) of women supported *all of the recommendations*, and just 2.6% (n=1) supported *a few*. Both individuals identifying in another way supported *all* recommendations (100%).

			Age					Total	
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74		75+
Supportiveness level: Recommendations	None of the recommendations	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	
	A few of the recommendations	Count	0	0	4	3	2	0	9
	% within Age group		0%	0%	18.2%	12.5%	16.7%	0%	13%
	Most of the recommendations	Count	2	3	16	15	5	4	45

	% within Age group	50%	100%	72.7%	62.5%	41.7%	100%	65.2%	
	All of the recommendations	Count	2	0	2	6	5	0	15
	% within Age group	50%	0%	9.1%	25%	41.7%	0%	21.7%	
	Total	Count	4	3	22	24	12	4	69
	% within Age group	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	

Support levels varied by age group, though most participants supported *most* or *all* of the recommendations. The youngest group (25-29) showed unanimous support for *most*, while the 19-24 and 65-74 groups were evenly split between *most* and *all*. Those aged 45-64 were more cautious, with 62.5% (n=15) selecting *most* and 25% (n=6) *all*, and some (12.5%, n=3) selecting *a few*. The lowest levels of full support came from the 30-44 group, where 72.7% (n=16) supported *most*, but only 9.1% (n=2) *all*, and 18.2% (n=4) selected *a few*.

			Ethnicity				
			Asian, Asian Scottish /British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	Total
Supportiveness level: Recommendations	None of the recommendations	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A few of the recommendations	Count	0	0	0	9	9
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	15%	13%
	Most of the recommendations	Count	1	2	4	38	45
	% within Ethnicity		50%	100%	80%	63.3%	65.2%
	All of the	Count	1	0	1	13	15

	recommendations						
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	20%	21.7%	21.7%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	60	69
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were **some differences by ethnicity, but a clear pattern of high support overall**. All respondents across minority ethnic groups supported *most* or *all* of the recommendations. Notably, only White Scottish/British respondents expressed support for *a few* (15%, n=9).

SQ: Thinking back to the goals and recommendations produced in the Assembly report, do you support

- Women were more likely to support all of the goals than men, while men were more evenly distributed across levels of support.
- Overall, support was high across all ages, but the younger and older groups showed the highest concentration of respondents fully endorsing the goals.
- There were no strong differences in views by ethnicity, with a majority in each group supporting most or all of the goals.

			Gender			
			In another way	Man	Woman	Total
Supportive ness level: goals produced in the Assembly report	None of the goals	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	4.5%	0%	2%
	A few of the goals	Count	0	5	0	5
	% within Gender		0%	22.7%	0%	9.8%
	Most of the goals	Count	0	11	17	28
	% within Gender		0%	50%	60.7%	54.9%
	All of the goals	Count	1	5	11	17
	% within Gender		100%	22.7%	39.3%	33.3%

	Total	Count	1	22	28	51
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were clear gender differences in how participants viewed the goals produced in the Assembly report. **Women were more likely to support *all of the goals* (39.3%, n=11) than men (22.7%, n=5), while men were more evenly distributed across levels of support.** For example, 50% (n=11) of men supported *most* of the goals compared to 60.7% (n=17) of women, and 22.7% (n=5) of men supported *a few*, whereas no women did. One man (4.5%) selected *none*, and both individuals identifying *in another way* split between *most* and *all*.

			Age						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Supportiveness level: goals produced in the Assembly report	None of the goals	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	4.5%	0%	0%	2%
	A few of the goals	Count	0	0	1	3	1	0	5
	% within Age group		0%	0%	8.3%	13.6%	14.3%	0%	9.8%
	Most of the goals	Count	1	2	6	14	3	2	28
	% within Age group		20%	100%	50%	63.6%	42.9%	66.7%	54.9%
	All of the goals	Count	4	0	5	4	3	1	17
	% within Age group		80%	0%	41.7%	18.2%	42.9%	33.3%	33.3%
	Total	Count	5	2	12	22	7	3	51
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some differences by age group in levels of support for the goals produced in the assembly report, though no clear linear pattern was evident. **Overall, support was high across all ages, but the younger and older groups showed the highest concentration of respondents fully endorsing the goals.**

The group aged 19-24 leaned heavily towards *all of the goals* (80%, n=4), as did 42.9% of the 65-74 group and 41.7% of those aged 30-44.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/British	Black, Black Scottish/British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other	White Scottish/British	
Supportiveness level: goals produced in the Assembly report	None of the goals	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	2.2%	2%
	A few of the goals	Count	0	0	0	5	5
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	11.1%	9.8%
	Most of the goals	Count	1	1	1	25	28
	% within Ethnicity		50%	50%	50%	55.6%	54.9%
	All of the goals	Count	1	1	1	14	17
	% within Ethnicity		50%	50%	50%	31.1%	33.3%
	Total	Count	2	2	2	45	51
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no strong differences in views by ethnicity on the extent to which the goals produced in the assembly report were supported. **Overall, across all groups, support was relatively high, with a majority in each group supporting *most or all of the goals*.** Among White Scottish/British respondents, 55.6% (n=25) supported *most of the goals* and 31.1% (n=14) supported *all of the goals*. Among all other ethnic groups, exactly 50% selected *most of the goals* and the remaining 50% selected *all of the goals*.

SQ: Thinking back to the goals and recommendations produced in the Assembly report, do you support

- There were strong differences by gender in support for the recommendations produced in the assembly report: women and those identifying in another way were more likely to show higher levels of support than men
- Some differences were observed by age group, with younger respondents generally showing higher support.
- There were no clear patterns of difference by ethnicity in support for the assembly's recommendations.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Supportive ness level: recommen dations produced in the Assembly report	None of the recommendations	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	4.5%	0%	2%
	A few of the recommendations	Count	0	7	1	8
	% within Gender		0%	31.8%	3.6%	15.7%
	Most of the recommendations	Count	0	13	20	33
	% within Gender		0%	59.1%	71.4%	64.7%
	All of the recommendations	Count	1	1	7	9
	% within Gender		100%	4.5%	25%	17.6%
	Total	Count	1	22	28	51
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were strong differences by gender in support for the recommendations produced in the assembly report. A large majority of women supported *most of the recommendations* (71.4%, n=20), while only 59.1% (n=13) of men did the same. Conversely, men were much more likely to report lower levels of support: 31.8% (n=7) selected *a few of the recommendations* compared with just 3.6% of women,

and one man (4.5%, n=1) selected *none of the recommendations*. Support among respondents identifying *in another way* was split evenly between *most* and *all of the recommendations* (50% each).

			Age					Total	
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74		75+
Supportiveness level: recommendations produced in the Assembly report	None of the recommendations	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	4.5%	0%	0%	2%
	A few of the recommendations	Count	0	0	2	5	1	0	8
	% within Age group		0%	0%	16.7%	22.7%	14.3%	0%	15.7%
	Most of the recommendations	Count	3	2	8	12	6	2	33
	% within Age group		60%	100%	66.7%	54.5%	85.7%	66.7%	64.7%
	All of the recommendations	Count	2	0	2	4	0	1	9
	% within Age group		40%	0%	16.7%	18.2%	0%	33.3%	17.6%
	Total	Count	5	2	12	22	7	3	51
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Some differences were observed by age group, with younger respondents generally showing higher support. The proportion supporting *most of the recommendations* was highest among those aged 65-74 (85.7%, n=6) and 25-29 (100%, n=2), and lowest among those aged 30-44 (66.7%, n=8) and 45-64 (54.5%, n=12). Support for *all of the recommendations* was relatively low across all groups, with the highest proportion in the 19-24 group (40%, n=2) and lowest among 25-29 (0%). A small number of respondents in the 45-64 group (4.5%, n=1) chose *none of the recommendations*.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish /British	Black, Black Scottish/British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish /Gypsy Traveller/Other	White Scottish /British	
Supportiveness level: recommendations produced in the Assembly report	None of the recommendations	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	2.2%	2%
	A few of the recommendations	Count	0	0	0	8	8
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	17.8%	15.7%
	Most of the recommendations	Count	2	1	2	28	33
	% within Ethnicity		100%	50%	100%	62.2%	64.7%
	All of the recommendations	Count	0	1	0	8	9
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	0%	17.8%	17.6%
	Total	Count	2	2	2	45	51
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no clear patterns of difference by ethnicity in support for the assembly’s recommendations. Most respondents in each group supported *most of the recommendations*, with the highest proportions among White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other (100%, n=2) and Asian, Asian Scottish/British (100%, n=2).

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the Assembly as a whole, and about your experience as a whole?: I am confident that the Assembly report will be taken seriously by Parliament and political parties

- There were no notable gender differences in participants' confidence that the assembly report would be taken seriously by Parliament and political parties.
- There were some differences across age groups in levels of confidence, with older age groups generally showing more uncertainty or scepticism.
- There were some differences in confidence across ethnic groups, though the patterns were not entirely consistent.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Agreement level: I am confident that the Assembly report will be taken seriously by Parliament and political parties	Strongly disagree	Count	0	2	0	2
	% within Gender		0%	9.1%	0%	3.9%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	4.5%	0%	2%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	6	10	16
	% within Gender		0%	27.3%	35.7%	31.4%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	8	13	22
	% within Gender		100%	36.4%	46.4%	43.1%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	5	5	10
	% within Gender		0%	22.7%	17.9%	19.6%
	Total	Count	1	22	28	51
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no strong notable gender differences in participants' confidence that the assembly report would be taken seriously by Parliament and political parties, **though women were slightly more likely to be confident than men.** Among men, 36.4% (n=8) *tended to agree* and 22.7% (n=5) *strongly agreed*, while among women, 46.4% (n=13) *tended to agree* and 17.9% (n=5) *strongly agreed*. Neutral responses were fairly common, with 27.3% (n=6) of men and 35.7% (n=10) of women selecting

neither agree nor disagree. Only 13.6% (n=3) of men expressed any level of *disagreement*, and no women *strongly disagreed*.

			Age group					Total	
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74		75+
Agreement level: I am confident that the Assembly report will be taken seriously by Parliament and political parties	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	2	1	0	0	3
	% within Age group		0%	0%	11.1%	4.5%	0%	0%	4.9%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	10%	0%	1.6%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	1	4	9	3	2	20
	% within Age group		25%	33.3%	22.2%	40.9%	30%	50%	32.8%
	Tend to agree	Count	3	2	9	8	5	0	27
	% within Age group		75%	66.7%	50%	36.4%	50%	0%	44.3%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	3	4	1	2	10
	% within Age group		0%	0%	16.7%	18.2%	10%	50%	16.4%
	Total	Count	4	3	18	22	10	4	61
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some differences across age groups in levels of confidence, with older age groups generally showing more uncertainty or scepticism. Support was highest among those aged 19-24 and 25-29, where 75% (n=3) and 66.7% (n=2), respectively, *tended to agree*. Meanwhile, older groups such as 45-64 and 65-74 had lower agreement. The age group 75+ had the lowest level of *agreement*, with only 50% (n=2) *strongly agreeing* and none *tending to agree*. Across all ages, *neither agree nor disagree* responses were relatively common (proportions ranging from 22.2% to 50%), and *strongly disagree* was selected most frequently by 30-44-year-olds (11.1%, n=2).

		Ethnicity
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			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/B ritish, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Poli sh/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	Total
Agreement level: I am confident that the Assembly report will be taken seriously by Parliament and political parties	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	3	3
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	5.7%	4.9%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	1.9%	1.6%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	3	17	20
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	60%	32.1%	32.8%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	1	1	24	27
	% within Ethnicity		100%	50%	20%	45.3%	44.3%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	1	1	8	10
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	20%	15.1%	16.4%
	Total	Count	1	2	5	53	61
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some differences in confidence across ethnic groups, though the patterns were not entirely consistent. Strong agreement was most prevalent among White Scottish/British participants (15.1%, n=8) and participants identifying as Black, Black Scottish/British, African or African Caribbean (50%, n=1). *Tend to agree* was the most common response for White Scottish/British (45.3%, n=24), while 60% (n=3) of those identifying as White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other selected *neither agree nor disagree*. *Strongly disagree* was selected only by White Scottish/British participants (5.7%, n=3). Overall, confidence was generally moderate, with most participants selecting *tend to agree* or *neither agree nor disagree*.

RQ: Outcomes: Do PMIMG feel a personal impact (e.g. a change in attitude or view on a topic, confidence, or sense of political agency), as a result of participation in the CA?

SQ: To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: I think my opinion is as valid as anyone else's

- Women were slightly more likely to report a positive shift, while men showed more variability, including stronger declines.
- There were some differences by age group in how agreement changed: positive changes (+1 or +2) were more common in the 45-64 group and among 19-24 year olds than other age groups.
- There were some differences by ethnicity, but no strong patterns overall.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Change in agreement with the statement: 'I think my opinion is as valid as anyone else's'	-4	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		N/A	0%	0%	0%
	-3	Count	0	2	0	2
	% within Gender		N/A	11.8%	0%	5.1%
	-2	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		N/A	5.9%	0%	2.6%
	-1	Count	0	2	2	4
	% within Gender		N/A	11.8%	9.1%	10.3%
	0	Count	0	10	13	23
	% within Gender		N/A	58.8%	59.1%	59%
	1	Count	0	1	7	8
	% within Gender		N/A	5.9%	31.8%	20.5%
	2	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		N/A	5.9%	0%	2.6%
	3	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		N/A	0%	0%	0%
	4	Count	0	0	0	0

	% within Gender		N/A	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	0	17	22	39
	% within Gender		N/A	100%	100%	100%

There were some differences by gender in changes in agreement with the statement “I think my opinion is as valid as anyone else’s”, particularly in terms of increases. **Overall, women were slightly more likely to report a positive shift, while men showed more variability, including stronger declines.** A majority of both women (59.1%, n=13) and men (n=10, 58.8%) reported no change (0), but women were more likely to report a small increase (+1), with 31.8% doing so compared to just 5.9% of men. No women reported a decrease of more than one point, whereas 11.8% (n=2) of men reported a drop of -3.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Change in agreement with the statement: 'I think my opinion is as valid as anyone else's'	-4	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	-3	Count	0	0	0	1	1	0	2
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	6.2%	16.7%	0%	5.1%
	-2	Count	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	16.7%	0%	2.6%
	-1	Count	0	2	1	0	0	1	4
	% within Age group		0%	100%	11.1%	0%	0%	33.3%	10.3%
	0	Count	1	0	7	9	4	2	23
	% within Age group		33.3%	0%	77.8%	56.2%	66.7%	66.7%	59%
	1	Count	1	0	1	6	0	0	8
	% within Age group		33.3%	0%	11.1%	37.5%	0%	0%	20.5%
	2	Count	1	0	0	0	0	0	1

	% within Age group	33.3%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	2.6%
3	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
4	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Total	Count	3	2	9	16	6	3	39
	% within Age group	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some differences by age group in how agreement changed, but no clear age-related pattern emerged. In most groups, a majority reported no change (0). Positive changes (+1 or +2) were common in the 45-64 group (37.5% n=6 reported +1) and among 19-24 year olds (33.3% n=1 reported +1 and 33.3% n=1 reported +2). The 25-29 and 75+ groups showed more people reporting a decrease (-1 or -3), though numbers were small. Overall, across all age groups, 59% experienced no change, 23.1% reported an increase, and 17.9% a decrease, with modest fluctuations by age.

			Ethnicity				
			Asian, Asian Scottish/British	Black, Black African Caribbean	Black Scottish/British, or African	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other	White Scottish/British
Change in agreement with the statement: 'I think my opinion is as valid as anyone else's'	-4	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	-3	Count	0	0	0	2	2
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	5.9%	5.1%
	-2	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	2.9%	2.6%
	-1	Count	1	0	0	3	4

% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	0%	8.8%	10.3%
0	Count	1	0	2	20	23
% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	100%	58.8%	59%
1	Count	0	1	0	7	8
% within Ethnicity		0%	100%	0%	20.6%	20.5%
2	Count	0	0	0	1	1
% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	2.9%	2.6%
3	Count	0	0	0	0	0
% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
4	Count	0	0	0	0	0
% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Total	Count	2	1	2	34	39
% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some differences by ethnicity, although sample sizes were small. Most participants across all ethnic groups reported no change (0), including 58.8% of White Scottish/British participants and 100% of those in the White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other group. A positive shift of +1 was seen in 20.6% of White Scottish/British participants and 100% of the one Black participant. Only White Scottish/British respondents reported changes of -3, -2, or +2, although again this may reflect the higher number of respondents in this group. Overall, 59% of all participants saw no change, 23.1% reported an increase, and 17.9% reported a decrease.

SQ: To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: I enjoy participating in discussions and debates

- There were no strong differences by gender in how participants' agreement with "I enjoy participating in discussions and debates" changed after the assembly.
- There were some differences by age group, but no clear overall pattern.
- In terms of ethnicity, there was a modest trend towards stability, with slightly more White participants reporting either decrease or increase compared to other ethnic groups.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Change in agreement with statement: I enjoy participating in discussions and debates	-4	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		N/A	0%	0%	0%
	-3	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		N/A	0%	0%	0%
	-2	Count	0	0	1	1
	% within Gender		N/A	0%	4.3%	2.6%
	-1	Count	0	6	5	11
	% within Gender		N/A	37.5%	21.7%	28.2%
	0	Count	0	6	11	17
	% within Gender		N/A	37.5%	47.8%	43.6%
	1	Count	0	3	5	8
	% within Gender		N/A	18.8%	21.7%	20.5%
	2	Count	0	1	1	2
	% within Gender		N/A	6.2%	4.3%	5.1%
	3	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		N/A	0%	0%	0%
	4	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		N/A	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	0	16	23	39
	% within Gender		N/A	100%	100%	100%

There were **no strong differences by gender** in how participants' agreement with "I enjoy participating in discussions and debates" changed after the assembly. The most common response across all genders was *no change*, selected by 43.6% overall, including 47.8% of women (n=11) and 37.5% of men (n=6). A minority in each group reported *increased agreement*, with +1 reported by **21.7% of women** (n=5) and 18.8% of men (n=3). *Decreased agreement* was also low.

Age group		

			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	Total
Change in agreement with statement: I enjoy participating in discussions and debates	-4	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	-3	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	-2	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	5.9%	0%	0%	2.6%
	-1	Count	0	1	3	4	1	2	11
	% within Age group		0%	50%	33.3%	23.5%	20%	66.7%	28.2%
	0	Count	3	0	4	7	2	1	17
	% within Age group		100%	0%	44.4%	41.2%	40%	33.3%	43.6%
	1	Count	0	0	1	5	2	0	8
	% within Age group		0%	0%	11.1%	29.4%	40%	0%	20.5%
	2	Count	0	1	1	0	0	0	2
	% within Age group		0%	50%	11.1%	0%	0%	0%	5.1%
	3	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	4	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	3	2	9	17	5	3	39
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were **some differences by age group**, but no clear overall pattern. Agreement remained stable for most participants, with *no change* most frequently selected in all age groups except 25-29. *No change* was reported by 66.7% of 19-24s (2 of 3), 44.4% of 30-44s (4 of 9), 41.2% of 45-64s (7 of 17), and 50% of

65-74s (2 of 4). Only the 25-29 and 75+ age groups showed *no one reporting no change*. Notably, -1 responses were reported across all age groups, most commonly by 66.7% of 75+ (2 of 3) and 50% of 25-29s (1 of 2). Instances of *increased agreement* (e.g. +1 or +2) were scattered, but highest among 65-74s, where 40% (2 of 5) reported +1. This suggests a mix of experiences across ages, with no group showing a uniform shift in enjoyment of discussion.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/British	Black, Black Scottish/British, African African Caribbean	Black or	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other	
Change in agreement with statement: I enjoy participating in discussions and debates	-4	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	-3	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	-2	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	2.9%	2.6%
	-1	Count	0	0	1	10	11
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	50%	29.4%	28.2%
	0	Count	1	1	0	15	17
	% within Ethnicity		50%	100%	0%	44.1%	43.6%
	1	Count	1	0	1	6	8
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	50%	17.6%	20.5%
	2	Count	0	0	0	2	2
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	5.9%	5.1%
	3	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	4	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Total	Count	2	1	2	34	39	

	% within Ethnicity	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
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There were **notable differences by ethnicity**, particularly in the distribution of *no change* and *increased agreement*. *No change* was most common amongst all age groups except White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other, who were evenly (50%, n=1) split between *increased agreement* of +1 and *decreased agreement* of -1. *Decreased agreement* of -1 was also reported by 29.4% (n=10) White Scottish/British respondents. Overall, there was a modest trend towards stability, with slightly more White participants reporting either *decrease* or *increase* compared to minoritised ethnic groups.

SQ: To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: I feel comfortable challenging someone's opinion during a conversation

- There were some differences by gender in comfortability challenging someone's opinion - there was a slight trend towards increased confidence among women and decreased or unchanged confidence among men.
- There were notable differences by age: most participants reported either no change or a small increase, while all participants over 75 reported a decrease in confidence.
- There were some differences by ethnicity, but no consistent patterns.

			Gender			
			In another way	Man	Woman	Total
Change in agreement with statement: I feel comfortable challenging someone's opinion during a conversation	-4	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		N/A	0%	0%	0%
	-3	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		N/A	0%	0%	0%
	-2	Count	0	0	1	1
	% within Gender		N/A	0%	4.3%	2.5%
	-1	Count	0	6	6	12
	% within Gender		N/A	35.3%	26.1%	30%
	0	Count	0	8	8	16
	% within Gender		N/A	47.1%	34.8%	40%

	1	Count	0	2	6	8
	% within Gender		N/A	11.8%	26.1%	20%
	2	Count	0	1	1	2
	% within Gender		N/A	5.9%	4.3%	5%
	3	Count	0	0	1	1
	% within Gender		N/A	0%	4.3%	2.5%
	4	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		N/A	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	0	17	23	40
	% within Gender		N/A	100%	100%	100%

There were **some differences by gender** in reported increases in confidence, though patterns were not consistent. The most common response among both men and women was *no change*, reported by 47.1% of men (n=8) and 34.8% of women (n=8), suggesting a relatively stable sense of comfort overall. However, *increased agreement* was notably more common among women: +1 was reported by 26.1% (n=6), compared to 11.8% of men (2). *Decreased agreement* was higher among men, with -1 selected by 35.3% (n=6), versus 26.1% of women (n=6). These results indicate a **slight trend towards increased confidence among women and decreased or unchanged confidence among men.**

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Change in agreement with statement: I feel comfortable challenging someone's opinion during a	-4	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	-3	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	-2	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	5.9%	0%	0%	2.5%
-1	Count	0	0	3	4	2	3	12	

conversion	% within Age group		0%	0%	33.3%	23.5%	33.3%	100%	30%
	0	Count	2	0	4	7	3	0	16
	% within Age group		66.7%	0%	44.4%	41.2%	50%	0%	40%
	1	Count	1	1	2	3	1	0	8
	% within Age group		33.3%	50%	22.2%	17.6%	16.7%	0%	20%
	2	Count	0	1	0	1	0	0	2
	% within Age group		0%	50%	0%	5.9%	0%	0%	5%
	3	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	5.9%	0%	0%	2.5%
	4	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	3	2	9	17	6	3	40
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were **notable differences by age**, particularly in the youngest and oldest groups. *No change* was the most common response across all age groups except for 25-29 and 75+, suggesting overall stability. *No change* was reported by 66.7% of 19-24s (n=3), 44.4% of 30-44s (n=4), 41.2% of 45-64s (n=7), and 50% of 65-74s (n=3). In contrast, 100% of 75+ (n=3) reported *-1*, indicating a clear drop in confidence among that small group. *Increased agreement* was modest but occurred in all groups except 75+: *+1* was highest among 25-29s (n=1; 50%), and *+2* was seen in two groups (25-29 and 45-64). Overall, most participants reported either no change or a small increase, though there was a notable decline among the oldest group.

	Ethnicity				Total
	Asian, Asian	Black, Scottish/British , African	Black or Traveller/	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ British	

		Scottish/ British	African Caribbean	Other		
Change in agreement with statement: I feel comfortable challenging someone's opinion during a conversation	-4	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%
	-3	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%
	-2	Count	0	0	1	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	50%	0%
	-1	Count	0	0	1	11
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	50%	31.4%
	0	Count	2	0	0	14
	% within Ethnicity		100%	0%	0%	40%
	1	Count	0	1	0	7
	% within Ethnicity		0%	100%	0%	20%
	2	Count	0	0	0	2
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	5.7%
	3	Count	0	0	0	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	2.9%
	4	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	2	1	2	35
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were **some differences by ethnicity, but no consistent patterns**. *No change* was the most common response for most groups, reported by 100% of Asian Scottish/British (n=2), 40% of White Scottish/British (n=14), and 50% of White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other (n=1). *Decreased agreement* (-1) was seen in 31.4% of White Scottish/British (n=11), and one White Irish/Other participant (50%). *Increased agreement* was present in all groups except Black Scottish/British participants (who had no respondents indicating a change). Among White Scottish/British, +1 was selected by 20% (n=7), and +2 by 5.7% (n=2). -2 was

reported only by a single White Irish/Other participant. These patterns suggest moderate shifts in confidence, with most participants in each group either maintaining their level or slightly increasing it, and declines primarily among White Scottish/British.

SQ: To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: I feel nervous speaking in front of a group

- There were some notable differences between men and women: a greater proportion of men remained unchanged compared to women.
- Decreases in nerves were only observed in the 65-74 and 45-64 age group, reflecting reduced nervousness. Increases in nerves were observed in all groups except 75+, especially 30-44s.
- By ethnicity, change was limited, but where it occurred, it skewed toward increased nervousness in minority groups and decreased nervousness among the White Scottish/British group.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Change in agreement with statement: I feel nervous speaking in front of a group	-4	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		N/A	0%	0%	0%
	-3	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		N/A	5.9%	0%	2.6%
	-2	Count	0	0	2	2
	% within Gender		N/A	0%	9.1%	5.1%
	-1	Count	0	5	2	7
	% within Gender		N/A	29.4%	9.1%	17.9%
	0	Count	0	10	9	19
	% within Gender		N/A	58.8%	40.9%	48.7%
	1	Count	0	1	5	6
	% within Gender		N/A	5.9%	22.7%	15.4%
	2	Count	0	0	3	3
	% within Gender		N/A	0%	13.6%	7.7%

	3	Count	0	0	1	1
	% within Gender		N/A	0%	4.5%	2.6%
	4	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		N/A	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	0	17	22	39
	% within Gender		N/A	100%	100%	100%

There were some notable differences between men and women in changes in agreement with the statement “*I feel nervous speaking in front of a group*”. **Overall, most participants reported *no change in agreement*, but a greater proportion of men remained unchanged (58.8%, n=10) compared to women (40.9%, n=9).** A notable share of women reported *increased agreement* (i.e. greater nervousness), with 22.7% (n=5) increasing by +1 and 13.6% (n=3) by +2. In contrast, only 5.9% (n=1) of men increased by +1, and none increased by +2. A larger proportion of men (29.4%, n=5) decreased by -1, suggesting reduced nervousness, compared to just 9.1% (n=2) of women. Overall, women were more likely than men to become more nervous over the course of the assembly.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Change in agreement with statement: I feel nervous speaking in front of a group	-4	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	-3	Count	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	33.3%	2.6%
	-2	Count	0	0	0	2	0	0	2
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	12.5%	0%	0%	5.1%
	-1	Count	0	0	0	3	4	0	7
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	18.8%	66.7%	0%	17.9%
0	Count	1	1	5	9	1	2	19	

	% within Age group	33.3%	50%	55.6%	56.2%	16.7%	66.7%	48.7%
1	Count	1	0	4	1	0	0	6
	% within Age group	33.3%	0%	44.4%	6.2%	0%	0%	15.4%
2	Count	0	1	0	1	1	0	3
	% within Age group	0%	50%	0%	6.2%	16.7%	0%	7.7%
3	Count	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	% within Age group	33.3%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	2.6%
4	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Total	Count	3	2	9	16	6	3	39
	% within Age group	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Patterns by age group suggest older participants were more likely to report reduced nervousness, while younger participants either showed no change or slight increases. The majority across all age groups reported 0 change (48.7% overall), especially those aged 30-44 (55.6%, n=5) and 45-64 (56.2%, n=9). **However, -1 change was more common in those aged 65-74 (66.7%, n=4) and 45-64 (18.8%, n=3), reflecting reduced nervousness.** In contrast, younger participants in the 19-24 and 25-29 groups were more evenly split, with some reporting increases (+1 or +3) or decreases. Notably, only the 19-24 group showed a +3 change (33.3%, n=1), suggesting increased nervousness in one case. Those aged 30-44 had the highest share reporting +1 (44.4%, n=4).

	Ethnicity				Total
	Asian, Asian Scottish/British	Black, Black Scottish/British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other	White Scottish/British	

Change in agreement with statement: I feel nervous speaking in front of a group	-4	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	-3	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	2.9%	2.6%
	-2	Count	0	0	0	2	2
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	5.9%	5.1%
	-1	Count	0	0	0	7	7
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	20.6%	17.9%
	0	Count	1	0	1	17	19
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	50%	50%	48.7%
	1	Count	1	0	1	4	6
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	50%	11.8%	15.4%
	2	Count	0	1	0	2	3
	% within Ethnicity		0%	100%	0%	5.9%	7.7%
	3	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	2.9%	2.6%
	4	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	2	1	2	34	39
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Most ethnic groups showed stability in their feelings of nervousness, with 0 change being the most common response across all categories. Among White Scottish/British participants, 20.6% reported -1 change (less nervous), and 11.8% reported +1 (more nervous). In the smaller ethnic minority groups, patterns varied: both Asian and White Irish/Polish/Other participants were split between 0 and +1,

while Black participants exclusively reported +2. White Scottish/British participants were the only group to show a -3 change (2.9%), indicating a notable decrease in nervousness for one person. Overall, **change was limited, but where it occurred, it skewed toward increased nervousness in minority groups and decreased nervousness among the White Scottish/British group.**

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: This weekend has made me feel that I want to continue as an Assembly participant

- Women were more likely to remain unchanged, whereas both increases and declines in agreement were more common among men.
- There was a broad trend toward stability across age groups, while negative and positive changes scattered and did not follow a strong age-related pattern.
- Non-White participants expressed total attitudinal stability regarding wanting to continue as an assembly participant from the first to sixth weekends of the assembly, while White participants showed negative and positive shifts.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Change in agreement with statement: This weekend has made me feel that I want to continue as an Assembly participant	-4	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	4.5%	0%	1.9%
	-3	Count	0	1	1	2
	% within Gender		0%	4.5%	3.6%	3.8%
	-2	Count	0	3	1	4
	% within Gender		0%	13.6%	3.6%	7.7%
	-1	Count	0	3	5	8
	% within Gender		0%	13.6%	17.9%	15.4%
	0	Count	1	10	18	29
	% within Gender		100%	45.5%	64.3%	55.8%
	1	Count	0	4	2	6
	% within Gender		0%	18.2%	7.1%	11.5%

	2	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	3	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	4	Count	0	0	1	1
	% within Gender		0%	0%	3.6%	1.9%
	Total	Count	1	22	28	51
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

Most participants did not change in their level of agreement with the statement “*This weekend has made me feel that I want to continue as an Assembly participant*”, with 0 change reported by 55.8% overall. **Women were more likely to remain unchanged** (64.3%, n=18) compared to men (45.5%, n=10). Notably, **declines in agreement were more common among men**: 31.8% (n=7) reported a decrease (with proportions ranging from -1 to -3), compared with 25% (n=7) of women. **Increases were uncommon but slightly more frequent among men**: 18.2% reported +1, compared to 7.1% of women. Overall, women showed slightly more stability, while men were more divided between positive and negative shifts.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Change in agreement with statement: This weekend has made me feel that I want to continue as an Assembly participant	-4	Count	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	7.1%	0%	0%	0%	1.9%
	-3	Count	1	0	0	1	0	0	2
	% within Age group		25%	0%	0%	6.2%	0%	0%	3.8%
	-2	Count	0	0	2	2	0	0	4
	% within Age group		0%	0%	14.3%	12.5%	0%	0%	7.7%
	-1	Count	1	1	2	1	3	0	8
	% within Age group		25%	25%	14.3%	6.2%	30%	0%	15.4%
	0	Count	1	3	9	9	6	1	29
	% within Age group		25%	75%	64.3%	56.2%	60%	33.3%	55.8%

	1	Count	1	0	0	2	1	2	6
	% within Age group		25%	0%	0%	12.5%	10%	66.7%	11.5%
	2	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	4	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	6.2%	0%	0%	1.9%
	Total	Count	4	4	14	16	10	3	51
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There was a broad trend toward stability across age groups, with the majority in each category reporting 0 change in agreement (55.8% overall). This was especially true for those aged 25-29 (75%, n=3), 30-44 (64.3%, n=9), and 65-74 (60%, n=6). **Negative changes were more common in younger and middle-aged participants.** For instance, 25% (n=1) of those aged 19-24 and 30% (n=3) of those aged 65-74 reported -1 change, while -2 was reported most often by the 30-44 and 45-64 groups (14.3%, n=2 and 12.5%, n=2 respectively). Only one +4 response was recorded, in the 45-64 group. Positive shifts were scattered, with +1 seen in small numbers across age groups. Overall, responses indicated a strong baseline of interest in continuing, with only modest shifts in either direction.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/British	Black, Black Scottish/British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other	White Scottish/British	
Change in agreement with statement: This weekend has made me feel	-4	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	2.3%	1.9%
	-3	Count	0	0	0	2	2
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	4.7%	3.8%

that I want to continue as an Assembly participant	-2	Count	0	0	0	4	4
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	9.3%	7.7%
	-1	Count	0	0	2	6	8
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	50%	14%	15.4%
	0	Count	2	2	2	23	29
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	50%	53.5%	55.8%
	1	Count	0	0	0	6	6
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	14%	11.5%
	2	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	4	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	2.3%	1.9%
	Total	Count	2	2	4	43	51
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Patterns by ethnicity suggest strong consistency in agreement with wanting to continue as an assembly participant, particularly among Asian and Black, Black Scottish/British, African or African Caribbean participants, who unanimously reported 0 change. Among White Scottish/British and White Irish/Polish/Other participants, there was more variability: 53.5% (n=23) White Scottish/British participants showed 0 change, but nearly a third (30.3%, n=13) of participants agreement had weakened since the first assembly weekend (with participants showing change from -1 to -4). Only this group had any participants report increases, with 14% (n=6) at +1 and one person (2.3%) at +4. Overall, while most remained stable, White Scottish/British participants showed the widest range of opinion shifts, but this is likely due to the number of participants in this group.

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: Climate change is likely to have a big impact on people like me

- Most participants did not change their agreement level on this statement, with no change reported by 45.3% overall, though modest increases were also observed.
- There were no striking differences by gender. Similar proportions of men and women showed no change or increased agreement.
- There was general stability across age groups, though increased agreement was more common among those aged 30-44 or 45-64.
- In terms of ethnicity, non-White participants expressed total attitudinal stability alongside the majority of both White groups. Positive shifts were only seen among White Scottish/British participants.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Change in agreement with statement: Climate change is likely to have a big impact on people like me	-4	Count	0	0	0	0
		% within Gender	0%	0%	0%	0%
	-3	Count	0	0	1	1
		% within Gender	0%	0%	3.4%	1.9%
	-2	Count	0	0	0	0
		% within Gender	0%	0%	0%	0%
	-1	Count	0	4	5	9
		% within Gender	0%	17.4%	17.2%	17%
	0	Count	1	11	12	24
		% within Gender	100%	47.8%	41.4%	45.3%
	1	Count	0	4	8	12
		% within Gender	0%	17.4%	27.6%	22.6%
	2	Count	0	3	3	6
		% within Gender	0%	13%	10.3%	11.3%
	3	Count	0	1	0	1
		% within Gender	0%	4.3%	0%	1.9%

	4	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
Total	Count	1	23	29	53	
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no striking differences by gender. Most participants did not change their agreement level on this statement, with *no change* reported by 45.3% overall—particularly among men (47.8%, n=11) and women (41.4%, n=12). A notable portion showed *increased agreement*, with 37.9% (n=11) of women and 30.4% (n=7) of men reporting a positive shift (+1 or +2). Very few participants reduced their *agreement*, suggesting a modest overall increase in recognition of climate impact.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Change in agreement with statement: Climate change is likely to have a big impact on people like me	-4	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	-3	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	5.9%	0%	0%	1.9%
	-2	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	-1	Count	0	1	4	2	1	1	9
	% within Age group		0%	33.3%	23.5%	11.8%	10%	33.3%	17%
	0	Count	3	2	6	6	6	1	24
	% within Age group		100%	66.7%	35.3%	35.3%	60%	33.3%	45.3%
	1	Count	0	0	6	4	2	0	12
	% within Age group		0%	0%	35.3%	23.5%	20%	0%	22.6%
2	Count	0	0	1	4	0	1	6	

	% within Age group	0%	0%	5.9%	23.5%	0%	33.3%	11.3%
3	Count	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
	% within Age group	0%	0%	0%	0%	10%	0%	1.9%
4	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Total	Count	3	3	17	17	10	3	53
	% within Age group	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There was general stability across age groups, with 45.3% reporting *no change*, especially in the 19-24 (100%, n=3) and 25-29 (66.7%, n=2) groups. However, *increased agreement* (+1 or +2) was more common among those aged 30-44 or 45-64, with 41.2% (n=7) of 30-44 and 47% (n=8) of 45-64s *increasing agreement*. Only one person (5.9%) aged 45-64 reported a negative shift of -3.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/British	Black, Black Scottish/British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other	White Scottish/British	
Change in agreement with statement: Climate change is likely to have a big impact on people like me	-4	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	2.3%	1.9%
	-3	Count	0	0	0	2	2
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	4.7%	3.8%
	-2	Count	0	0	0	4	4
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	9.3%	7.7%
	-1	Count	0	0	2	6	8
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	50%	14%	15.4%

0	Count	2	2	2	23	29
% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	50%	53.5%	55.8%
1	Count	0	0	0	6	6
% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	14%	11.5%
2	Count	0	0	0	0	0
% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
3	Count	0	0	0	0	0
% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
4	Count	0	0	0	1	1
% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	2.3%	1.9%
Total	Count	2	2	4	43	51
% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

The pattern was largely consistent across ethnic groups, with **the majority in each group reporting *no change***—notably **100% (n=2) among Asian and Black participants**, and 53.5% (n=23) among White Scottish/British respondents. Positive shifts of +1 were seen among White Scottish/British participants (14%, n=6) but were absent in other groups. **Small negative changes (-1 to -3) were more frequent among White participants.** Overall, concern remained stable or grew slightly, especially among White respondents.

SQ: How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: The effects of climate change are felt equally by all groups of society

- While a plurality of both men and women did not change their agreement with this statement, overall men were more likely to become more sceptical while women leaned toward increased or stable agreement.
- Positive changes (+1 or more) were more common among 30-44 and 45-64-year-olds, while negative changes were most frequent in the 25-44 range.

- Some differences were observed by ethnicity, but with no clear pattern.

			Gender			
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Change in agreement with statement: The effects of climate change are felt equally by all groups of society	-4	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	4.3%	0%	2%
	-3	Count	0	2	1	3
	% within Gender		0%	8.7%	3.7%	5.9%
	-2	Count	0	3	2	5
	% within Gender		0%	13%	7.4%	9.8%
	-1	Count	0	5	2	7
	% within Gender		0%	21.7%	7.4%	13.7%
	0	Count	0	8	14	22
	% within Gender		0%	34.8%	51.9%	43.1%
	1	Count	0	0	5	5
	% within Gender		0%	0%	18.5%	9.8%
	2	Count	0	1	2	3
	% within Gender		0%	4.3%	7.4%	5.9%
	3	Count	1	2	1	4
	% within Gender		100%	8.7%	3.7%	7.8%
	4	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	4.3%	0%	2%
	Total	Count	1	23	27	51
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

A plurality of participants reported *no change* (43.1%), with this most common among women (51.9%, n=14). Women were also more likely to report an increase in agreement (+1 to +4) at 29.6% (n=8) compared to men (17.3%, n=4). Notably, **47.8% of men showed a decrease in agreement (-1 to -4), versus 18.5% of women.** This suggests a gender gap in shifting perceptions, with men becoming more sceptical and women leaning toward increased or stable agreement.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Change in agreement with statement: The effects of climate change are felt equally by all groups of society	-4	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	-3	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	5.9%	0%	0%	1.9%
	-2	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	-1	Count	0	1	4	2	1	1	9
	% within Age group		0%	33.3%	23.5%	11.8%	10%	33.3%	17%
	0	Count	3	2	6	6	6	1	24
	% within Age group		100%	66.7%	35.3%	35.3%	60%	33.3%	45.3%
	1	Count	0	0	6	4	2	0	12
	% within Age group		0%	0%	35.3%	23.5%	20%	0%	22.6%
	2	Count	0	0	1	4	0	1	6
	% within Age group		0%	0%	5.9%	23.5%	0%	33.3%	11.3%
	3	Count	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	10%	0%	1.9%
	4	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	3	3	17	17	10	3	53
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Agreement remained stable for 45.3% overall, particularly in the 19-24 (100%, n=3) and 25-29 (66.7%, n=2) age groups. **Positive changes (+1 or more) were more common among 30-64-year-olds, while negative changes were most frequent**

in the 25-44 range. For instance, 23.5% of 30-44s and 33.3% of 75+ participants reported a decrease (-1 or more). Overall, most participants saw no shift, though some older and younger adults became more critical of equality in climate impacts.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Scottish/British , African African Caribbean	Black or	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	
Change in agreement with statement: The effects of climate change are felt equally by all groups of society	-4	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	2.2%	2%
	-3	Count	1	0	0	2	3
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	0%	4.4%	5.9%
	-2	Count	0	0	0	5	5
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	11.1%	9.8%
	-1	Count	0	0	1	6	7
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	33.3%	13.3%	13.7%
	0	Count	0	1	1	20	22
	% within Ethnicity		0%	100%	33.3%	44.4%	43.1%
	1	Count	0	0	0	5	5
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	11.1%	9.8%
	2	Count	0	0	0	3	3
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	6.7%	5.9%
	3	Count	1	0	1	2	4
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	33.3%	4.4%	7.8%
	4	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	2.2%	2%
	Total	Count	2	1	3	45	51
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

A plurality of participants in the White Scottish/British (44.4%, n=20) and Black Scottish/British (100%, n=1) groups reported *no change*. White Irish/Polish/Gypsy/Other respondents were split across increases and decreases. Overall, the data indicate some declining belief in the equity of climate impacts—especially among Asian and White Scottish/British participants.

SQ: To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements: I feel more confident to engage in political decision-making as a result of being involved in this citizens' assembly

- Increased confidence to engage in political decision-making was generally high across genders, particularly among women, with very low levels of disagreement.
- Confidence increases were observed across nearly all age groups, but were especially prominent in those aged 45-64.
- There were no notable differences by ethnicity in agreement.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Agreement with statement: I feel more confident to engage in political decision-making as a result of being involved in this citizens' assembly	Strongly disagree	Count	0	2	0	2
	% within Gender		0%	9.1%	0%	3.9%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	4.5%	0%	2%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	6	10	16
	% within Gender		0%	27.3%	35.7%	31.4%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	8	13	22
	% within Gender		100%	36.4%	46.4%	43.1%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	5	5	10
	% within Gender		0%	22.7%	17.9%	19.6%
	Total	Count	1	22	28	51
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no major gender differences in overall trends, but women leaned slightly more toward **agreement**. Women were most likely to *tend to agree* (46.4%, n=13), followed by men (36.4%, n=8). *Neither agree nor disagree* views were common as well, more so among women (35.7%, n=10) than men (27.3%, n=6). Only a small minority of men expressed *disagreement*: 9.1% (n=2) *strongly disagreed* and 4.5% (n=1) *tended to disagree*.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement with statement: I feel more confident to engage in political decision-making as a result of being involved in this citizens' assembly	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	1	0	1	0	2
	% within Age group		0%	0%	8.3%	0%	14.3%	0%	3.9%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	33.3%	2%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	1	5	8	1	0	16
	% within Age group		20%	50%	41.7%	36.4%	14.3%	0%	31.4%
	Tend to agree	Count	3	1	4	9	3	2	22
	% within Age group		60%	50%	33.3%	40.9%	42.9%	66.7%	43.1%
	Strongly agree	Count	1	0	2	5	2	0	10
	% within Age group		20%	0%	16.7%	22.7%	28.6%	0%	19.6%
	Total	Count	5	2	12	22	7	3	51
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Confidence increases (*tend to agree* or *strongly agree*) were observed across nearly all age groups, but were especially prominent in those aged 45-64 (63.6%, n=14 *agreed*), 65-74 (71.5%, n=5), and 75+ (66.7%, n=2). Younger participants (19-24 and 25-29) were split: while 60% (n= of 19-24s *tended to agree*, half of 25-29s *neither agreed nor disagreed*. Notably, only one participant across all ages *strongly disagreed*, and only one *tended to disagree*. The rest were neutral or leaned toward *agreement*.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish /British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbea n	White Irish/Poli sh/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	
Agreement with statement : I feel more confident to engage in political decision-making as a result of being involved in this citizens' assembly	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	2	2
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	4.4%	3.9%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	2.2%	2%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	0	1	14	16
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	50%	31.1%	31.4%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	1	1	19	22
	% within Ethnicity		50%	50%	50%	42.2%	43.1%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	1	0	9	10
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	0%	20%	19.6%
	Total	Count	2	2	2	45	51
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no notable differences by ethnicity in agreement with the statement “I feel more confident to engage in political decision-making as a result of being involved in this citizens’ assembly.” Overall, most participants tended to agree (43.1%, n=22) or neither agreed nor disagreed (31.4%, n=16), with fewer strongly agreeing (n=10, 19.6%). Among White Scottish/British respondents, 42.2% (n=19) tended to agree and 20% (n=9) strongly agreed. Responses from other ethnic groups were limited in number but similarly positive, with no disagreement expressed by Asian, Black, or White Irish/Polish/Gypsy/Other participants.

SQ: To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements: Taking part in this citizens' assembly has made me want to be more involved in other aspects of Government decision making

- There were no notable gender differences in how participants responded.
- Overall agreement was highest among those aged 65-74 and 19-24 age group, with older participants expressing the most strength in their agreement.
- Patterns by ethnicity were broadly consistent, with no clear notable differences in agreement levels.

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Woman	Man	
Agreement with statement: Taking part in this citizens' assembly has made me want to be more involved in other aspects of Government decision making	Strongly disagree	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	5.3%	0%	2.1%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	4	2	6
	% within Gender		0%	21.1%	7.1%	12.5%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	2	12	14
	% within Gender		0%	10.5%	42.9%	29.2%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	8	11	20
	% within Gender		100%	42.1%	39.3%	41.7%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	4	3	7
	% within Gender		0%	21.1%	10.7%	14.6%
	Total	Count	1	19	28	48
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no notable gender differences in how participants responded to the statement that **taking part in the citizens' assembly made them want to be more involved in other aspects of government decision-making**. The most common response for both men and women was *tend to agree*, selected by 42.1% of women (n=8) and 39.3% of men (n=11). *Strongly agree* was also more common among women (21.1%, n=4) than among men (10.7%, n=3). Men were also more likely than

women to select *neither agree nor disagree* (42.9% of men, n=12, compared to 10.5% of women, n=2). Only a small number of participants selected *tend to disagree* (n=6) or *strongly disagree* (n=1).

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement with statement: Taking part in this citizens' assembly has made me want to be more involved in other aspects of Government decision making	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	4.5%	0%	0%	2.1%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	1	1	3	0	1	6
	% within Age group		0%	100%	9.1%	13.6%	0%	50%	12.5%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	0	5	6	1	1	14
	% within Age group		20%	0%	45.5%	27.3%	14.3%	50%	29.2%
	Tend to agree	Count	3	0	5	8	4	0	20
	% within Age group		60%	0%	45.5%	36.4%	57.1%	0%	41.7%
	Strongly agree	Count	1	0	0	4	2	0	7
	% within Age group		20%	0%	0%	18.2%	28.6%	0%	14.6%
	Total	Count	5	1	11	22	7	2	48
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some age related differences in response to this question. *Tend to agree* was the most frequently selected response for most age brackets. **Overall agreement was highest among those aged 65-74**, with 85.7% (n=6) agreeing to some extent, followed by 80% (n=4) in the **19-24 age group**. The 30-44 group showed more divided views: 45.5% (n=5) *tended to agree*, but another 45.5% (n=5) selected *neither agree nor disagree*. Older participants were slightly more likely to select *strongly agree*, particularly those aged 65-74 (28.6%, n=2) and 45-64 (18.2%, n=4). The response *tend to disagree* was chosen most by the 45-64 group (13.6%, n=3).

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/B ritish, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Poli sh/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	
Agreement with statement : Taking part in this citizens' assembly has made me want to be more involved in other aspects of Government decision making	Strongly disagree	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	2.4%	2.1%
	Tend to disagree	Count	1	0	0	5	6
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	0%	11.9%	12.5%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	1	13	14
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	50%	31%	29.2%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	1	1	17	20
	% within Ethnicity		50%	50%	50%	40.5%	41.7%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	1	0	6	7
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	0%	14.3%	14.6%
	Total	Count	2	2	2	42	48
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Patterns by ethnicity were broadly consistent, with no clear notable differences in agreement levels. Across all ethnic groups, *tend to agree* was the most selected response, chosen by 41.7% overall (n=20). Among White Scottish/British participants, 40.5% (n=17) *tended to agree* and 14.3% (n=6) *strongly agreed*. The three other ethnic groups — Asian, Asian Scottish/British; Black, Black Scottish/British, African or African Caribbean; and White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other — each had one person (50%) selecting *tend to agree* and one person (50%) selecting either *tend to disagree*, *neither agree nor disagree*, or *strongly agree*. No ethnic group showed a strong divergence from the overall pattern.

RQ: What was the impact of technology on participants' perception of the CA? Were there differences in experiences based on online versus face-to-face formats? Was the use of technology experienced differently depending on social groups?

SQ: Can you let us know your views about the arrangements leading up to and during this weekend?: Using the online learning platform¹²

- There were no notable gender differences in satisfaction levels, with large proportions of both men, women, and those identifying in another way expressing *satisfaction*.
- *Satisfaction* was high across all age groups, with no major variation.
- Patterns were consistent across ethnic groups with most participants expressing *satisfaction*, though notably, two respondents from the Asian group were *neutral*.

			Gender			
			In another way	Man	Woman	Total
Satisfaction level: Using the online learning platform	Very dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Neutral	Count	0	6	4	10
	% within Gender		0%	17.6%	9.5%	12.8%
	Satisfied	Count	2	17	17	36
	% within Gender		100%	50%	40.5%	46.2%
	Very satisfied	Count	0	11	21	32
	% within Gender		0%	32.4%	50%	41%
	Total	Count	2	34	42	78
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

¹² Median variable used, averaging participants' responses across the Assembly weekends

There were no notable gender differences in satisfaction levels. A large majority of men (50%, n=17) and women (40.5%, n=17) reported being *satisfied*, while a further 32.4% of men (n=11) and 50% of women (n=21) were *very satisfied*. *Neutral* responses were less common (17.6%, n=6 for men; 9.5%, n=4 for women), and no participants expressed *dissatisfaction*.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Satisfaction level: Using the online learning platform	Very dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Neutral	Count	1	1	5	1	1	1	10
	% within Age group		16.7%	25%	22.7%	4%	8.3%	25%	13.7%
	Satisfied	Count	2	2	8	12	6	2	32
	% within Age group		33.3%	50%	36.4%	48%	50%	50%	43.8%
	Very satisfied	Count	3	1	9	12	5	1	31
	% within Age group		50%	25%	40.9%	48%	41.7%	25%	42.5%
	Total	Count	6	4	22	25	12	4	73
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Satisfaction was high across all age groups, with no major variation. The proportion *satisfied* ranged from 33.3% (n=2) among 19-24s to 50% (n=6) among both 65-74s and 75+. *Very satisfied* was the most common response among 45-64s (n=12, 48%) and 30-44s (n=9, 40.9%). *Neutral* responses were more frequent among younger participants, particularly 19-24s (n=1, 16.7%) and 25-29s (n=1, 25%), but still a minority overall. No one reported *dissatisfaction*

Ethnicity		
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			Asian, Asian Scottish h/Britis h	Black, Black Scottish/B ritish, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Poli sh/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	Total
Satisfacti on level: Using the online learning platform	Very dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Dissatisfied	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Neutral	Count	2	0	1	7	10
	% within Ethnicity		100%	0%	20%	10.9%	13.7%
	Satisfied	Count	0	1	3	28	32
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	60%	43.8%	43.8%
	Very satisfied	Count	0	1	1	29	31
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	20%	45.3%	42.5%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	64	73
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Patterns were consistent across ethnic groups, though numbers were small. Among White Scottish/British participants, n=28 (43.8%) were *satisfied* and n=29 (45.3%) *very satisfied*. Among White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other participants, n=3 (60%) were *satisfied* and n=1 (20%) *very satisfied*. Notably, two respondents from the Asian group were *neutral* (n=2, 100%). No one reported *dissatisfaction* in any group.

SQ: To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?:
*Distractions in my home environment reduced my ability to participate in the Assembly this weekend*¹³

- No meaningful gender differences were found; large majorities of both men and women disagreed that distractions in their home environment reduced their ability to participate.
- Differences were notable across age groups, with older participants less likely to report being affected.
- Differences across ethnic groups were minimal, with a consistent overall trend of disagreement.

			Gender			
			In another way	Man	Woman	Total
Agreement level: Distractions in my home environment reduced my ability to participate in the Assembly this weekend	Strongly disagree	Count	0	21	28	49
	% within Gender		0%	61.8%	66.7%	62.8%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	9	10	19
	% within Gender		0%	26.5%	23.8%	24.4%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	2	3	4	9
	% within Gender		100%	8.8%	9.5%	11.5%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	2.9%	0%	1.3%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	2	34	42	78
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

No meaningful gender differences were found. A clear majority of women (66.7%, n=28), and men (61.8%, n=21) *strongly disagreed* that distractions reduced their participation. A further n=10 women (23.8%) and n=9 men (26.5%) *tended to*

¹³ Median variable used, averaging participants' responses across the Assembly weekends

disagree. Only small numbers selected *neither agree nor disagree* (n=4 women, 9.5%; n=3 men, 8.8%), and just one person, a man, *tended to agree* (n=1, 2.9%).

			Age group					Total	
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74		75+
Agreement level: Distractions in my home environment reduced my ability to participate in the Assembly this weekend	Strongly disagree	Count	3	1	13	16	11	3	47
	% within Age group		50%	25%	59.1%	64%	91.7%	75%	64.4%
	Tend to disagree	Count	1	1	6	7	1	1	17
	% within Age group		16.7%	25%	27.3%	28%	8.3%	25%	23.3%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	2	2	3	1	0	0	8
	% within Age group		33.3%	50%	13.6%	4%	0%	0%	11%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	4%	0%	0%	1.4%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	6	4	22	25	12	4	73
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Differences were notable across age groups, with older participants less likely to report being affected. *Strongly disagree* was the most frequent response across all groups and highest among those aged 65-74 (91.7%, n=11) and 75+ (75%, n=3). In contrast, among 19-24s, only (50%, n=3) *strongly disagreed*, and (16.7%, n=1) *tended to disagree*. *Neutral* responses were more common among younger groups, including 25-29s (50%, n=2) and 19-24s (33.3%, n=2). *Agreement* with the statement was extremely rare across all ages.

Ethnicity	
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			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	Total
Agreement level: Distractions in my home environment reduced my ability to participate in the Assembly this weekend	Strongly disagree	Count	1	1	4	41	47
	% within Ethnicity		50%	50%	80%	64.1%	64.4%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	1	0	16	17
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	0%	25%	23.3%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	0	1	6	8
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	20%	9.4%	11%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	1.6%	1.4%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	64	73
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Differences across ethnic groups were minimal, with a consistent overall trend of *disagreement*. A majority in each group *strongly disagreed* with the statement: 64.1% of White Scottish/British (n=41), 80% of White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other (n=4), and 50% in both Asian (n=1) and Black (n=1) groups. *Tend to disagree* was selected by 25% of White Scottish/British participants (n=16) and 50% of Black participants (n=1), while the remaining responses were more sparsely distributed. *Neither agree nor disagree* was chosen by 20% of the White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other group (n=1), 9.4% of White Scottish/British (n=6),

and 50% of Asian participants (n=1). Only one participant selected *tend to agree* (White Scottish/British, n=1), and no respondents selected *Strongly agree*.

SQ: *To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: Connection difficulties reduced my ability to participate in the Assembly this weekend*¹⁴

- There were no meaningful gender differences in perceptions of connection difficulties.
- Older age groups were less likely to report being affected by connection issues.
- There were no substantial differences by ethnicity. The majority of participants in all groups strongly disagreed that connection difficulties reduced their participation,

			Gender			Total
			In another way	Man	Woman	
Agreement level: Connection difficulties reduced my ability to participate in the Assembly this weekend	Strongly disagree	Count	0	19	32	51
	% within Gender		0%	55.9%	76.2%	65.4%
	Tend to disagree	Count	1	8	5	14
	% within Gender		50%	23.5%	11.9%	17.9%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	3	3	6
	% within Gender		0%	8.8%	7.1%	7.7%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	3	2	6
	% within Gender		50%	8.8%	4.8%	7.7%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	1	0	1
	% within Gender		0%	2.9%	0%	1.3%
	Total	Count	2	34	42	78
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no meaningful gender differences in perceptions of connection difficulties. A large majority of women (76.2%, n=32) and men (55.9%, n=19)

¹⁴ Median variable used, averaging participants' responses across the Assembly weekends

strongly disagreed that connection issues reduced participation. *Tend to disagree* responses were slightly more common among men (23.5%, n=8) than women (11.9%, n=5). Very few participants selected *neither agree nor disagree* (n=3 each) or *tend to agree* (n=3 men, n=2 women), and only one participant, a man, *strongly agreed* (2.9%, n=1).

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: Connection difficulties reduced my ability to participate in the Assembly this weekend	Strongly disagree	Count	2	2	13	18	10	3	48
	% within Age group		33.3%	50%	59.1%	72%	83.3%	75%	65.8%
	Tend to disagree	Count	1	0	5	6	0	1	13
	% within Age group		16.7%	0%	22.7%	24%	0%	25%	17.8%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	2	1	2	1	0	0	6
	% within Age group		33.3%	25%	9.1%	4%	0%	0%	8.2%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	1	2	0	1	0	5
	% within Age group		16.7%	25%	9.1%	0%	8.3%	0%	6.8%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	8.3%	0%	1.4%
	Total	Count	6	4	22	25	12	4	73
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Older age groups were less likely to report being affected by connection issues; *strongly disagree* was selected by 83.3% of 65-74s (n=18) and 75% of 75+ (n=3), compared to just 33.3% of 19-24s (n=2). *Tend to disagree* responses were more common among younger participants (e.g. 22.7%, n=5 among 30-44s). *Neutral* and *agree* responses were low overall, and only one participant *strongly agreed* (n=1, 1.4%), from the 65-74 group.

Ethnicity		

			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	Total
Agreement level: Connection difficulties reduced my ability to participate in the Assembly this weekend	Strongly disagree	Count	1	1	4	42	48
	% within Ethnicity		50%	50%	80%	65.6%	65.8%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	1	1	11	13
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	20%	17.2%	17.8%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	0	0	5	6
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	0%	7.8%	8.2%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	0	0	5	5
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	7.8%	6.8%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	0	1	1
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	1.6%	1.4%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	64	73
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no substantial differences by ethnicity. The majority of participants in all groups **strongly disagreed** that connection difficulties reduced their participation, including 65.6% of White Scottish/British (n=42), 80% of White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other (n=4), and 50% of both Asian (n=1) and Black (n=1) respondents. *Tend to disagree* was selected by n=11 White Scottish/British participants (17.2%) and only one Black respondent. *Neutral* and *agree* responses were rare or absent.

SQ: To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: The device I was using reduced my ability to participate in the Assembly this weekend¹⁵

- There were no meaningful differences by gender - high proportions *disagreed* across gender groups.
- There was a strong overall trend of *disagreement* across all age groups, with the *strongly disagree* response most common in each.
- There were no notable differences by ethnicity.

			Gender			
			In another way	Man	Woman	Total
Agreement level: The device I was using reduced my ability to participate in the Assembly this weekend	Strongly disagree	Count	0	22	35	57
	% within Gender		0%	64.7%	83.3%	73.1%
	Tend to disagree	Count	1	9	4	14
	% within Gender		50%	26.5%	9.5%	17.9%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	3	3	7
	% within Gender		50%	8.8%	7.1%	9%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	2	34	42	78
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no meaningful differences by gender - similarly proportions of women (92.8%, n=39), and men (91.2%, n=31) *disagreed* to some extent that their device reduced their ability to participate over the assembly. No respondents in any group selected *tend to agree* or *strongly agree*.

	Age group						Total
	19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	

¹⁵ Median variable used, averaging participants' responses across the Assembly weekends

Agreement level: The device I was using reduced my ability to participate in the Assembly this weekend	Strongly disagree	Count	3	3	15	20	10	3	54
	% within Age group		50%	75%	68.2%	80%	83.3%	75%	74%
	Tend to disagree	Count	2	1	3	5	0	1	12
	% within Age group		33.3%	25%	13.6%	20%	0%	25%	16.4%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	0	4	0	2	0	7
	% within Age group		16.7%	0%	18.2%	0%	16.7%	0%	9.6%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	6	4	22	25	12	4	73
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There was a strong overall trend of *disagreement* across all age groups, with the *Strongly disagree* response most common in each. This was highest among those aged 65-74 (n=20, 83.3%) and 75+ (n=3, 75%), followed by 45-64 (n=15, 80%) and 30-44 (n=15, 68.2%). In contrast, only 50% of the 19-24 group (n=3) and 25-29 group (n=3) selected *strongly disagree*. The *tend to disagree* response was most common among the 19-24s (n=2, 33.3%) and 45-64s (n=5, 20%). Neutral responses were rare (total n=7, 9.6%), and no participants selected *tend to agree* or *strongly agree*.

	Ethnicity				Total
	Asian, Asian Scottish/British	Black, Black Scottish/British, African or African	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other	White Scottish/British	

			Caribbean				
Agreement level: The device I was using reduced my ability to participate in the Assembly this weekend	Strongly disagree	Count	1	1	4	48	54
	% within Ethnicity		50%	50%	80%	75%	74%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	1	1	10	12
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	20%	15.6%	16.4%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	0	0	6	7
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	0%	9.4%	9.6%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	64	73
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no notable differences by ethnicity. In every group, most participants *strongly disagreed* that their device reduced participation: 75% of White Scottish/British (n=48), 80% of White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other (n=4), and 50% in both Asian (n=1) and Black (n=1) groups. No participants selected *tend to agree* or *strongly agree*.

SQ: *To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: The length of the sessions online reduced my ability to participate in the Assembly this weekend*¹⁶

- *Disagreement* was widespread for this statement, with only 2 participants selecting *agree*.
- In terms of gender, the overall pattern was *disagreement*, with women more likely to express *strong disagreement*.

¹⁶ Median variable used, averaging participants' responses across the Assembly weekends

- Older participants were also more likely to *strongly disagree* that session length was a barrier.
- Most participants across all ethnic groups *disagreed* that session length was a barrier.

			Gender			
			In another way	Man	Woman	Total
Agreement level: The length of the sessions online reduced my ability to participate in the Assembly this weekend	Strongly disagree	Count	0	17	29	46
	% within Gender		0%	50%	69%	59%
	Tend to disagree	Count	1	14	8	23
	% within Gender		50%	41.2%	19%	29.5%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	2	4	7
	% within Gender		50%	5.9%	9.5%	9%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	1	1	2
	% within Gender		0%	2.9%	2.4%	2.6%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	2	34	42	78
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some gender differences, but the overall pattern was **disagreement**. *Strongly disagree* was the most common response among both women (69%, n=29) and men (50%, n=17). However, men were more likely than women to select *tend to disagree* (41.2%, n=14 compared 19%, n=8). Neutral responses were low for both groups (men: 5.9%, n=2; women: 9.5%, n=4). Only two participants (2.6%) selected *tend to agree*, and no one selected *strongly agree*.

			Age group						
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	Total
Agreement level: The length of the	Strongly disagree	Count	3	1	9	17	9	4	43
	% within Age group		50%	25%	40.9%	68%	75%	100%	58.9%

sessions online reduced my ability to participate in the Assembly this weekend	Tend to disagree	Count	2	2	10	6	3	0	23
	% within Age group		33.3%	50%	45.5%	24%	25%	0%	31.5%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	0	2	2	0	0	5
	% within Age group		16.7%	0%	9.1%	8%	0%	0%	6.8%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	1	1	0	0	0	2
	% within Age group		0%	25%	4.5%	0%	0%	0%	2.7%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	6	4	22	25	12	4	73
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Older participants were more likely to *strongly disagree* that session length was a barrier. This view was expressed by 100% of those aged 75+ (n=4), 75% of those aged 65-74 (n=9), and 68% of those aged 45-64 (n=17). The proportion was lower among 19-24s (n=3, 50%) and 25-29s (n=1, 25%). The *tend to disagree* response was most common among the 30-44 group (n=10, 45.5%), with lower proportions in older age brackets. Neutral responses were rare (n=5 total, 6.8%), and only 2 participants (2.7%) selected *tend to agree*. No one selected *strongly agree*.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	
Agreement level: The	Strongly disagree	Count	1	1	4	37	43

length of the sessions online reduced my ability to participate in the Assembly this weekend	% within Ethnicity		50%	50%	80%	57.8%	58.9%
	Tend to disagree	Count	0	1	0	22	23
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	0%	34.4%	31.5%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	0	1	4	5
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	20%	6.2%	6.8%
	Tend to agree	Count	1	0	0	1	2
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	0%	1.6%	2.7%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	64	73
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Most participants across all ethnic groups *disagreed* that session length was a barrier. *Strongly disagree* was the most common response, including 57.8% of White Scottish/British (n=37), 80% of White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other (n=4), and 50% of both Asian (n=1) and Black (n=1) groups. *Tend to disagree* was selected by 50% of the Black group (n=1) and 34.4% of White Scottish/British (n=22). Neutral responses were selected by just 6.8% overall (n=5), and only two participants (2.7%) selected *tend to agree*. No one selected *strongly agree*.

SQ: *To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?: Difficulties with the online learning platform reduced my ability to participate in the Assembly this weekend*¹⁷

- A vast majority of all participants *strongly disagreed* that difficulties with the online platform reduced their ability to participate.
- There were no notable differences by gender regarding difficulties with the online platform.
- Patterns by age group revealed consistently high levels of *disagreement*, particularly in older age brackets.
- No major differences were observed by ethnicity.

¹⁷ Median variable used, averaging participants' responses across the Assembly weekends

			Gender			
			In another way	Man	Woman	Total
Agreement level: Difficulties with the online learning platform reduced my ability to participate in the Assembly this weekend	Strongly disagree	Count	0	21	32	53
	% within Gender		0%	61.8%	76.2%	67.9%
	Tend to disagree	Count	2	11	8	21
	% within Gender		100%	32.4%	19%	26.9%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	2	2	4
	% within Gender		0%	5.9%	4.8%	5.1%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	2	34	42	78
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no notable differences by gender regarding difficulties with the online platform. A majority of all participants (67.9%, n=53) *strongly disagreed* that difficulties with the online platform reduced their ability to participate (76.2% women, n=32; 61.8% men, n=21). Very few participants selected *neither agree nor disagree*—5.9% of men (n=2) and 4.8% of women (n=2). No participants selected *tend to agree* or *strongly agree* across any gender group.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: Difficulties with the online learning platform reduced my ability to participate in the	Strongly disagree	Count	4	2	14	17	10	3	50
	% within Age group		66.7%	50%	63.6%	68%	83.3%	75%	68.5%
	Tend to disagree	Count	2	1	5	8	2	1	19
	% within Age group		33.3%	25%	22.7%	32%	16.7%	25%	26%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	1	3	0	0	0	4

Assembly this weekend	disagree								
	% within Age group		0%	25%	13.6%	0%	0%	0%	5.5%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	6	4	22	25	12	4	73
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Patterns by age group revealed consistently high levels of *disagreement*, particularly in older age brackets. *Strongly disagree* was most common across all ages: 83.3% of those aged 65-74 (n=10), 75% of those aged 75+ (n=3), and 68% of those aged 45-64 (n=17). Younger participants also showed high *disagreement*: 66.7% of 19-24 year olds (n=4), 50% of 25-29 year olds (n=2), and 63.6% of 30-44 year olds (n=14). *Tend to disagree* was chosen by between 16.7% and 33.3% of participants across most age groups (e.g. 32% of 45-64, n=8; 22.7% of 30-44, n=5). Only 4 people in total selected *neither agree nor disagree*, and no one selected either *tend to agree* or *strongly agree*.

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	
Agreement level: Difficulties with the online learning	Strongly disagree	Count	1	1	3	45	50
	% within Ethnicity		50%	50%	60%	70.3%	68.5%
	Tend to	Count	0	1	2	16	19

platform reduced my ability to participate in the Assembly this weekend	disagree						
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	40%	25%	26%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	0	0	3	4
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	0%	4.7%	5.5%
	Tend to agree	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Strongly agree	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Total	Count	2	2	5	64	73
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

No major differences were observed by ethnicity. *Strongly disagree* was the dominant response across all groups: 70.3% of White Scottish/British (n=45), 60% of White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other (n=3), and 50% of both Asian (n=1) and Black (n=1) participants. *Tend to disagree* was selected by 25% of White Scottish/British (n=16), 40% of White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other (n=2), and 50% of Black participants (n=1). Only 4 respondents in total selected *neither agree nor disagree*, and none selected *tend to agree* or *strongly agree*.

SQ: How useful did you find the online Hub for helping you to participate in the Assembly?

- There were no notable differences between gender groups in how helpful they found the Online Hub.
- Patterns by age group showed limited variation in perceived helpfulness of the Online Hub.
- While response patterns were broadly similar across ethnic groups, those identifying as White Scottish/British were most likely to find the Online Hub *quite helpful* or *very helpful*.

	Gender			Total
	In another way	Man	Woman	

Helpfulness level: Online Hub	Not at all helpful	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	3	4	7
	% within Gender		0%	12.5%	13.8%	12.7%
	Somewhat	Count	0	5	5	10
	% within Gender		0%	20.8%	17.2%	18.2%
	Quite helpful	Count	1	10	9	20
	% within Gender		50%	41.7%	31%	36.4%
	Very helpful	Count	1	6	11	18
	% within Gender		50%	25%	37.9%	32.7%
	Total	Count	2	24	29	55
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no notable differences between gender groups in how helpful they found the Online Hub. Across all respondents, the most common response was *quite helpful* (36.4%, n=20), followed by *very helpful* (32.7%, n=18). Among women, 37.9% found it *very helpful* (n=11) and 31% *quite helpful* (n=9). Men showed similar distributions, with 41.7% finding it *quite helpful* (n=10) and 25% *very helpful* (n=6). Few found it only *a little helpful*—12.5% of men (n=3) and 13.8% of women (n=4)—and none selected *not at all helpful*.

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Helpfulness level: Online Hub	Not at all helpful	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	1	3	2	0	1	7
	% within Age group		0%	50%	20%	10.5%	0%	25%	12.7%
	Somewhat	Count	1	0	4	4	1	0	10
	% within Age group		20%	0%	26.7%	21.1%	10%	0%	18.2%
	Quite helpful	Count	2	0	5	6	5	2	20
	% within Age group		40%	0%	33.3%	31.6%	50%	50%	36.4%

	Very helpful	Count	2	1	3	7	4	1	18
	% within Age group		40%	50%	20%	36.8%	40%	25%	32.7%
	Total	Count	5	2	15	19	10	4	55
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Patterns by age group showed limited variation in perceived helpfulness of the Online Hub. In every age bracket, the most common answers were *quite helpful* or *very helpful*. For instance, in the 45-64 group, 31.6% found it *quite helpful* (n=6) and 36.8% *very helpful* (n=7). Among those aged 65-74, 50% found it *quite helpful* (n=5) and 40% *very helpful* (n=4). In contrast, younger participants were slightly more divided: in the 19-24 group, 40% rated it *quite helpful* (n=2), 40% *very helpful* (n=2), and 20% *somewhat helpful* (n=1).

			Ethnicity				Total
			Asian, Asian Scottish/ British	Black, Black Scottish/ British, African or African Caribbean	White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/ Other	White Scottish/ British	
Helpfulness level: Online Hub	Not at all helpful	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	1	0	1	5	7
	% within Ethnicity		50%	0%	25%	10.6%	12.7%
	Somewhat	Count	1	1	1	7	10
	% within Ethnicity		50%	50%	25%	14.9%	18.2%
	Quite helpful	Count	0	0	1	19	20
	% within Ethnicity		0%	0%	25%	40.4%	36.4%
	Very helpful	Count	0	1	1	16	18
	% within Ethnicity		0%	50%	25%	34%	32.7%

	Total	Count	2	2	4	47	55
	% within Ethnicity		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

While response patterns were broadly similar across ethnic groups, those identifying as **White Scottish/British** (n=47) were **most likely to find the Online Hub *quite helpful*** (40.4%, n=19) **or *very helpful*** (34%, n=16). Respondents from the White Irish/Polish/Gypsy Traveller/Other category (n=4) were more mixed, with one respondent each choosing *a little*, *somewhat*, *quite helpful*, and *very helpful* (all 25%). Among Asian Scottish/British respondents (n=2), one selected *a little* and one *somewhat*; Black Scottish/British/African/Caribbean respondents (n=2) chose *somewhat* and *very helpful*. No group selected *not at all helpful*.

RQ: What are the drivers of non-participation in CAs by potential participants from different social groups?

No data was available in Scotland's Climate Assembly evaluation dataset to address this research question.

II. CITIZENS' ASSEMBLY FOR THE CLIMATE OF CATALONIA

Methodological details

The Citizens' Assembly for the Climate of Catalonia was evaluated by distributing a post-assembly questionnaire to all participants. The demographic variables available were **language**, **age**, **gender**¹⁸, **achieved education**, and **place of birth**. As such, our analysis is limited to exploring different experiences based on these factors alone.

While 100 participants were recruited for the Assembly, the maximum number of participants at any one meeting was 97, while the lowest was 81. 83 participants attended the final Assembly meeting. 68 participants responded to the evaluation, which represents a 68% response rate compared to the number of people recruited. Not all participants responded to every survey question. The table below sets out the difference in response rates across demographic categories, compared to the number of people recruited.

Table 2. Evaluation response rates by demographic category¹⁹

Demographic variable	Category	Target N (informed by census data)	Recruited N ²⁰	Maximum N from evaluation dataset	Response rate
Gender	Male	49	46	34	73.9%
	Female	50	54	34	63%
	Non-binary	1	0	0	N/A
Age	16-29 years old	18	20	8	40%
	30-44 years old	25	26	14	53.8%
	45-59 years old	28	30	17	56.7%
	60+ years old	26	29	19	65.5%
Place of birth	Spain	83	83	57	68.7%
	Other EU countries	4	5	3	60%
	Non-EU countries	13	12	8	66.7%

¹⁸ While a third gender category beyond 'male' and 'female' was provided, no one belonging to this gender category participated.

¹⁹ Catalonia's CA recruitment data and evaluation dataset use different variables and categories, so some data transformation and recoding was required to produce this table.

²⁰ Actual Assembly attendance rates separated by demographic categories were not visible in the data supplied to us.

Achieved education	Highly educated	32	41	36	87.8%
	Secondary studies	51	48	28	58.3%
	No studies or primary studies	17	11	4	36.4%

These results point to notable underrepresentation in the evaluation data of several groups, particularly those with no studies or primary studies (36.4% response rate), and those aged 16-29 years old (40% response rate).

While differences in how different demographic groups responded to questions were identifiable, the small sample sizes in some groups mean that the strength of conclusions about these groups on the basis of this data is limited.

Results

RQ: How were different elements of Citizens' Assemblies (CAs) perceived by participants from different social groups?

SQ: Were the topics covered in the training appropriate for the Assembly's objectives? Women were more likely than men to rate the training topics as highly (a lot) appropriate while older and younger age groups (30-44 and 75+) showed the highest levels of satisfaction.

- The oldest age group, 75+, were most likely to rate the training as highly (a lot) appropriate.
- No notable variation by education level; responses were consistently positive across groups.
- Participants born outside Spain perceived topics as notably more appropriate compared to those from Catalonia and the rest of Spain.
- Catalan speakers showed slightly greater positivity overall, compared to Spanish speakers.

	Gender		Total
	Female	Male	

Appropriateness level: Topics covered in training	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	4	2	6
	% within Gender		11.8%	5.9%	8.8%
	Quite a bit	Count	14	21	35
	% within Gender		41.2%	61.8%	51.5%
	A lot	Count	16	11	27
	% within Gender		47.1%	32.4%	39.7%
	Total	Count	34	34	68
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

There were moderate gender differences in how appropriate participants found the training topics for the assembly's objectives. **Women were more likely than men to feel the training aligned strongly with the assembly's goals.** Specifically, 47.1% of women (n=16) selected *a lot* compared to 32.4% of men (n=11), while a greater proportion of men (61.8%, n=21) chose *quite a bit* relative to 41.2% of women (n=14).

			Age group						Total
			16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Appropriateness level: Topics covered in training	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	0	1	3	2	0	6
	% within Age group		0%	0%	5.6%	11.1%	25%	0%	8.8%
	Quite a bit	Count	3	3	12	14	3	0	35
	% within Age group		50%	60%	66.7%	51.9%	37.5%	0%	51.5%
	A lot	Count	3	2	5	10	3	4	27
	% within Age group		50%	40%	27.8%	37%	37.5%	100%	39.7%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	27	8	4	68
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Age group data showed a fairly even distribution of responses, with *quite a bit* being the most common across all brackets except 75+. **The oldest age group, 75+, were most likely to rate the training as highly appropriate (a lot, 100%, n=4).**

			Achieved education					Total
			No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education (GCSE equivalent)	Spanish Baccalaureate (A levels equivalent)	University degree (undergraduate)	
Appropriateness level: Topics covered in training	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A Little	Count	0	0	1	1	3	1
	% within Education		0%	0%	11.1%	5.3%	11.1%	11.1%
	Quite a bit	Count	1	2	5	9	13	5
	% within Education		100%	66.7%	55.6%	47.4%	48.1%	55.6%
	A lot	Count	0	1	3	9	11	3
	% within Education		0%	33.3%	33.3%	47.4%	40.7%	33.3%
	Total	Count	1	3	9	19	27	9
	% within Education		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Education level revealed consistent satisfaction regardless of academic background. **Participants across all education levels found the training broadly appropriate, with no major divergence by qualification.** The percentage choosing *a lot* ranged from 33.3% (postgraduate, n=9) to 47.4% (Spanish Baccalaureate, n=9), with *quite a bit* as the dominant choice for most education demographics.

			Place of birth				Total
			Catalonia	Rest of Spain	South America	Other	
Appropriateness level: Topics	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Birthplace		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

covered in training	A little	Count	3	2	1	0	6
	% within Birthplace		6%	28.6%	16.7%	0%	8.8%
	Quite a bit	Count	28	3	2	2	35
	% within Birthplace		56%	42.9%	33.3%	40%	51.5%
	A lot	Count	19	2	3	3	27
	% within Birthplace		38%	28.6%	50%	60%	39.7%
	Total	Count	50	7	6	5	68
	% within Birthplace		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Perceptions of appropriateness of training topics varied notably by birthplace. **Participants born outside Spain perceived topics as notably more appropriate compared to those from Catalonia and the rest of Spain.** Specifically, 60% (n=3) from other regions and 50% (n=3) from South America selected *a lot*, higher than participants from Catalonia (38%, n=19) and rest of Spain (28.6%, n=2).

			Language		
			Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	Total
Appropriateness level: Topics covered in training	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	5	1	6
	% within Gender		13.9%	3.1%	8.8%
	Quite a bit	Count	17	18	35
	% within Gender		47.2%	56.3%	51.5%
	A lot	Count	14	13	27
	% within Gender		38.9%	40.6%	39.7%
	Total	Count	36	32	68
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

There were small differences between Catalan and Spanish speakers regarding the appropriateness of topics covered in training. **Catalan speakers showed slightly greater positivity overall.** Specifically, 56.3% (n=18) of Catalan speakers reported

appropriateness as *quite a bit*, compared to 47.2% (n=17) of Spanish speakers. However, the proportions reporting *a lot* were closely aligned, at 40.6% (n=13) for Catalan speakers and 38.9% (n=14) for Spanish speakers.

SQ: Did the working methodology allow you to learn what was necessary to debate the dilemmas?

- Overall satisfaction was high across all demographics, with *quite a bit* being the dominant response.
- Women were more likely than men to rate the methodology *a lot* helpful.
- Participants aged 65-74 showed the highest share selecting *a lot*.
- There was minor variation in responses by education level.
- Participants from South America showed notably higher satisfaction (*a lot*) compared to other groups.
- Catalan speakers reported higher overall helpfulness than Spanish speakers.

			Gender		Total
			Female	Male	
Learning level: Methodology to debate dilemmas	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	5	6	11
	% within Gender		15.2%	17.6%	16.4%
	Quite a bit	Count	21	23	44
	% within Gender		63.6%	67.6%	65.7%
	A lot	Count	7	5	12
	% within Gender		21.2%	14.7%	17.9%
	Total	Count	33	34	67
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

Satisfaction with the working methodology was generally high across both gender groups. **Women were more likely than men to say the methodology helped a lot with learning.** Specifically, 21.2% of women (n=7) selected *a lot* compared to 14.7% of men (n=5). A clear majority of both women (63.6%, n=21) and men (67.6%, n=23)

chose *quite a bit*, indicating that most participants felt the methodology was effective in supporting learning.

			Age group						Total
			16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Learning level: Methodology to debate dilemmas	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	2	2	6	1	0	11
	% within Age group		0%	40%	11.1%	22.2%	14.3%	0%	16.4%
	Quite a bit	Count	5	2	13	18	4	2	44
	% within Age group		83.3%	40%	72.2%	66.7%	57.1%	50%	65.7%
	A lot	Count	1	1	3	3	2	2	12
	% within Age group		16.7%	20%	16.7%	11.1%	28.6%	50%	17.9%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	27	7	4	67
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Age-based responses were broadly positive, with *quite a bit* the most selected across all age brackets. **Participants aged 65-74 had the highest proportion selecting a lot, suggesting a stronger perceived learning benefit from the methodology in this group.** In this cohort, 28.6% (n=2) selected *a lot*, compared to just 11.1% (n=3) in the 45-64 group and 20% (n=1) in the 25-29 group. Notably, 83.3% (n=5) of those aged 16-24 chose *quite a bit*, indicating high satisfaction among younger participants as well.

			Achieved education					Total
			No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education (GCSE equivalent)	Spanish Baccalareate (A levels equivalent)	University degree (undergraduate)	
Learning level:	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0

Methodology to debate dilemmas	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	0	0	2	4	5	11
	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	10.5%	14.8%	55.6%	16.4%
	Quite a bit	Count	1	1	5	14	20	3	44
	% within Education		100%	33.3%	62.5%	73.7%	74.1%	33.3%	65.7%
	A lot	Count	0	2	3	3	3	1	12
	% within Education		0%	66.7%	37.5%	15.8%	11.1%	11.1%	17.9%
	Total	Count	1	3	8	19	27	9	67
	% within Education		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There was minor variation in responses by education level, though all groups leaned positive. **Participants with primary education showed slightly higher endorsement of the methodology's usefulness:** 66.7% (n=2) of participants with primary education selected *a lot*. However, due to a small number of participants in this education group, results should be interpreted with caution. Those with postgraduate degrees showed more mixed views, with only 11.1% (n=3) selecting *a lot*.

			Place of birth				Total
			Catalonia	Rest of Spain	South America	Other	
Helpfulness level: Methodology to debate dilemmas	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Birthplace		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	6	2	1	2	11
	% within Birthplace		12.2%	28.6%	16.7%	40%	16.4%
	Quite a bit	Count	35	5	1	3	44
	% within Birthplace		71.4%	71.4%	16.7%	60%	65.7%
	A lot	Count	8	0	4	0	12
	% within Birthplace		16.3%	0%	66.7%	0%	17.9%
	Total	Count	49	7	6	5	67
	% within Birthplace		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were clear birthplace-related differences regarding the methodology to debate dilemmas. **Participants from South America showed notably higher satisfaction (a lot) compared to other groups.** Specifically, 66.7% (n=4) of South American participants selected *a lot*, whereas no participants from the rest of Spain or other regions did, and only 16.3% (n=8) from Catalonia did so. Participants from Catalonia and the rest of Spain predominantly chose *quite a bit* (71.4%, n=35; 71.4%, n=5).

			Language		Total
			Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	
Helpfulness level: Methodology to debate dilemmas	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Language		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	9	2	11
	% within Language		25.7%	6.2%	16.4%
	Quite a bit	Count	17	27	44
	% within Language		48.6%	84.4%	65.7%
	A lot	Count	9	3	12
	% within Language		25.7%	9.4%	17.9%
	Total	Count	35	32	67
	% within Language		100%	100%	100%

Clear differences were observed regarding the perceived helpfulness of the methodology used to debate dilemmas. **Catalan speakers reported higher overall helpfulness than Spanish speakers.** A larger proportion of Catalan speakers reported the methodology as *quite a bit* helpful (84.4%, n=27) compared to Spanish speakers (48.6%, n=17). Conversely, a higher percentage of Spanish speakers rated helpfulness as *a little* (25.7%, n=9) compared to Catalan speakers (6.3%, n=2).

SQ: *Do you think the supporting materials for the sessions were clear and appropriate?*

- Responses were largely consistent across gender, with *quite a bit* as the most frequent answer for both groups.

- Participants aged 65-74 and 75+ reported the highest levels of satisfaction with the materials.
- Responses varied slightly by education, with postgraduate respondents slightly less likely to select *quite a bit* than other groups.
- Participants from South America rated materials notably more positively (*a lot*) compared to other birthplaces.
- Responses were similarly distributed, with only a slight indication of greater positivity among Catalan speakers.

			Gender		Total
			Female	Male	
Clarity and appropriateness level: Supporting materials for sessions	Not at all	Count	0	1	1
	% within Gender		0%	2.9%	1.5%
	A little	Count	7	7	14
	% within Gender		21.2%	20.6%	20.9%
	Quite a bit	Count	20	22	42
	% within Gender		60.6%	64.7%	62.7%
	A lot	Count	6	4	10
	% within Gender		18.2%	11.8%	14.9%
	Total	Count	33	34	67
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

There were minimal differences in responses between men and women regarding the clarity and appropriateness of supporting materials. **Both groups primarily selected *quite a bit*, indicating broad agreement on the quality of the materials.** Specifically, 64.7% of men (n=22) and 60.6% of women (n=20) gave this response. A slightly higher proportion of women (18.2%, n=6) than men (11.8%, n=4) selected *a lot*, but this gap is not especially large.

			Age group						Total
			16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Clarity and	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1

appropriateness level: Supporting materials for sessions	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	3.7%	0%	0%	1.5%
	A little	Count	1	3	3	7	0	0	14
	% within Age group		16.7%	60%	16.7%	25.9%	0%	0%	20.9%
	Quite a bit	Count	4	1	12	16	6	3	42
	% within Age group		66.7%	20%	66.7%	59.3%	85.7%	75%	62.7%
	A lot	Count	1	1	3	3	1	1	10
	% within Age group		16.7%	20%	16.7%	11.1%	14.3%	25%	14.9%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	27	7	4	67
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Most age groups responded positively, with a strong lean toward *quite a bit* across the board. **Older participants, particularly those aged 65-74 and 75+ gave the most favorable ratings.** Among the 65-74 group, 85.7% (n=6) selected *quite a bit*, and 14.3% (n=1) *a lot*. In the 75+ group, 75% (n=3) chose *quite a bit*, and 25% (n=1) *a lot*. In contrast, the 45-64 group showed more mixed ratings, with 25.9% (n=7) selecting *a little* and only 14.8% (n=4) selecting *a lot*.

			Achieved education					Total	
			No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education (GCSE equivalent)	Spanish Baccal aureate (A levels equivalent)	University degree (undergraduate)		Postgraduate university studies (Master's, PhD)
Clarity and appropriateness level: Supporting materials for sessions	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	0%	3.7%	0%	1.5%
	A little	Count	0	1	0	4	5	4	14
	% within Education		0%	33.3%	0%	21.1%	18.5%	44.4%	20.9%
	Quite a bit	Count	1	1	6	12	18	4	42
	% within Education		100%	33.3%	75%	63.2%	66.7%	44.4%	62.7%
	A lot	Count	0	1	2	3	3	1	10
	% within Education		0%	33.3%	25%	15.8%	11.1%	11.1%	14.9%

	Total	Count	1	3	8	19	27	9	67
	% within Education		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Participants across all education levels generally agreed that the materials were clear, though small differences exist. **Respondents with postgraduate degrees were somewhat less likely to choose *quite a bit* than other groups.** For instance, 44.4% (n=4) of postgraduates selected *quite a bit*, while higher shares were seen among those with Spanish Baccalaureates (63.2%, n=12) and undergraduate degrees (66.7%, n=18). The percentage selecting *a lot* remained low across all groups.

			Place of birth				Total
			Catalonia	Rest of Spain	South America	Other	
Clarity and appropriateness level: Supporting materials for sessions	Not at all	Count	1	0	0	0	1
	% within Birthplace		2%	0%	0%	0%	1.5%
	A little	Count	11	2	0	1	14
	% within Birthplace		22.5%	28.6%	0%	20%	20.9%
	Quite a bit	Count	31	4	3	4	42
	% within Birthplace		63.3%	57.1%	50%	80%	62.7%
	A lot	Count	6	1	3	0	10
	% within Birthplace		12.2%	14.3%	50%	0%	14.9%
	Total	Count	49	7	6	5	67
	% within Birthplace		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Notable differences emerged in perceptions of the clarity and appropriateness of supporting materials by birthplace. **Participants from South America rated materials notably more positively (*a lot*) compared to other birthplaces.** Half (50%, n=3) of South American respondents selected *a lot*, far exceeding those from Catalonia (12.2%, n=6) or the rest of Spain (14.3%, n=1). Participants from "Other" regions primarily rated materials as *quite a bit* (80%, n=4).

			Language		Total
			Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	
Clarity and appropriateness level: Supporting materials for sessions	Not at all	Count	1	0	1
	% within Language		2.9%	0%	1.5%
	A little	Count	8	6	14
	% within Language		22.9%	18.8%	20.9%
	Quite a bit	Count	21	21	42
	% within Language		60%	65.6%	62.7%
	A lot	Count	5	5	10
	% within Language		14.3%	15.6%	14.9%
	Total	Count	35	32	67
	% within Language		100%	100%	100%

There were minimal differences between language groups concerning clarity and appropriateness of supporting materials. **Responses were similarly distributed, with only a slight indication of greater positivity among Catalan speakers.** Specifically, 65.6% (n=21) of Catalan and 60% (n=21) of Spanish speakers rated materials *quite a bit* clear and appropriate. Little meaningful divergence was observed across other response categories.

SQ: Did the speakers and trainers explain the discussed topics well?

- Women were more likely than men to say the explanations were *a lot* clear.
- Participants aged 19-24 and 75+ were most likely to report the highest clarity from speakers and trainers.
- Education level showed some variation: those at the compulsory secondary education and primary education level reporting the highest satisfaction.
- Participants from South America and "Other" regions were notably more satisfied (a lot) than those from Catalonia or the rest of Spain.
- Catalan speakers marginally reported higher satisfaction levels.

			Gender		Total
			Female	Male	
Quality level: Topic explanation	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	1	1	2
	% within Gender		2.9%	2.9%	2.9%
	Quite a bit	Count	14	19	33
	% within Gender		41.2%	55.9%	48.5%
	A lot	Count	19	14	33
	% within Gender		55.9%	41.2%	48.5%
	Total	Count	34	34	68
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

Responses were positive across both genders, but **women were more likely than men to say that the explanations were a lot clear and effective**. Specifically, 55.9% of women (n=19) selected a *lot*, compared to 41.2% of men (n=14). Meanwhile, 55.9% of men (n=19) and 41.2% of women (n=14) chose *quite a bit*, showing both groups generally rated the speakers' performance highly.

			Age group						Total
			16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Quality level: Topic explanation	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	0	0	1	1	0	2
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	3.7%	12.5%	0%	2.9%
	Quite a bit	Count	2	3	8	15	4	1	33
	% within Age group		33.3%	60%	44.4%	55.6%	50%	25%	48.5%
	A lot	Count	4	2	10	11	3	3	33
	% within Age group		66.7%	40%	55.6%	40.7%	37.5%	75%	48.5%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	27	8	4	68
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Satisfaction was consistent across age groups, but **participants aged 19-24 and 75+ were particularly likely to select a lot**. In the 19-24 group, 66.7% (n=4) selected *a lot*, with 33.3% (n=2) selecting *quite a bit*. Among those aged 75+, 75% (n=3) selected *a lot*.

			Achieved education					Total
			No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education (GCSE equivalent)	Spanish Baccal aureate (A levels equivalent)	University degree (undergraduate)	
Quality level: Topic explanation	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Little	Count	0	0	1	0	1	2
	% within Education		0%	0%	11.1%	0%	3.7%	2.9%
	Quite a bit	Count	1	1	1	12	12	33
	% within Education		100%	33.3%	11.1%	63.2%	44.4%	48.5%
	A lot	Count	0	2	7	7	14	33
	% within Education		0%	66.7%	77.8%	36.8%	51.9%	48.5%
	Total	Count	1	3	9	19	27	68
	% within Education		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Participants with compulsory secondary education and primary education stood out slightly in their ratings. **These two education groups reported the highest levels of satisfaction with explanations**. Specifically, 77.8% (n=7) of those with compulsory secondary education and 66.7% (n=2) of those with primary education chose *a lot*. In contrast, those with university degrees (undergraduate) were more evenly split, with 44.4% (n=12) selecting *quite a bit* and 51.9% (n=14) *a lot*.

		Place of birth				Total
		Catalonia	Rest of	South	Other	

			Spain	America		
Quality level: Topic explanation	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0
	% within Birthplace		0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	2	0	0	2
	% within Birthplace		4%	0%	0%	2.9%
	Quite a bit	Count	26	3	2	33
	% within Birthplace		52%	42.9%	33.3%	40%
	A lot	Count	22	4	4	33
	% within Birthplace		44%	57.1%	66.7%	60%
	Total	Count	50	7	6	5
	% within Birthplace		100%	100%	100%	100%

Distinct birthplace differences were evident regarding the quality of topic explanations. **Participants from South America and "Other" regions were notably more satisfied (a lot) than those from Catalonia or the rest of Spain.** Specifically, 66.7% (n=4) from South America and 60% (n=3) from "Other" selected a *lot*, compared to 44% (n=22) from Catalonia and 57.1% (n=4) from the rest of Spain, indicating greater satisfaction outside of Spain.

			Language		
			Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	Total
Quality level: Topic explanation	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Language		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	2	0	2
	% within Language		5.6%	0%	2.9%
	Quite a bit	Count	18	15	33
	% within Language		50%	46.9%	48.5%
	A lot	Count	16	17	33
	% within Language		44.4%	53.1%	48.5%
	Total	Count	36	32	68

	% within Language	100%	100%	100%
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Very slight differences emerged between language groups regarding the quality of topic explanations. **Catalan speakers marginally reported higher satisfaction levels.** The proportion rating the quality as *a lot* was slightly higher among Catalan speakers (53.1%, n=17) compared to Spanish speakers (44.4%, n=16). The difference is modest, however, with both groups being similarly positive overall.

SQ: How satisfied are you with the training sessions?

- Responses were positive across both genders, though women were more likely than men to report the highest level of satisfaction with the training sessions.
- Participants aged 45-64 showed slightly lower satisfaction, while the 75+ group showed the highest.
- Those with compulsory secondary education reported the highest satisfaction; postgraduates the lowest.
- South American-born participants expressed higher satisfaction levels (*a lot*) compared to other groups.
- Catalan speakers reported marginally higher satisfaction than Spanish speakers.

			Gender		
			Female	Male	Total
Satisfaction level: Training sessions	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	3	5	8
	% within Gender		8.8%	14.7%	11.8%
	Quite a bit	Count	17	20	37
	% within Gender		50%	58.8%	54.4%
	A lot	Count	14	9	23
	% within Gender		41.2%	26.5%	33.8%
	Total	Count	34	34	68
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

Satisfaction with the training sessions was high across both genders, but **women were more likely than men to report being very satisfied**. Among women, 41.2% (n=14) selected *a lot*, compared to 26.5% (n=9) of men. Conversely, more men (58.8%, n=20) selected *quite a bit* compared to women (50%, n=17), suggesting both groups were broadly positive, though with different intensity.

			Age group						Total
			16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Satisfaction level: Training sessions	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	2	1	4	1	0	8
	% within Age group		0%	40%	5.6%	14.8%	12.5%	0%	11.8%
	Quite a bit	Count	4	3	11	13	4	2	37
	% within Age group		66.7%	60%	61.1%	48.1%	50%	50%	54.4%
	A lot	Count	2	0	6	10	3	2	23
	% within Age group		33.3%	0%	33.3%	37%	37.5%	50%	33.8%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	27	8	4	68
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Most age groups leaned toward *quite a bit* of satisfaction, but **participants aged 75+ reported the highest satisfaction, while those aged 45-64 showed more moderate responses**. Specifically, 50% (n=2) of the 75+ group selected *a lot*, compared to just 33.3% (n=10) of those aged 45-64. Notably, 66.7% (n=4) of 16-24s and 60% (n=3) of 25-29s selected *quite a bit*, suggesting solid overall satisfaction among younger participants.

		Achieved education						Total
		No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education	Spanish Baccalareate (A levels)	University degree (undergraduate)	Postgraduate university studies (Master)	

					(GCSE equivalent)	equivalent)		's, PhD)	
Satisfaction level: Training sessions	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	0	1	2	4	1	8
	% within Education		0%	0%	11.1%	10.5%	14.8%	11.1%	11.8%
	Quite a bit	Count	1	2	3	13	11	7	37
	% within Education		100%	66.7%	33.3%	68.4%	40.7%	77.8%	54.4%
	A lot	Count	0	1	5	4	12	1	23
	% within Education		0%	33.3%	55.6%	21.1%	44.4%	11.1%	33.8%
	Total	Count	1	3	9	19	27	9	68
	% within Education		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were marked differences by education level. **Participants with compulsory secondary education reported the highest satisfaction (selecting a lot), while those with postgraduate degrees were least likely to select a lot.** Specifically, 55.6% (n=5) of those with compulsory secondary education selected a lot, compared to 11.1% (n=3) of postgraduates. Participants with primary education also reported high satisfaction, with 33.3% (n=1) selecting a lot and 66.7% (n=2) quite a bit.

		Place of birth					
		Catalonia	Rest of Spain	South America	Other	Total	
Satisfaction level: Training sessions	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Birthplace		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	6	1	0	1	8
	% within Birthplace		12%	14.3%	0%	20%	11.8%
	Quite a bit	Count	29	3	3	2	37
	% within Birthplace		58%	42.9%	50%	40%	54.4%
	A lot	Count	15	3	3	2	23
	% within Birthplace		30%	42.9%	50%	40%	33.8%
	Total	Count	50	7	6	5	68

	% within Birthplace	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
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Participants' satisfaction with training sessions varied notably by birthplace. **South American-born participants expressed higher satisfaction levels (a lot) compared to other groups.** Half (50%, n=3) of participants from South America selected *a lot*, higher than those from Catalonia (30%, n=15) and other regions (40%, n=2). The majority across all birthplaces chose *quite a bit*, indicating broadly moderate satisfaction.

			Language		
			Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	Total
Satisfaction level: Training sessions	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Language		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	7	1	8
	% within Language		19.4%	3.1%	11.8%
	Quite a bit	Count	18	19	37
	% within Language		50%	59.4%	54.4%
	A lot	Count	11	12	23
	% within Language		30.6%	37.5%	33.8%
	Total	Count	36	32	68
	% within Language		100%	100%	100%

Minor differences were present regarding overall satisfaction with training sessions. **Catalan speakers reported marginally higher satisfaction than Spanish speakers.** For instance, 37.5% (n=12) of Catalan speakers reported *a lot* of satisfaction, compared to 30.6% (n=11) of Spanish speakers. Slightly more Spanish speakers reported *a little* satisfaction (19.4%, n=7) compared to Catalan speakers (3.1%, n=1).

SQ: *Do you think the Assembly's objectives have been achieved?*

- There were no major gender differences; both men and women reported similar levels of agreement.

- Younger participants (16-24) unanimously reported achieving objectives *quite a bit*, whereas all other age groups gave more varied responses.
- Education level showed only minor variation, with participants across all backgrounds tending to respond *quite a bit*.
- Participants born in South America expressed notably higher clarity (*a lot*) compared to other groups.
- Catalan speakers were slightly more likely to report higher achievement levels.

			Gender		Total
			Female	Male	
Achievement: Assembly objectives	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	5	4	9
	% within Gender		14.7%	12.5%	13.6%
	Quite a bit	Count	24	24	48
	% within Gender		70.6%	75%	72.7%
	A lot	Count	5	4	9
	% within Gender		14.7%	12.5%	13.6%
	Total	Count	34	32	66
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

There was a high level of *agreement* across genders regarding whether the Assembly's objectives were achieved. **No meaningful differences emerged between men and women.** A majority of both groups, 70.6% of women (n=24) and 75% of men (n=24), selected *quite a bit*. Smaller proportions of women (14.7%, n=5) and men (12.5%, n=4) selected *a lot*, with the rest selecting *a little*.

			Age group					Total
			16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	
Achievement: Assembly	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

objectives	A little	Count	0	1	2	5	1	0	9
	% within Age group		0%	20%	11.1%	19.2%	12.5%	0%	13.6%
	Quite a bit	Count	6	3	13	18	6	2	48
	% within Age group		100%	60%	72.2%	69.2%	75%	66.7%	72.7%
	A lot	Count	0	1	3	3	1	1	9
	% within Age group		0%	20%	16.7%	11.5%	12.5%	33.3%	13.6%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	26	8	3	66
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some notable differences across age groups regarding perceptions of achieving assembly objectives, though all age groups leaned positive. **Younger participants (16-24) unanimously reported achieving objectives quite a bit, whereas all other age groups gave more varied responses.** However, *quite a bit* was still the dominant response across all age bands.

			Achieved education					Total
			No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education (GCSE equivalent)	Spanish Baccal aureate (A levels equivalent)	University degree (undergraduate)	
Achievement: Assembly objectives	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	1	1	2	4	1
	% within Education		0%	33.3%	11.1%	10.5%	15.4%	12.5%
	Quite a bit	Count	1	0	7	16	18	6
	% within Education		100%	0%	77.8%	84.2%	69.2%	75%
	A lot	Count	0	2	1	1	4	1
	% within Education		0%	66.7%	11.1%	5.3%	15.4%	12.5%
	Total	Count	1	3	9	19	26	8
% within Education		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	

Responses by education level were broadly consistent. **Participants across all education groups tended to agree the assembly’s objectives had been achieved, mostly selecting *quite a bit*.** For instance, 84.2% (n=16) of Spanish Baccalaureate holders and 75% (n=6) of postgraduates selected *quite a bit*. Only two subgroups, primary education (66.7%, n=2) and undergraduate (15.4%, n=4) showed *a lot* as a noticeable share, but differences were minor.

			Place of birth				Total
			Catalonia	Rest of Spain	South America	Other	
Achievement: Assembly objectives	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Birthplace		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	7	2	0	0	9
	% within Birthplace		14.6%	28.6%	0%	0%	13.64%
	Quite a bit	Count	37	4	3	4	48
	% within Birthplace		77.1%	57.1%	50%	80%	72.73%
	A lot	Count	4	1	3	1	9
	% within Birthplace		8.3%	14.3%	50%	20%	13.64%
	Total	Count	48	7	6	5	66
	% within Birthplace		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Notable differences emerged based on participants’ birthplace regarding perceptions of how well the assembly achieved its objectives. **South American-born participants reported notably higher levels of achievement (*a lot*) compared to other groups.** Specifically, 50% (n=3) of South American participants chose *a lot*, distinctly higher than Catalonia (8.3%, n=4), rest of Spain (14.3%, n=1), and other regions (20%, n=1). Conversely, participants from Catalonia predominantly selected *quite a bit* (77.1%, n=37), reflecting a more moderate evaluation of achievement.

		Language		Total
		Spanish (Spain, international)	Catalan	

			literacy)		
Achievement: Assembly objectives	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Language		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	6	3	9
	% within Language		16.7%	10%	13.6%
	Quite a bit	Count	26	22	48
	% within Language		72.2%	73.3%	72.7%
	A lot	Count	4	5	9
	% within Language		11.1%	16.7%	13.6%
	Total	Count	36	30	66
	% within Language		100%	100%	100%

There were very minor differences in perceptions of achieving assembly objectives between language groups. **Catalan speakers were slightly more likely to report higher achievement levels.** Specifically, 16.7% (n=5) of Catalan speakers responded with *a lot*, compared to 11.1% (n=4) of Spanish speakers. Both groups predominantly indicated *quite a bit*, with little meaningful divergence.

SQ: Were the objectives of the debate sessions clear?

- Men were more likely than women to say the debate session objectives were *quite a bit* clear, while women were more evenly split between *quite a bit* and *a lot*.
- No clear differences in age group proportions selecting different response options were observed.
- Participants with postgraduate education were notably less likely to report high clarity compared to those with undergraduate or primary education.
- Participants from the rest of Spain perceived a higher absence of relevant perspectives (*quite a bit*) than other groups.
- Catalan speakers indicated marginally greater clarity overall.

			Gender		
			Female	Male	Total
Clarity level: Objectives of	Not at all	Count	0	0	0

debate	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	7	2	9
	% within Gender		20.6%	5.9%	13.2%
	Quite a bit	Count	19	24	43
	% within Gender		55.9%	70.6%	63.2%
	A lot	Count	8	8	16
	% within Gender		23.5%	23.5%	23.5%
	Total	Count	34	34	68
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

Participants across genders generally found the objectives of the debate sessions clear, with only modest variation. **Men were more likely to select *quite a bit*, while women were more evenly split between *quite a bit* and *a lot*.** Specifically, 70.6% of men (n=24) chose *quite a bit* versus 55.9% of women (n=19). Meanwhile, 23.5% of both men and women (n=8 each) selected *a lot*, indicating a shared top-tier confidence level across genders despite different distributions.

			Age group						Total
			16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Clarity level: Objectives of debate	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	2	1	2	4	0	0	9
	% within Age group		33.3%	20%	11.1%	14.8%	0%	0%	13.2%
	Quite a bit	Count	2	3	12	18	5	3	43
	% within Age group		33.3%	60%	66.7%	66.7%	62.5%	75%	63.2%
	A lot	Count	2	1	4	5	3	1	16
	% within Age group		33.3%	20%	22.2%	18.5%	37.5%	25%	23.5%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	27	8	4	68
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

A plurality of all age groups indicated the objectives of the debate were *quite a bit* clear. No clear differences in age group proportions selecting different response options were observed.

			Achieved education					Total
			No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education (GCSE equivalent)	Spanish Baccal aureate (A levels equivalent)	University degree (undergraduate)	
Clarity level: Objectives of debate	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	0	1	3	2	3
	% within Education		0%	0%	11.1%	15.8%	7.4%	33.3%
	Quite a bit	Count	1	2	5	12	18	5
	% within Education		100%	66.7%	55.6%	63.2%	66.7%	55.6%
	A lot	Count	0	1	3	4	7	1
	% within Education		0%	33.3%	33.3%	21.1%	25.9%	11.1%
	Total	Count	1	3	9	19	27	9
	% within Education		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were clear differences by education level regarding the perceived clarity of debate objectives. **Participants with postgraduate education were notably less likely to report high clarity compared to those with undergraduate or primary education.** Specifically, only 11.1% (n=1) of postgraduate participants reported *a lot* of clarity, compared to 25.9% (n=7) of undergraduate participants and 33.3% (n=1) of those with primary education. Conversely, a higher proportion of postgraduate participants reported *a little* clarity (33.3%, n=3), highlighting a trend of lower perceived clarity among the most highly educated group.

	Place of birth				Total
	Catalonia	Rest of Spain	South America	Other	

Clarity level: Objectives of debate	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Birthplace		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	7	2	0	0	9
	% within Birthplace		14%	28.6%	0%	0%	13.2%
	Quite a bit	Count	30	5	3	5	43
	% within Birthplace		60%	71.4%	50%	100%	63.2%
	A lot	Count	13	0	3	0	16
	% within Birthplace		26%	0%	50%	0%	23.5%
	Total	Count	50	7	6	5	68
	% within Birthplace		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were clear birthplace-related differences in clarity perceptions of debate objectives. **Participants born in South America expressed notably higher clarity (a lot) compared to other groups.** Specifically, 50% (n=3) of South American participants selected *a lot*, whereas no participants from the rest of Spain or other regions did, and only 26% (n=13) from Catalonia did so. Participants from "Other" regions unanimously selected *quite a bit* (100%, n=5), highlighting clear but moderate perceptions of clarity.

			Language		
			Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	Total
Clarity level: Objectives of debate	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Language		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	6	3	9
	% within Language		16.7%	9.4%	13.2%
	Quite a bit	Count	21	22	43
	% within Language		58.3%	68.8%	63.2%
	A lot	Count	9	7	16
	% within Language		25%	21.9%	23.5%
	Total	Count	36	32	68

	% within Language	100%	100%	100%
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Minimal differences were found in perceptions of the clarity of debate objectives by language. **Catalan speakers indicated marginally greater clarity overall.** For instance, 68.8% (n=22) of Catalan speakers indicated *quite a bit* of clarity, compared to 58.3% (n=21) of Spanish speakers, with broadly similar positive responses across both groups.

RQ: How inclusive was the CA in terms of representation?

SQ: Do you think there are relevant perspectives on the discussed topics that were not covered in the training sessions?

- Most participants felt *a little* or *quite a bit* of relevant perspectives were missing; only 5.9% said *a lot* of perspectives were excluded.
- No substantial differences were observed across gender; perceptions were similar.
- Younger age groups (especially 25-29) were slightly more likely to believe perspectives were missed.
- Participants with compulsory secondary education were more inclined to feel perspectives were missing compared to other education groups.
- Participants from the rest of Spain perceived a higher absence of relevant perspectives (*quite a bit*) than other groups.
- Catalan speakers more frequently perceived *a little* absence, whereas Spanish speakers were somewhat more critical.

			Gender		
			Female	Male	Total
Perception of absence of relevant perspectives in training	Not at all	Count	1	1	2
	% within Gender		2.9%	2.9%	2.9%
	A little	Count	17	18	35
	% within Gender		50%	52.9%	51.5%
	Quite a bit	Count	14	13	27
	% within Gender		41.2%	38.2%	39.7%
	A lot	Count	2	2	4

	% within Gender		5.9%	5.9%	5.9%
	Total	Count	34	34	68
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

Participants across genders reported very similar views on whether relevant perspectives were excluded. **No notable differences were observed between men and women.** Around half of both women (50%, n=17) and men (52.9%, n=18) selected *a little*, while 41.2% of women (n=14) and 38.2% of men (n=13) chose *quite a bit*. Only 5.9% (n=2) of both groups felt that *a lot* of relevant perspectives were not covered.

			Age group						Total
			16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Perception of absence of relevant perspectives in training	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	2	0	0	2
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	7.4%	0%	0%	2.9%
	A little	Count	3	2	11	13	4	2	35
	% within Age group		50%	40%	61.1%	48.1%	50%	50%	51.5%
	Quite a bit	Count	1	3	5	12	4	2	27
	% within Age group		16.7%	60%	27.8%	44.4%	50%	50%	39.7%
	A lot	Count	2	0	2	0	0	0	4
	% within Age group		33.3%	0%	11.1%	0%	0%	0%	5.9%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	27	8	4	68
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Perceptions of missing perspectives varied slightly by age. **Younger participants were somewhat more likely to feel relevant perspectives were excluded.** In the 25-29 age group, 60% (n=3) *quite a bit*, and amongst the 19-24 group, 33.3% (n=2) chose *a lot*, the highest share of *a lot* across any age group, though 11.1% (n=2) of 30-44s also chose *a lot*. Older age groups (45- 64, 65-74 and 75+) reported lower concern, with no respondents selecting *a lot* and smaller proportions than the 25-29 group selecting *quite a bit*.

			Achieved education					Total	
			No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education (GCSE equivalent)	Spanish Baccalaureate (A levels equivalent)	University degree (undergraduate)		Postgraduate university studies (Master's, PhD)
Perception of absence of relevant perspectives in training	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	1	1	0	2
	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	5.3%	3.7%	0%	2.9%
	A little	Count	0	2	4	10	14	5	35
	% within Education		0%	66.7%	44.4%	52.6%	51.9%	55.6%	51.5%
	Quite a bit	Count	1	1	4	6	11	4	27
	% within Education		100%	33.3%	44.4%	31.6%	40.7%	44.4%	39.7%
	A lot	Count	0	0	1	2	1	0	4
	% within Education		0%	0%	11.1%	10.5%	3.7%	0%	5.9%
	Total	Count	1	3	9	19	27	9	68
	% within Education		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Participants with compulsory secondary education stood out slightly. **Participants with compulsory secondary education were more likely to feel relevant perspectives were missed, with nearly half selecting *quite a bit*.** Specifically, 44.4% (n=4) chose *quite a bit* and 11.1% (n=1) *a lot*, compared to 10.5% (n=2) *a lot* among Spanish Baccalaureate holders. Still, the most common response across all education levels was *a little* (ranging from 44% to 66.7%).

			Place of birth				Total
			Catalonia	Rest of Spain	South America	Other	
Perception of absence of relevant perspectives in training	Not at all	Count	1	0	0	1	2
	% within Birthplace		2%	0%	0%	20%	2.9%
	A little	Count	26	3	4	2	35
	% within Birthplace		52%	42.9%	66.7%	40%	51.5%

	Quite a bit	Count	19	4	2	2	27
	% within Birthplace		38%	57.1%	33.3%	40%	39.7%
	A lot	Count	4	0	0	0	4
	% within Birthplace		8%	0%	0%	0%	5.9%
	Total	Count	50	7	6	5	68
	% within Birthplace		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Differences existed based on birthplace regarding perceptions of absent perspectives in training. **Participants from the rest of Spain perceived a higher absence of relevant perspectives (*quite a bit*) than other groups.** Specifically, 57.1% (n=4) from the rest of Spain selected *quite a bit*, higher than those from Catalonia (38%, n=19) and South America (33.3%, n=2). A plurality of participants across all groups other than the rest of Spain chose *a little*, indicating a general view that most relevant perspectives were covered.

			Language		
			Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	Total
Perception of absence of relevant perspectives	Not at all	Count	0	2	2
	% within Language		0%	6.3%	2.9%

in training	A little	Count	16	19	35
	% within Language		44.4%	59.4%	51.5%
	Quite a bit	Count	17	10	27
	% within Language		47.2%	31.3%	39.7%
	A lot	Count	3	1	4
	% within Language		8.3%	3.1%	5.9%
	Total	Count	36	32	68
	% within Language		100%	100%	100%

Clear differences emerged regarding perceptions of missing relevant perspectives. **Catalan speakers more frequently perceived a *little* absence, whereas Spanish speakers were somewhat more critical.** Specifically, 59.4% (n=19) of Catalan speakers indicated a *little* absence, compared to 44.4% (n=16) of Spanish speakers. Conversely, more Spanish speakers indicated absence *quite a bit* (47.2%, n=17) versus Catalan speakers (31.3%, n=10).

SQ: Has the diversity of people in the Assembly helped to achieve results?

- Most participants viewed diversity as beneficial to outcomes, with 88.3% selecting *quite a bit* or *a lot*.
- Men were slightly more likely than women to say diversity helped *a lot*.
- Participants aged 30-44 and 75+ were most likely to report that diversity helped *a lot*.
- Lower education levels correlated with stronger agreement; participants with no formal education or compulsory education were most likely to choose *a lot*.
- Participants from South America rated diversity significantly more positively (*a lot*) compared to other groups.

			Gender		Total
			Female	Male	
Helpfulness level: diversity of people to achieve results	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	2	6	8
	% within Gender		5.9%	17.6%	11.8%

	Quite a bit	Count	22	16	38
	% within Gender		64.7%	47.1%	55.9%
	A lot	Count	10	12	22
	% within Gender		29.4%	35.3%	32.4%
	Total	Count	34	34	68
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

There was broad agreement that diversity contributed to achieving results. **Men were slightly more likely than women to rate the impact of diversity as a lot.** Specifically, 35.3% of men (n=12) selected *a lot* compared to 29.4% of women (n=10). However, more women (64.7%, n=22) than men (47.1%, n=16) selected *quite a bit*. Only a small proportion in each group selected *a little*.

			Age group						Total
			16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Helpfulness level: diversity of people to achieve results	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	1	1	3	3	0	0	8
	% within Age group		16.7%	20%	16.7%	11.1%	0%	0%	11.8%
	Quite a bit	Count	4	3	6	18	5	2	38
	% within Age group		66.7%	60%	33.3%	66.7%	62.5%	50%	55.9%
	A lot	Count	1	1	9	6	3	2	22
	% within Age group		16.7%	20%	50%	22.2%	37.5%	50%	32.4%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	27	8	4	68
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Most age groups positively assessed the role of diversity, but **participants aged 30-44 and 75+ were the most emphatic, with 50% (n=9, n=2 respectively) selecting a lot.** Other age groups leaned more toward *quite a bit*, such as the 45-64 group (66.7%, n=18) and 65-74 group (62.5%, n=5). The lowest *a lot* response came

from the 25-29 group (20%, n=1), although this group had a high share choosing *quite a bit* (60%, n=3).

			Achieved education					Total	
			No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education (GCSE equivalent)	Spanish Baccalureate (A levels equivalent)	University degree (undergraduate)		Postgraduate university studies (Master's, PhD)
Helpfulness level: diversity of people to achieve results	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	0	1	2	4	1	8
	% within Education		0%	0%	11.1%	10.5%	14.8%	11.1%	11.8%
	Quite a bit	Count	0	1	5	13	13	6	38
	% within Education		0%	33.3%	55.6%	68.4%	48.1%	66.7%	55.9%
	A lot	Count	1	2	3	4	10	2	22
	% within Education		100%	66.7%	33.3%	21.1%	37%	22.2%	32.4%
	Total	Count	1	3	9	19	27	9	68
	% within Education		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Views on the benefits of diversity varied with education level. **Participants with no formal education and primary education were more likely to view diversity as strongly helpful.** Among those with primary education, 66.7% (n=2) selected *a lot*, as did 100% (n=1) of those with no formal education. However, these categories both have very small counts. In contrast, only 22.2% (n=2) of postgraduate degree holders selected *a lot*, and this group accounted for the largest share of those selecting *a little* (14.8%, n=4). Nonetheless, the majority across all education levels still chose either *quite a bit* or *a lot*.

	Place of birth				Total
	Catalonia	Rest of Spain	South America	Other	

Helpfulness level: diversity of people to achieve results	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Birthplace		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	4	1	1	2	8
	% within Birthplace		8%	14.3%	16.7%	40%	11.8%
	Quite a bit	Count	30	4	2	2	38
	% within Birthplace		60%	57.1%	33.3%	40%	55.9%
	A lot	Count	16	2	3	1	22
	% within Birthplace		32%	28.6%	50%	20%	32.3%
	Total	Count	50	7	6	5	68
	% within Birthplace		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Participants' views on the helpfulness of diversity varied by birthplace. **Participants from South America rated diversity significantly more positively (a lot) compared to other groups.** Half (50%, n=3) from South America selected *a lot*, higher than those from Catalonia (32%, n=16) and other regions (20%, n=1). Across all birthplaces, a majority saw diversity as at least *quite a bit* helpful.

			Language		
			Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	Total
Helpfulness level: diversity of people to achieve results	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Language		0%	0%	0%
	Little	Count	6	2	8
	% within Language		16.7%	6.2%	11.8%
	Quite a bit	Count	19	19	38
	% within Language		52.8%	59.4%	55.9%
	A lot	Count	11	11	22
	% within Language		30.5%	34.4%	32.3%
	Total	Count	36	32	68
	% within Language		100%	100%	100%

Only slight differences were observed regarding perceptions of diversity's helpfulness in achieving results. **Catalan speakers reported slightly greater helpfulness than Spanish speakers.** Specifically, 34.4% (n=11) of Catalan speakers responded *a lot*, compared to 30.6% (n=11) of Spanish speakers. Both groups showed a predominantly positive response overall.

SQ: Do you think the people in the Assembly reflect the social diversity of Catalonia?

- Most participants agreed that the assembly reflected Catalonia's social diversity, with 83.9% selecting *quite a bit* or *a lot*.
- Perceptions were consistent across gender, with no notable differences.
- Older participants, particularly those in the 65-74 age group, showed the broadest, strongest agreement.
- Participants with lower educational levels notably perceived greater representativeness in the assembly.
- Participants born in South America most strongly perceived high representativeness in the assembly.
- Catalan speakers were slightly more likely to view the assembly as representative to a moderate extent, while Spanish speakers were more likely to report higher agreement.

			Gender		Total
			Female	Male	
Agreement level: assembly representativeness	Not at all	Count	1	0	1
	% within Gender		2.9%	0%	1.5%
	A little	Count	5	5	10
	% within Gender		14.7%	14.7%	14.7%
	Quite a bit	Count	16	16	32
	% within Gender		47.1%	47.1%	47.1%
	A lot	Count	12	13	25
	% within Gender		35.3%	38.2%	36.8%
	Total	Count	34	34	68
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

Perceptions of the assembly's social representativeness were consistent across gender. **There were no major gender differences in the responses.** Both women and men had identical proportions selecting *quite a bit*, 47.1% (n=16 each). Likewise, 35.3% of women (n=12) and 38.2% of men (n=13) selected *a lot*, with the remaining percentages choosing *a little* or *not at all*.

			Age group						Total
			16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: assembly representativeness	Not at all	Count	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	% within Age group		16.7%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	1.5%
	A little	Count	1	2	2	4	0	1	10
	% within Age group		16.7%	40%	11.1%	14.8%	0%	25%	14.7%
	Quite a bit	Count	2	1	7	17	4	1	32
	% within Age group		33.3%	20%	38.9%	63%	50%	25%	47.1%
	A lot	Count	2	2	9	6	4	2	25
	% within Age group		33.3%	40%	50%	22.2%	50%	50%	36.8%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	27	8	4	68
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

While responses were generally positive across age groups, **older participants, particularly those in the 65-74 age group, showed the broadest, strongest agreement**, with no one selecting *a little*. Additionally, in the 75+ group, 50% (n=2) selected *a lot*, compared to only 22.2% (n=6) of those aged 45-64 and 33.3% (n=2) of those aged 16-24. The 65-75 group showed the highest *agreement* overall, with 50% (n=4) selecting *a lot* and 50% (n=4) *quite a bit*.

		Achieved education					Total
		No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education (GCSE equivalent)	Spanish Baccalaurate (A levels equivalent)	University degree (undergraduate)	

				ent)					
Agreement level: assembly representativeness	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	5.3%	0%	0%	1.5%
	A little	Count	0	0	2	2	4	2	10
	% within Education		0%	0%	22.2%	10.5%	14.8%	22.2%	14.7%
	Quite a bit	Count	0	1	2	11	13	5	32
	% within Education		0%	33.3%	22.2%	57.9%	48.1%	55.6%	47.1%
	A lot	Count	1	2	5	5	10	2	25
	% within Education		100%	66.7%	55.6%	26.3%	37%	22.2%	36.8%
	Total	Count	1	3	9	19	27	9	68
	% within Education		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Educational attainment influenced perceptions of representativeness. **Participants with lower educational levels notably perceived greater representativeness in the assembly.** Those with no formal education (100%, n=1) and primary education (66.7%, n=2) overwhelmingly responded with *a lot*, compared to 22.2% (n=2) of postgraduate participants. This highlights that higher education levels correlated with more moderate perceptions of representativeness.

		Place of birth					
		Catalonia	Rest of Spain	South America	Other	Total	
Agreement level: assembly representativeness	Not at all	Count	1	0	0	0	1
	% within Birthplace		2%	0%	0%	0%	1.5%
	A little	Count	8	1	0	1	10
	% within Birthplace		16%	14.3%	0%	20%	14.7%
	Quite a bit	Count	23	4	2	3	32
	% within Birthplace		46%	57.1%	33.3%	60%	47%
	A lot	Count	18	2	4	1	25
	% within Birthplace		36%	28.6%	66.7%	20%	36.8%
	Total	Count	50	7	6	5	68
	% within Birthplace		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Place of birth influenced perceptions notably. **Participants born in South America most strongly perceived high representativeness in the assembly.** Specifically, 66.7% (n=4) of South American-born participants responded with *a lot*, contrasting with 36% (n=18) of those born in Catalonia and only 20% (n=1) of those born elsewhere. Participants from "Other" regions notably leaned towards moderate views, with 60% (n=3) selecting *quite a bit*.

			Language		
			Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	Total
Agreement level: assembly representative ness	Not at all	Count	1	0	1
	% within Language		2.8%	0%	1.5%
	A little	Count	4	6	10
	% within Language		11.1%	18.8%	14.7%
	Quite a bit	Count	16	16	32
	% within Language		44.4%	50%	47.1%
	A lot	Count	15	10	25
	% within Language		41.7%	31.3%	36.8%
	Total	Count	36	32	68
	% within Language		100%	100%	100%

Small differences were present regarding views on representativeness. **Catalan speakers were slightly more likely to view the assembly as representative to a moderate extent, while Spanish speakers were more likely to report higher agreement.** For instance, 50% (n=16) of Catalan speakers selected *quite a bit* compared to 44.4% (n=16) of Spanish speakers. In contrast, 41.7% (n=15) of Spanish speakers chose *a lot*, versus 31.3% (n=10) of Catalan speakers.

SQ: Do you think there is any group or collective that is not represented in the Assembly?

- Women were more likely than men to feel some groups were not represented.
- The 24-29 and 45-64 age groups were the most likely to believe a group was missing.
- Responses varied with education level, though no major education-related patterns were identified.
- Participants from South America were much less likely to feel that there were some groups or collectives not well represented in the assembly compared to others.
- Catalan speakers were more likely than Spanish speakers to report that some groups or collectives were not represented.

			Gender		Total
			Female	Male	
Agreement level: group or collective not represented in Assembly	Yes	Count	18	13	31
	% within Gender		54.5%	38.2%	46.3%
	No	Count	15	21	36
	% within Gender		45.5%	61.8%	53.7%
	Total	Count	33	34	67
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

Perceptions of representation differed somewhat by gender. **Women were notably more likely than men to believe a group or collective was not represented in the assembly.** Specifically, 54.5% of women (n=18) responded *yes*, compared to just 38.2% of men (n=13). Conversely, 61.8% of men (n=21) responded *no*, indicating a stronger perception among men that representation was sufficient.

			Age group					Total	
			16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74		75+
Agreement level: group or collective	Yes	Count	2	3	5	15	4	2	31
	% within Age group		33.3%	60%	27.8%	57.7%	50%	50%	46.3%

not represented in Assembly	No	Count	4	2	13	11	4	2	36
	% within Age group		66.7%	40%	72.2%	42.3%	50%	50%	53.7%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	26	8	4	67
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Age group patterns showed varied perceptions. **Participants aged 24-29 and 45-64 were the most likely to believe a group was missing, with 60% (n=3) and 57.7% (n=15) selecting yes, respectively.** Younger participants (16-24) and older ones (65+) were less likely to perceive missing representation, with 33.3% (n=2) and 50% (n=2) responding yes, respectively. The 30-44 group was least likely to agree, with only 27.8% (n=5) selecting yes.

			Achieved education					Total	
			No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education (GCSE equivalent)	Spanish Baccalaureate (A levels equivalent)	University degree (undergraduate)		Postgraduate university studies (Master's, PhD)
Agreement level: group or collective not represented in Assembly	Yes	Count	0	2	4	10	10	5	31
	% within Education		0%	66.7%	44.4%	55.6%	37%	55.6%	46.3%
	No	Count	1	1	5	8	17	4	36
	% within Education		100%	33.3%	55.6%	44.4%	63%	44.4%	53.7%
	Total	Count	1	3	9	18	27	9	67
	% within Education		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Responses varied with education level, though no major education-related patterns were identified. Participants with primary education, Spanish Baccalaureate education or postgraduate education were more likely to report underrepresentation. Specifically, 66.7% (n=2) of those with primary education and 55.6% of both Spanish Baccalaureate holders (n=10) and postgraduates (n=5), a selected yes. This contrasts with university undergraduates (37%, n=10) and those with no formal education (0%, n=0), who were less likely to perceive exclusion.

			Place of birth				Total
			Catalonia	Rest of Spain	South America	Other	
Agreement level: group or collective not represented in Assembly	Yes	Count	24	4	1	2	31
	% within Birthplace		49%	57.1%	16.7%	40%	46.3%
	No	Count	25	3	5	3	36
	% within Birthplace		51%	42.9%	83.3%	60%	53.7%
	Total	Count	49	7	6	5	67
	% within Birthplace		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Notable differences emerged regarding perceptions of representation by birthplace. **Participants from South America were much less likely to feel that there were some groups or collectives not well represented in the assembly compared to others.** Specifically, 83.3% (n=5) of South American-born participants selected *No*, indicating they did not see unrepresented groups, notably higher than those from Catalonia (51%, n=25) and other regions (60%, n=3). Participants from the rest of Spain were more evenly split.

			Language		Total
			Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	
Agreement level: group or collective not represented in Assembly	Yes	Count	14	17	31
	% within Language		38.9%	54.8%	46.3%
	No	Count	22	14	36
	% within Language		61.1%	45.2%	53.7%
	Total	Count	36	31	67
	% within Language		100%	100%	100%

Clearer differences emerged in perceptions of underrepresentation. **Catalan speakers were more likely than Spanish speakers to report that some groups**

or collectives were not represented. 54.8% (n=17) of Catalan speakers responded yes, compared to 38.9% (n=14) of Spanish speakers.

SQ: Do you think there is any group or collective that is overrepresented in the Assembly?

- Women were more likely than men to perceive overrepresentation in the assembly.
- The 16-24 age group was most likely to report perceived overrepresentation.
- No education group showed markedly high concern, though university-educated participants were slightly more likely to say yes.
- There were no notable differences by birthplace; most participants from all birthplaces answered *No*.

			Gender		Total
			Female	Male	
Agreement level: group or collective overrepresented in Assembly	Yes	Count	11	4	15
	% within Gender		32.4%	12.1%	22.4%
	No	Count	23	29	52
	% within Gender		67.6%	87.9%	77.6%
	Total	Count	34	33	67
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

Perceptions of overrepresentation varied notably by gender. **Women were notably more likely than men to feel that a group was overrepresented.** Specifically, 32.4% of women (n=11) answered *yes*, compared to just 12.1% of men (n=4). Conversely, 87.9% of men (n=29) responded *no*, indicating a stronger consensus among men that representation was balanced.

			Age group					Total	
			16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74		75+
Agreement level:	Yes	Count	4	1	3	7	0	0	15

group or collective overrepresented in Assembly	% within Age group		66.7%	20%	16.7%	25.9%	0%	0%	22.4%
	No	Count	2	4	15	20	7	4	52
	% within Age group		33.3%	80%	83.3%	74.1%	100%	100%	77.6%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	27	7	4	67
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Age differences were clear in perceptions of overrepresentation. **Participants aged 16-24 were the most likely to report that a group was overrepresented, with 66.7% (n=4) answering yes.** This sharply contrasts with older groups, e.g., 0% in both the 65-74 and 75+ categories. The 45-64 age group had a moderate level of concern, with 25.9% (n=7) selecting yes.

			Achieved education					Total	
			No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education (GCSE equivalent)	Spanish Baccal aureate (A levels equivalent)	University degree (undergraduate)		Postgraduate university studies (Master's, PhD)
Agreement level: group or collective overrepresented in Assembly	Yes	Count	0	1	2	3	7	2	15
	% within Education		0%	33.3%	22.2%	16.7%	25.9%	22.2%	22.4%
	No	Count	1	2	7	15	20	7	52
	% within Education		100%	66.7%	77.8%	83.3%	74.1%	77.8%	77.6%
	Total	Count	1	3	9	18	27	9	67
	% within Education		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Perceptions of overrepresentation were relatively stable across education levels. **No group showed markedly high concern, though university-educated participants were slightly more likely to say yes - 25.9% (n=7) of university undergraduates felt a group was overrepresented.**

		Place of birth				Total
		Catalonia	Rest of	South	Other	

				Spain	America		
Agreement level: group or collective overrepresented in Assembly	Yes	Count	10	2	1	2	15
	% within Birthplace		20.4%	28.6%	16.7%	40%	22.4%
	No	Count	39	5	5	3	52
	% within Birthplace		79.6%	71.4%	83.3%	60%	77.6%
	Total	Count	49	7	6	5	67
	% within Birthplace		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no notable differences by birthplace in the perception of whether any group was overrepresented in the assembly. Most participants from all birthplaces answered *No*, with percentages ranging from 71.4% (n=5) for the Rest of Spain to 83.3% (n=5) for South America.

			Language		
			Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	Total
Agreement level: group or collective overrepresented in Assembly	Yes	Count	9	6	15
	% within Language		25%	19.4%	22.4%
	No	Count	27	25	52
	% within Language		75%	80.7%	77.6%
	Total	Count	36	31	67
	% within Language		100%	100%	100%

There were no strong differences in perceptions of overrepresentation. **Both groups mostly felt that no group or collective was overrepresented.** Specifically, 80.7% (n=25) of Catalan speakers and 75% (n=27) of Spanish speakers selected *no*.

RQ: How inclusive was the CA process, in terms of its design and organisation?

SQ: Was the methodology used appropriate to achieve the objectives of the working sessions?

- Strong consensus across all groups that the methodology was appropriate, with over 83% selecting *quite a bit* or *a lot*.
- Minor gender and age variation; overall responses were highly positive.
- Undergraduates and postgraduates were the most likely to select *a little*, while those with compulsory secondary education were most likely to select *a lot*.
- South American-born participants rated the methodology notably higher (*a lot*) compared to others
- Catalan speakers were more likely to describe the methodology as appropriate to *quite a bit*, while Spanish speakers were slightly more likely than Catalan speakers to describe it as *a lot* appropriate.

			Gender		Total
			Female	Male	
Appropriateness level: Working sessions methodology	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	6	5	11
	% within Gender		17.6%	14.7%	16.2%
	Quite a bit	Count	22	24	46
	% within Gender		64.7%	70.6%	67.6%
	A lot	Count	6	5	11
	% within Gender		17.6%	14.7%	16.2%
	Total	Count	34	34	68
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

Participants across both genders strongly agreed that the working session methodology was appropriate. **There was near-identical satisfaction across women and men.** Among women, 64.7% (n=22) selected *quite a bit* and 17.6% (n=6) *a lot*. Men followed closely, with 70.6% (n=24) selecting *quite a bit* and 14.7%

(n=5) a lot. Very few participants from either group selected *a little*, and none chose *not at all*.

			Age group						Total
			16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Appropriateness level: Working sessions methodology	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	2	1	7	1	0	11
	% within Age group		0%	40%	5.6%	25.9%	12.5%	0%	16.2%
	Quite a bit	Count	3	2	15	16	6	4	46
	% within Age group		50%	40%	83.3%	59.3%	75%	100%	67.6%
	A lot	Count	3	1	2	4	1	0	11
	% within Age group		50%	20%	11.1%	14.8%	12.5%	0%	16.2%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	27	8	4	68
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

The response pattern was consistent across age groups. **Participants aged 30-44 were the most likely to say the methodology was *quite a bit* appropriate, at 83.3% (n=15).** The 75+ group unanimously selected *quite a bit* (100%, n=3), while younger groups (e.g., 16-24) were more split between *quite a bit* and *a lot*. Only a small fraction in each group selected *a little*, with no group showing meaningful dissatisfaction.

			Achieved education						Total
			No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education (GCSE equivalent)	Spanish Baccalaureate (A levels equivalent)	University degree (undergraduate)	Postgraduate university studies (Master's, PhD)	
Appropriateness level: Working	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

sessions methodology	A little	Count	0	0	1	2	5	3	11
	% within Education		0%	0%	11.1%	10.5%	18.5%	33.3%	16.2%
	Quite a bit	Count	1	2	4	16	17	6	46
	% within Education		100%	66.7%	44.4%	84.2%	63%	66.7%	67.6%
	A lot	Count	0	1	4	1	5	0	11
	% within Education		0%	33.3%	44.4%	5.3%	18.5%	0%	16.2%
	Total	Count	1	3	9	19	27	9	68
	% within Education		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

All education levels reflected positive agreement. **Those with compulsory secondary education were most likely to rate the methodology as a lot appropriate (44.4%, n=4).** Undergraduates and postgraduates were the most likely to select *a little* (18.5%, n=5 and 33.3%, n=3, respectively). No one selected *not at all*.

			Place of birth				Total
			Catalonia	Rest of Spain	South America	Other	
Appropriateness level: Working sessions methodology	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Birthplace		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	8	3	0	0	11
	% within Birthplace		16%	42.9%	0%	0%	16.2%
	Quite a bit	Count	34	4	3	5	46
	% within Birthplace		68%	57.1%	50%	100%	67.6%
	A lot	Count	8	0	3	0	11
	% within Birthplace		16%	0%	50%	0%	16.2%
	Total	Count	50	7	6	5	68
	% within Birthplace		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Participants' birthplace influenced how appropriate they felt the working sessions' methodology was. **South American-born participants rated the methodology notably higher (a lot) compared to others.** Specifically, 50% (n=3) from South America selected *a lot*, significantly above the responses from Catalonia (16%, n=8),

Rest of Spain (0%), and Other (0%). Most participants from Catalonia and Other chose *quite a bit*, at 68% (n=34) and 100% (n=5), respectively.

			Language		Total
			Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	
Appropriateness level: Working sessions methodology	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Language		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	8	3	11
	% within Language		22.2%	9.4%	16.2%
	Quite a bit	Count	21	25	46
	% within Language		58.3%	78.1%	67.7%
	A lot	Count	7	4	11
	% within Language		19.4%	12.5%	16.2%
	Total	Count	36	32	68
	% within Language		100%	100%	100%

There were some differences between groups on perceptions of working session methodology. **Catalan speakers were more likely to describe the methodology as appropriate to *quite a bit*, while Spanish speakers were slightly more likely than Catalan speakers to describe it as *a lot* appropriate.** Among Catalan speakers, 78.1% (n=25) chose *quite a bit*, compared to 58.3% (n=21) of Spanish speakers. In contrast, 19.4% (n=7) of Spanish speakers chose *a lot* versus 12.5% (n=4) of Catalan speakers.

RQ: How inclusive was the CA process, in terms of facilitation and deliberation?

SQ: *During the debate, do you think everyone had the opportunity to speak and participate?*

- Most participants believed opportunities to speak were fair, with 82.3% selecting *quite a bit* or *a lot*.

- Men were slightly more likely than women to report high levels of participation opportunity.
- Participants aged 30-44 and 75+ were slightly more likely to report only *a little* opportunity for everyone to speak.
- There were no noticeable differences by education level.
- Participants from Other countries were more likely to express higher satisfaction, with 40% (n=2) selecting *a lot*, while smaller proportions of other birthplaces chose this option
- Only small differences were observed by language; both language groups reported broadly positive experiences.

			Gender		Total
			Female	Male	
Perception of opportunity for everyone to speak and participate	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	6	6	12
	% within Gender		17.6%	17.6%	17.6%
	Quite a bit	Count	25	23	48
	% within Gender		73.5%	67.6%	70.6%
	A lot	Count	3	5	8
	% within Gender		8.8%	14.7%	11.8%
	Total	Count	34	34	68
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

Perceptions of speaking opportunities were largely positive across both genders. **Men were slightly more likely than women to report that everyone had a lot of opportunity to participate.** Specifically, 14.7% of men (n=5) chose *a lot* compared to 8.8% of women (n=3), while 67.6% of men (n=23) and 73.5% of women (n=25) selected *quite a bit*. An equal share of both genders - 17.6% (n=6 each) - said *a little*.

	Age group						Total
	16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	

Perception of opportunity for everyone to speak and participate	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	1	1	5	4	0	1	12
	% within Age group		16.7%	20%	27.8%	14.8%	0%	25%	17.6%
	Quite a bit	Count	5	2	12	21	7	1	48
	% within Age group		83.3%	40%	66.7%	77.8%	87.5%	25%	70.6%
	A lot	Count	0	2	1	2	1	2	8
	% within Age group		0%	40%	5.6%	7.4%	12.5%	50%	11.8%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	27	8	4	68
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Perceptions varied modestly by age. **Participants aged 30-44 and 75+ were slightly more likely to report only a *little* opportunity for everyone to participate, though they were still the minority within their age groups.** Specifically, 27.8% (n=5) of 30-44s and 25% (n=1) of those aged 75+ selected a *little*, higher than in other age brackets.

			Achieved education					Total
			No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education (GCSE equivalent)	Spanish Baccal aureate (A levels equivalent)	University degree (undergraduate)	
Perception of opportunity for everyone to speak and participate	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	1	0	4	5	2
	% within Education		0%	33.3%	0%	21.1%	18.5%	22.2%
	Quite a bit	Count	1	1	7	14	19	6
	% within Education		100%	33.3%	77.8%	73.7%	70.4%	66.7%
	A lot	Count	0	1	2	1	3	1
	% within Education		0%	33.3%	22.2%	5.3%	11.1%	11.1%

	Total	Count	1	3	9	19	27	9	68
	% within Education		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no noticeable differences between educational groups regarding perceived opportunities for everyone to speak. **Large majorities of all groups except those with primary education responded with *quite a bit*.** Those with primary education were evenly split between *a little*, *quite a bit*, and *a lot* (33.3%, n=1 for each).

			Place of birth				Total
			Catalonia	Rest of Spain	South America	Other	
Perception of opportunity for everyone to speak and participate	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Birthplace		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	9	2	0	1	12
	% within Birthplace		18%	28.6%	0%	20%	17.7%
	Quite a bit	Count	36	5	5	2	48
	% within Birthplace		72%	71.4%	83.33%	40%	70.6%
	A lot	Count	5	0	1	2	8
	% within Birthplace		10%	0%	16.67%	40%	11.7%
	Total	Count	50	7	6	5	68
	% within Birthplace		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Perceptions regarding opportunities for everyone to speak and participate showed minor differences. **Participants from Other countries were more likely to express higher satisfaction, with 40% (n=2) selecting *a lot*, while smaller proportions of other birthplaces chose this option.** A plurality of participants, irrespective of birthplace, chose *quite a bit* (ranging from 40%, n=2, for Other to 83.3%, n=5, for South America).

		Language		Total
		Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	

Perception of opportunity for everyone to speak and participate	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Language		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	5	7	12
	% within Language		13.9%	21.9%	17.7%
	Quite a bit	Count	27	21	48
	% within Language		75%	65.6%	70.6%
	A lot	Count	4	4	8
	% within Language		11.1%	12.5%	11.8%
	Total	Count	36	32	68
	% within Language		100%	100%	100%

Only small differences were observed in perceived opportunity to speak and participate. **Both groups reported broadly positive experiences.** 75% (n=27) of Spanish speakers selected *quite a bit* compared to 65.6% (n=21) of Catalan speakers, with very similar proportions also selecting *a lot* (11.1% vs 12.5%).

SQ: Did the facilitation team help and encourage the debate?

- The facilitation team was overwhelmingly viewed as effective, with 92.6% selecting *a lot* or *quite a bit*.
- Women were more likely than men to report very high satisfaction.
- Younger and older participants (under 30 and over 65) were especially likely to select *a lot*.
- University and postgraduate participants were slightly more reserved, but still strongly positive.
- Participants from Other origins expressed the strongest agreement, while from the Rest of Spain were the only group to say *a little*.
- There were no notable differences in how facilitation was perceived by language.

			Gender		Total
			Man	Woman	
Agreement	Not at all	Count	0	0	0

level: facilitation team helped and encouraged debate	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	2	3	5
	% within Gender		5.9%	8.8%	7.4%
	Quite a bit	Count	12	7	19
	% within Gender		35.3%	20.6%	27.9%
	A lot	Count	20	24	44
	% within Gender		58.8%	70.6%	64.7%
	Total	Count	34	34	68
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

Overall ratings were high, but **women were more likely than men to say the facilitation team helped a lot**. Specifically, 70.6% of women (n=24) selected *a lot*, compared to 58.8% of men (n=20). Men were more likely to choose *quite a bit* (35.3%, n=12), while women's responses leaned more strongly toward the top rating. Only a small portion in each group selected *a little*, with proportions ranging from 5.9% (men, n=2) to 8.8% (women, n=3).

			Age group						Total
			19-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: facilitation team helped and encouraged debate	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	2	0	3	0	0	5
	% within Age group		0%	40%	0%	11.1%	0%	0%	7.4%
	Quite a bit	Count	1	1	4	10	3	0	19
	% within Age group		16.7%	20%	22.2%	37%	37.5%	0%	27.9%
	A lot	Count	5	2	14	14	5	4	44
	% within Age group		83.3%	40%	77.8%	51.9%	62.5%	100%	64.7%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	27	8	4	68
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Ratings were consistently high across age groups. **Participants aged 19-24 and 75+ reported the highest approval of the facilitation team, with 83.3% (n=5) and 100% (n=4) selecting a lot, respectively.** The 25-29 age group was more mixed, with 40% (n=2) selecting *a little*.

			Achieved education					Total	
			No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education (GCSE equivalent)	Spanish Baccalareate (A levels equivalent)	University degree (undergraduate)		Postgraduate university studies (Master's, PhD)
Agreement level: facilitation team helped and encouraged debate	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	0	0	1	2	2	5
	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	5.3%	7.4%	22.2%	7.4%
	Quite a bit	Count	0	0	1	5	10	3	19
	% within Education		0%	0%	11.1%	26.3%	37%	33.3%	27.9%
	A lot	Count	1	3	8	13	15	4	44
	% within Education		100%	100%	88.9%	68.4%	55.6%	44.4%	64.7%
	Total	Count	1	3	9	19	27	9	68
	% within Education		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Perceptions were very positive across all education levels, though **participants with undergraduate or postgraduate degrees were slightly more moderate.** Among university undergraduates, 55.6% (n=15) selected *a lot* and 37% (n=10) *quite a bit*. Postgraduates had 44.4% (n=4) choosing *a lot*. In contrast, 100% of those with primary education and 88.9% of those with compulsory secondary education gave the top rating.

	Place of birth				Total
	Catalonia	Rest of Spain	South America	Other	

Agreement level: facilitation team helped and encouraged debate	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Birthplace		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	3	2	0	0	5
	% within Birthplace		6%	28.57%	0%	0%	7.35%
	Quite a bit	Count	14	2	2	1	19
	% within Birthplace		28%	28.57%	33.33%	20%	27.94%
	A lot	Count	33	3	4	4	44
	% within Birthplace		66%	42.86%	66.67%	80%	64.71%
	Total	Count	50	7	6	5	68
	% within Birthplace		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were notable differences by birthplace regarding whether participants felt the facilitation team helped and encouraged debate. **Participants from Other origins expressed the *strongest agreement*, with 80% (n=4) selecting a *lot*, followed closely by participants from South America (66.7%, n=4) and Catalonia (66%, n=33).** By contrast, participants from the Rest of Spain expressed a comparatively lower level of *strong agreement* at 42.9% (n=3). Responses indicating moderate support (*quite a bit*) were more evenly distributed across all groups, ranging from 20% (n=1) for Other to 33.3% (n=2) for South America.

			Language		
			Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	Total
Agreement level: facilitation team helped and encouraged debate	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Language		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	3	2	5
	% within Language		8.3%	6.3%	7.4%
	Quite a bit	Count	9	10	19
	% within Language		25%	31.3%	27.9%
	A lot	Count	24	20	44
	% within Language		66.7%	62.5%	64.7%

	Total	Count	36	32	68
	% within Language		100%	100%	100%

There were no notable differences in how facilitation was perceived. **Both language groups reported high levels of support from the facilitation team.** For example, 66.7% (n=24) of Spanish speakers and 62.5% (n=20) of Catalan speakers answered *a lot*.

SQ: Do you think the facilitation team remained neutral?

- Most participants viewed the facilitation team as neutral, with 89.7% selecting *quite a bit* or *a lot*.
- Women were more likely than men to rate the team as fully neutral (*a lot*), while men leaned slightly toward *quite a bit*.
- Younger participants (under 45) reported higher neutrality perceptions than older groups.
- Participants with postgraduate degrees were slightly more reserved in their assessments.
- Participants from South America strongly agreed (*a lot*) at the highest rate, 83.3% (n=5), notably exceeding other groups.
- Catalan speakers were more likely to report neutrality to a moderate (*quite a bit*) extent, while Spanish speakers were more likely to report it to a high extent.

			Gender		
			Female	Male	Total
Agreement level: facilitation team remained neutral	Not at all	Count	0	1	1
	% within Gender		0%	2.9%	1.5%
	A little	Count	4	2	6
	% within Gender		11.8%	5.9%	8.8%
	Quite a bit	Count	11	16	27
	% within Gender		32.4%	47.1%	39.7%
	A lot	Count	19	15	34
	% within Gender		55.9%	44.1%	50%

	Total	Count	34	34	68
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

Perceptions of neutrality were generally strong across genders. **Women were more likely to believe the facilitation team remained completely neutral, with 55.9% (n=19) selecting a lot, compared to 44.1% (n=15) of men.** Conversely, men were more likely to choose *quite a bit* (47.1%, n=16) than women (32.4%, n=11). Very few participants selected *a little* or *not at all*.

			Age group						Total
			16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: facilitation team remained neutral	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	3.7%	0%	0%	1.5%
	A little	Count	0	0	2	2	2	0	6
	% within Age group		0%	0%	11.1%	7.4%	25%	0%	8.8%
	Quite a bit	Count	2	3	3	14	3	2	27
	% within Age group		33.3%	60%	16.7%	51.9%	37.5%	50%	39.7%
	A lot	Count	4	2	13	10	3	2	34
	% within Age group		66.7%	40%	72.2%	37%	37.5%	50%	50%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	27	8	4	68
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Neutrality ratings decreased slightly with age. **Younger participants (especially 30-44) were the most likely to view the team as fully neutral.** For instance, 72.2% (n=13) of those aged 30-44 chose *a lot*, while only 37.5% (n=3) of those 65-74 did so. Participants aged 45-64 were more likely to select *quite a bit* (51.9%, n=14) and 3.7% (n=1) chose *not at all*.

		Achieved education						Total
		No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary	Spanish Baccalaureate	University degree (undergraduate)	Postgraduate university	

					Education (GCSE equivalent)	(A levels equivalent)	graduate)	studies (Master's, PhD)	
Agreement level: facilitation team remained neutral	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	0%	3.7%	0%	1.5%
	A little	Count	0	0	1	2	1	2	6
	% within Education		0%	0%	11.1%	10.5%	3.7%	22.2%	8.8%
	Quite a bit	Count	0	0	2	9	13	3	27
	% within Education		0%	0%	22.2%	47.4%	48.1%	33.3%	39.7%
	A lot	Count	1	3	6	8	12	4	34
	% within Education		100%	100%	66.7%	42.1%	44.4%	44.4%	50%
	Total	Count	1	3	9	19	27	9	68
	% within Education		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Neutrality perceptions varied slightly by education level. **Participants with Spanish Baccalaureate, postgraduate, and undergraduate degrees were the most hesitant, with less than half of each category selecting a lot.** In contrast, 66.7% (n=6) of those with compulsory secondary education and 100% of both those with primary education and no formal education (n=3, n=1 respectively) selected a lot. A small share of postgraduate (22.2%, n=2) respondents selected a little, suggesting modest uncertainty in this higher education bracket.

			Place of birth				
			Catalonia	Rest of Spain	South America	Other	Total
Agreement level: facilitation team remained neutral	Not at all	Count	1	0	0	0	1
	% within Birthplace		2%	0%	0%	0%	1.5%
	A little	Count	4	1	1	0	6
	% within Birthplace		8%	14.3%	16.7%	0%	8.8%
	Quite a bit	Count	21	4	0	2	27

	% within Birthplace		42%	57.1%	0%	40%	39.7%
	A lot	Count	24	2	5	3	34
	% within Birthplace		48%	28.6%	83.3%	60%	50%
	Total	Count	50	7	6	5	68
	% within Birthplace		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Birthplace notably affected perceptions of facilitation neutrality. **Participants from South America strongly agreed (*a lot*) at the highest rate, 83.3% (n=5), notably exceeding other groups.** By contrast, the Rest of Spain reported only 28.6% (n=2) selecting *a lot*. Catalonia showed a balanced distribution between *quite a bit* (42%, n=21) and *a lot* (48%, n=24).

			Language		
			Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	Total
Agreement level: facilitation team remained neutral	Not at all	Count	1	0	1
	% within Language		2.8%	0%	1.5%
	Little	Count	5	1	6
	% within Language		13.9%	3.1%	8.8%
	Quite a bit	Count	10	17	27
	% within Language		27.8%	53.1%	39.7%
	A lot	Count	20	14	34
	% within Language		55.6%	43.8%	50%
	Total	Count	36	32	68
	% within Language		100%	100%	100%

Some divergence emerged between the groups on perceptions of neutrality. **Catalan speakers were more likely to report neutrality to a moderate (*quite a bit*) extent, while Spanish speakers were more likely to report it to a high extent.** For instance, 53.1% (n=17) of Catalan speakers chose *quite a bit*, compared to 27.8%

(n=10) of Spanish speakers. Conversely, 55.6% (n=20) of Spanish speakers selected *a lot* versus 43.8% (n=14) of Catalan speakers.

SQ: Are you satisfied with your level of participation during the debate/work sessions?

- Most participants were satisfied, with 94.1% selecting *quite a bit* or *a lot*.
- Men were slightly more likely than women to report very high satisfaction with their own level of participation.
- Highest satisfaction levels were reported among participants aged 30-44 and 75+.
- Education levels showed a subtle trend: mid-education levels expressed highest satisfaction.
- No significant differences appeared regarding personal satisfaction with their participation across birthplace groups.
- Perceptions of personal participation were broadly similar across both language groups.

			Gender		Total
			Female	Male	
Satisfaction level: personal level of participation	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	2	2	4
	% within Gender		5.9%	5.9%	5.9%
	Quite a bit	Count	22	20	42
	% within Gender		64.7%	58.8%	61.8%
	A lot	Count	10	12	22
	% within Gender		29.4%	35.3%	32.4%
	Total	Count	34	34	68
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

Both men and women felt largely satisfied with their participation. **Men were slightly more likely to select a lot (35.3%, n=12) compared to women (29.4%, n=10),**

though both groups reported identical proportions for a *little* (5.9%, n=2). The dominant response for both genders was *quite a bit*, 64.7% of women (n=22) and 58.8% of men (n=20).

			Age group						Total
			16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Satisfaction level: personal level of participation	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	1	2	1	0	0	0	4
	% within Age group		16.7%	40%	5.6%	0%	0%	0%	5.9%
	Quite a bit	Count	4	2	6	22	6	2	42
	% within Age group		66.7%	40%	33.3%	81.5%	75%	50%	61.8%
	A lot	Count	1	1	11	5	2	2	22
	% within Age group		16.7%	20%	61.1%	18.5%	25%	50%	32.4%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	27	8	4	68
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Satisfaction was highest among the middle-aged and oldest cohorts. **Participants aged 30-44 (61.1%, n=11) and 75+ (50%, n=2) had the highest proportion selecting a lot**, indicating stronger perceptions of meaningful participation. By contrast, participants aged 25-29 had the highest share selecting a *little* (40%, n=2), though most still leaned toward positive responses overall.

			Achieved education						Total
			No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education (GCSE equivalent)	Spanish Baccal aureate (A levels equivalent)	University degree (undergraduate)	Postgraduate university studies (Master's, PhD)	
Satisfaction level: personal level of	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

participation	A little	Count	0	0	1	0	1	2	4
	% within Education		0%	0%	11.1%	0%	3.7%	22.2%	5.9%
	Quite a bit	Count	1	2	3	15	16	5	42
	% within Education		100%	66.7%	33.3%	78.9%	59.3%	55.6%	61.8%
	A lot	Count	0	1	5	4	10	2	22
	% within Education		0%	33.3%	55.6%	21.1%	37%	22.2%	32.4%
	Total	Count	1	3	9	19	27	9	68
	% within Education		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Perceived participation satisfaction varied slightly across education levels. **Participants with compulsory secondary education reported the highest satisfaction, with 55.6% (n=5) selecting a lot.** University undergraduates followed at 37% (n=10). Those with postgraduate degrees (22.2%, n=2) and primary education (33.3%, n=3) were less likely to select a lot, though most responses were still positive. The overall percentage selecting a little remained low across all groups (max 22.2%, n=2 among postgraduates).

			Place of birth				Total
			Catalonia	Rest of Spain	South America	Other	
Satisfaction level: personal level of participation	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Birthplace		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	2	1	0	1	4
	% within Birthplace		4%	14.29%	0%	20%	5.88%
	Quite a bit	Count	33	3	4	2	42
	% within Birthplace		66%	42.86%	66.67%	40%	61.76%
	A lot	Count	15	3	2	2	22
	% within Birthplace		30%	42.86%	33.33%	40%	32.35%
	Total	Count	50	7	6	5	68
	% within Birthplace		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

No significant differences appeared regarding personal satisfaction with their participation across birthplace groups. Most respondents from all backgrounds rated their participation level predominantly as *quite a bit*, ranging from 40% (n=2) for Other to 66.7% (n=4) for South America and Catalonia.

			Language		Total
			Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	
Satisfaction level: personal level of participation	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Language		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	1	3	4
	% within Language		2.8%	9.4%	5.9%
	Quite a bit	Count	24	18	42
	% within Language		66.7%	56.3%	61.8%
	A lot	Count	11	11	22
	% within Language		30.6%	34.4%	32.4%
	Total	Count	36	32	68
	% within Language		100%	100%	100%

Perceptions of personal participation were broadly similar across groups. **Spanish speakers were slightly more likely to report *quite a bit* of satisfaction with participating.** Specifically, 66.7% (n=24) selected *quite a bit*, compared to 56.3% (n=18) of Catalan speakers. Rates for *a lot* were comparable (30.6% vs 34.4%).

RQ: Outputs: Do PMIMG participants feel their perspectives are included in CA outputs? Do these participants feel a sense of co-ownership of CA outputs?

SQ: Are you satisfied with the results of the assembly?

- There were minor differences between genders in satisfaction levels regarding the assembly's general results. Male participants were slightly more likely to express moderate satisfaction (*quite a bit*) compared to females.

- Older age groups (65-74 and 75+) were unified in their expression of moderate satisfaction, while younger groups were more polarised
- Participants with primary education expressed notably higher satisfaction levels compared to other educational groups.
- South American-born participants expressed notably higher levels of satisfaction than participants born elsewhere.
- Catalan speakers were more likely to rate the results as positive overall.

			Gender		Total
			Female	Male	
Satisfaction level: general results of assembly	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	5	3	8
	% within Gender		14.7%	9.4%	12.1%
	Quite a bit	Count	19	22	41
	% within Gender		55.9%	68.8%	62.1%
	A lot	Count	10	7	17
	% within Gender		29.4%	21.9%	25.8%
	Total	Count	34	32	66
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

There were minor differences between genders in satisfaction levels regarding the assembly's general results. **Male participants were slightly more likely to express moderate satisfaction (*quite a bit*) compared to females.** Specifically, 68.8% (n=22) of males selected *quite a bit*, compared to 55.9% (n=19) of females. Conversely, females showed slightly higher extremes, with more selecting *a lot* (29.4%, n=10) or *a little* (14.7%, n=5), suggesting a modestly more polarised satisfaction distribution among women.

			Age group					Total
			16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	
Satisfaction level: general	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

results of assembly	A little	Count	1	2	1	3	1	0	8
	% within Age group		16.7%	40%	5.6%	12%	12.5%	0%	12.1%
	Quite a bit	Count	3	1	11	17	6	3	41
	% within Age group		50%	20%	61.1%	68%	75%	75%	62.1%
	A lot	Count	2	2	6	5	1	1	17
	% within Age group		33.3%	40%	33.3%	20%	12.5%	25%	25.8%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	25	8	4	66
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were notable differences across age groups in satisfaction levels with the assembly's general results. **Older age groups (65-74 and 75+) were unified in their expression of moderate satisfaction, while younger groups were more polarised.** Notably, 75% of both those aged 65-74 (n=6) and 75+ (n=3) selected *quite a bit*, the highest among all groups. Younger participants, especially those aged 25-29, were more polarised, with 40% (n=2) selecting *a lot* but also 40% (n=2) choosing *a little*.

			Achieved education					Total
			No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education (GCSE equivalent)	Spanish Baccal aureate (A levels equivalent)	University degree (undergraduate)	
Satisfaction level: general results of assembly	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	0	1	2	3	2
	% within Education		0%	0%	11.1%	11.1%	11.1%	25%
	Quite a bit	Count	1	1	6	13	16	4
	% within Education		100%	33.3%	66.7%	72.2%	59.3%	50%
	A lot	Count	0	2	2	3	8	2
	% within Education		0%	66.7%	22.2%	16.7%	29.6%	25%

	Total	Count	1	3	9	18	27	8	66
	% within Education		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Clear differences appeared based on education level regarding satisfaction with the assembly's general results. **Participants with primary education expressed notably higher satisfaction levels compared to other educational groups.** Specifically, 66.7% (n=2) of primary-educated respondents selected *a lot*, distinctly higher than the 16.7% (n=3) of Spanish Baccalaureate and undergraduate participants. Those with compulsory secondary education were predominantly moderately satisfied, with 66.7% (n=6) selecting *quite a bit*.

			Place of birth				Total
			Catalonia	Rest of Spain	South America	Other	
Satisfaction level: general results of assembly	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Birthplace		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	6	2	0	0	8
	% within Birthplace		12.5%	28.6%	0%	0%	12.1%
	Quite a bit	Count	32	3	2	4	41
	% within Birthplace		66.7%	42.9%	33.3%	80%	62.1%
	A lot	Count	10	2	4	1	17
	% within Birthplace		20.8%	28.6%	66.7%	20%	25.8%
	Total	Count	48	7	6	5	66
	% within Birthplace		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Participants' satisfaction varied notably based on birthplace. **South American-born participants expressed notably higher levels of satisfaction than participants born elsewhere.** Among those from South America, 66.7% (n=4) selected *a lot*, substantially higher than those from Catalonia (20.8%, n=10) or elsewhere (20%, n=1). Participants from regions outside Spain and South America predominantly chose *quite a bit* (80%, n=4), indicating strong but slightly less enthusiastic satisfaction.

			Language		
			Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	Total
Satisfaction level: general results of assembly	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Language		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	7	1	8
	% within Language		20%	3.2%	12.1%
	Quite a bit	Count	18	23	41
	% within Language		51.4%	74.2%	62.1%
	A lot	Count	10	7	17
	% within Language		28.6%	22.6%	25.8%
	Total	Count	35	31	66
	% within Language		100%	100%	100%

There were some differences between groups in overall satisfaction with the assembly's results. **Catalan speakers were more likely to rate the results as positive overall.** Specifically, 74.2% (n=23) of Catalan speakers chose *quite a bit*, compared to 51.4% (n=18) of Spanish speakers. A higher proportion of Spanish speakers selected *a little* at 20% (n=7), versus just 3.2% (n=1) of Catalan speakers.

SQ: Do you think your opinions have been included in the final recommendations?

- There was broad agreement that participants' views were included, with 91.2% selecting *quite a bit* or *a lot*.
- Men were more confident than women in feeling their opinions were fully included.
- Ages 25-29 showed the strongest perception of inclusion.
- Higher educational attainment correlated slightly with reduced certainty of full inclusion.
- Participants from Other places felt their opinions were included strongly (*a lot*) at the highest rate.
- Catalan speakers were more likely to report a high level of inclusion of their perspectives compared to Spanish speakers.

			Gender		Total
			Female	Male	
Agreement level: opinions included in final recommendations	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	2	3	5
	% within Gender		5.9%	8.8%	7.4%
	Quite a bit	Count	12	7	19
	% within Gender		35.3%	20.6%	27.9%
	A lot	Count	20	24	44
	% within Gender		58.8%	70.6%	64.7%
	Total	Count	34	34	68
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

Perceptions of opinion inclusion were positive across genders. **Men were more likely than women to feel their views were fully reflected (a lot), with 70.6% (n=24) selecting a lot, compared to 58.8% (n=20) of women.** Conversely, women were more likely to choose *quite a bit* (35.3%, n=12 vs. 20.6%, n=7 among men). Very few participants in either group selected *a little*, and none chose *not at all*.

			Age group						Total
			16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: opinions included in final recommendations	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	0	3	3	1	0	7
	% within Age group		0%	0%	16.7%	11.1%	12.5%	0%	10.3%
	Quite a bit	Count	4	2	9	21	4	3	43
	% within Age group		66.7%	40%	50%	77.8%	50%	75%	63.2%
	A lot	Count	2	3	6	3	3	1	18
	% within Age group		33.3%	60%	33.3%	11.1%	37.5%	25%	26.5%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	27	8	4	68
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Confidence in inclusion peaked among participants aged 25-29. **A notable 60% (n=3) of this age group selected a lot, the highest among all age brackets.** Other groups leaned more toward *quite a bit*, particularly 45-64-year-olds, where 77.8% (n=21) chose this mid-level response.

			Achieved education					Total	
			No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education (GCSE equivalent)	Spanish Baccal aureate (A levels equivalent)	University degree (undergraduate)		Postgraduate university studies (Master's, PhD)
Agreement level: opinions included in final recommendations	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	
	A little	Count	0	0	1	2	4	7	
	% within Education		0%	0%	11.1%	10.5%	14.8%	0%	10.3%
	Quite a bit	Count	1	1	6	15	15	5	43
	% within Education		100%	33.3%	66.7%	78.9%	55.6%	55.6%	63.2%
	A lot	Count	0	2	2	2	8	4	18
	% within Education		0%	66.7%	22.2%	10.5%	29.6%	44.4%	26.5%
	Total	Count	1	3	9	19	27	9	68
	% within Education		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Perceptions of inclusion declined slightly with education level. **Participants with primary education reported the highest perception of full inclusion, with 66.7% (n=2) selecting a lot.** In contrast, only 29.6% (n=8) of university undergraduates chose *a lot*, and 14.8% (n=4) selected *a little*, the highest among any education group.

		Place of birth				Total
		Catalonia	Rest of Spain	South America	Other	

Agreement level: opinions included in final recommendations	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Birthplace		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	4	2	0	1	7
	% within Birthplace		8%	28.6%	0%	20%	10.3%
	Quite a bit	Count	37	3	3	0	43
	% within Birthplace		74%	42.9%	50%	0%	63.2%
	A lot	Count	9	2	3	4	18
	% within Birthplace		18%	28.6%	50%	80%	26.5%
	Total	Count	50	7	6	5	68
	% within Birthplace		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Birthplace affected participants' perceptions of whether their opinions were reflected in final recommendations. **Participants from Other places felt their opinions were included strongly (a lot) at the highest rate (80%, n=4).** In contrast, only 18% (n=9) from Catalonia reported feeling their opinions were strongly included, with most participants from Catalonia choosing *quite a bit* (74%, n=37).

			Language		
			Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	Total
Agreement level: opinions included in final recommendations	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Language		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	5	2	7
	% within Language		13.9%	6.3%	10.3%
	Quite a bit	Count	24	19	43
	% within Language		66.7%	59.4%	63.2%
	A lot	Count	7	11	18
	% within Language		19.4%	34.4%	26.5%
	Total	Count	36	32	68
	% within Language		100%	100%	100%

Small differences emerged in perceptions of how well participants' opinions were included in final recommendations. **Catalan speakers were more likely to report a high level of inclusion.** 34.4% (n=11) selected *a lot*, compared to 19.4% (n=7) of Spanish speakers. Conversely, 13.9% (n=5) of Spanish speakers chose *a little* compared to 6.3% (n=2) of Catalan speakers.

SQ: If your contributions were not included, do you think the proposal formulation process was fair?

- General perceptions of the fairness of the proposal formulation process were high, with 88% selecting *quite a bit* or *a lot*.
- Men were more likely than women to rate the process as *a lot* fair.
- Agreement was highest among participants aged 75+ and 30-44.
- Participants with postgraduate degrees and primary education were most likely to report full confidence in fairness.
- South American-born participants rated fairness as *a lot* notably more frequently compared to participants from Catalonia and Other places.
- Catalan speakers were more likely than Spanish speakers to report the process was fair to a high degree (*a lot*).

			Gender		Total
			Female	Male	
Agreement level: proposal formulation process was fair	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	5	2	7
	% within Gender		18.5%	6.5%	12.1%
	Quite a bit	Count	14	18	32
	% within Gender		51.9%	58.1%	55.2%
	A lot	Count	8	11	19
	% within Gender		29.6%	35.5%	32.8%
	Total	Count	27	31	58
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

Perceived fairness was strong across gender groups. **Men were more likely than women to indicate full agreement, with 35.5% (n=11) selecting a lot, compared to 29.6% (n=8) of women.** Conversely, women were more likely to indicate *a little* (18.5%, n=5) than men (6.5%, n=2), suggesting some slightly lower confidence among female participants. The most common response overall for both genders was *quite a bit* (51.9% of women and 58.1% of men).

			Age group						Total
			16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: proposal formulation process was fair	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	1	1	4	1	0	7
	% within Age group		0%	20%	6.2%	18.2%	14.3%	0%	12.1%
	Quite a bit	Count	3	1	10	12	5	1	32
	% within Age group		75%	20%	62.5%	54.5%	71.4%	25%	55.2%
	A lot	Count	1	3	5	6	1	3	19
	% within Age group		25%	60%	31.2%	27.3%	14.3%	75%	32.8%
	Total	Count	4	5	16	22	7	4	58
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Agreement was highest among participants aged 75+ and 30-44. **In the 75+ group, 75% (n=3) selected a lot and the remaining 25% (n=1) selected quite a bit, reflecting particularly strong perceptions of fairness.** Other groups generally followed similar patterns, with *quite a bit* being the most common response for all other groups except 25-29, who also leaned more towards *a lot* (60%, n=3). Participants aged 45-64 were the most hesitant, with 18.2% (n=4) selecting *a little*.

		Achieved education					Total
		No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education	Spanish Baccalaurate (A	University degree (undergraduate)	

					on (GCSE equival ent)	levels equival ent))	(Master 's, PhD)	
Agreement level: proposal formulation process was fair	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	0	1	2	3	1	7
	% within Education		0%	0%	12.5%	12.5%	12.5%	16.7%	12.1%
	Quite a bit	Count	1	1	6	13	10	1	32
	% within Education		100%	33.3%	75%	81.2%	41.7%	16.7%	55.2%
	A lot	Count	0	2	1	1	11	4	19
	% within Education		0%	66.7%	12.5%	6.2%	45.8%	66.7%	32.8%
	Total	Count	1	3	8	16	24	6	58
	% within Education		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some differences by education group, though with no strong overall pattern. **Participants with postgraduate degrees were the most likely to choose a lot, at 66.7% (n=4), along with those with primary education (66.7%, n=2).** Those with Spanish Baccalaureates or equivalent reported a more mixed view, with only 6.2% (n=1) selecting a lot and 81.3% (n=13) selecting quite a bit.

		Place of birth					
		Catalonia	Rest of Spain	South America	Other	Total	
Agreement level: proposal formulation process was fair	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Birthplace		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	3	3	0	1	7
	% within Birthplace		6.82%	50%	0%	33.33%	12.07%
	Quite a bit	Count	30	0	1	1	32
	% within Birthplace		68.18%	0%	20%	33.33%	55.17%
	A lot	Count	11	3	4	1	19
	% within Birthplace		25%	50%	80%	33.33%	32.76%
	Total	Count	44	6	5	3	58

	% within Birthplace	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
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There was a notable difference by birthplace in perceived fairness of the proposal formulation process. **South American-born participants rated fairness as a lot notably more frequently (80%, n=4) compared to participants from Catalonia (25%, n=11) and Other places (33.3%, n=1).** Participants from the Rest of Spain were evenly split between perceiving fairness as *a little* (50%, n=3) and *a lot* (50%, n=3).

			Language		
			Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	Total
Agreement level: proposal formulation process was fair	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Language		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	5	2	7
	% within Language		16.1%	7.4%	12.1%
	Quite a bit	Count	18	14	32
	% within Language		58.1%	51.9%	55.2%
	A lot	Count	8	11	19
	% within Language		25.8%	40.7%	32.8%
	Total	Count	31	27	58
	% within Language		100%	100%	100%

There were some differences between language groups in perceptions of fairness in the proposal process. **Catalan speakers were more likely than Spanish speakers to report the process was fair to a high degree.** Specifically, 40.7% (n=11) of Catalan speakers selected *a lot*, compared to 25.8% (n=8) of Spanish speakers. Meanwhile, 58.1% (n=18) of Spanish speakers chose *quite a bit*, slightly higher than 51.9% (n=14) of Catalan speakers.

SQ: How consensual are the recommendations proposed by the Assembly?

- Overall, the vast majority of participants reported that the recommendations proposed by the assembly were *quite a bit* or *a lot* consensual.
- There were no strong differences by gender.
- There were no strong noticeable differences by age, with a majority of all age groups choosing *quite a bit*.
- Low ratings of consensuality came exclusively from those with Spanish Baccalaureates, undergraduates and postgraduates, while those with primary education were the most positive.
- Participants born in the Rest of Spain and South America were equally as likely to agree *quite a bit* or *a lot* that recommendations were consensual, whereas those born in Spain or Other countries were much more likely to say *quite a bit*.
- Catalan speakers were slightly more likely than Spanish speakers to rate the recommendations as highly consensual.

			Gender		Total
			Female	Male	
Agreement level: Assembly recommendations are consensual	Not at all	Count	0	1	1
	% within Gender		0%	2.9%	1.5%
	A little	Count	2	0	2
	% within Gender		5.9%	0%	2.9%
	Quite a bit	Count	23	22	45
	% within Gender		67.6%	64.7%	66.2%
	A lot	Count	9	11	20
	% within Gender		26.5%	32.4%	29.4%
	Total	Count	34	34	68
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

Overall, **both genders expressed similar levels of agreement.** Among women, 67.6% (n=23) said the recommendations were *quite a bit* consensual, 26.5% (n=9)

said *a lot*, and 5.9% (n=2) said *a little*. Among men, 64.7% (n=22) said *quite a bit*, 32.4% (n=11) *a lot*, and no men selected *a little* or *not at all*.

			Age group						Total
			16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	
Agreement level: recommendations are consensual	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	3.7%	0%	0%	1.5%
	A little	Count	0	0	1	1	0	0	2
	% within Age group		0%	0%	5.6%	3.7%	0%	0%	2.9%
	Quite a bit	Count	4	3	11	18	6	3	45
	% within Age group		66.7%	60%	61.1%	66.7%	75%	75%	66.2%
	A lot	Count	2	2	6	7	2	1	20
	% within Age group		33.3%	40%	33.3%	25.9%	25%	25%	29.4%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	27	8	4	68
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were no strong noticeable differences by age, **with a majority of all age groups choosing quite a bit**. The age groups 65-74 and 75+ had the strongest unanimous agreement: 75% in each group (n=6, n=3, respectively) said *quite a bit*, with the remaining 25% for both chose *a lot* (n=2, n=1 respectively).

			Achieved education						Total
			No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education (GCSE equivalent)	Spanish Baccal aureate (A levels equivalent)	University degree (undergraduate)	Postgraduate university studies (Master's, PhD)	
Agreement level: Assembly recommendations are	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	0%	3.7%	0%	1.5%
	A little	Count	0	0	0	1	0	1	2
	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	5.3%	0%	11.1%	2.9%

consensual	Quite a bit	Count	1	1	5	15	17	6	45
	% within Education		100%	33.3%	55.6%	78.9%	63%	66.7%	66.2%
	A lot	Count	0	2	4	3	9	2	20
	% within Education		0%	66.7%	44.4%	15.8%	33.3%	22.2%	29.4%
	Total	Count	1	3	9	19	27	9	68
	% within Education		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were minor differences by education: while agreement at the *quite a bit* level was consistent across education levels, **the only low ratings of *not at all* or *a little* came from those with Spanish Baccalaureates, undergraduates, or postgraduates.** Respondents with primary education were most likely to rate the recommendations as *a lot* consensual (66.7%, n=2), followed by those with compulsory secondary education (44.4%, n=4). In contrast, only 15.8% (n=3) of those with Spanish Baccalaureates said *a lot*.

			Place of birth				Total
			Catalonia	Rest of Spain	South America	Other	
Agreement level: Assembly recommendations are consensual	Not at all	Count	1	0	0	0	1
	% within Birthplace		2%	0%	0%	0%	1.5%
	A little	Count	1	1	0	0	2
	% within Birthplace		2%	14.3%	0%	0%	2.9%
	Quite a bit	Count	35	3	3	4	45
	% within Birthplace		70%	42.9%	50%	80%	66.2%
	A lot	Count	13	3	3	1	20
	% within Birthplace		26%	42.9%	50%	20%	29.4%
	Total	Count	50	7	6	5	68
	% within Birthplace		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some differences by birthplace regarding perceptions of consensuality of the assembly recommendations. **Participants from the rest of Spain and South America were both evenly split (42.9%, n=3 and 50%, n=3 respectively) between *quite a bit* and *a lot* except for 14.3% (n=1) from the rest of Spain who chose *a little*.**

Majorities of both participants from Catalonia and Other countries chose *quite a bit* (70%, n=35 for Catalonia; 80%, n=4 for Other countries). The only *not at all* response came from a participant born in Catalonia.

			Language		Total
			Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	
Agreement level: Assembly recommendations are consensual	Not at all	Count	1	0	1
	% within Language		2.8%	0%	1.5%
	A little	Count	2	0	2
	% within Language		5.6%	0%	2.9%
	Quite a bit	Count	24	21	45
	% within Language		66.7%	65.6%	66.2%
	A lot	Count	9	11	20
	% within Language		25%	34.4%	29.4%
	Total	Count	36	32	68
	% within Language		100%	100%	100%

There were small differences in how consensual the recommendations were perceived to be. **Catalan speakers were slightly more likely than Spanish speakers to rate the recommendations as highly consensual.** While *quite a bit* was selected at similar levels by both groups—66.7% (n=24) of Spanish speakers and 65.6% (n=21) of Catalan speakers—Catalan speakers were more likely to choose *a lot* (34.4%, n=11) compared to Spanish speakers (25%, n=9). Only Spanish speakers selected *not at all* (2.8%, n=1) or *a little* (5.6%, n=2), suggesting a slightly more uniform view among Catalan participants.

SQ: Do the Assembly's recommendations reflect the debates that took place?

- Participants were broadly positive that recommendations reflected the debates that took place, with 92.6% (n=62) of respondents answering *quite a bit* or *a lot*.

- Women were slightly less likely than men to say *a lot*.
- There were some notable differences by age: the 25-29 group showed the strongest unanimous positivity, while the 45-64 group showed the most variation.
- Those with no formal education and primary education were the most likely to say *a lot*.
- Participants from South America showed stronger agreement (*a lot*), compared with the rest of Spain and Catalonia.
- Perceptions of how well recommendations reflected prior debate were very similar across language groups; both groups were overwhelmingly positive.

			Gender		Total
			Female	Male	
Agreement level: Assembly recommendations reflect debates that took place	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Gender		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	4	1	5
	% within Gender		11.8%	3%	7.5%
	Quite a bit	Count	21	21	42
	% within Gender		61.8%	63.6%	62.7%
	A lot	Count	9	11	20
	% within Gender		26.5%	33.3%	29.9%
	Total	Count	34	33	67
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

Only minor differences by gender were observed for perceptions of female participants were slightly more likely to say *quite a bit* (61.8%, n=21) and less likely to say *a lot* (26.5%, n=9) compared to male participants, who reported 63.6% (n=21) *quite a bit* and 33.3% (n=11) *a lot*. Only 4 women (11.8%) selected *a little*, while just 1 man (3%) did. No respondents chose *not at all*.

			Age group					Total
			16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	
Agreement level:	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0

Agreement level: Assembly recommendations reflect debates that took place	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	0	0	4	1	0	5
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	15.4%	12.5%	0%	7.5%
	Quite a bit	Count	5	2	13	15	4	3	42
	% within Age group		83.3%	40%	72.2%	57.7%	50%	75%	62.7%
	A lot	Count	1	3	5	7	3	1	20
	% within Age group		16.7%	60%	27.8%	26.9%	37.5%	25%	29.9%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	26	8	4	67
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were some notable differences by age: the 25-29 group showed the strongest unanimous positivity, while the 45-64 group showed the most variation. A majority of all age groups chose *quite a bit* except for the 25-29 group, 60% (n=3) of whom chose *a lot*. Those aged 45-64 showed the most variation: 57.7% (n=15) *quite a bit*, 26.9% (n=7) *a lot*, and 15.4% (n=4) *a little*. No group showed strong disagreement with the question - *not at all* was 0% across all ages.

			Achieved education					Total	
			No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education (GCSE equivalent)	Spanish Baccal aureate (A levels equivalent)	University degree (undergraduate)		Postgraduate university studies (Master's, PhD)
Agreement level: Assembly recommendations reflect debates that took place	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	% within Education		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	0	0	1	2	2	0	5
	% within Education		0%	0%	11.1%	10.5%	7.4%	0%	7.5%
	Quite a bit	Count	0	1	5	17	13	6	42
	% within Education		0%	33.3%	55.6%	89.5%	48.1%	75%	62.7%
	A lot	Count	1	2	3	0	12	2	20
	% within Education		100%	66.7%	33.3%	0%	44.4%	25%	29.9%

	Total	Count	1	3	9	19	27	8	67
	% within Education		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Across all education levels except primary education, *quite a bit* was the dominant response, ranging from 55.6% (n=5) among those with compulsory secondary education to 75% (n=6) among postgraduates. **Those with no formal education and primary education were the most likely to say *a lot*** (100%, n=1; 66.7%, n=2), suggesting a more favourable view among participants with lower levels of formal education.

			Place of birth				Total
			Catalonia	Rest of Spain	South America	Other	
Agreement level: Assembly recommendations reflect debates that took place	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	0
	% within Birthplace		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	3	2	0	0	5
	% within Birthplace		6.1%	28.6%	0%	0%	7.5%
	Quite a bit	Count	34	2	2	4	42
	% within Birthplace		69.4%	28.6%	33.3%	80%	62.7%
	A lot	Count	12	3	4	1	20
	% within Birthplace		24.5%	42.9%	66.7%	20%	29.9%
	Total	Count	49	7	6	5	67
	% within Birthplace		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Clear differences emerged in participants' perceptions of whether recommendations reflected assembly debates. **Participants from South America showed stronger agreement (*a lot*, 66.7%, n=4), compared with the rest of Spain (42.9%, n=3) and Catalonia (24.5%, n=12).** Participants from Other origins primarily responded *quite a bit* (80%, n=4).

		Language		Total
		Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	

Agreement level: Assembly recommendations reflect debates that took place	Not at all	Count	0	0	0
	% within Language		0%	0%	0%
	A little	Count	4	1	5
	% within Language		11.1%	3.2%	7.5%
	Quite a bit	Count	22	20	42
	% within Language		61.1%	64.5%	62.7%
	A lot	Count	10	10	20
	% within Language		27.8%	32.3%	29.9%
	Total	Count	36	31	67
	% within Language		100%	100%	100%

Perceptions of how well recommendations reflected prior debate were very similar across language groups. **Both groups were overwhelmingly positive.** For example, 64.5% (n=20) of Catalan and 61.1% (n=22) of Spanish speakers selected *quite a bit*, and *a lot* was chosen by 32.3% (n=10) and 27.8% (n=10) respectively.

SQ: Do you think the Assembly's recommendations will be adopted by the Government of Catalonia to address the challenges raised?

- Overall, the majority (62.1%) of participants were pessimistic, selecting that they only thought the recommendations would be adopted to *a little* extent.
- Men were somewhat more likely than women to express higher levels of confidence that the assembly's recommendations would be adopted.
- Confidence was lowest among the youngest age group (16-24), while those aged 30-44 and 65-74 showed a wider spread of views.
- Participants with postgraduate degrees were most confident regarding recommendation uptake.
- Respondents born in South America and the "Other" category expressed greater confidence overall, those born in the rest of Spain were most sceptical.
- Spanish speakers were more likely to express complete lack of confidence compared to none among Catalan speakers.

	Gender	
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			Female	Male	Total
Agreement level: Assembly recommendations will be adopted by the Government of Catalonia	Not at all	Count	2	1	3
	% within Gender		6.3%	2.9%	4.6%
	A little	Count	21	20	41
	% within Gender		65.6%	58.8%	62.1%
	Quite a bit	Count	5	11	16
	% within Gender		15.6%	32.4%	24.2%
	A lot	Count	4	2	6
	% within Gender		12.5%	5.9%	9.1%
	Total	Count	32	34	66
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

There were some differences by gender in levels of agreement that the Government of Catalonia would adopt the assembly's recommendations. **Overall, both groups were most likely to express a *little* confidence (62.1%, n=41), but men were somewhat more likely than women to express higher levels of agreement.** For example, 32.4% of men said *quite a bit* (n=11), compared to 15.6% of women (n=5). Women were slightly more likely to express no confidence at all (*not at all*, 6.3%, n=2) compared to men (2.9%, n=1).

			Age group						
			16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74	75+	Total
Agreement level: Assembly recommendations will be adopted by the Government of Catalonia	Not at all	Count	1	1	0	1	0	0	3
	% within Age group		16.7%	20%	0%	3.9%	0%	0%	4.6%
	A little	Count	3	3	10	19	3	3	41
	% within Age group		50%	60%	55.6%	73.1%	42.9%	75%	62.1%
	Quite a bit	Count	1	1	5	6	3	0	16
	% within Age group		16.7%	20%	27.8%	23%	42.9%	0%	24.2%
	A lot	Count	1	0	3	0	1	1	6
	% within Age group		16.7%	0%	16.7%	0%	14.3%	25%	9.1%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	26	7	4	66

	% within Age group	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
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Notable differences were observed by age group. **Confidence was lowest among the youngest age group (16-24)**, with 66.7% selecting either *not at all* or *a little* (n=4), while only one respondent (16.7%) in this group selected *a lot*. In contrast, those aged 45-64 were more likely to say *a little* (73.1%, n=19), but no one in this group expressed the highest level of agreement (*a lot*, 0%). **Those aged 30-44 and 65-74 showed a wider spread of views**, with 27.8% and 42.9% respectively selecting *quite a bit*, but both groups also had a high proportion responding *a little* (55.6% and 42.9%). The 75+ group was most polarised: 75% (n=3) said *a little* and 25% (n=1) said *a lot*, with no respondents selecting *quite a bit*.

			Achieved education						Total
			No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education (GCSE equivalent)	Spanish Baccalureate (A levels equivalent)	University degree (undergraduate)	Postgraduate university studies (Master's, PhD)	
Agreement level: Assembly recommendations will be adopted by the Government of Catalonia	Not at all	Count	0	1	0	1	1	0	3
	% within Education		N/A	33.3%	0%	5.3%	3.7%	0%	4.6%
	A little	Count	0	0	8	12	13	8	41
	% within Education		N/A	0%	88.9%	63.2%	48.2%	100%	62.1%
	Quite a bit	Count	0	1	0	6	9	0	16
	% within Education		N/A	33.3%	0%	31.6%	33.3%	0%	24.2%
	A lot	Count	0	1	1	0	4	0	6
	% within Education		N/A	33.3%	11.1%	0%	14.8%	0%	9.1%
	Total	Count	0	3	9	19	27	8	66
% within Education		N/A	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	

There were observable differences across education levels. **Participants with postgraduate degrees were most confident, with 33.3% selecting quite a bit** (n=9) and 14.8% *a lot* (n=4), while none in this group selected *not at all* or *a little*. By contrast, those with only compulsory secondary education (GCSE equivalent) were

most sceptical: 88.9% selected *a little* (n=8), and none expressed higher confidence. Those with undergraduate degrees were split, with nearly half (48.2%, n=13) selecting *a little*, and smaller proportions choosing *quite a bit* (33.3%, n=9) or *a lot* (14.8%, n=4). Only one person without formal education responded, and they selected *a little*.

			Place of birth				Total
			Catalonia	Rest of Spain	South America	Other	
Agreement level: Assembly recommendations will be adopted by the Government of Catalonia	Not at all	Count	3	0	0	0	3
	% within Birthplace		6.3%	0%	0%	0%	4.6%
	A little	Count	31	6	1	3	41
	% within Birthplace		64.6%	85.7%	16.7%	60%	62.1%
	Quite a bit	Count	10	1	3	2	16
	% within Birthplace		20.8%	14.3%	50%	40%	24.2%
	A lot	Count	4	0	2	0	6
	% within Birthplace		8.3%	0%	33.3%	0%	9.1%
	Total	Count	48	7	6	5	66
	% within Birthplace		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Confidence levels also varied by place of birth. **Respondents born in South America and the “Other” category expressed greater confidence overall:** 50% of those born in South America said *quite a bit* and 33.3% said *a lot*, while among the “Other” group, 40% said *quite a bit*. In contrast, **those born in the rest of Spain were most sceptical**, with 85.7% (n=6) selecting *a little*. Among Catalonia-born respondents, 64.6% chose *a little* (n=31), 20.8% *quite a bit* (n=10), and only 8.3% *a lot* (n=4). Those born outside of Spain had more varied and positive responses overall.

			Language		Total
			Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	
Agreement	Not at all	Count	3	0	3

level: Assembly recommendations will be adopted by the Government of Catalonia	% within Language		8.6%	0%	4.6%
	A little	Count	22	19	41
	% within Language		62.9%	61.3%	62.1%
	Quite a bit	Count	6	10	16
	% within Language		17.1%	32.3%	24.2%
	A lot	Count	4	2	6
	% within Language		11.4%	6.5%	9.1%
	Total	Count	35	31	66
	% within Language		100%	100%	100%

Language background showed moderate differences. Among Catalan-speaking participants, 32.3% selected *quite a bit* (n=10) and 6.5% *a lot* (n=2), compared to 17.1% and 11.4% respectively for Spanish-speaking participants. **Spanish speakers were more likely to express complete lack of confidence (*not at all*, 8.6%, n=3) compared to none among Catalan speakers.** However, both groups had similar proportions selecting *a little* (62.9% and 61.3%), suggesting a broadly shared scepticism across language groups, with Catalan speakers showing slightly more optimism overall.

RQ: Outcomes: Do PMIMG feel a personal impact (e.g. a change in attitude or view on a topic, confidence, or sense of political agency), as a result of participation in the CA?

SQ: Would you be willing to participate in another citizens' Assembly?

- There were only modest differences between genders: female participants were slightly more likely than male participants to report the highest level of willingness.
- Participants aged 30–44 showed the strongest willingness, while those aged 75+ were least likely to select the highest response.

- Participants with postgraduate qualifications were more evenly split across responses, while most other education groups reported higher levels of willingness.
- Participants born outside Spain, particularly those born in South America or categorised as 'Other', were more likely to report high willingness.
- There were only minor differences in willingness to participate in another assembly by language: Catalan speakers were slightly more likely to express the highest level of willingness.

			Gender		Total
			Female	Male	
Willingness level: participation in another citizens' Assembly	Not at all	Count	0	2	2
	% within Gender		0%	5.9%	2.9%
	A little	Count	2	3	5
	% within Gender		5.9%	8.8%	7.4%
	Quite a bit	Count	13	12	25
	% within Gender		38.2%	35.3%	36.8%
	A lot	Count	19	17	36
	% within Gender		55.9%	50%	52.9%
	Total	Count	34	34	68
	% within Gender		100%	100%	100%

There were only modest differences between genders in willingness to participate again. **Female participants were slightly more likely than male participants to report the highest level of willingness.** Among women, 55.9% (n=19) selected a *lot*, compared to 50% (n=17) of men. A small number of men (5.9%, n=2) selected *not at all*, whereas no women selected this option.

			Age group					Total	
			16-24	25-29	30-44	45-64	65-74		75+
Willingness level: participation in	Not at all	Count	0	0	0	0	2	0	2
	% within Age group		0%	0%	0%	0%	25%	0%	3%

another citizens' Assembly	A little	Count	1	1	0	3	0	0	5
	% within Age group		16.7%	20%	0%	11.1%	0%	0%	7.35%
	Quite a bit	Count	2	1	4	13	2	3	25
	% within Age group		33.3%	20%	22.2%	48.2%	25%	75%	36.8%
	A lot	Count	3	3	14	11	4	1	36
	% within Age group		50%	60%	77.8%	40.7%	50%	25%	52.9%
	Total	Count	6	5	18	27	8	4	68
	% within Age group		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Age appeared to influence willingness to participate again in some clear ways. **Participants aged 30–44 showed the strongest willingness, while those aged 75+ were least likely to select the highest response.** Specifically, 77.8% (n=14) of those aged 30–44 selected *a lot*, compared to just 25% (n=1) of those aged 75+. Conversely, *quite a bit* was selected by 75% (n=3) of those aged 75+, suggesting a preference for moderate enthusiasm in that group.

			Achieved education					Total	
			No formal education	Primary education	Compulsory Secondary Education (GCSE equivalent)	Spanish Baccal aureate (A levels equivalent)	University degree (undergraduate)		Postgraduate university studies (Master's, PhD)
Willingness level: participation in another citizens' Assembly	Not at all	Count	0	0	1	0	0	1	2
	% within Education		0%	0%	11.1%	0%	0%	11.1%	2.9%
	A little	Count	0	0	1	1	2	1	5
	% within Education		0%	0%	11.1%	5.3%	7.4%	11.1%	7.4%
	Quite a bit	Count	0	0	1	12	7	5	25
	% within Education		0%	0%	11.1%	63.2%	25.9%	55.6%	36.8%
	A lot	Count	1	3	6	6	18	2	36
	% within Education		100%	100%	66.7%	31.6%	66.7%	22.2%	52.9%
Total	Count	1	3	9	19	27	9	68	

	% within Education	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
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Differences in willingness to participate again also varied by educational background. **Participants with postgraduate qualifications were more evenly split across responses, while those with no formal education, primary education, compulsory secondary education or undergraduates showed higher levels of willingness.** Specifically, 100% of both those with primary education (n=1), 66.7% (n=18) of those with university degrees and 66.7% (n=6) with compulsory secondary education selected *a lot*, compared to only 22.2% (n=2) of those with postgraduate degrees. Meanwhile, participants with Spanish Baccalaureates and postgraduate participants were more likely to select *quite a bit* (63.2%, n=12, 55.6%, n=5 respectively), indicating a slightly more cautious outlook.

			Place of birth				Total
			Catalonia	Rest of Spain	South America	Other	
Willingness level: participation in another citizens' Assembly	Not at all	Count	1	0	1	0	2
	% within Birthplace		2%	0%	16.7%	0%	2.9%
	A little	Count	3	2	0	0	5
	% within Birthplace		6%	28.6%	0%	0%	7.4%
	Quite a bit	Count	20	3	1	1	25
	% within Birthplace		40%	42.9%	16.7%	20%	36.8%
	A lot	Count	26	2	4	4	36
	% within Birthplace		52%	28.6%	66.7%	80%	52.9%
	Total	Count	50	7	6	5	68
	% within Birthplace		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

There were notable differences in willingness to participate again based on place of birth. **Participants born outside Spain, particularly those born in South America or categorised as 'Other', were more likely to report high willingness.** For example, *a lot* was selected by 80% (n=4) of those born in the 'Other' category and 66.7% (n=4) of those born in South America, compared with 52% (n=26) of those born in Catalonia and just 28.6% (n=2) of those from the rest of Spain. Conversely,

28.6% (n=2) of participants born in the rest of Spain chose *a little*, the highest proportion across all groups.

			Language		Total
			Spanish (Spain, international literacy)	Catalan	
Willingness level: participation in another citizens' Assembly	Not at all	Count	2	0	2
	% within Language		5.6%	0%	2.9%
	A little	Count	3	2	5
	% within Language		8.3%	6.3%	7.4%
	Quite a bit	Count	13	12	25
	% within Language		36.1%	37.5%	36.8%
	A lot	Count	18	18	36
	% within Language		50%	56.3%	52.9%
	Total	Count	36	32	68
	% within Language		100%	100%	100%

There were only minor differences in willingness to participate in another assembly by language. **Catalan speakers were slightly more likely to express the highest level of willingness.** Specifically, 56.3% (n=18) of Catalan speakers selected *a lot*, compared to 50% (n=18) of Spanish speakers. Other response categories were closely aligned, with 36.1% (n=13) of Spanish and 37.5% (n=12) of Catalan speakers selecting *quite a bit*.

RQ: What was the impact of technology on participants' perception of the CA? Were there differences in experiences based on online versus face-to-face formats? Was the use of technology experienced differently depending on social groups?

No participant experience variables were available in the Climate Assembly of Catalonia dataset to address this research question.

RQ: What are the drivers of non-participation in CAs by potential participants from different social groups?

No data was available in the Climate Assembly of Catalonia dataset to address this research question.

III. Conclusion

This section has provided full crosstabulations and short write-ups for participant experience variables across both Scotland's Climate Assembly and the Citizens' Assembly for the Climate of Catalonia, organised by research questions.

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